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Index

Sl. No.	Paper Title	Author	Page No.
01	The Educational Status of Minority Community in Bhatli Village, Bargarh, Odisha: A Study	Mrs. Sonia Mahakur	04-12
02	A Study of Effect of Teaching Aptitude of English Teachers of Secondary Schools upon the Academic Achievement of Students	Dr. Vikrant Mishra	13-19
03	Academic Optimism and Academic Achievement	Mahmood Safari MohammadHassanKavoosi SeyedHassanChavoshi	20-34
04	Professional Aspiration Pattern of Prospective-Teachers	Dr. Shruti Tandon	35-55
05	Choice Based Credit System-Do Our Universities Prepare for it?	Indrajeet Dutta	56-68
06	Comparative Study of the Teaching Aptitude of Fresh Categories of Student Teachers with those of In-Service Categories in Relation to their Rural-Urban Background	Rajesh Kumar Srivastav Dr. V.K.Rai	69-81
07	Self-Help Groups: Poverty Alleviation- A Case Study of Nayagarh District of Odisha.	Gopal Krishna Jena	82-98
08	Personal and Social Adjustment of Potential Delinquents and Non-Delinquents of District – Baramulla	Ghulam Mohammad Wani Dr. Geeta Rani Sharma	99-113
09	Personality and Self Efficacy as Determinants of Job Satisfaction of Senior Secondary School Teachers of Haryana.	Dr. Anju SHARMA Dr. Madhu SAHNI	114-137
10	An Assessment of Mid Day Meal Scheme in Primary Schools of Jalpaiguri District (undivided) in West Bengal	Manik Aich Sarkar	138-157
11	National Mission on Higher Education (RUSA)-What Does It Mean for State Funded Universities?	Dr. Neeti Dutta	158-178
12	Problems of Education in India: Theory or Practical	Dr. Ritu Bala	179-185
13	Primary Education System in Lakshadweep	Dr. Baiju K. Nath Farsana A.K.	186-194
14	Psychological predictors of academic achievement in adolescent students of XI grade.	Honey Premendra	195-209
15	Relation between Substance Use and Parental Control among undergraduate student	Suvashree Roy Chowdhury	210-218

16	A Study of Scientific Temperament Among Higher Secondary Students	Dr. Vinod Kumar Singh Raghavendra Pratap Shukla	219-229
17	Enhancement of Creative Writing Ability in Poetry through Participatory Approach	Rajkumari Mishra Chhaya Goel	230-255
18	Impact of Socio-Emotional Adjustment on Academic achievement of Adolescent Girls in Jammu and Kashmir	Dr. Showkeen Bilal Ahmad Gul	256-267
19	Role of Education in Knowledge-based Economy	Dr. Asadollahabbasi Omid Arad	268-276
20	Teaching in the Knowledge Age: Challenges for Teachers and Schools of India	Dr. Sutapa Bose	277-291
21	Self Evaluation in Student Teaching	Dr. S.Prakash	292-300
22	Reflective Practice – A Valuable Tool for Building Social Inclusion in India?	Dr. Susan M.B. Davies	301-329
23	Students' Perception of Academic Library Services in their Learning Progress	Sumayya Al Rasbi Solomon Arulraj David	330-358
24	Current Innovation for Teacher Education in Indian Education	Dr. Sunil Kumar Sain	359-370
25	A Study of attitude of teacher trainees towards teaching profession.	Sailaja kaza	371-279
26	The Octa-Hedral Structure of Intellect	Moumita Saha	380-388
27	New horizons of ICT for Women	Monika Gupta Prof. Nidhi Bala	389-405
28	Implementation of Health Service Program in Schools	Dr. Sunita Singh	406-420
29	Decentralised Educational Governance in India- Challenges to Universalisation of Elementary Education	Anuradha Bose	421-434

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Paper-1

**The Educational Status of Minority
Community in Bhatli Village, Bargarh,
Odisha: A Study**

Mrs. Sonia Mahakur

The Educational Status of Minority Community in Bhatli Village, Bargarh, Odisha: A Study

Mrs. Sonia Mahakur¹

Abstract

Education shows us the best way or path for better lively hood; it is the key to development education considered to be a boon best wood upon man by god makes him different from other animals. Education shows the bright path in darkness. Thousand years' progress and marked changes has been possibly only through education. Man search for knowledge is continuing since the creation of civilization and it will continue till the time in finite. For this reason Govt. is taking so many steps like Sarva Sikshya Abhiyan (SSA), Rastriya Madyamik Sikshya Abhiyan (RMSA) and Right to education Act for free and compulsory education up to 6-14 year of students and for development of Gross enrollment ratio in education. Besides the educational condition of the villages are low. Literacy figure in India indicates that literacy percentage of men is much higher than women, which is considered as an obstacle on the way of development of our country.

Keywords: Minority Community, Drop Out, Wastage, stagnation, Gross enrollment Ratio.

Introduction-

Bargarh District formed on the 1st April 1993. Bargarh District lies on the western most corner of Odisha .As per administrative set ups are implicated, Bargarh is the headquarters of the District. There are two sub divisions in the District, Bargarh and Padampur. Total number of Tahasils is 12 viz. Attabita, Bargarh, Barpali, Bhatli, Bheden, Padampur, Paikmal, Sohella, Bijepur and Gaisilet. There are total 248 Gram Panchayats and 1208 Revenue villages in the

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District. Bhatli being the Tahasils headquarter it is also an important cultural place of Bargarh, around 25000 people lives here from different communities. Although maximum Hindu community lives in Bhatali other minority community likes Muslim and Christian also lives here peacefully and cooperatively. Muslim population is constituted second to any other community after Hindus in Bahtali village. Author taken study of Muslim community among any other minority communities for research studies. In Bhatli village the population of Muslim community taken for studies is 192 members of 30 families, out of which 86 male, 68 female and 38 children below 18 age group.

Needs of the study-

To know the problems related to their education of students depends upon different factors like home and school environment socially economy condition of parents of education and their related factors. Education is a pivotal process for reconstruction of nation and society is a faithfully attempts to find out the educational status of Muslim community of Bhatli village.

Statement of the problem-

The problem has been studied as “The Educational status of Minority Community in Bhatali Village: A Study”.

Objective of the study-

- To study the educational status of Muslim community of Bhatli village.
- To investigate the ignorance of people regarding population explosion and about its hamper.
- To find out economic standard of people from different income groups.
- To find out the educational problem of this category of people.

Aims of the study-

The aims of the study are-

- To find out the numbers of children of school going age in Bhatli village.
- To find out educational status of the people.
- To find out wastage of boys and girls.
- To find out stagnation of boys and girls.

Significance of the study-

There are some reasons. These are-

- There are some families who are not able to send their children to school because of poor financial condition.
- Some orthodox people do not like girl's education.
- Girls help their mother at home, therefore they withdraw from school without completion of primary education.
- Early marriage is another cause.

Delimitation of the study-

- The study is delimited to Muslim community of Bhatli village both male and female.
- The study is limited to the 30 families of Bhatli village.
- The study is limited to the educational status of Muslim community only in Bhatli village.

Hypothesis-

The main hypothesis of my study is that the Muslim community shows positive attitude towards education but the educational status of Muslim community in Bhatli village is very low.

Methodology-

Methodologies the vital aspect of any research work the investigator has used survey method for the collection of data.

Nature of Sample-

Sample is the true representative of whole population. It is the reflection of whole population. It is a study conducted on all the villagers of the Village Bhatli. The sample has been purpose fully for the study.

Collection of Data-

In under to collect data the investigator keeping in view objectives of the study prepared on interview schedule. The interview schedule was prepared to collect information from the villagers. After preparing the schedules the investigator personally went to the village and meet the family members and collected information as stated above with the help of the information schedule.

Tools and techniques use for data collection-

For the purpose of data collection in the present survey and questionnaire schedule was prepared .The schedule deal with educational status of Muslim community in Bhatli village. The schedule provision for collecting data regarding their educational status, financial problem, needs etc. I went to the village and conducted to seek data from the villagers of Muslim community. I had already all opinion and all view of the Muslim community of Bhatli village. The total observation has been noted down by the investigator.

Analysis and Interpretation-

After collecting data they were tabulated to derive desirable finding of the study.

Table – 1

Educational status of adult male and female persons of Muslim community in Bhatli village (Above 18years)

Members	Total Adult Members	Literate		Illiterate
Male	86	85	98%	1
Female	68	56	82%	12
Total	154	141	91%	13

Interpretation-

There are 154 adult members of Muslim community in village Bhatli. Out of which 86 male and 68 are female. Total literacy percentage among them is 91% (141). Male literacy percentage is 98% (85) and Female literacy percentage is 82% (56)

Table – 2

Educational status of male & female school going age children (3-14 years)

Members	Total no. of school going aged children	Going School	Not going school
Male	13	11	02
Female	11	09	02
Total	24	20(83%)	04

Interpretation-

There are total 24 schools going age children between 3 to 14 years in Muslim community of village Bhatli, out of which 13 are male and 11 are female. Total percentage of school going children is 83% (20) and rest 4 is not going to schools.

Table – 3

Educational status of male & female youth of college going age in village Bhatli (15-20 years)

Members	Total no. of college going youth	Going to college	Not going to college
Male	13	02	11
Female	17	04	13
Total	29	06 (20%)	24 (82%)

Interpretation-

There is total 29 college going age adolescents between ages 15 to 20 years. Out of which 13 are male and 17 are female. The total no. of college going students is only 06 (20%) rest 24 (82%) are not going to college.

Table – 4

Total percentage of matriculate & +2 & B.A. above age 15.

Age	Total Persons	Matriculate	+2	B.A.
15-25	40	17	5	2
25-35	22	11	1	2
35-45	12	7	-	-
45-55	27	7	1	-
55-65	27	1	-	-
65-75	04	-	-	-
75 & above	02	-	-	-
Total	134	33 (25%)	7 (6%)	4 (3%)

Interpretation-

Among the persons above age 15 onwards in Muslim communities in village Bhatli. There are total 134 members out of them there are total 33 (25%) are matriculate, 7 (6%) are +2 completed person and 4 (3%) are graduates. Among the age group 15-25 there are highest 75 members are +2 completed and 2 members are graduates. Above age 65 all are under metric.

Summary and Conclusion-

Findings-

On the basis of analysis and interpretation of collect data in the preceding chapter the main findings derived in the present study are as under –

- The educational status of people of Muslim community in Bhatli village is satisfactory.
- There are total 44 (33%) persons having educational qualification above matriculate.
- Total literacy percentage is 91% (141 out of 154).
- Female literacy is 82% and male literacy is 98%
- Out of 24 school going children, 83% (24) are going to school
- Among the college going age youth that is 29 total persons only 06 (20%) are going to college rest 82% (24) have drop out.

- Dropout rate among the college going age children is very high among them.

Suggestions-

- The dropout rate should reduce among the youth college going age .Children should be motivated financially by stipends, scholarship and other facilities to go college and continue higher education.
- Separate school should be opened at primary level for them.
- Adult education program me should be opened for illiterate adults.
- Those who have left out education in completed should be encouraged to continue education by non-formal mode.
- Language, culture and interest of Muslim community must be respected and taken care of minority groups.

Conclusion -

Muslim community constitutes a major portion of village Bhatli. Development of Bhatli's in parable without the educational, economical & social development of people of this community. It was found that the educational status of Muslim people in village Bhatli satisfactory, But there is a need to take care of the dropout among them. They should be encourage to continue higher education because the poor, so they should be motivated for higher education.

References-

- Dash, M. K., Puhan, R. R., & Malla, L. (2013). Education of Tribal Girl's In Keonjhar District of Odisha: A Critical Analysis. Available at http://www.edupublication.com/eperspectives/second%20volume/Education%20of%20Tribal%20Girl_s%20In%20Keonjhar%20District%20of%20Odisha.pdf
- Kazi, S. (1999). Muslim women in India (Vol. 98, No. 2). London: Minority Rights Group International. Available at <http://www.iiav.nl/epublications/1999/muslimwomenindia.pdf>

- Nangia, P., & Khan, N. (2002). Educational Deprivation and Employment Status of Children in Rural Areas of Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh and Orissa: Evidences from NFHS-2. Coming to Grip with Rural Child Work: A Food Security Approach, Institute for Human Development and United Nations World Food Programme, New Delhi.
- Patel, S. (1991). Tribal Education in India: A Case Study of Orissa. Mittal Publications. Available at Tribal Education in India: A Case Study of Orissa (Google eBook)
- Rout, A. (2013). Socio-economic conditions of Hill Kharia tribe in Jashipur block in Mayurbhanj district of Odisha (India). International Journal of Research in Sociology and Social Anthropology, 1(2), 45-51. Available at <http://open.ijrssa.com/index.php?journal=j&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=2>

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Paper-2

**A Study of Effect of Teaching Aptitude of English
Teachers of Secondary Schools upon the Academic
Achievement of Students**

Dr. Vikrant Mishra

A Study of Effect of Teaching Aptitude of English Teachers of Secondary Schools upon the Academic Achievement of Students

Dr. Vikrant Mishra²

Abstract

Aptitude is everything. If you have a positive aptitude, you can do each and everything in life. You can achieve your goals successfully .A teacher with a positive or high teaching aptitude can do miracles in the life of his students. He can be an asset to the nation. With his efforts, the goals of education can be attained fruitfully. Similarly a teacher with negative or low teaching aptitude can't be a role model for his students. He can't make them an ideal and competent citizen of the country. A teacher with a negative or low teaching aptitude can ruin the career of the students. This paper throws light on the teaching aptitude of the English teachers and the effect of the aptitude on the academic achievement of their students. It shows that the English teachers of secondary schools having high teaching aptitude resulted in better productivity of young minds.

Key Words: Teaching Aptitude, Academic Achievement, Secondary School English Teachers

Introduction-

Primary learning begins at home but secondary and formal learning starts from school. The school is considered as a second home for most kids. Teachers are one of the more influential people in the lives of our children. Teachers are those who impart education to students who will be tomorrow's leaders. A teacher is the embodiment of honesty, courage, justice and wisdom and above all he is a Karamayogi who believes in purity of thought and action. The document "challenge of education- a policy perspective (1985)" has highlighted

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teacher's performance in the most crucial input in the field of education. No development of new technology can revolutionize the classroom teaching unless capable and committed teachers are in teaching profession. The success of a teacher depends not only what he does but also on what he is. A competent teacher has self-control, good teaching aptitude and work-oriented mind.

In our Indian culture, we call teacher "the Guru", **Gu** means darkness and **Ru** means light; which when put the syllables together it means "a person who takes you out of the darkness in order to see light". The primary and main aim of an ideal teacher is to prepare the student with the vision of leadership, through motivated educational system. The thought is that Mothers bring children to this World, but teachers bring the World to them. A teacher is a leader, who is always dynamic and believes in change and have the capacity to prepare future leaders and develop in them the skills that they may need to succeed in the future. A teacher who leads understands the human aspect of living; not just someone who is all about academic standards or just following the national curriculum. A teacher who leads knows exactly what the world needs, what his student needs. He is compassionate, warm, lovable, optimistic, kind and well-meaning person. He offers not just the time of the day at school – rather he offers his life to the children he teaches. He is confident in his students; he gets to their spirits and empowers them to grow, mature and develop into the best possible citizen for the future.

The following objectives have been framed for the present study.

Objectives-

1. To study the teaching aptitude of English teachers of secondary schools.
2. To study the difference between teaching aptitude of government and private English teachers of secondary schools.
3. To study the difference between teaching aptitude of male and female English teachers of secondary schools.

4. To study the difference between academic achievement of government and private schools.

Methodology of Research-

The purpose of the study was to study the teaching aptitude of English teachers of secondary schools and its effect upon academic achievement of students. To achieve it, the survey method was adopted. The survey approach to educational problems is one of the most commonly used approaches. It is used in studying local as well as state, national and international aspects of education.

Sample-

A good sample is representative of the entire population as possible and ideally it must provide whole of the information about the population from which the sample has been drawn. In the present study, 50 English teachers of 10 secondary schools of Faridabad district were selected as a sample from the population through the convenient sampling method. The sample consisted of 25 male and 25 female English teachers out of which 25 teachers were from government and 25 from private schools.

Tool Used-

After determining the sample of the study, the next step is to select suitable tool for the collection of data. Success of research depends upon how objectively and adequately the required and relevant data are collected. The investigator used Teacher's Teaching Aptitude Questionnaire by Dr. R. P. Srivastava and Dr. (Smt.) Geeta Tiwari (1986) for the present study.

Administration of the Tool-

The investigators personally visited the schools and met the Head master/Head mistress of the selected schools. Questionnaire was distributed among the teachers and the same was collected by the investigator.

Statistical technique Employed-

In the present study, there have been one dependent variable i.e. Academic Achievement and one independent variable i.e. Teachers Teaching Aptitude. In order to find out the relationship between academic achievement and teaching aptitude, t – test was administered.

Main Findings-

1. There existed no significant difference between teaching aptitude of government and private secondary school English teachers. It stated that all government and private secondary school English teachers had the same capacity of teaching aptitude.
2. There existed no significant difference between teaching aptitude of male and female secondary school English teachers. This meant that all male and female English teachers of secondary schools had the same capacity of teaching aptitude.
3. There existed no significant difference between academic achievement of students of government and private secondary schools. It stated that all government and private secondary school English teachers had the same capacity of teaching aptitude and teaching competency.
4. There existed significant difference between academic achievement of students of high teaching aptitude English teachers and low teaching aptitude English teachers. It stated that the English teachers who had high teaching aptitude showed better academic achievement of the students.

Educational Implications-

1. The schools whose teachers show more teaching aptitude, show better academic achievement of students.
2. The educational qualification of the English teachers does influence their aptitude towards teaching.
3. The high teaching aptitude English teachers should be given proper training through seminars, workshops and refresher courses so that there

is increase in their potentialities that will be beneficial on part of the students.

Conclusion-

After going through the paper, we can conclude that the teacher plays an important role in the life of his students. He should be a role model for the students. The future of the nation i.e. the students should get maximum benefit from him. The Teaching aptitude of the teacher play vital role in framing the future of the students. If the teacher is having high teaching aptitude, only then he can understand the child and help him in finding his place in the society which will uplift the nation.

References-

- Anita Devi (2013). A comparative study of teacher educators of government-financed and self financed colleges of education in relation to their professional values, teaching aptitude and job satisfaction. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis. Maharishi Dayanand University.
- Dushyant Kaur. (2007). Academic achievement, teaching aptitude and the personality traits as the predictors of success in elementary teacher training. Ph.D. thesis. Jamia Milia, Islamia University, New Delhi.
- Garg, M. and Gakhar, S (2009). Explaining academic achievement in secondary teacher training programme through distance mode, Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education - TOJDE, Vol. 10, No. 3, Article 8.
- Mangal, S.K. (2009). Advanced Educational Psychology. Ed.2, New Delhi: PHI Learning private Limited.
- Mishra, S.G. (2007). Teaching Attitude Score a criterion for Admission in colleges of education. Edutracks, February 2007, Vol.6 – No.6 pg.25-27.
- Green, R. (2000). Natural forces: How to significantly increase student achievement in the third millennium. Monticello, FL: Educational Services Consortium.

- Gill, S., & Reynolds, A. (1999). Educational expectations and school achievement in urban African American children. *Journal of School Psychology, 37*(4), 403-424.
- Goodard, R., Hoy, W., & Woolfolk-Hoy, A. (2000). Collective teacher efficacy: Its meaning, measure, and impact on student achievement. *American Educational Research Journal, 37*(2), 279-507.
- Howley, C., & Howley, A. (2004). School size and the influence of socioeconomic status on student achievement: Confronting the threat of size bias in national data sets. *Educational Policy Analysis Archives, 12*(52). Retrieved September 2009, from <http://epaa.asu.edu/epaa/v12n52/>
- Gopalacharyalu, R.V.V. (1984). A study of relationship between certain psychological factors and achievement of student teachers in teacher training institutes of Andhra Pradesh. Unpublished doctoral thesis. In Buch M.B. (Ed.) *4th Survey of Educational Research, (1991), 2, 941.*

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Paper-3

**Academic Optimism and Academic
Achievement**

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Academic Optimism and Academic Achievement

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Abstract

The most important factor that should be considered at schools is called academic optimism that depends on positive psychology. The academic optimism has three components consisting of academic emphasis, collective efficacy and faculty trust. Academic emphasis is the push for particular behaviors in the school workplace; it captures the behavioral enactment of efficacy and trust. Collective efficacy is a group belief so it is cognitive. Faculty trust in parents and teachers is an affective response of the school. These three elements of collective optimism interact with each other. Student achievement is a critical feature of school effectiveness. Finally, the academic optimism and its three aspects increase student achievement.

Keywords: Academic optimism, academic emphasis, collective efficacy, faculty trust, student achievement

Introduction-

Today, student achievement has become a hot topic in education, especially with increased accountability for classroom teachers. The ultimate goal for any teacher is to improve the ability level and prepare students for adulthood. Defining student achievement and factors that impact progress is critical to becoming a successful teacher. Therefore, the schools administrators and teachers should considered to the factors that influence student achievement. There are many different cultures in schools. It is essential to understand the

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different cultures in schools. School administrators and teachers need to understand the culture in which they work.

A way to conceptualize the culture of a school is in terms of the collective optimism of principals and teachers. Such optimism is a function of efficacy, faculty trust, and academic emphasis of the school. These three collective properties are not only similar in their nature and function but also in their potent and positive impact on student achievement; in fact, the three properties work together in a unified fashion to create a positive school environment called academic optimism (Hoy, Tarter, and Woolfolk Hoy, 2006a, 2006b; McGuigan and Hoy, 2006; Smith and Hoy, 2006). Many conceptions treat optimism as a cognitive characteristic (Peterson, 2000; Snyder et al., 2002). The current conception of academic optimism, however, includes cognitive, affective, and behavioral components. Collective efficacy is a group belief; it is cognitive. Faculty trust in parents and teachers is an affective response of the school, and academic emphasis is the behavioral enactment of efficacy and trust (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

Academic optimism is a collective set of beliefs about strengths and capabilities in schools that paints a rich picture of human agency in which optimism is the overarching theme that unites efficacy and trust with academic emphasis. A school culture imbued with such beliefs has a sense of the possible. Efficacy provides the belief that the faculty can make a positive difference in student learning; teachers believe in themselves. Faculty trust in students and parents reflects the belief that teachers, parents, and students can cooperate to improve learning, that is, the faculty believes in its students. Academic emphasis is the enacted behavior prompted by these beliefs, that is, the faculty focus on student success in academics. Thus, a school with high academic optimism defines a culture in which the faculty believes that it can make a difference, that students can learn, and academic performance can be achieved (Hoy, Tarter, and

Woolfolk Hoy, 2006b). These three aspects of collective optimism interact with each other (see Figure 1). For example, faculty trust in parents and students facilitates a sense of collective efficacy, but collective efficacy reinforces the trust. Similarly, when the faculty trusts parents, teachers believe they can insist on higher academic standards without fear that parents will undermine them, and emphasis on high academic standards in turn reinforces the faculty trust in parents and students. Finally, when the faculty as a whole believes it can organize and execute actions needed to have a positive effect on student achievement, they will stress academic achievement, and academic emphasis will in turn reinforce a strong sense of collective efficacy. In brief, all the dimensions of academic optimism are in transactional relationships with each other and interact to create a culture of academic optimism in the school workplace (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

FIGURE-1 *The Reciprocal Nature of the Three Dimensions of Academic Optimism*

Source: (Hoy & Miskel, 2013)

Academic Emphasis-

Academic emphasis is the extent to which the school holds high expectations for its students and the degree to which the school community supports those expectations (Hoy & Miskel, 2013). Academic emphasis is the extent to which a school is driven by a quest for academic excellence—a press for academic achievement. High but achievable academic goals are set for students; the

learning environment is orderly and serious; students are motivated to work hard; and students respect academic achievement (Hoy & Miskel, 2005; Hoy, Tarter, & Kottkamp, 1991). Lee and Bryk (1989) were two early researchers who underscored the importance of academic emphasis and student achievement. Hoy and his colleagues (Hoy et al., 1991) also demonstrated that academic emphasis as a collective property was positively and directly related to student achievement in high schools after controlling for SES. Whether school effectiveness was conceived as the commitment of teachers to the school, teachers' judgments of the effectiveness of the school, or actual student test scores, academic emphasis remained a potent force. Academic emphasis and achievement were positively related at both the middle school and high school levels, even after controlling for socioeconomic factors (Hoy & Hannum, 1997; Hoy & Sabo, 1998; Hoy, Tarter, & Bliss, 1990).

Academic emphasis is the enacted behavior prompted by collective efficacy and faculty trust—an emphasis on intellectual pursuits and academic success. In brief, a school with high academic optimism defines a culture in which the faculty believes that it can make a difference, that all students can learn, and that academic performance can be achieved (Hoy, Tarter, and Woolfolk Hoy, 2006b). Although academic optimism has been consistently related to academic achievement regardless of socioeconomic status, how academic optimism explains student achievement has received less attention. We turn to an organizational model for student achievement that synthesizes the research and theory as well as advances an explanation of the dynamics of school achievement (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

Collective Efficacy-

Social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1986, 1997) is a general framework for understanding human learning and motivation. Self-efficacy, a critical component of the theory, is an individual's belief about her or his capacity to

organize and execute the actions required to produce a given level of attainment (Bandura, 1997). Efficacy beliefs are central mechanisms in human agency, the intentional pursuit of a course of action. Individuals and groups are unlikely to initiate action without a positive sense of efficacy. The strength of efficacy beliefs affects the choices individuals and schools make about future plans and actions (Hoy et. al., 2010).

Student achievement and sense of efficacy are related. Researchers have found positive associations between student achievement and three kinds of efficacy beliefs: self-efficacy beliefs of students (Pajares, 1994, 1997), self-efficacy beliefs of teachers (Tschannen-Moran, Woolfolk Hoy, & Hoy, 1998), and teachers' collective efficacy beliefs about the school (Goddard, Hoy, & Woolfolk Hoy, 2000). We focus on the collective efficacy of schools and student achievement because collective efficacy is a school property amenable to change. Within schools, perceived collective efficacy represents judgments about the performance capability of the social system as a whole (Bandura, 1997). Teachers have efficacy beliefs about themselves as well as the entire faculty. Simply put, perceived collective efficacy is the judgment of teachers that the faculty as a whole can organize and execute the actions required to have positive effects on students (Goddard, Hoy, & Woolfolk Hoy, 2004). Bandura (1993) was the first to show the relationship between a sense of collective efficacy and academic school performance, a relationship that existed in spite of low SES. Schools in which the faculty had a strong sense of collective efficacy flourished, whereas those in which faculty members had serious doubts about their collective efficacy declined in academic performance or showed little academic progress. Continuing research has provided support for the importance of collective efficacy in explaining student achievement. Goddard, Hoy, and Woolfolk Hoy (2000) supported the role of collective efficacy in promoting school achievement in urban elementary schools.

The shared beliefs of capacity and ability of teachers and administrators are an important part of the culture of a school. Collective teacher efficacy is the shared perception of teachers in a school that the efforts of the faculty as a whole will have a positive effect on students. According to Bandura (1993, 1997), collective teacher efficacy is an important school property from an organizational perspective because it helps explain the differential effect that schools have on student achievement. At the collective level, a culture of efficacy is a set of beliefs or social perceptions that are strengthened rather than depleted through their use and that give the school a distinctive identity (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

Sources of Collective Efficacy Organizations, like individuals, learn (Cohen and Sproull, 1996); in fact, organizations use processes akin to learning in individuals (Cook and Yanon, 1996). Schools act purposefully in pursuit of their educational goals. For example, one school may be working to raise student achievement scores, whereas another works to increase the rate and quality of parental involvement. Organizational functioning depends on the knowledge, vicarious learning, self-reflection, and self-regulation of individual members. For example, a school that responds to declining achievement scores by implementing a curricular reform that was effective in a neighboring district is engaged in a self-regulatory process that is informed by the vicarious learning of its members. Such examples demonstrate the importance of vicarious learning and self-regulation at the organizational level, although we must recognize that it is through individuals that organizations act. As we have seen, the four primary sources of self-efficacy information are mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and emotional arousal. Just as these sources are critical for individuals, they are also fundamental in the development of collective teaching efficacy (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

Mastery experiences are important for organizations. Teachers as a group experience successes and failures. Successes build strong beliefs in a faculty's sense of collective efficacy; failures undermine it. If success, however, is frequent and too easy, failure is likely to produce discouragement. A resilient sense of collective efficacy requires experience in overcoming difficulties through persistent effort. Indeed, organizations learn by experience and thus are likely to succeed in attaining their goals (Huber, 1996; Levitt and March, 1996).

Direct experience is not the only source of information for teachers about their collective efficacy. Teachers also listen to stories about the accomplishments of their colleagues as well as success stories of other schools. Similarly, the effective schools research describes the characteristics of exemplary schools. So just as *vicarious experience and modeling* serve as effective sources of personal teacher efficacy, they also promote collective teacher efficacy. Organizations learn by observing other organizations (Huber, 1996).

Verbal persuasion is another means of strengthening a faculty's conviction that they have the capabilities to achieve what they seek. Teachers can be changed by talks, workshops, professional development activities, and feedback about achievement. In fact, the more cohesive the faculty the more likely the group as a whole can be persuaded by sound argument. Verbal persuasion alone, however, is not likely to be a powerful change agent, but coupled with models of success and positive direct experience, it can influence the collective efficacy. Persuasion can promote extra effort and persistence, both of which can lead to the solution of problems (Hoy & DiPaola, 2014).

Organizations have affective states. Just as individuals react to stress, so do organizations. Efficacious organizations tolerate pressure and crises and continue to function effectively; in fact, they learn how to adapt and cope with disruptive forces. Less efficacious organizations react in dysfunctional ways when confronted by such problems, which often reinforces their basic

dispositions toward failure. They misinterpret stimuli—sometimes overreacting and other times underreacting or not reacting at all. The affective state of an organization has much to do with how it interprets challenges (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

Formation of Collective Efficacy Although all four of these sources of information are pivotal in the creation of collective efficacy, processing and interpreting the information is critical. Teachers assess what they will require as they engage in teaching; we call this process the analysis of the teaching task. Such analysis occurs at two levels—the individual and the school. At the school level, the analysis produces inferences about the challenges of teaching in that school, that is, what it would take for the school to be successful. Considerations include the abilities and motivations of students, availability of instructional materials, community constraints, and the quality of physical facilities of the school, as well as a general optimism about the capability of the school to deal with negative situations in the students' homes as well as in the school. Teachers analyze the means needed to make the school successful, the barriers or limitations to be overcome, and the resources that are available. Then teachers evaluate the teaching task in conjunction with their assessment of the teaching competency of the faculty; in fact, teachers make explicit judgments of the teaching competence of their colleagues in light of the teaching tasks in their specific school. At the school level, the analysis of teaching competence leads to inferences about the faculty's teaching skills, methods, training, and expertise. Judgments of teaching competence might include faculty beliefs in the ability of all children in their school to succeed. Because the analyses of task and competence occur simultaneously, it is difficult to separate these two domains of collective teaching efficacy. They interact with each other as collective teacher efficacy emerges (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

In sum, the major influences on collective teacher efficacy are assumed to be the analysis and interpretation of the four sources of information—mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and emotional state. In these processes, the organization focuses its attention on two related domains: the teaching task and teaching competence. Both domains are assessed in terms of whether the organization has the capacities to succeed in teaching students. The interactions of these assessments shape collective teacher efficacy in a school. The consequences of high collective teacher efficacy will be the acceptance of challenging goals, strong organizational effort, and a persistence that leads to better performance. Of course, the opposite is also true. Lower collective efficacy leads to less effort, the propensity to give up, and a lower level of performance. The process and components of collective teacher efficacy are similar to those of individual teacher efficacy and are illustrated in Figure 2. As the figure shows, the proficiency of performance provides feedback to the organization, which provides new information that will further shape the collective teacher efficacy of the school. Beliefs about both the task of teaching and the teaching competence, however, are likely to remain unchanged unless something dramatic occurs because, once established, a school culture of efficacy is a relatively stable property that requires substantial effort to change. It is relatively easy to map the collective efficacy of a school because Goddard and his colleagues (Goddard, Hoy, and Woolfolk Hoy, 2000; Goddard, 2002a) have developed several valid and reliable instruments to measure it. Information about the Collective Efficacy Scale (CE Scale), its properties, and scoring directions is available at www.waynekhoy.com.

FIGURE-2 A Model of Collective Efficacy

Source: (Hoy & Miskel, 2013)

Faculty Trust in Parents and Students-

Faculty trust in parents and students is the third school property that is related to student achievement. Faculty trust in parents and students is a collective school property in the same fashion as collective efficacy and academic emphasis. Although one might think that trust in parents and trust in students are separate concepts, several factor analyses have demonstrated they are not (Goddard, Tschannen-Moran, & Hoy, 2001; Hoy & Tschannen-Moran, 1999). Furthermore, Bryk and Schneider (2002) made the theoretical argument that teacher-student trust in elementary schools operates primarily through teacher-parent trust.

Trust is one's vulnerability to another in terms of the belief that the other will act in one's best interests. Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2000), after an extensive review of the literature, concluded that trust is a general concept with at least five facets: benevolence, reliability, competence, honesty, and openness. Although it is theoretically possible that these facets do not vary together, research on schools shows that all five facets of trust in schools do indeed vary together to form an integrated construct of faculty trust in schools, whether the schools are elementary (Hoy & Tschannen-Moran, 1999, 2003) or secondary (Smith, Hoy,

&Sweetland, 2001). Thus, we defined faculty trust as a willingness to be vulnerable to another party based on the confidence that that party is benevolent, reliable, competent, honest, and open (Hoy & Tschannen-Moran, 2003). Cooperation and trust should set the stage for effective student learning, but only a few studies have examined this relationship. Goddard et al. (2001) examined the role of faculty trust in promoting achievement in urban elementary schools. Using a multilevel model, they demonstrated a significant direct relationship between faculty trust in clients (students and parents) and higher student achievement, even after controlling for SES. Similar to collective efficacy, faculty trust was a key property enabling schools to overcome some of the disadvantages of low SES (Hoy et al., 2010).

Conclusion-

The relationships among the three major aspects of academic optimism can be seen as a triadic set of interactions with each element functionally dependent on the others. Faculty trust in parents and students encourages a sense of collective efficacy, and collective efficacy reinforces and enhances trust. Similarly, when the faculty trusts parents, teachers can insist on higher academic standards with confidence that they will not be undermined by parents, and high academic standards in turn reinforce faculty trust. Finally, when the faculty believes it has the capability to organize and execute actions that will have positive effects on student achievement, academic achievement is emphasized, and academic emphasis in turn reinforces a strong sense of collective efficacy. In summary, all of the elements of academic optimism have transactional relationships with each other and interact to create a culture of academic optimism in schools. Hoy and his colleagues (2006) chose the term academic optimism to reflect beliefs about agency in schools. They explained: Optimism is an appropriate overarching construct to unite efficacy, trust, and academic emphasis because each concept contains a sense of the possible. Efficacy is the belief that the faculty can make

positive Academic Optimism of Schools difference in student learning; teachers believe in themselves. Faculty trust in students and parents is the belief that teachers, parents, and students can cooperate to improve learning, that is, the faculty believes in its students. Academic emphasis is the enacted behavior prompted by these beliefs, that is, the focus is student success. Thus, a school with high academic optimism is a collectivity in which the faculty believes that it can make a difference, that students can learn and academic performance can be achieved. Another attraction to the term academic optimism is the idea that it can be learned; a pessimistic school can become optimistic. Academic optimism gains its name from the conviction that its composite properties all express optimism and are malleable. Administrators and teachers have reason to be optimistic. They can be empowered; neither they nor their students are irretrievably trapped by socioeconomic factors.

References-

- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-Efficacy: Toward a Unifying Theory of Behavioral Change. *Psychological Review*, 84, 191—215.
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social Foundations of Thought and Action*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice
- Cohen, M. D., and Sproull, L. S. (Eds.). (1996). *Organizational Learning*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Cook, S. D., and Yanon, D. (1996). Culture and Organizational Learning. In M. D. Cohen and L. S. Sproull (Eds.). *Organizational Learning* (pp. 430—59). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Goddard, R. D., Hoy, W. K., and Woolfolk Hoy, A. (2000). Collective Teacher Efficacy: Its Meaning, Measure, and Impact on Student Achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*, 37, 479—508.
- Goddard, R. D., Tschannen-Moran, M., and Hoy, W. K. (2001). Teacher Trust in Students and Parents: A Multilevel Examination of the

Distribution and Effects of Teacher Trust in Elementary Schools. *Elementary School Journal*, 102, 3—17.

- Hoy, W. K., and Hannum, J. (1997). *Middle School. Climate: An Empirical Assessment of Organizational Health and Student Achievement*. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 33, 290—311.
- Hoy, W. K., and Miskel, C. G. (1991). *Educational Administration: Theory, Research, and Practice* (4th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Hoy, W. K., and Miskel, C. G. (2013). *Educational Administration: Theory, Research, and Practice* (9th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Hoy, W. K., and Sweetland, S. R. (2001). Designing Better Schools: The Meaning and Nature of Enabling School Structure. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 37, 296—321.
- Hoy, W. K., and Tarter, C. J. (1997a). *The Road to Open and Healthy Schools: A Handbook for Change, Secondary Edition*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Hoy, W. K., and Tarter, C. J. (2003). *Administrators Solving the Problems of Practice: Decision-Making Concepts, Cases, and Consequences*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Hoy, W. K., and Tschannen-Moran, M. (1999). Five Faces of Trust: An Empirical Confirmation in Urban Elementary Schools. *Journal of School Leadership*, 9, 184—208.
- Hoy, W. K., and Tschannen-Moran, M. (2003). The Conceptualization and Measurement of Faculty Trust in Schools. In W. K. Hoy and C. Miskel (Eds.). *Studies in Leading and Organizing Schools* (pp. 181—207).
- Hoy, W. K., Tarter, C. J., and Kottkamp, R. (1991). *Open Schools/Healthy Schools: Measuring Organizational Climate*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.

- Hoy, W. K. and Tarter, C. J. (1997b). The Road to Open and Health Schools: Handbook for Change, Elementary Edition. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Huber, G. P. (1996). Organizational Learning: The Contributing Processes and Literatures. In M. D. Cohen, and L. S. Sproull, (Eds.). Organizational Learning (pp. 124—62). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- McGuigan, L., and Hoy, W. K. (2006). Creating a Culture of Optimism to Improve School Achievement. Leadership and Policy in Schools.
- Pajares, F. (1996). Current Directions in Self Research: Self-Efficacy. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, New York.
- Smith, D. D. (2006). Introduction to Special Education: Teaching in an Age of Opportunity (5th ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.

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Paper-4

**Professional Aspiration Pattern of
prospective-Teachers**

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Professional Aspiration Pattern of prospective–Teachers

Dr. Shruti Tandon⁶

Introduction-

In study of professions, social scientists give attention to the career pattern of professionals. Career pattern includes the occupational choice– the socio psychological factors which motivate the individual to choose and enter a particular profession. According to the existing norms, one is supposed to be free, at least theoretically, to choose a profession. At the same time, there are many instances to show the role of kith and kin to encourage, advice and guide the aspirants to steer along to the road of the profession.

Choosing a profession is a normative phenomenon. It includes, on the one hand, identifiable societal values and norms which, mainly through primary group agencies motivate, direct and condition one's entry to a certain occupation, on the other, it includes the discrete stages through which individuals pass and experience a life's walk in occupational area. Hence, the study of career decision–making provides some understanding about underlying factors determining the choice of career.

There is a series of studies on various aspects of occupational career pattern. Lezarsfeld (1958) was first to make a systematic analysis of occupational choice as a socio–psychological process by reviewing the European studies on this aspect. Ginzberg and his colleagues (1951) build a theory based on an evolution of increasing self–determination as well as increasingly realistic attainment of the individual to his environment as he matures. The individual is thought to go through a period of fantasy (when he cannot assess his capacities), a tentative period (when he weighs various satisfactions) and finally, a realistic period (when he makes compromises between his individual wants and the actual

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opportunities which exist for him). Ginzberg's basic thesis is that occupational choice is a process, that "the process is largely irreversible" (that is, decision once made cannot be "unmade" and that they affect the subsequent career life), and that the process "ends in a compromise". Ginzberg and his associates systematized the process of occupational choice by classifying them in three stages, namely, Fantasy, Tentative and Realistic. They emphasized the role of educational structure and emotional conditions but failed to take into account the reference group members of the chooser.

Miller and Form (1951) are of the view that rational occupational choice is rare and in most cases chance is a deciding factor. Blau and his associates (1956) maintain that lack of information concerning real opportunities restricts choosing an occupation. In India Hiremath (1983) while presenting a comparative profile of Indian and Australian academics career pattern comes to the conclusion that teachers content to take upon academic career even if its extrinsic rewards, e.g., income are less than those offered by other occupations provided that they can enjoy more intrinsic occupational rewards.

Sullivan (1968) is one of those researchers who have conducted empirical study of Teacher-Training Institutes. He shows that these institutes make little impact, if any, on the value orientations and professional aspirations of trainees.

In Indian context the study of career pattern is important from two point of views. Firstly, till seventies the career options were limited and occupations were also having influence of caste but in the current scenario caste as a barrier in the choice of occupation has lost its importance and development of new occupations have provided chance to all to enter in new areas irrespective of their caste. Secondly, entry of females in the professional world is comparatively a new phenomenon. In male dominating Indian society, male is the bread earner of the family but for female members' choice of profession is dependent on their ability, educational level, family condition etc.

Keeping in view different aspects and findings of various studies, a modest attempt has been made in the present study to bring out decision making and other relevant aspects of career pattern of prospective –teachers.

The Study Data-

The present study is based on empirical study of prospective-teachers(also known as student –teachers,future-teachers)who were pursuing B.Ed. in teachers’ training institutes ,affiliated to Jai Narain Vyas University,Jodhpur.As this is the study of both male and female student-teachers,multistage sampling was used for the selection of sample.In the first stage seven training colleges including both women teachers’ training and co-ed teachers’training institutes were selected by lottery method. In second stage, by stratified random sampling using regular method, our sample of 100 male and 100 female student-teachers was selected for the study.The data were collected through interview–schedule. For analysis of quantitative data, besides, mean other statistical techniques such as chi-square, correlation and contingency coefficient were used at appropriate places and .05 was generally accepted as level of significance.

Stages of Choosing a Career-

Teaching could not have the only career the respondents got acquainted with. It is a well known fact that as a child grows and comes in the contact with persons playing different roles, he starts dreaming of his own future role, imagining himself in different roles, he observes other playing. This process goes on over a number of years till the final career choice is made. Keeping this in mind, respondents were asked about their desired occupations in childhood. Interestingly, 70.0 percent of the respondents mentioned a variety of occupations as their childhood desire. Remaining 30.0 percent of respondents had not thought for going for some occupation in their childhood.

Table 1 clearly reflects respondents’ imagination of their future occupational role. The largest group of respondents (15.5 percent) mentioned teaching as

their childhood dream occupation. In conversation such respondents credited their teachers who were their role models for generating their inclination towards teaching profession. Another 8.0 percent of our respondents desired to go for engineering services. Other occupations, as mentioned by our respondents were Banking services (6.0 percent) and corporate services/accountancy (6.0 percent). While 5.5 percent respondents mentioned their dream to become doctor. Similar proportion of respondents mentioned about administrative services (5.5 percent) and aviation services (5.5 percent) as their childhood desire. Explaining their dreams, these respondents admitted that they thought that by becoming IAS officers and joining other allied services, they can contribute much towards their motherlands service. Another 5.5 percent respondents also dreamed of serving their motherland by becoming Pilot in Air Force which was classified in Aviation category. A few student-teachers mentioned some other services they desired for, such as Military services, Police services, Designing, Legal provision and Singing. Interestingly, these respondents had gather impressions of these various services by seeing their kith and kins in their childhood.

Table-1

Respondents Desired Occupation in Childhood

Occupation	Male	Female	Total
Teaching	12 (12.0)	19 (19.0)	31 (15.5)
Engineering	10 (10.0)	6 (6.0)	16 (8.0)
Banking Services	5 (5.0)	7 (7.0)	12 (6.0)
Corporate Services/Accountancy	4 (4.0)	8 (8.0)	12 (6.0)
Medical Services	5 (5.0)	6 (6.0)	11 (5.5)
Administrative Services	5 (5.0)	6 (6.0)	11 (5.5)
Aviation Services	3 (3.0)	8 (8.0)	11 (5.5)

Military Services	4 (4.0)	5 (5.0)	9 (4.5)
Designing	5 (5.0)	3 (3.0)	8 (4.0)
Legal Services	5 (5.0)	2 (2.0)	7 (3.5)
Police Services	2 (2.0)	5 (5.0)	7 (3.5)
Singing	–	5 (5.0)	5 (2.5)
Not Applicable	40 (40.0)	20 (20.0)	60 (30.0)
Total	100 (100.0)	100 (100.0)	200 (100.0)

A comparison of data in terms of sex shows that slightly more female (19.0 percent) than male student-teachers (12.0 percent) thought of becoming teachers in their childhood. There is not much difference for other occupations but a sufficiently high proportion of male respondents (40.0 percent) than their female counterparts (20.0 percent) have not thought of their future career in their childhood.

To desire any occupation in childhood may not necessarily continue in realistic stage of life when one weighs his own capabilities and social pressures in making choice for future. Further, in our educational system after qualifying secondary examination candidates opt for subjects essential for desired occupation.

Respondents were asked whether after qualifying secondary examination they opted for subjects essential for their desired occupation. Two-thirds (66.5 percent) of our respondents claimed that they were able to opt required subjects. Remaining 33.5 percent of respondents could not opt the subjects essential for their desired occupations.

These respondents mentioned various reasons for this. Non-availability of subjects in school which were essential to go in for desired occupations, hampered the way of 8.5 percent of our respondents. Lower percentage in secondary examination affected 4.5 percent respondents adversely whereas family problems denied another 4.5 percent respondents' choice to opt for the

subject of their choice. A handful of students admitted that they could not get proper guidance at the time of choosing subjects (8.0 percent) while an equal proportion of respondents (8.0 percent) were not serious about their future career.

Respondents' Stage to Opt Some Occupation-

Though learning is a life long process but at a certain specific state of formal education an individual has to opt for a stream of education to pursue for certain career in future. Respondents were asked about the stage they thought to opt some occupation.

Analysis of Table 2 shows that only 17.5 percent of our respondents in their childhood only thought to opt some occupation. School stage proved influencing to opt for some occupation for 27.5 percent of respondents. There were 35.0 percent of respondent who said that in college/university stage they thought to opt for some occupation. They said that at college/university stage career was the major topic of discussion among classmates which forced them to opt some occupation. Remaining 20.0 percent of respondents mentioned to opt for some occupation after completing P.G.

Table-2
Respondents' Stage to Opt Some Occupation

Stage	Male	Female	Total
During childhood stage	20 (20.0)	15 (15.0)	35 (17.5)
At school stage	25 (25.0)	30 (30.0)	55 (27.5)
At college/university stage	30 (30.0)	40 (40.0)	70 (35.0)
After completing education (Post graduation)	25 (25.0)	15 (15.0)	40 (20.0)
Total	100 (100.0)	100 (100.0)	200 (100.0)

$\chi^2 = 5.05$, non significant at .05 level

It is generally assumed that boys thought of their career earlier in life as they are socialized to perform their role of bread winner in the family. Girls, on the other hand are mainly socialized to perform domestic duties. They have the choice to opt or not to opt professional role, though proportion of girls opting for a career is increasing gradually. Keeping this in view the dependence of both the variables, i.e. sex and stage to opt some occupation was tested.

Sexwise comparison shows that more than a half of our respondents irrespective of sex, thought of some career in college/university stage or after completing their education, i.e., in realistic stage of their life. χ^2 test does not show the probability of association. Both variables are independent. Hence it can safely be said that the stage to opt some occupation is not influenced by the sex of student-teachers.

Level of Academic Performance-

The level of intelligence is, generally, determined by measuring the I.Q. Since the testing of I.Q. was not practical in this study, the level of intelligence was deduced objectively on the basis of academic performance of our respondents. They were asked to mention divisions obtained in various examinations, namely Secondary, Senior Secondary, Graduation and Post-Graduation. The respective scores given for obtaining first, second and third division were 3, 2 and 1. Mean scores ranging from 2.5 to 3.0 were included in the category of 'Bright' academic performance, mean scores ranging from 2.0 to 2.4, the category of 'Average' academic performance and mean scores less than 2.0 in the category of 'Low' academic performance. Data are presented in Table 3.

Table-3

Academic Performance of Respondents

Academic performance	Male	Female	Total
Bright	50 (50.0)	40 (40.0)	90 (45.0)

Average	44 (44.0)	51 (51.0)	95 (47.5)
Low	6 (6.0)	9 (9.0)	15 (7.5)
Total	100 (100.0)	100 (100.0)	200 (100.0)

$\chi^2 = 2.23$, Non-significant at .05 level

It is evident from the Table 3 that 45.0 percent of the respondents have a 'Bright' academic performance. A little less than a half (47.5 percent) of respondents have an 'Average' academic performance. Remaining 7.5 percent of respondents have 'Low' academic performance.

Sexwise comparison of data shows that a half of our male respondents and 40.0 percent of our female respondents possess bright academic performance. A little more than a half of our female student-teachers, on the other hand, possess an average academic performance while 44.0 percent of male respondents come in this category. However, chi-square test does not show any significant difference in this regard. Hence it can be said that both the variables are independent.

Relationship between Level of Academic Performance and Preference to Teaching-

Having brought out the level of academic performance of our respondents, it was considered worthwhile to find out if the level of academic performance has any influence on preference to teaching as a career. To analyze this aspect, respondents' choice for profession was classified in two categories namely 'Teaching' and 'Other professions' and its relationship with the level of academic performance was analyzed.

Data reveals that among those respondents who have a bright academic career, 54.4 percent have preferred teaching as their career choice while 45.6 percent wanted to go in some other profession.

Among those who have an average academic calibre, 56.8 percent respondents preferred to opt for teaching while 43.2 percent respondents desired for some other profession. Among those respondents who have a low academic

performance, 60.0 percent student–teachers wanted to go for teaching against 40.0 percent of their counterparts who wanted to go for some other profession. It indicates the tendency of increase in proportion of those students who have liking for teaching with decrease in level of academic performance but the difference is negligible. Chi–square is non–significant at 0.5 level hence it can be inferred that both the variables are independent. There is no evidence of association between level of academic performance and preference to teaching and hypothesis can be rejected.

Analysis in terms of sex shows interesting pattern. As is clear from Table 4 among those male respondents who have either bright or average academic performance, a little more than a half of them (52.0 percent and 52.2 percent respectively) had preferred other professions and opted for teaching as an alternative choice. Contrary to it, more respondents with low academic calibre had liking for teaching.

Table-4
Level of Academic Performance and Preference of Male Respondents for Teaching

Academic performance of respondents	Teaching	Other profession	Total
Bright	24 (48.0)	26 (52.0)	50 (100.0)
Average	21 (47.7)	23 (52.2)	44 (100.0)
Low	4 (66.7)	2 (33.3)	6 (100.0)
Total	49 (49.0)	51 (51.0)	100 (100.0)

$\chi^2=0.795$, Non– significant at .05 level

However, chi–square does not show any significant relationship between the two variables.

As far as female respondents are concerned we find the same pattern. Table 5 clearly shows that more than a half of female student–teachers of each category of academic level preferred teaching than other profession to opt for. Among those who have a bright academic performance, 62.5 percent preferred teaching while 64.7 percent of those respondents who have an average academic career, preferred teaching. In comparison to those, only 55.6 percent female respondents with low academic performance preferred teaching. However, chi–square is non–significant at 0.05 level hence proves that both the variables are independent to each other and no association is observed in level of academic performance and preference to teaching in case of female respondents.

Table-5

Level of Academic Performance and Preference of Female Respondents for Teaching

Academic performance of respondents	Teaching	Other profession	Total
Bright	25 (62.5)	15 (37.5)	40 (100.0)
Average	33 (64.7)	18 (35.3)	51 (100.0)
Low	5 (55.6)	4 (44.4)	9 (100.0)
Total	63 (63.0)	37 (37.0)	100 (100.0)

$\chi^2=0.158$, Non– significant at .05 level

Motivating Factors in Choice of Teaching as a Career-

Choice of a career depends on many factors ranging from socio–cultural to personal and accidental. According to Rosenberg (1957) choice is made having in view some value perspectives which determine the priority of the choice. While making occupational choice one could be influenced by certain attitudes which condition the individual perception of the world. Money and security are the two important values which influence the occupational choice in the modern

society. About social determinants of occupational choice, Rosenberg observes that the prevailing conditions– both economic and social– and the society determine the range and context of fulfillment of the individuals’ expectations and aspirations. Thus, understanding of motivation behind choice of career provides a basis for a clear perspective about a profession.

In conformity with the dominant social values, it is likely that generally idealistic reasons would be reported for entering a career such as intrinsic interest in teaching or service orientation. Salary consideration and strenuous work situation would seldom be reported.

However, when asked to estimate the motivation to enter the teaching profession, an interesting syndrome has emerged from the responses obtained. For the convenience of analysis these responses were grouped in the following broad categories:

(1)	Self orientation	[including responses like earning of name and fame]
(2)	Professional orientation	[including responses like interest in teaching]
(3)	Utilitarian orientation	[it includes responses like earning of money, safe job, preparation for other competitive exams, more job opportunities, more government vacancies etc.]
(4)	Humanitarian orientation	[includes responses like noble profession and to serve the country]
(5)	Familistic orientation	[it includes responses like to fulfill parent’s desire, time for family]
(6)	No particular orientation	[Includes response like got selected in B.Ed.]

Data shown in Table 6 reflect that not a single factor worked as the central factor in motivating our respondents to opt for this career. Utilitarian orientation worked as an important factor in case of 20.0 percent respondents. These respondents were those who considered teaching job as a guarantee of safe and secured future. They regarded teaching as a gateway for safe job, sufficient earnings, more opportunities especially in government school i.e., public sector as well as availability of time and chance for preparation for other competitive examinations.

The second group is constituted of those 19.0 percent respondents who categorically mentioned that they entered in this profession with professional orientation. Their interest in teaching serves as the motivating factor for these candidates.

The third group is constituted of those respondents who were having the motivation of earning name and fame. These 18.5 percent of respondents regarded self-orientation as motivational factor in the choice of teaching as a career. Almost an equal number of male and female respondents mentioned self orientation as their motivation.

Another 17.5 percent of the respondents mentioned familistic orientation as motivating factor. These respondents said that they choose teaching career to fulfill their parents' desire to be in this profession. This group of respondents also felt that this is the profession in which time for family can be taken out easily along with fulfillment of professional liabilities.

The next category 'humanitarian orientation' weighed importance in case of 16.5 percent of the respondents. Their conscience motivated them to serve the society and this profession, according to them, offered a way to that end.

In respect of some respondents (8.5 percent) chance played a role. These respondents admitted that they got selected in B.Ed., as a result, without any particular orientation, they were pursuing this degree course.

Table-6

Motivating Factors in Choice of Teaching as a Career

Factor	Male	Female	Total
Utilitarian orientation	27 (27.0)	13 (13.0)	40 (20.0)
Professional orientation	17 (17.0)	21 (21.0)	38 (19.0)
Self orientation	19 (19.0)	18 (18.0)	37 (18.5)
Familistic orientation	14 (14.0)	21 (21.0)	35 (17.5)
Humanitarian orientation	14 (14.0)	19 (19.0)	33 (16.5)
No particular orientation	9 (9.0)	8 (8.0)	17 (8.5)
Total	100 (100.0)	100 (100.0)	200 (100.0)

Comparison of data in terms of sex shows interesting gender consideration. Though almost an equal proportion of male and female student-teachers were motivated by professional, self and humanitarian orientations, the proportion of women having familistic orientation was little higher (21.0 percent) than male respondents (14.0 percent). Further, the number of male student-teachers with utilitarian orientation was almost double (27.0 percent) than that of females (13.0 percent). It reflects that economic values, one of the salient components of consumeristic culture, weighed heavily for them.

Stage of Decision for B.Ed.-

One of the characteristics of a profession as mentioned by most of the sociologists including Goode (1957) and Greenwood (1957, 1980) is specialized training in a body of abstract knowledge or theory. The skills that characterize the profession of teaching flow from and are supported by a fund of knowledge gained through systematic research. The science and art of teaching are generally taught in teachers' training institutes.

Respondents were asked that at what stage did they decide to go for B.Ed. Data shown in Table 8 depict that only 5.0 percent of respondents said that at school stage only they decided to get B.Ed. degree and become teacher. A little more

than two fifth (43.5 percent) of respondents decided to go for B.Ed. at the time of completing their graduation, while 17.5 percent respondents decided to pursue for B.Ed. degree at post graduation level. However, 13.0 percent respondents who were already teaching in private institutions without having B.Ed. degree opt to pursue for B.Ed. degree because they felt that salary wise and performance wise they were behind those colleagues who had B.Ed. degree. They realized the importance of B.Ed. degree by experience and hence opted to go for B.Ed. course.

There were 21.0 percent respondents who were preparing for different competitive exams simultaneously, saw the notification for PTET examination in newspapers. As they were aware of the importance of this professional degree in both government and private sector, they choose to appear for this examination also and succeeded in getting admission in this course. Data are shown in Table 7

Table-7
Respondents' Stage to Decide for B.Ed.

Occupation	Male	Female	Total
At school stage	5 (5.0)	5 (5.0)	10 (5.0)
At graduation stage	38 (38.0)	49 (49.0)	87 (43.5)
At post graduation stage	16 (16.0)	19 (19.0)	35 (17.5)
After teaching experience	16 (16.0)	10 (10.0)	26 (13.0)
After seeing notification for PTET exam	25 (25.0)	17 (17.0)	42 (21.0)
Total	100 (100.0)	100 (100.0)	200 (100.0)

$\chi^2 = 4.55$, non significant at .05 level

It is a general assumption that women who are aspirant for a job are more inclined for teaching profession and take decision to choose this profession

earlier than their male counterparts. Sexwise comparison of data shows that while 68.0 percent of women respondents decided to opt teaching career during their college education, 54.0 percent of male respondents thought so. On the other hand, male respondent thought to take up teaching as their career while experiencing teaching (16.0 percent) or preparing for various jobs (25.0 percent) than their female counterparts. The χ^2 test shows that the difference is, however, non significant. Both variables namely, sex and decision for B.Ed. to go for teaching are independent. Hence it can be concluded that sex has not influenced respondents' stage to decide to go for B.Ed.

Career Decision Makers-

It is clear from the collected data that 31.0 percent respondents themselves choose this career. One-fourth of our respondents (25.0 percent) accepted that all major decisions about them were taken by their parents and hence also about their career. These respondents confidently told that they accept parents' decisions which definitely prove beneficial for them in the long run of life.

The role of friends in career decision making was accepted by 23.5 percent of the respondents. Such respondents mentioned that those friends who suggested them for B.Ed. had already completed their B.Ed. course and were in government services of teaching.

Other than friends, some of our respondents (11.5 percent) gave credit to their teachers who provided guidance to them in this perspective. These respondents in conversation accepted that their teachers not only motivated them for B.Ed., but also provided material for preparation for doing B.Ed. entrance examination. Not only that, they were also providing guidance in completing B.Ed. course.

The role of relatives was also accepted by 9.0 percent of the respondents. Hence, it is proved that primary group and significant others have played an important role in deciding about the career of our respondents. It is clear from

the data that in comparison to male respondents (17.0 percent) more female respondents (33.0 percent) were having the suggestion of parents to opt for course of B.Ed. This shows that for female respondents, parents suggestion have great importance for them. For male respondents, the suggestion of friends matters a lot. In comparison to female counterparts (17.0 percent) more male respondents (30.0 percent) discuss issues related to career to their friends and followed their suggestions.

Further, more male (35.0 percent) than female respondents (27.0 percent) were self oriented i.e., they decided on their own to opt for this career. However, primary associates, parents and friends played a major role in case of almost a half of our respondents. Interestingly, parents' role was a more significant in case of female student-teachers, while friends played decisive role in case of male (30.0 percent) respondents than their counterparts (17.0 percent). Chi-square test confirms the existence association between both the variables, namely sex of respondents and decision makers. Contingency coefficient, c , further confirms high level of associate between the two variables.

Socio-Economic Prestige of Occupations-

In every society, each occupation has its own social and economic prestige though not always synonymous. Sometimes social prestige of a given occupation is higher than its associated economic benefits or vice-a-versa.

Respondents were asked to rank first five occupations in the enlisted 13 professions on the basis of:

- i. their respective social prestige and,
- ii. economic benefits attached to them in society, separately.

Preference on the Basis of Social Prestige of Professions-

We have asked the respondents to give their first five preferences to enlisted professions on the basis of their social status and prestige in society. We gave these preferences as 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 score respectively and multiplied them with

their respective frequencies. The profession with highest score was given the first rank profession with the second highest score as second and so on. Data are shown in Table-8

It is clearly evident from the Table 8 that from the point of view of social prestige in society both male and female respondents gave first preference to Medical profession followed by University teaching.

There is, however, slight difference in consecutive ranking of remaining professions. Our female respondents gave third preference to school teaching followed by administrative services of the Center and of State as fourth and fifth preference which were more preferred by male respondents in comparison to school teaching.

Irrespective of sex, Engineering was ranked at sixth. At seventh position our respondents placed Military services followed by Business. Similarly, there is not much difference in their preference to other professions except that Nursing was given eleventh position by female respondents which was given thirteenth position by male respondents. This indicates that though both assign it comparatively low status in hierarchy of professions, in comparison to their male counterparts, female respondents have more soft corner for school teaching and nursing profession which were traditionally considered as feminine professions as they require qualities of affection, softness and care for kids and patients and were more preferred occupations for and by women.

Table-8
Social Prestige of Occupation by Respondents

Occupation	Male	Female
Medical	1	1
University teaching	2	2
Administrative services of the Centre	3	4

Administrative services of the State	4	5
School Teaching	5	3
Engineering	6	6
Military services	7	7
Business	8	8
Legal	9	10
Scientific work	10	12
Chartered Accountant	11	9
Business executive	12	13
Nursing	13	11

$\rho = 0.9$

Spearman's Rho (0.9) shows a very high level of correlation in preference given by our male and female respondents.

Preference on the basis of Economic Benefits Associated with Professions-

The preferences given were then scored as 5 to 1 respectively and total scores for each profession was calculated. Data are shown in Table 9

In this case also our both male and female respondents gave first preference to medical profession followed by administrative services of the Centre at second rank. However, university teaching was placed at third rank and engineering was given fourth rank by our male respondents. From the point of view of economic benefits business was preferred at fifth rank. However, female respondents gave Engineering, Business and University teaching as their third, fourth and fifth preference.

Irrespective of sex, administrative services of the State at sixth rank by male and female respondents. Male respondents gave legal, chartered accountant and military services seventh, eighth and ninth rank respectively, whereas twelfth, seventh and eleventh rank respectively were given by female respondents to these professions. School teaching was given tenth rank by our respondents.

Male respondents gave nursing, scientific work and business executive as eleventh, twelfth and thirteen rank respectively and female respondents gave them thirteen, ninth and eighth rank respectively.

Table-9

Respondents' Preference by Economic Benefits of Occupations

Occupation	Male	Female
Medical	1	1
Administrative services of the Centre	2	2
University teaching	3	5
Engineering	4	3
Business	5	4
Administrative services of the State	6	6
Legal	7	12
Chartered Accountant	8	7
Military services	9	11
School Teaching	10	10
Nursing	11	13
Scientific work	12	9
Business executive	13	8

$\rho = 0.8$

Spearman's Rho (0.8) shows a very high level of correlation in preferences given by our male and female respondents on the basis of economic benefits associated with these occupations. In short, it may be concluded that medical profession, university teaching and administrative services are such jobs which are considered socially and economically prestigious in society.

References-

- Blau, P. et.al., (1956); Occupational Choice: A Conceptual Framework, *Industrial & Labour Relation Review*, Vol. IX, pp. 531-43.

- Ginzberg,et.al.,(1951); *Occupational Choice: An Approach to a General Theory*, New York, Columbia University Press
- Goode,W.J.,(1957); *Community within a Community: The Professions, American Sociological Review*, Vol.22
- Greenwood, E., (1957); “Attributes of a Profession”, *Social Work*, Vol. 2 pp. 45–55
- Greenwood, E., (1980); *Attributes of a Profession: Revisited, “The Emergence of Social Welfare & Social Work, Gilbert N. & Herry Specht”, Itasca, Illinois, F. E. Peacock Publishers.*
- Hiremath, S.G., (1983); *Sociology of Academics in India & Abroad*, Delhi, Sundeep Prakashan.
- Lezersfeld,P.F.,(1958); “Judges and Beruf” quoted in Merton, R.K., *The Student Physician*, Cambridge, Harvard University Press.
- Miller, D.C. & W.H. Form, (1951); *Industrial Sociology*, New York, Harper & Row, p. 651
- Rosenberg, (1957); *Occupations and Values*, Glencoe & Illinois, The Free Press
- Sullivan, E.E., (1968); *Education in Social Change*: New Delhi, Asia Publishing House.

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Paper-5

**Choice Based Credit System-Do Our
Universities prepare for it?**

Indrajeet Dutta

Choice Based Credit System-Do Our Universities prepare for it?

Indrajeet Dutta⁷

Abstract

Academic reform is on the agenda of higher education as envisioned in the XII plan document. Several academic reforms are initiated whether it is related to skill development, public private partnership model, curriculum designing, teacher recruitment and their professional development, opening of institutions at educationally backward districts. The background of all these developments is access to higher education (increasing GER by 30%), equity (availability of higher education to all the disadvantaged sections of society) and excellence (high quality of higher education being offered in higher educational institutions). Choice based credit system is one of the academic reforms linked with quality higher education wherein students have the opportunity to choose subjects/courses from the available pool of courses. It offers the students the flexibility to choose subjects beyond their discipline i.e. approach is cafeteria in nature where students have knowledge not only from their parent discipline but also from other disciplines. Students will have knowledge in interdisciplinary subjects which will help students not only to understand his/her subjects but also its link with other subjects or how main subject knowledge can be related to other subjects knowledge. It also facilitates students' mobility within and outside the university system. UGC has made guidelines for its smooth transition but does our university system are really prepared for it. The present article highlights the challenges our university system faces related to CBCS and preparation of higher education system.

Key Words: Choice Based Credit System, Higher Education, University, Courses

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Introduction-

As a teacher in the university system I often wondered why certain decisions are taken so hastily without building any consensus among the teachers as well as with other stakeholders especially students for whom the entire education system is working. The fate of any major systemic reform until well conceived and well accepted by its stakeholders is not worth trying it? The burning example is of Delhi University Four Year Undergraduate Programme (FYUP). The four year programme was launched in 2013 with the backing of MHRD, UGC against the wishes of the teaching and students fraternity. The university teachers of the premier university protest all throughout the year and it was supported by students union, educationist and administrators as well as from other sections of the society. The fate of it is that in the year 2014 Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) along with UGC forced Delhi University to take back the FYUP programme in the interest of the students. It is not that four year undergraduate programme has not has its merits. It was kept in back burners as the teachers were not convinced with the idea of four year programme. Though, reasons might be more political than the academic. Hema Raghavan former Dean of students' welfare in her article CBCS: A SWOT Analysis in the University News has pointed out 'change for the sake of the change should not be brought into the system'. Until and unless its pros and con are weighed it should be not be implemented. Credit system is all ready in place in many of our universities like JNU, IITs, BITs, IIMs etc. CBCS is on UGC agenda almost a decade back. Sam Pitroda the Chairman of National Knowledge Commission (2006) in his letter to Prime Minister of India has written:

“We propose a transition to a course credit system where degrees are granted on the basis of completing a requisite number of credits from different courses which provides students with choices.”

It was the time when National Knowledge Commission has submitted his report to PM of India. Report talks about the present CBCS. When the XII plan for higher education was formalized three guiding forces related to higher education was discussed. One of them is access other is equity and third one is excellence. As far as access is concerned increasing the number of higher educational institutions through government efforts as well as through PPP model mainly in those areas which are educationally backward districts. The case of equity could be addressed by increasing the GER of all the disadvantaged groups through strategic interventions at school level as well as at higher education level in the forms of scholarships and fellowships; finally excellence could be achieved through quality academic reforms. Switching over to grading system from the existing numerical marking system, annual to semester mode system and introduction to Choice Based Credit System are the key academic reforms which ensures quality and excellence. But, it was in UGC XII plan document (2012-17) where CBCS system is given high priority as other two mentioned above followed it. CBCS system is just like 10+2+3 system as envisaged in NPE, 1986. The Government plans that new credit system would be learner centric and definitely allow more flexibility in learning patterns with greater course choices, the ability to transfer credits between institutions, improved quality standards, and greater flexibility for mature students to complete programs over an extended period of time. It is also hoped that the new semester and credit system will encourage more frequent revisions to curriculum and more relevance to the labor market. The reason behind implementing the CBCS system is what said by the K.S.Pathania & Anuradha Pathak (2013) in University News and to quote:

“It is a national aspiration that every graduate should not only have disciplinary knowledge but also be armed with set of core competencies and switchable skills.This will act as great enabler for employment,

entrepreneurship, good citizenry, knowledge and wealth creation and should be viewed as inherently complementary to learning for scholarship, disciplinary expertise and intellectual enrichment” (p.1).

Hema Raghvan(2015) in her article further stated that “rather than studying restricted microgroove of just one discipline students will have the option to expose themselves to other disciplines for a holistic and enhanced learning”. Thus, Choice Based Credit System is an academic reform wherein students have the opportunity to choose and study interdisciplinary subjects/courses in his/her undergraduate programme for a particular discipline. The choice based credit system is a ‘cafeteria’ type approach in which the students can take courses of their choice, learn at their own pace, undergo additional courses and acquire more than the required credits, and adopt an interdisciplinary approach to learning (UGC Guidelines, 2015). It simply means, if student’s have gone for a major of science programme then apart from selecting science they could select some of the courses from the list of offered courses from humanities and social sciences or languages or even some from vocational courses like with major in chemistry one can study economics, business studies and French, if student is interested in doing it. This type of system is working very well in the American, UK and other European Universities for very long time. The premise behind CBCS is that one cannot compartmentalize disciplines/subjects in today’s knowledge society and if we provide such system that students will be benefitted the most. It will give the student an opportunity to abreast himself/herself about the developments taking place in the field and acquire knowledge on it and apply the knowledge in his/her discipline. Another, aspect about CBCS is that student desires to study any other subjects in higher education; higher education should not restrict it merely because he has not studied in higher education. Moreover, it also helps the students to develop a taste in other fields and if possible go for innovation in his/her interested field.

In western countries, it is very common that students' studies inter-disciplinary subjects at graduate and post graduate level which help students to give better insight about the relevance of one subject in other allied fields. The universities have the flexibility and freedom in designing the examination and evaluation methods that best fits the curriculum, syllabi and teaching-learning methods, there is a need to devise a sensible system.

No doubt, system has its merits and in recently held meetings of Central Universities Vice-Chancellors with UGC officials wherein it is agreed in principle to implement it from the current academic session. But question arises do our universities are ready for it? Whether students at large will be benefitted or not? Whether the executers of the reforms are well trained on this aspect? No doubt, any reforms in the academics will not yield result in a year or two but also any reform cannot be well executed unless teachers are taken into confidence. The strength and weakness of reform rests on how teachers perceived those reforms and if it goes down well with teachers then, it is being implemented in letter and spirit. Before giving answers to these questions, let's understand how CBCS system will work in the university system.

CBCS: How will it works?

UGC in the recent guidelines has proposed that in a programme three different kinds of courses will be offered. One course will be on core, second will be on elective and last will be on foundation. The Core course will be the compulsory part of the programme and it will be the discipline of the study on which students' degree will be conferred. Student has to study it in every semester. Elective Course as the name suggests will be the pool of optional courses and students have to select from this pool of courses. It may be: (i) Supportive to the discipline of study, (2) Providing an expanded scope, (3) Enabling an exposure to some other discipline/domain, and (4) Nurturing student's proficiency/skill. An elective may be "Generic Elective" focusing on those courses which add

generic proficiency to the students. An elective may be “Discipline centric” or may be chosen from an unrelated discipline. It may be called an “Open Elective.” The Foundation Courses may be of two kinds: Compulsory Foundation and Elective foundation. “Compulsory Foundation” courses are the courses based upon the content that leads to Knowledge enhancement. They are mandatory for all disciplines. Elective Foundation courses are value-based and are aimed at man-making education (UGC Guidelines, 2015). Credits under the Choice Based Credit System are awarded based on the successful completion of a course of study measured in terms of classroom contact hours and volume of content studied. A semester credit is measured as one lecture (one hour) per week over the course of the semester, a minimum of two hours of tutorials a week, or one practical session per week. Most courses of study are weighted at three or four credits, with instruction and learning divided across one or more of the three LTP delivery options. Courses may be constructed to combine all three LTP elements, so a four-credit course, for example, might involve 2 one-hour lectures per week (two credits), 1 two-hour tutorial (one credit), and one practicum (one credit). A more interactive course might be structured with no lecture, two 2-hour tutorials (two credits), and two labs (two credits) per week. The specific credit make-up of a course will vary from subject to subject and from institution to institution based on curriculum design and desired learning outcomes (Clark, N. 2014). To illustrate, suppose a student want to do B.Sc Chemistry (Hons.) from a university. Then the total credit of the programme is 140. Now, the core course will have 14 papers and each paper will be of either 4 or 5 credit. Since it is practical oriented programme therefore, these 14 papers will have either practical or tutorial on offer. Therefore, 2 credits will be given to each paper if theory paper has weighted 4 credits and if 5 then 1 credit is will be given for tutorial or practical. In this way core papers have 56 or 70 credits and its tutorial or practical will have 28 or 14 credits. These credits will be

distributed in three years programme. Next, in case of elective course, there will be two kinds of elective course. One discipline specific and other generic. Both of them have tutorial or practical component. Therefore, UGC has suggested 4 credits to each of specific and generic electives as well as 4 credits each for their respective tutorials or practical. Discipline and generic have 4 papers each. The total credits for both the theory papers are 16 or 20(4 or 5 credit for each paper) whereas practical or tutorial component has 8 or 4 credits (2 or 1 credit tutorials or practical). Lastly, in foundation course as mentioned earlier there are two kinds of foundation: compulsory and elective. Both in compulsory and elective (ability enhancement courses) there are 2 papers each of 2 credits each i.e. 4 credits for compulsory and 4 for elective course are given in the programme. Thus, one can see Core course have 56/70 credits, elective have 48/ credits and foundation have 8 credits to complete a programme. Similar choice based credit system for various programme have been given by UGC and uploaded on the website <http://www.ugc.ac.in/ugcnotice> (Syllabi for the following Under Graduate courses under Choice Based Credit System).

Do University System prepare for it?

Indian higher education is the second largest education system in the world. It has almost 712 universities which includes 43 central universities, 323 state universities, 127 deemed universities, 143 private universities and 68 institutions of national importance and around 36,671 degree colleges and almost 11000 stand alone institutions with gross enrolment of 29,629,000 students in different types programmes (GOI,2014). These programmes are very diverse in nature and offering innumerable options of subjects within a programme and within a university. Think of the case like Delhi University which has almost 85 constituent and affiliated colleges to it running almost hundreds of undergraduate programmes and has a cumulative enrolment of almost 2 lakhs of students in the undergraduate programmes means several

challenges before the university system. The very first challenge university is not only to design the curriculum of core courses but also design the curriculum of elective and foundation courses. While designing the curriculum of elective courses key consideration should be it should be linked with core courses whereas foundation courses are normally skill enhancement courses therefore, skills associated with the core courses. It means when a student will study a major discipline, he/she has the option to study inter disciplinary subjects branches out from the major or allied discipline. Thus it will be a herculean task for the teachers of all disciplines to sit together and re-design the curriculum giving adequate weightage to each of three courses and also mix and match in a manner(options to choose) that students can earn desired number of credits to complete the undergraduate programme through the cafeteria approach. Second challenge university system will face is on the area of teachers. Most of the universities are facing acute shortage of teachers. Almost majority of the universities are functioning on half of its sanctioned strength and if students are given options to choose interdisciplinary courses then we should have enough faculty strength to cater to the demands of the students. Presently, our faculties are overloaded. It means with introduction of CBCS, there teaching load will be increased manifold. Moreover, think of a situation where students from different core courses opting for a particular elective course, how can teacher teaches them until and unless teachers are not given any specialized training. The third challenge comes from the infrastructure side of the university system. Recently, I have attended refresher course from an academic staff college wherein the Professor of the same university was invited to give a lecture and provided us with a fact that presently university has almost cumulative strength of 40,000 and university has not enough of space to accommodate all of them. I quote: "Acha sabhi dakhile vale bache vishwvidalya nahi aate nahi to hum unko kaha bithathe. Unka absent rahna vishwidalya ke liye bahut fayademand hota hai.

Bahut saalo se infrastructure mein koi bhi barodteri nahi huya hai”. (Thanks to god that all the enrolled students are not regularly attending the university otherwise it will be difficult for the university to make sitting arrangement for them. It is good that they remain absent as it is beneficial for the university. University infrastructure has not enhanced for so many years.) Similar type of picture can arise with the CBCS system, if for a specified course if large number of students opt for it then, imagine the class strength and top of it how a teacher would teach such a large number of students. Definitely, teacher requires PA system to address and class requires big screens and other electronic gadgets. If our universities are not in a position to accommodate all of them then the very purpose of CBCS is defeated. Fourth challenge universities have to face related to CBCS is the seamless of the students among and within the university. If inter-university mobility is allowed, then the very first thing required is the parity of the curriculum between the two universities. Next, whether the university has a fixed number of seats or it is a flexible in the number with respect to a particular programme. What will happen to the pupil teacher ratio? Moreover, from many of the state universities there will be an exodus of the students to the premier universities like Delhi University, Jawaharlal Nehru University, Jamia Millia Islamia, Punjab University, and others as result it will be difficult to manage such a huge influx of students in these premier universities. This phenomenon will also be observed in case of intra-institution mobility within a university. In one of the instance in Delhi University in the course of Mass communication and Journalism one of the colleges has almost 150 students enrolled. If CBCS system is operated last year this figure could have gone into few hundred as one cannot deny admission based on the CBCS system as quoted by Hema Raghavan in her article. She further pointed out in her article that CBCS system will not be applicable for inter-university mobility whereas in American, UK and European universities

there is provision of inter-university mobility. Therefore, I strongly feel then there is no point in introducing CBCS system when it is not helping the students to freely mobilize among the institutions seeking for specialized course. Fifth challenge university will face is on time-table area. When the institutions offer students with choices of their courses from the foundation automatically it will be difficult to set a time table as it will further constrained by space and shortage of teachers. Sixth challenge, university system will face on the front of training of teachers. Though, UGC has conducted eight workshops with representatives of Universities and Colleges at different places across the Country from 20th March to 16th April, 2015 and many of the teachers have undergone training. In one of the workshop of CBCS held in JMI, one of the experts Prof. S.S. Chahal Vice Chancellor Punjab Agriculture University suggested that Academic Staff College should take the responsibility of training the in-service teachers through short training programme or within the ambit of orientation and refresher course organize special lecture to train teachers on CBCS. But, unfortunately thousand of teachers, the real executors of the CBCS system are still untrained in this aspect. So, one can understand how the CBCS system will work in the university system. Seventh challenge university system and especially state universities has to face in the wake of CBCS system is on the evaluation system. There is a twofold challenge for the university system. One, most of the university and college teachers is in the habit of marking the students numerically. But with CBCS system in place, teachers have to give them grades on ten point grading system. Attitude and awareness of the teachers about the grading system will be key to the success of grading system. Furthermore, the Higher Educational Institutions have to issue the transcript for each semester based on Semester Grade Point Average (SGPA) and a consolidated Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) transcript indicating the performance in all semesters. Though, technology will reduce the work but with

large number of students on the roll of university, it will be a tougher task to complete on time. Second, presently almost 4/5th the total students enrolled at higher education are at undergraduate level. Now, with the onset of semester system at undergraduate level university has to conduct exams twice a year. It means it not only requires financial resources but also human resources (RUSA Document, 2013). Moreover, in most of the state universities, the number of colleges affiliated to it ranges from few hundreds to almost thousand in numbers. The number of students in a particular programme also runs in thousands. State universities are facing a great challenge to declare the results on time. On the top of it, if they have to carry such exercise twice in a year, it will be asking too much from them when especially human, financial and technological resources are scarce.

No doubt, CBCS has its own merits and heavily inclined towards the students and their benefits and it is the responsibility of the teachers not to stall the implementation of the new academic reform. But it is equally important, that university system should readily prepare for it. It is heartening to note that around 71 HEIs have formally agreed to implement the CBCS system from the ensuing academic session as informed by Hon'ble HRD Minister on the floor of the Rajya Sabha as published on 29th July 2015, Central India national newspaper Hitavada. Out of 71 institutions 39 are central universities, 21 state universities, 5 private universities and six deemed to be universities. It is indeed an excellent beginning and stepping stone towards a new era of higher education. Let's join our hands together to make the future of our students and thus bring our universities on the map of global world.

References-

- Clark, N. (2014). *Higher Education Reforms in India: Credits, Semesters & Access* World Education News & Reviews.

<http://wenr.wes.org/2014/09/higher-education-reforms-in-india-credits-semesters-and-access/>

- GOI.(2006). *Report of National Knowledge Commission*. New Delhi.
- GOI.(2014). *Educational Statistics at a Glance*. Ministry of Human Resource Development, Bureau of planning, monitoring & statistics, New Delhi.
- <http://www.ugc.ac.in/ugcnotice> (Syllabi for the following Under Graduate courses under Choice Based Credit System).
- MHRD(2013). *Report of Rashtriya Uchatar Shiksha Abhiyan*, MHRD. New Delhi.
- Pathania, K.S., & Pathak, A. (2013). Choice based credit system: Need of the hour, *University New*, 51(8), 1-3.
- Planning Commission (2011). *Report of the working group on higher education for the XII five year plan*. Retrieved from http://planningcommission.gov.in/aboutus/committee/wrkgrp12/hrd/wg_hiedu.pdf
- PTI(2015, July, 29th).39 Central varsities agree to adopt CBCS. *Hitavada* p. 4.Bhopal
- Ragahvan, H.(2015). Choice based credit system: A swot analysis. *University News*, 30(28).
- UGC (2015). UGC guidelines on adoption of choice based Credit system. Retrieved from http://www.du.ac.in/du/uploads/Guidelines/UGC_credit_Guidelines.pdf

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Paper-6

**Comparative Study of the Teaching Aptitude of Fresh
Categories of Student Teachers with those of In-Service
Categories in Relation to their Rural-Urban
Background**

Rajesh Kumar Srivastav
Dr. V.K.Rai

**Comparative Study of the Teaching Aptitude of Fresh Categories
of Student Teachers with those of In-Service Categories in
Relation to their Rural-Urban Background**

Rajesh Kumar Srivastav⁸

Dr. V.K.Rai⁹

Abstract

This paper deals with the study of Teaching Aptitude of B. Ed. Student teachers and in-service teachers of teachers training colleges and elementary schools at Satna district in Madhya Pradesh. To know the teaching aptitude of student teachers and in-service Teachers standardized teaching aptitude test was used. The main objective of the study was to know the effect of independent variables like gender and locality of student teachers and in-service teachers on their teaching aptitude. Critical Ratio test and ANOVA were done to know the effect of independent variables on the teaching aptitude of student teachers and In-service teachers of teachers training colleges and elementary schools at Satna district in Madhya Pradesh.. The population of the study consists of student teachers and in-service teachers of teachers training colleges and elementary schools at Satna district in Madhya Pradesh. and the sample was taken from three teachers training colleges and ten elementary school's teachers at Satna district in Madhya Pradesh. The findings of the study show the fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude. There are significant effect of locality and interaction among the independent variables on the teaching aptitude of student teachers and teachers.

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Keywords: 1. Teacher Trainees 2. In-Service Teachers 3. Gender (Male & Female) 4. Locality (Rural and urban)

Introduction-

Aptitude tests attempt to predict the degree of achievement that may be expected from individuals in a particular activity. To the extent that they measure past learning, they are similar to achievement tests. To the extent that they measure non-deliberate or unplanned learning, they are different. Aptitude tests attempt to predict an individual's capacity to acquire improved performance with additional training. The quality of professional performance of a teacher depends mainly on his/her aptitude for teaching. The purpose of the study was to understand the extent of aptitude's relationship between teacher trainees and elementary teachers in relation to their locality.

Review of Related Literature-

Anwar et.al. (2012) found that overall high teaching aptitude was found among primary teachers. Among the regions of Panjab, Southern Panjab's teachers were significantly low in their teaching aptitude. The average aptitude was revealed low among the teachers working in rural areas as well as on contract basis. **Raval et.al. (2012)** found there is no significant effect of area on the scores of teaching aptitude test. **Sarasani, Mahender Reddy et.al. (2010)** found locality influences the performance of adolescents. **Vasugi et. al. (2009)** found that the urban and rural high school students differ significantly in the scientific aptitude. **Shanmunga (1989)** found that high achieving rural students were having higher achievement motivation than the urban students. Low achieving rural students were positive self concept and higher manifest anxiety low achieving urban students were higher intelligence and higher adjustment problems. **Schneider et.al. (1989)** found that the levels of soccer knowledge and of overall aptitude were varied between rural and urban schools.

Statement of the Problem-

Comparative Study of the Teaching Aptitude of Fresh Categories of Student Teachers with those of In-Service Categories in Relation to their Rural-Urban Background.

Variables-

1. **Independent Variables :** sex (Male & Female) and Locality (Rural and Urban)
2. **Dependent Variable:** Teaching Aptitude of student teachers and in-service teachers.

Objectives of the Study-

1. To find out the difference between male of fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers in terms of teaching aptitude.
2. To find out the effect of fresh categories urban student teachers and in-service categories urban teachers in terms of teaching aptitude.
3. To find out the interaction effect of sex and locality of fresh categories student teachers and in-service teachers in terms of teaching aptitude.

Null Hypotheses of the Study-

1. The fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
2. Fresh categories rural student teachers and in-service categories rural teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
3. Fresh categories of urban student teachers and in-service categories urban teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
4. Fresh categories rural and urban student teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
5. In-service categories rural and urban background teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.

6. There is no significant interaction effect of gender and locality of fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers on their teaching aptitude.

Limitations of the Study-

Teacher trainees were selected from three B. Ed. Colleges at Satna district in Madhya Pradesh in the academic year of 2012-2013. Elementary teachers of ten schools were selected from Satna district of Madhya Pradesh.

Research Design-

Normative survey method was used to conduct the present study.

Sample & Population-

The sample was consisted of five hundred student teachers & teachers (250 Males & 250 Females) from Satna district of Madhya Pradesh, studying and working in B.Ed. Training Colleges & elementary colleges.

Tools and Techniques to be used-

1. Teaching Aptitude Test Battery (TATB) construction and standardization by Dr. R. P. Singh (Patna) and Dr. S. N. Sharma (Patna).
2. Locality of the student teachers is asked by student teachers and elementary teachers to write on questionnaire.

Procedure for Data Collection-

The study was conducted on a sample of 500 students of B.Ed. training colleges & In-service teacher of elementary schools from Satna district of Madhya Pradesh. The entire test, viz. teaching Aptitude test Battery and localities were filled by the sample students and returned back to investigator.

Statistical Analysis-

For analyzing data statistic techniques namely mean, standard deviation, 't' tests and ANOVA were applied.

- i. **Testing of Hypothesis – 1**

To test hypothesis one, five hundred teachers (two hundred fifty male student teachers and two hundred fifty female teachers) were taken from various schools of Satna district of Madhya Pradesh. Teaching Aptitude Test Battery (TATB) was filled by them and same was returned back to investigator. Obtained data on TATB was analyzed by using critical ratio test. The results are given in Table-1.

Table-1

Table showing the Value of Critical Ratio of Teaching Aptitude Scale of Fresh Categories Student Teachers and In-service Categories Teachers

Groups	N	M	SD	df	Calculate d Critical Ratio	Level of Significanc e	Tabulate d Critical Ratio Result	Result
Student Teacher s	25 0	77.1 8	9.97	49 8	1.36	0.05	1.96	Not Signifi -
Teacher s	25 0	75.7 4	13.5 4					- cant

Table – 1 indicates that the critical value of teachers on Teaching Aptitude Scale is 1.36. This value is not significant at .05 level of significance because it is less than the required Critical Value (1.96 for df is 498). It shows that the fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude. Thus, the hypothesis, “The fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude” may be accepted.

ii. **Testing of Hypothesis – 2**

To test hypothesis two, three hundred seventy two teachers of fresh categories student teachers with rural background and In-service categories teachers with rural background (one hundred ninety one student teachers and one hundred eighty one teachers) were taken from various schools of Satna district of Madhya Pradesh. Teacher Aptitude Test Battery (TATB) was filled by them and same was returned back to investigator. Obtained data on student teachers and teachers with rural background was analyzed by using critical ratio test. The results are given in Table-2.

Table-2

Table showing the Value of Critical Ratio of Fresh Categories Student Teachers and In-Service Categories Teachers of Rural Background

Groups	N	M	SD	df	Calculate d Critical Ratio	Level of Significanc e	Tabulate d Critical Ratio Result	Result
Student Teacher s	19 1	75.8 8	9.97	37 0	2.50	0.05	1.97	Signifi - -cant
Teacher s	18 1	78.9 4	13.3 6					

Table – 2 indicates that the critical value of teachers on rural background of Teaching Aptitude Test is 2.50. This value is significant at .05 level of significance because it is greater than the required Critical Value (1.97 for df is 370). It shows that the Fresh categories rural student teachers and in-service categories rural teachers differ significantly in their teaching aptitude. Thus, the hypothesis, “Fresh categories rural student teachers and in-service categories

rural teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude” may be rejected.

iii. **Testing of Hypothesis – 3**

To test hypothesis three, one hundred twenty one teachers of fresh categories student teachers with urban background and In-service categories teachers with urban background (forty eight student teachers and seventy three teachers) were taken from various schools of Satna district of Madhya Pradesh. Teacher Aptitude Test Battery (TATB) was filled by them and same was returned back to investigator. Obtained data on student teachers and teachers with urban background was analyzed by using critical ratio test. The results are given in Table-4.

Table-3

Table showing the Value of Critical Ratio of Fresh Categories Student Teachers and In-Service Categories Teachers of Urban Background

Groups	N	M	SD	df	Calculate d Critical Ratio	Level of Significanc e	Tabulate d Critical Ratio Result	Result
Student Teacher s	4 8	79.5	2.88 6	11 9	12.05	0.05	1.98	Signifi - -cant
Teacher s	7 3	68.1 3	7.27 4					

Table – 3 indicates that the critical value of teachers on urban background of Teaching Aptitude Test is 12.05. This value is significant at .05 level of significance because it is greater than the required Critical Value (1.98 for df is 119). It shows that the Fresh categories urban student teachers and in-service

categories urban teachers differ significantly in their teaching aptitude. Thus, the hypothesis, “Fresh categories of urban student teachers and in-service categories urban teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude” may be rejected.

iv. Testing of Hypothesis – 4

To test hypothesis four, two hundred thirty two Fresh Categories Student Teachers with Rural and Urban Background (one hundred ninety one student teachers with rural background and forty one student teachers with urban background) were taken from various schools of Satna district of Madhya Pradesh. Teacher Aptitude Test Battery (TATB) was filled by them and same was returned back to investigator. Obtained data on rural and urban background of fresh categories student teachers was analyzed by using critical ratio test. The results are given in Table-4.

Table-4

Table showing the Value of Critical Ratio of Fresh Categories Student Teachers with Rural and Urban Background

Groups	N	M	SD	df	Calculate d Critical Ratio	Level of Significanc e	Tabulate d Critical Ratio Result	Result
Rural student teacher s	191	75.88	9.97	230	4.52	0.05	1.97	Signifi - -cant
Urban student teacher	41	79.5	2.88					

Table – 4 indicates that the critical value of student teachers on rural and urban background of Teaching Aptitude Test is 4.52. This value is significant at .05 level of significance because it is greater than the required Critical Value (1.97 for df is 230). It shows that the Fresh categories rural and urban student teachers differ significantly in their teaching aptitude. Thus, the hypothesis, “Fresh categories rural and urban student teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude” may be rejected.

v. **Testing of Hypothesis – 5**

To test hypothesis five, two hundred fifty four In-service Categories Teachers with Rural and Urban Background (one hundred eighty one teachers with rural background and seventy three teachers with urban background) were taken from various schools of Satna district of Madhya Pradesh. Teacher Aptitude Test Battery (TATB) was filled by them and same was returned back to investigator. Obtained data on rural and urban background of In-service categories teachers was analyzed by using critical ratio test. The results are given in Table-5.

Table-5

Table showing the Value of Critical Ratio of In-Service Categories Teachers with Rural and Urban Background

Groups	N	M	SD	Df	Calculate d Critical Ratio	Level of Significanc e	Tabulate d Critical Ratio Result	Result
Rural Backgroun d Teachers	18 1	78.9 4	13.3 6	25 2	8.29	0.05	1.97	Signifi - -cant
Urban Backgroun d Teachers	73	68.1 3	7.27					

Table – 5 indicates that the critical value of teachers on rural and urban background of Teaching Aptitude Test is 8.29. This value is significant at .05 level of significance because it is greater than the required Critical Value (1.97 for df is 252). It shows that the In-service categories rural and urban background teachers differ significantly in their teaching aptitude. Thus, the hypothesis, “In-service categories rural and urban background teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude” may be rejected.

vi. **Testing of Hypothesis – 6**

To test hypothesis six, the gender and locality (Urban and Rural Background) of fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers were (N = 80) taken randomly to test interaction effect on their teaching aptitude. To analyze the score ANOVA was applied and ‘F’ was obtained. The results are shown in table - 6.

Table – 6
Summary of Eight Groups of Student Teachers and Teachers Analysis of Variance

Sources of Variance	SS	df	MS	F
Between Group	3793. 35	7	541.9 0	7.95
Within Groups	4902. 50	72	68.09	
Total	8695. 95	79		

Table-6 indicates that ‘F’ values obtained on eight groups of student teachers and teachers are 7.95. This value is significant at 0.05 level of significance because it is more than the required ‘F’ value 2.33 when df is 79. It shows that there is significant interaction effect of gender and locality of fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers on their teaching aptitude.

Thus, the hypothesis, “There is no significant interaction effect of gender and locality of fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers on their teaching aptitude”, may be rejected.

Findings: Findings of the study are as under:

1. The fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers do not differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
2. Fresh categories rural student teachers and in-service categories rural teachers differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
3. Fresh categories of urban student teachers and in-service categories urban teachers differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
4. Fresh categories rural and urban student teachers differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
5. In-service categories rural and urban background teachers differ significantly in their teaching aptitude.
6. There is significant interaction effect of gender and locality of fresh categories student teachers and in-service categories teachers on their teaching aptitude.

Implications of the Study-

Aptitude is innate capacity of a person which can be increase by extensive training programme. To increase the innate capacity of teacher trainees, more pedagogical discussion and practice teaching should be done. Role of the teacher in developing learning habit must be discussed in detail. Counseling sessions should be made more extensive. Practical assignments should be based on teaching–learning process only. Teacher trainees should be asked to find out the problems of students they experience during their teaching work in schools and they should be asked to find out the most suitable solution for the same. Teacher trainees belonging to other medium and faculty of Arts should be given more extensive knowledge of pedagogy of education. To increase the

competency in teaching of in-service teachers, it is important by education department to arrange orientation programme, seminar, symposium, workshop etc. for them.

Reference-

- Anwar, Nadeem et al. (2012) An Examination of Teaching Aptitude of Teachers Working at Primary Level: Demographic differences. International Interdisciplinary Journal of Education 1, 2.
- Panda, B. N. & Tiwari, A. D. (1997) Teacher Education. APH Publishing Corporation, New Delhi.
- Raval. Sheetal et al. (2012) A study of the teaching aptitude of primary teacher trainees in relation to certain variables. International Journal of Education and Knowledge (IJEK) 3, 4.
- Schneider, W., Korkel, J. and Weinert, F.E.(1989) Domain specific knowledge and memory performance: A comparison of high and low aptitude children. Journal of Educational Psychology 81, 3, 306-312.
- Shanmuga, S.R. (1989) Urban-rural difference in academic achievement and achievement related factors. Journal of Educational Research and Extension 25, 3, 121-129.
- Sharma, R. A. (2010) Teacher Education & Pedagogical Training. Surya Publication, Meerut.
- Vasugi, K. and Padamakalavathy, Smt. K. (2009) A Study of Scientific Aptitude among High School Students. Journal of Educational Research and Extension, Coimbatore 46, 2, p.43-50.
- Sarsani, Mahender Reddy & Maddini Ravi (2010) Achievement in Mathematics of Secondary School students in Selected Variables. Edu Tracks 9,6, 38-42.

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Paper-7

**Self-Help Groups: Poverty Alleviation- A
Case Study of Nayagarh District of Odisha.**

Gopal Krishna Jena

Self-Help Groups: Poverty Alleviation- A Case Study of Nayagarh District of Odisha.

Gopal Krishna Jena¹⁰

Abstract

Poverty is almost a social misery, contaminated in an every socio-economic sector, spread itself amid deprived section of the populace steadily. The concerned article basically assessing the role of Self-help groups for the abolition of poverty, and also its successiveness in generating income and the impact of micro credit on the empowerment of the women member of the self-help groups. The study is primarily based on the field survey, conducted in the three underdeveloped blocks of the Nayagarh district in Odisha. This study takes into account the official members of the self-help groups for better understanding of their process through which they build up their income generating sources. To figure out the impact of self-help groups in these directions, a simple chi-square tests as well as the t-test have been used to rectify the changes that have been taken place due to injection of group approach in the field of rural development. The outcome shown that self-help groups promote awareness among the women member and provide sufficient opportunities to contest with poverty. Further the self-help groups have come out as a significant factor in generation of income and occupations of the members and others which also requires conditions like better disbursement of the micro credit to the members, generating feasible employment and these things should be taken care of for getting more active success in this area.

Key Words: *Extreme, Chronic, Poverty, SHG, NGOs, NABARD, DRDA , Micro Credit.*

Introduction-

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Poverty actually requires no definition, since everyone knows or recognizes who is actually poor. Poverty is itself reflecting on the face of the poor, which is a constant companion of the poor and its presence or rather the symbols of its presence, serve a number of purposes. Hunger and threat of famine are the most potent symbols of poverty.

Poverty actually means of those who have nothing, people whose lives are in constant danger due to the lack of all basic resources that are required for their survival. In general, extreme poverty means extreme deprivation i.e. deprivation of all basic amenities of life. It is seen that along with the urbanization and modernization people met with different forms of poverty and every definitions related to poverty are also changes with the inclusion of new dimensions.

Definitions of poverty and its impact on the socio-economic aspect of life can be referred to as the most viable question which needs to be addressed properly in different directions. Poverty is infecting everyone those who are already resides under the poverty line or those who are about to come under the grief of poverty. Therefore, it needs to be cured as soon as possible because it quickly spread its poisonous aspect in all over the parts of the society.

Removal of poverty is the main objective of planning in India since from the inception of planning periods and so; the poverty alleviation programmes have been given greatest importance in the field of economic development. For the removal of poverty, a direct anti-poverty scheme is required so that it can combat with all those factors which tend to increase the forces of poverty in the both rural and urban areas. But the process of poverty alleviation can be more sustainable when all the members of the family are involved. Therefore, reduction of poverty should be an important concern of the development countries in order to attain economic development and welfare of the people. For alleviating rural poverty and freeing the rural masses from the vicious circle of poverty, a direct implementation of anti-poverty scheme is urgently required

for which credit has long been identified as one of the most crucial input for the upliftment of people.

The self-help group (SHG) approach is a new paradigm into the field of rural development which main objectives are to increase the well-being of the poor people, provide access to resources and credit, increase self-confidence, self-esteem and increase their creditability in all aspects of lives. Self-help group is a voluntary and self-managed group of women, belonging to similar socio-economic characteristics, who come together to promote savings among themselves. The poverty alleviation intervention of the SHG is in the form of undertaking economic programmes to provide employment, giving micro finance ¹¹services to the poor so that they can get themselves acquainted with skills and occupational diversification. This new initiative was taken up by Swarnajayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana, implemented in 1999, to organize the poor into Self-help group.

Area of the Study, Data Base, Sample Design and Analytical Tool of the Study-

The current study is conducted on the role of SHG for poverty alleviation. The area of study for this article is confined to the three development blocks i.e. Nayagarh block, Daspalla block and Gania block of Nayagarh district of Odisha.

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. The primary data are collected in the month of November, 2014 with the use of a set of structured schedule which were basically administered to the members of SHGs in selection basis. The secondary data will be collected from various reports of the government, NGOs, NABARD, DRDA, Odisha Gramya Bank, documents of Self-help groups and other records of the banks and block level institutions. From the three development blocks, the SHGs are selected on the basis of their

grade. There are two grades that were given to the SHGs i.e. A and B. In the second stage, from each grade 20 SHGs were selected randomly from each development block. Then the samples were collected by the door to door survey of the official members of the SHGs. So, the total One Hundred Twenty sample SHGs were selected from the Nayagarh block of Odisha.

Review of Literature-

The approach of Self-help Groups (SHGs) towards poverty alleviation is that it should be self-help. The logic is that individual effort is too inadequate to improve their fate. This brings about the necessity for organizing them in a group by which they get the benefit of collective perception, collective decision making and collective implementation of programmes for common benefit (Karmakar, 1999). There are many studies found which are basically related with assessment of the self help group approach in poverty reduction, mainly the initiatives taken up by the micro finance institutions in promoting all round skills among the poor masses (specially women). Almost all the literatures revealed that a strong financial base is primarily required for all these to happen Mukharjee (2007) stated that core strategy of any new invention to poverty eradication was to reach the poorest of the poor, who are basically resides in the rural areas and therefore, an institution is necessary at the central level for looking into the financial needs the poor at the grass root level. Removal of poverty has been an important objective of the planning in India, and here importance should be given to Schedule Caste (SC) and Schedule Tribe (ST) who constituted the poorest segment of the rural society (Prasad, 1986).

On the other hand, the literatures also emphasize on the potentiality of the SHG concept that would become more viable through the linking programme with the banking services or bring it to the doorstep of the poor, especially to the women who have been neglected by the formal financial agencies in the past (NABARD, 2002a). But the problems like uneven spread across and within

different states, inadequate response from the banks and prevalence of high rate of interest charged to ultimate borrower raising question about the ability of the intervention for poverty alleviation (Shetty, 2001). Still the vision of empowering the rural poor by improving their access to the formal credit system should implemented in a cost-effective and sustainable manner. (Shylendra, 2004; Tripathy, 2003).

Impacts of Self-help Groups on poverty, income generation and occupation. -

Incidence of poverty among the members-

The analysis of the incidence of poverty provides a relevant portrait on to what extent poverty lies amongst the poor women at three blocks of Nayagarh district of Odisha. Because only through analyzing the incidence of poverty, successiveness of a group approach can be measured. Therefore, to carried out this study the average annual per capita incomes of the women members are categorized into three income earning categories. The following table shows the incidence of poverty of the women members of the sample SHGs.

Table 1:- Distribution of members, according to their income earning status (in percentage)

Income status	Percentage of SHGs		Total
	A Grade	B Grade	
Extremely poor (Annual income less than Rs.3000)	30	53.33	41.67
BPL(Rs.3000-Rs.5000)	41.67	31.67	36.67
APL(Annual income above Rs.5000)	28.33	15	21.66
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2014

Table 1 shows that prior to the formulation of SHGs, a significant portion of population in the Nayagarh district falls under below poverty line category. In

78.34 percent (%) of SHGs, members are earning less than Rs.5000 which clearly indicates that they are falling under below poverty line category and 21.66 percent of SHGs, members are falling under above poverty line income category.

Area of Activities of the members of the sample SHGs-

Table 2 shows the total and grade-wise distribution of activities among the members of the sample SHGs.

Table 2:- Distribution of activities among the members of the sample SHGs (in percentage).

Activity	Percentage of SHGs		Total	χ^2 Values		
	A Grade	B Grade		A Grade	B Grade	Total
Agriculture	10	11.66	10.83	2.00	2.79	5.19
Animal Husbandry	70	61.66	65.83	114.81*	88.80*	205.43*
Weaving/ Handloom and Textile	13.33	15	14.16	3.73	4.80	9.06
Other Activities	6.66	11.66	9.16	0.799	2.79	3.66
Total	99.99	99.98	99.98			

Source: Field Survey, 2014

Table 2 shows that in 65.83 percent of the total SHGs, members have engaged in animal husbandry. The animal husbandry practices basically include dairy, piggery firming, goatery, poultry, duckery, veterinary etc. The grade-wise distribution of activities also clearly shows that out of the total A grade SHGs (60), in 70 percent of SHGs, members take animal husbandry as their primary activity and in 61.66 percent of total B grade SHGs (60) the members are engaged in animal husbandry and in the rest of the SHGs, it has been observed that members are disbursed among the activities like agriculture, weaving and handloom and textile and other activities.

The calculated values of chi-square (χ^2) are found as 114.81, 88.80 and 205.43 in case of adoption of animal husbandry as a main area of activity by the members of A grade, B grade and the total SHGs respectively which are highly significant in 41, 36 and 78 degrees of freedoms. Thus we can conclude that there is a significant preponderance among the members of the SHG to adopt animal husbandry as their main source of activity than the other activities.

Status of income generation in the sample SHGs.-

The distribution of average annual per capita income among the SHGs show that before formulation of SHGs, the average annual per capita income of the members in the region are seen as very low and most of them are falling under below poverty line category. But after the formulation of SHGs the incomes of the members have been increasing marginally. Table 3 shows the difference of the mean of the average annual per capita income of the members of the A and B grade SHGs in three development blocks under Nayagarh District.

Table 3:- t-test for difference of mean of the average annual per capita income of the members of the A and B grade sample SHGs (before and after their formulation) in three development blocks under Nayagarh District.

Development Block	Grade of the SHG	Average income before formulation of SHG	Average income after formulation of SHG	Calculated 't' value
Nayagarh	A	Rs.3943.95	Rs.12042.95	-5.49*
	B	Rs.4011	Rs.9736.35	-3.16*
Gania	A	Rs.2866.5	Rs.11684.35	-7.91*
	B	Rs.1435.1	Rs.7469.85	-8.92*
Daspalla	A	Rs.4935.5	Rs.14345	-7.86*
	B	Rs.4280	Rs.10760.65	-4.29*

The t- statistic is found as significant at 0 percent level of consequence. Thus a noteworthy difference between the average incomes of the SHG members has

been found in all the blocks of the Nayagarh District, which indicates the variations of annual income of the SHG members after the formulation of their SHGs. Therefore, it can be concluded that the group benefit approach can be taken as resource mobilization support for the rural poor women since the self-help approach give a sense of achieving collective strength by generating their income as well as capacity building processes through the means of providing productive assets to them.

Impact of micro credit on occupational change of the SHG members-

The execution of SHG can generate opportunities for the rural poor so that they can involve in diverse self-employment activities. The self-help group is nothing but an effective tool for providing self-sustaining occupations to the rural poor women with an effective delivery micro credit system. Table 4 shows that perception of the impact of micro credit facilities on the occupational structure of the women members in the Nayagarh District.

Table 4:- Perception of impact of the micro credit on the occupational structure of the members of the sample SHGs.

	Number of SHGs	Percentage	χ^2 value
Yes	112	93.33	207.2*
No	8	6.67	0.93
Total	120	100.00	

Source: Field survey, 2014

Out of the 120 sample SHGs of the study region, in 93.3 percent of SHGs, members felt that there was some impact of micro credit facilities on their occupational structure, whereas only in 6.66 percent of SHGs, members were not agree with this view.

The primary field survey conducted in the Nayagarh District reveals that the perception of impact of micro credit is shown as significant (χ^2 test values of Table 4) among the members of the sample SHGs i.e. most of the SHG

members felt that there is an impact of micro credit facilities on their occupational structure.

To analyze how the occupational structure of members have changed so far as an impact of micro credit facilities that are provided to the members of the SHGs, we have to scrutinize the distribution of past occupation among the SHG members before the formulation of SHGs and also their present occupations after the formulation of SHGs. The Table below shows how the members of the SHGs are distributed in various occupations before the formulation of SHG.

Table 5:- Distribution of past occupation among the members of sample SHGs before its formulation.

Occupation	Number of SHGs	Percentage	χ^2 value
No occupation	22	18.33	34.65**
Agriculture	59	49.17	256.65*
Business	11	9.17	8.25
Daily Labour	17	14.17	20.4
Other	1	0.83	0
Agriculture/ Business	4	3.33	0.9
Agriculture/Daily labour	3	2.5	0.45
Agriculture/ Others	3	2.5	0.45
Business/ Others	0	0	0
Total	120	100.00	

Source: Field survey, 2014

Table 5 shows that in 49.17 percent of SHGs, the members of the SHGs were primarily engaged in agricultural activities before formulation. Whereas, the number of SHGs, where their members had no occupation till the SHG formulation was about 18.3 percent respectively. Among the other SHGs, in 24.17 percent of SHGs, members were doing activities like business, daily

labourer and some other activities. Out of that, in about 14.17 percent SHGs, members were engaged as a daily laborer and in a few number of SHGs i.e. 8.33 percent of the total sample SHGs, members were took part in multiple occupations like agriculture and business, agriculture and other activities, agriculture and daily labour and business and other activities etc.

It is observed from the Table 5 that χ^2 ($\chi^2= 256.65$ for 58 d.f.) of preponderance of members in the traditional agricultural sector is shown as significant at 1 percent level of significance which indicates that a significant portion of women members are engaged with agricultural sector before the formulation of SHGs.

Another factor that has been observed from the analysis that the χ^2 ($\chi^2= 34.65$ for 21 d.f.) of occurrence of members who have not engaged in any activity is shown as significant at 5 percent level of significance. Thus we can conclude that a major portion of the SHG members were either directly engaged with agriculture sector or not engaged with any occupation before formulation of SHG. Besides these, only a less no. of women members were engaged with activities like business, other allied activities and multiple occupations etc.

But after formulation of SHG, the occupational structure of the members in the sub-division has been changed. Table 6 shows the present occupational structure of SHG members after the formulation of SHG.

Table 6:- Distribution of present occupation among the members of the sample SHGs after formulating SHG.

Occupation	Number of SHGs	Percentage	χ^2 Value
Agriculture	6	5	5.75
Dairy	7	5.83	8.05
Tailoring	0	0	0
Flower Vending	0	0	0
Cloth Business	8	6.67	10.73
Animal Husbandry	33	27.5	202.4*

others	4	3.33	2.3
Agriculture/ Dairy	4	3.33	2.3
Agriculture/Cloth Business	1	0.83	0
Agriculture/Animal Husbandry	5	4.17	3.833
Dairy/Cloth Business	2	1.67	0.383
Dairy/ Animal Husbandry	6	5	5.75
Dairy/ Others	1	0.83	0
Tailoring/Cloth Business	1	0.83	0
Cloth Business/Animal Husbandry	27	22.5	134.55*
Cloth Business/Others	2	1.67	0.383
Animal Husbandry/Others	4	3.33	2.3
Agriculture/Dairy/Others	2	1.67	0.383
Agriculture/Cloth Business/Animal Husbandry	1	0.83	0
Dairy/Cloth Business/Animal Husbandry	2	1.67	0.383
Tailoring/Cloth Business/Animal Husbandry	1	0.83	0
Cloth Business/Animal Husbandry/Others	2	1.67	0.383
Agriculture/Dairy/Cloth Business/ Animal Husbandry	1	0.83	0
Total	120	100.00	

Source: Field survey, 2014

It is observed from the Table 6 that after joining SHG, the members are motivated to engage with various occupations. It has been seen that the members of the sample SHGs undertakes various multiple occupations as their main source of self-employment after the formulation of SHG.

Thus we can draw a conclusion that most of women members choose animal husbandry and cloth business and the animal husbandry as their main key activity.

Status availability of micro credit to the members of the SHG-

The availability of micro credit is a prolonged question particularly for the women section which comprising the largest section of deprived population and hence the lack of capital becomes a serious constraint to the development of women in rural areas. The table below shows the perception of adequacy of financial support from bank and other institutions that are provided to SHG members.

Table 7:- Perception of adequacy of financial support of bank and other financial institutions to SHGs members (in number and percentage)

Financial Support	Number of SHG	Percentage	χ^2 value
Yes	10	8.33	1.5
No	110	91.67	199.83*
Total	120	100	

Source: Field survey, 2014

Table 7 reveals that out of the total 120 sample SHGs, in 91.67 percent of SHGs, members have felt that there is inadequate support from the banks and other financial institutions regarding the imposition of micro credit towards their upliftment. Or in other words, most of the members did feel that they have not getting enough micro credit support from bank and other financial institutions in respect of development of their capacity building and income

generating processes. Thus we can infer that a major portion of the SHG members could not able to get a better access to credit facilities. Hence, it is seen that the SHGs have provided a good environment for the upliftment of the rural poor women in the study area. Even though, it is seen that poverty still persists among the rural poor women as some of their average annual per capita income is not able to cross completely the below poverty line mark.

Conclusion-

The findings from the scrutiny provide evidence support to withdraw a conclusion in respect of the hypotheses that have taken up for carrying out the study. The entire observation shows that SHGs are functioning well in organizing the poor women section into a self-serviced economic forum. The formation of SHG can create opportunities for the poor people to participate into the various income earning activities for the women members in the region. Poverty is generally recognized as a consequence of unemployment and lack of availability of income earning sources. And SHG provides a motivation for the building up capabilities on the part of their members in the sample area through providing various income earning sources and shifting their occupational structure. In the χ^2 and t-test analysis on the assessment of SHG on poverty reduction also shows that formulation of SHG and enrolment of the members after the formulation of SHGs have come out as the significant factor of reducing incidence of poverty in the Nayagarh District. In other words, it can be concluded that participation of members in this micro credit programme provides a significant impact towards the upliftment of the members from the grief of poverty in the study region.

References-

- Banerjee, Amalesh. (2004), "*Dynamics of Rural Development: A note*", "Dimension of Rural Development in North East India," (ed.) B. Ray and Gurudas Das, Akansha Publishing House, New Delhi.

- Bhagyalakshmi, J. (2004), “*Empowerment of Women and Marginalised Groups in Panchayats*”, “Rural Development through Women’s Participation and Electronic Media,” (ed.) Dr. Sawalia Bihari Verma and Dr. Shiv Kr. Singh, Pointer Publication, Jaipur
- DasGupta, K. (2001), “*An Informal Journey through Self-Help groups,*” *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 50(3), July-Sept. pp.370-86
- Gadanayak, B.B. (2008), “*Poverty alleviation at the grass root level, Self-help groups as an instrument,*” Dev4India.org
- Kachari, Sumitra Bithi, Sahoo, Dukhabandhu., “*Self-help Groups for Poverty Alleviation a case study of Titabor sub-division of Jorhat district of Assam*”.
- Gupta, Dr. M. Shankar. (2005), “*Poverty Eradication through Micro-Finance/SHG,*” “*Poverty and Sustainable Development: Third World Perspectives,*” (ed.) Ravishankar Kumar Singh, (vol.2), Abhijeet Publication, Delhi
- Harper, M. (2002), “*Practical Micro Finance: A training guide for South Asia*”, Vistaar Publication, New Delhi
- Karmakar, K.G. (1999), “*Rural Credit and Self-Help Group, Micro finance Needs and Concept in India,*” Sage publication, New Delhi
- Mandal, A. (2005), “*Swarnajayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana and Self-help group: An Assessment*”, Kurukshetra, *A Journal of Ministry of Rural Development*, January
- Matiki, R.E. (2008), “*A New Rural Development Strategy for Rapid and Sustainable development countries,*” *Journal of Rural Development*, A Quarterly of NIRD, Vol.27, No.3, July-Sept., pp 449-667

- Mehta, S.R. (1997), “*Poverty, Population and Sustainable Development: Issues and Perspectives*”, in S.R. Mehta (ed.) “Poverty, Population and Sustainable Development,” Rawat Publication, Jaipur and New Delhi
- Mohapatra, S. and B.K. Sahoo (2009), “*Microfinance and the Rural Poor: A empirical Investigation from India*”, A paper submitted to TIES, Guwahati University, Assam
- Mukharjee, D. (2007), “*Relevance of Micro Credit, Bangladesh Example Needs to be Emulated*,” Kurukshetra, A Journal of Ministry of Rural Development, Vol. 55, No. 3, January
- Nath, D. (2008), “*Self-help Group and Women empowerment*, Assam Tribune Online
- Pillai, J.K. (1995), “*Women and Empowerment*”, Gyan Publishing House, New Delhi
- Prasad, K. (1986), “*Poverty in Rural India*”, “*Studies in Indian Agriculture and Rural Development*” (ed.) Dr. V.S. Mahajan, Deep and Deep Publication, New Delhi
- Seabrook, J. (2003), “*The Non-sense Guide to World Poverty*”, Rawat Publication, Jaipur, New Delhi, Mumbai
- Shetty, S.L. (2001), “*Rapporteur’s Report on Working and Impact of Self-help Groups and other Forms of Micro financing*,” Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics 50(3), July-Sept., pp.580-604
- Shylendra,H.S. (2004), “ *The SHG-Bank Linkage Programme, An assessment and Future strategies*,” Journal of Rural Development, a quarterly of NIRD, Vol. 23, No. 4 Oct-Dec
- Tripathy, K.K. (2003), “*Poverty alleviation: Making micro-finance sustainable*,” A financial daily from The Hindus Group of publications, Nov. 01

- Verma, S.B. and K.K.C. Patro (2004), *“Theoretical Concepts of Rural Development”*, *“Rural Development through Women’s Participation and Electronic Media”*, (ed.) Dr. S.B. Verma and Dr. Shiv Kr. Singh, Pointer Publisher, Jaipur.

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Paper-8

**Personal and Social Adjustment of Potential
Delinquents and Non-Delinquents of District–
Baramulla**

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Personal and Social Adjustment of Potential Delinquents and Non-Delinquents of District–Baramulla

Ghulam Mohammad Wani¹²

Dr. Geeta Rani Sharma¹³

Abstract

The present paper examines the personal and social adjustment of potential delinquents and non-delinquents of District Baramulla. The Sample for this study was 50 delinquents and 50 non- delinquents. The result revealed that there is a significant difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on various dimensions of personal and social adjustments.

Keywords: Delinquents, non- delinquents, social and personal adjustment

Introduction-

Youth nowadays, regardless of gender, social origin or country of residence, are subject to individual risks but are also being presented with new individual opportunities-some beneficial and some potentially harmful. Quite often, advantage is being taken of illegal opportunities as young people commit various offences, become addicted to drugs, and use violence against their peers. The majority of studies and programmes dealing with delinquency focus on youth as offenders. Those most likely to be on the receiving end of violence are between the ages of 16 and 19 years. It has long been assumed that religious beliefs are effective deterrents to delinquent behaviour. It has been argued that religious beliefs are the foundation for moral behaviour. Thus the more religious a person is the less likely he or she will be to participant in delinquent or criminal behaviour (Durkheim 1915, Davis 1948, coogan 1954, Yinger 1957). It is claimed that the multiple and diverse function of religion in a person life

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makes it an effective personal control against deviant behaviour (Rohrbaugh and Jessor 1975) Stark (1985) stressed that if we conceptualize religion as a group or social characteristic ‘majority of an adolescence friends are religious “then its relation to deviance is negative”’.

Tittle and Weich (1983) conducted a study on delinquency and criminal behaviour of 1993 individuals. It was found that religion had a strong relation to deviant behaviour when there was normative ambiguity, low social integration, perception of low peer conformity and a relatively high proportion of people who were not religious, the proportion of Delinquents in such population were high. These findings suggest that religiosity has its great affect on adult deviance a disorganized social context, because the other social mechanisms that foster conformity are absent Religiosity was determined by how frequently the respondent read the Bible, watched religious TV programmes listened to religious radio programmes and held a family prayer. It was discovered in a strong religious community context, religiosity was related to lower occurrence of self projected deviant behaviour.

Need and Importance-

A new menace has come to plague the valley schools and higher education with a sizable segments of students bunking off their institutions and spending time roaming about deserted roads or hanging around busy city squares or restaurants during class hours. Over the recent months in particular the number of such students has increased manifold without evoking any concern among teachers and parents. Though these students leave home early morning for school they play truant instead. They skip their schools at the ideal spots for bunking or the comparatively less populated bunds along Sopore, and main chowk Baramulla.. Besides Restaurants and Snooker Points permit these fugitives in without even a cursory inquiry for they are just concerned about their money. On lookers divulge that apart from boys, girls too resort to absconding from their schools.

Fleeing and roaming around roads can prove dangerous and can push these young students into the tentacles of various anti-social and illicit activities. The activities of delinquents is a great cause worry for parents and teachers, sometimes they feel as mute spectators and helpless before the delinquent activities of their children. These fugitive children are more prone to smoking, drug abuse, alcoholism, gambling, sexual exploitation, crimes and many other undesirable activities. The question before us is why these delinquent children engage in various anti-social activities like violence, lack of motivation and commitment towards studies, drug addiction, and damage to public property and disrespecting their elders and parents. Is it that the parental grip is loosening and the value system is collapsing, is it that the basic physiological need of love and belongingness is missing from the society and relations have become more contractual and mechanical. The question before us is why children show cold behaviour towards their parents and teachers and lack empathy. Worrying trend is attributed to numerous factors but after making in-depth probe the investigator found that the research that has been carried in this direction has been in piece meals. Many people have their individual opinion on the factors responsible for delinquency. What is the need of the hour is to generate/pool sufficient data on delinquency with the help of standardized constructed tools. The investigator is committed to make an in-depth study of delinquency and the findings that shall be generated shall help the clinical psychologists, teachers, parents, students and future researchers interested in delinquency to reflect and chalk out the pragmatic and effective intervention strategies to deal with the problem of delinquency.

Statement of the Problem-

The Problem for the present study is: Personal and Social Adjustment of Potential Delinquents And Non-Delinquents of District – Baramulla.

Objectives of the Study-

The following objective has been formulated for the proposed study.

1. To identify potential Delinquents, and Non Delinquents.
2. To study the personal and social adjustment
3. To compare potential Delinquents and Non-Delinquents.

Hypothesis-

The following hypothesis are formulated for the proposed study

- There is a significant difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on various dimensions of personal and social adjustments.

Review of Related Literature-

Lahri, S.K. 1977: Conducted study on Differential Personality Patterns of Normal, Vagabond and Delinquent Children. The main aim of the study was to find out the differences in the personality patterns of normal, vagabond and delinquents children (12-16) years old). A Hindi Version of IPAT's Jr. And Sr. H.S.P.Q., form B (standardized in the Indian Situation by Mehrotra) was used. Personality profiles based on mean scores were drawn. Mean, SD, T-Test, etc. were employed. Some of the major conclusions were:-While the differences between normal and vagabonds were less compared to normals and delinquents, it was more compared to vagabonds and delinquents. Adolescent normal's, adolescent vagabonds the delinquents differed more in personality patterns than pre-adolescents belonging to similar groups. Pre-adolescent the adolescents vagabonds and delinquent children differed more or less equally Vagabonds and delinquents had normal emotional stability and stronger super-ego strength. They had shown a tendency of self-sufficiency as normal. Vagabonds and delinquents had moral values to accept social norms to rehabilitate in a society.

Neelofar Khan, N. A. Gash 2011: Comparative Study of Extreme Groups of Delinquency Proneness, on the Verbal Dimensions of Creativity –In Kashmir Region. The study was executed with the objective to work on the title, “A

Comparative Study of Extreme Groups of Delinquency Proneness, on the Verbal Dimensions of Creativity – in Kashmir Region”. Firstly the objective of the study is to identify high and low delinquency prone adolescents, to compare these delinquency prone adolescent groups on the various dimensions of verbal creativity i.e, Fluency, Flexibility and originality accordingly. The 100 adolescent subjects were drawn randomly, Lidhoo`s delinquency proneness scale and Baqer Mehdi`s verbal tool of creativity were administered. The extreme group technique was used, to categorize high and low delinquency prone groups. These groups were compared on the various dimensions of verbal creativity by using recognized statistical technique viz, Mean, S.D, and ‘t’ value respectively, to pool out the required results of the study. The results of the said study revealed that the high and low delinquency prone adolescents show no significant difference on the originality dimension of verbal creativity. But on fluency and flexibility dimensions of verbal creativity shows significant difference.

Wu Yuan 2009: Conducted study on Factors Affecting Adolescent Delinquency in Singapore. The objective of this study is to find out if adolescent conduct problems are affected by inadequate parental bonding (paternal and maternal care and protection) during their growing up years. Socio demographic background variables, such as gender, occupation of the adolescent`s parents, living arrangements of the adolescent, home intactness of his family, family income, family size, age and the marital relationship between the adolescent`s parents, are also taken into consideration to see if they have an impact on the delinquency behaviour of the adolescent.. It was found that paternal care towards an adolescent, age of the adolescent, family size and family income had a significant impact on adolescent delinquency. It is hoped that the results of this study will prove useful in influencing the attitudes of

parents towards the development of their children in order to prevent them from turning to crime.

Selection of Sample-

Initial sample shall be 200 male students. After the administration of Lidhoo delinquency scale, 25% extreme group technique shall employ for identification of potential delinquents and non delinquents. Fifty delinquents and fifty non delinquents from private High School shall from the final sample for the proposed study of District Baramulla

Tools Used-

For the collection of data the investigator shall employ the following data gathering tools.

1. Lidhoo delinquency proneness scale shall (LDPS) be employed for the identifications of potential delinquents and non delinquents.
2. California Test of personality developed by Thorpe, Clark and Teigs shall be employed for measuring the personal and social adjustment of potential delinquents and non delinquents.

Result and Interpretation-

Table showing the significance of mean difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents of following dimensions of personal adjustment

Dim.	Name of the dimension	Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Level of Significance
1A	Self Reliance	PD	50	2.86	1.49	17.29	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	8.1	1.55		
1B	Sense of	PD	50	3.2	1.72	20.8	Significant .01 level

	personal worth	PND	50	9.32	1.18	8	Significant .01 level
1C	Sense of personal Freedom	PD	50	2.64	1.24	15.2	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	8.2	2.27	3	Significant .01 level
1D	Feeling of Belongingness	PD	50	2.5	1.21	26.7	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	9.36	1.36	9	Significant .01 level
1E	Withdrawal Tendencies	PD	50	8.78	1.43	19.5	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	2.94	1.56	7	Significant .01 level
1F	Nervous Symptoms	PD	50	8.6	1.91	16.6	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	2.76	1.59	8	Significant .01 level
Composite	Total	PD	50	28.5	3.23	14.7	Significant .01 level
				8		5	
		PND	50	40.6	4.82		
				8			

The perusal of Table I, showing the significance of mean difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents, on various dimensions of personal adjustment.

The perusal of Table 1:1 shows that there is a significant mean-difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents in 'self-reliance' dimension of personal adjustment and mean score favours potential non-delinquents. This signifies that potential- non delinquents (PND) are self-reliant personalities. They have a capacity to identify their strength and weakness. They believe in self-support. They have a faith in themselves which provides them the momentum to do things. Non-Delinquents, complete their assignments well in time. It has been observed by the investigator that Non-Delinquents display a faith in themselves. The perusal of Table 1:2, shows a significant mean

difference between potential delinquents and Non-delinquents on 'sense of personal worth' dimension of personal adjustment and mean difference favours non-delinquents. This signifies that non-delinquents appreciate and acknowledge, the sincere efforts they put in accomplishment of the target. For them process is important not the product. Non-delinquents goal directed personalities. Whatever little they achieve in their life act as a catalyst for their future growth and development. They attach aesthetic value to their work. They derive pleasure and satisfaction from their job. They attach meaning to their life by engaging in purposeful activities. They strike a balance between intrinsic and extrinsic values of life.

The perusal of Table 1:3 shows a significant mean-difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on 'sense of personal freedom' dimension of personal adjustment and the mean difference favours non-delinquents. This picture reveals that non-delinquents work with open-mindedness. They want a space to express themselves. They want to work in a culture which promotes fresh inquiry and independence of mind. It is because of this sense of personal freedom, that non-delinquents ask diversified question on the topic. This trait is responsible for imitiveness in non-delinquents. Whenever their services are called for, they offer them without any ifs and buts. They love to take responsibility. They like a work in a culture which provides them a platform for self-expression. On the other hand, delinquents, work with a closed mind. Their aggression arrests their sense of personal freedom. Since delinquents are involved in various anti-social activities, this results in the creation of a culture which breeds narrow-mindedness. The perusal of Table 1:4 shows that there is a significant mean difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on 'Feeling of belongingness' dimension of personal adjustment and mean difference favours non-delinquents. This picture reveals that non-delinquents express warmth and love towards relations. They attach their identity to the

family they belong they care for their family members. Whenever there is any stress or strain in the family it has a direct bearing on the non-delinquents. Non-delinquent is socially-sensitive. He shows a great concern and love for his family members. At times he displays a sense of maturity and responsible person. He attaches great importance to social and family values. It has been observed that non-delinquents come from a family where members understand the importance of relations. Parents do not quarrel with each other. They give due time and attention to their children with the result, children reciprocate with same-feelings. They feel secure. Their emotions are addressed in an atmosphere of love. On the other hand delinquents are somewhat cold-blooded. They do not shoulder the family responsibilities when called for. Pain and tension in the family do not touch their heart nor make them to move. They live in their own-world. They keep their mind busy with unnecessary things. They engage in theft, eve-teasing and other antisocial activities. They lack empathy. They fail to understand the value of relations. They weigh relations in terms of material gains. They display an inconsistency in their behavior. They quarrel with their parents and siblings. The perusal of Table 1.5 shows that there is a significant mean difference between potential delinquent and non-delinquents on “withdrawal tendencies’ dimension of personal adjustment and mean difference favoured delinquents. The picture reveals that delinquents display an attitude of escapism. They do not display the courage to face the hard realities of life. They believe in a life of comfort which does not demand struggle. When they fail to achieve the specified goal they resort to various defense mechanisms. They project their weakness on others. For e.g., if they fail in the examination, they feel that the teacher was not competent or I lacked good study material or question-paper set was difficult. But the reality is that they had non-worked hard and wasted their time in unnecessary things. To hide their weakness they involve in blame gaming. Sometime they involve in unfair practices like

copying, etc. These are all 'withdrawal tendencies'. They lack a capacity to self-introspect. They waste their precious time in activities like meaningless gossips, chatting, on social networking sites, eve teasing, fashion etc. When the time, to test their efforts comes, they escape and display behavioural inconsistency. On the other hand non-delinquents remain focused throughout their academic session. They prepare a academic calendar and strike to it in letter and spirit. They engage in meaningful discourse. They submit their home-work and other assignment as per the specified schedule. They work consistently and are accordingly rewarded for their efforts. They do not resort to defense mechanism or hunt for excuses. In case of any weakness, they display courage to confess and admit their weakness. They learn from their failures. Every experience of life is educating and rewarding for them. They face the harsh realities of life with boldness. They are firm in their conviction The perusal of Table 1:6 shows that there is a significant mean difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on 'Nervous Symptom' dimension of personal adjustment and mean score favours delinquents. The result reveals that delinquents display emotional swings. Sometimes they display a state of stress and tension, which crates behavior problems in them. It is this tendency towards 'Nervous symptoms' that delinquent became drug-addicts. These delinquent are always seen in a state of restlessness. They wander from one place to another, without any aim. They always think of some mischief. Advices, repeated warning have no effect on them. At the end of the day they are dictated by their own thoughts, which are sub-merged in nervousness. Because of this nervous tendency, delinquent find to difficult to accomplish a task. They start a task, get deviated leave it unfinished and start a new activity. They cannot put their heart into their work. Because of this nervousness, they fail to maintain a consistency in their mind. Parents, teachers find it very difficult to read the psychology of the delinquent. There is fluctuation in a behavioural clock. On the other hand, non-

delinquents are somewhat composed and self-contained personalities. They do not get disturbed the ups and downs in life. They display a positive outlook towards life. They display a balanced mental health. In the face of success or failure, they are cool and composed. They do not get pricked on slight provocation. If someone criticizes them or blames them, they hear the inner voice.

Table showing the significance of mean difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents of following dimensions of social adjustment

Dimension	Name of the dimension	Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Level of Significance
2A	Social Standards	PD	50	2.8	1.39	24	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	9.40	1.22		
2B	Social Skills	PD	50	2.38	0.98	30.26	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	9.34	1.30		
2C	Anti Social Tendencies	PD	50	9.02	1.46	8.4	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	2.3	1.03		
2D	Family Relations	PD	50	2.38	0.83	32.60	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	9.52	1.32		

2E	School Relations	PD	50	2.84	1.07	17.86	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	8.54	1.99		
2F	Community Relations	PD	50	3.16	1.07	18.87	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	9.18	1.61		
Composite	Total	PD	50	22.58	3.32	36.2	Significant .01 level
		PND	50	47.92	3.70		

The perusal of Table 2.1 shows the significance of mean difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on 'social standard' dimension of social adjustment and mean difference favours non-delinquents. Non-delinquents understand the rights of others and subordinate certain desires to need of the group. This case study shall make it clear. There was a road-race, and one runner was speeding at serial no. he saw his physically challenged colleague getting unconscious and offered him water at the cost of winning the game. Non-delinquents confirm and acknowledge the desirable social standard. On the other hand, delinquents challenge the desirable social standards. They indulge in those activities which are approved by the society like eve-teasing and truancy. The perusal of Table 2.2 shows the significance of mean difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on 'social skills' dimension of social adjustment and mean difference favour non-delinquents. Non-Delinquents show liking for the people. They are identified as stars in the class. They take part in various social activities like Red-Cross Day, co-curricular activities. They are appointed as monitors of the class and are assigned various

social responsibilities by the teacher. They exhibit a sense of social maturity. He is in good terms with his friends and teachers. He is always ready to extend a helping hand, to his friends. Whenever his services are called for he does not shy away from the responsibility. Individual interests are sub-servient to Association Interests. He shows a feeling of empathy, love and warmth towards the members of the group. He exhibits group-dynamism and works for the cohesiveness of the group. On the other hand delinquents live in their own-world. They are not bothered about the welfare of the group they belong to their self-centeredness revolves around material things. They cannot feel the pain and suffering of their friends. The perusal of Table 2.3 shows the significance of mean difference, between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on 'Anti-social' dimension of 'social Adjustment' and mean difference favours delinquents. The result reveals that delinquent engage in various 'anti social activities'. Some of the anti-social activities include cheating in the examination, bullying, stealing, truancy, quarrel with the parents, eve-teasing, drug addiction, posting objectionable photographs and material in social networking sites like face book and orkut. The personal of Table 2.4 shows, the significance of mean difference between potential delinquents and non-delinquents on 'family relations' dimension of social adjustment, and the mean-difference favours non-delinquents. The result reveals that non-delinquents made good family relations. They are not quarrelsome. They respect and love their family members. If any untoward incident happens in the family, they share the responsibility. They do not ask for undue demands, from their family members. Non-delinquent value the time and money parents spent on them. On the other hand, delinquents are very aggressive.

References-

- Arora Neeru 1992 Stressful life events and personality make up in drug dependence Ph.D Psy Agra Univ,

- Arunima, 1998 Aggression among Children: A Socio-psychological appraisal. Ph. D Psy. Punjab University
- Bagulia, A M 2006: Child and Crime. SBS Pub. & Distributors, New Delhi,
- Biswas P.C 1989, Reaction to frustration in school children, Ph.D Edu Univ. Of Kalyani.
- National Conference on Juvenile System in India Feb 3-4 2007 Annual Report national human Rights Commission, New Delhi
- Parveen , Kausar (2007) Offence among youth in urban population and its impact on family Ph.D Sociology, University of Karachi
- Regoli, Rebort M. And Hewitt, John D. 2006 “Delinquency in Society”, 6th ed.
- Yadav, R B: Treatment of neglected, uncontrollable destitute and abandoned children under the juvenile act. (Nyaya Kiran, vol 4, No. 4, October-December 2005, p 26-30)

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Paper-9

**Personality and Self Efficacy as Determinants of
Job Satisfaction of Senior Secondary School
Teachers of Haryana.**

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Personality and Self Efficacy as Determinants of Job Satisfaction of Senior Secondary School Teachers of Haryana.

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Abstract

The main purpose of the investigation was to assess the level of job satisfaction of senior secondary school teachers of Haryana and to examine the influence of Gender, Personality and Self Efficacy on Job Satisfaction of Sr. Secondary school teachers. In doing so, multistage random sampling procedure was employed to elicit responses from 400 senior secondary school teachers identified in various parts of the State. Standardized questionnaires were administered as tools for data collection. The data was analyzed using three way ANOVA (2x2x2 factorial design). The findings revealed that (i) the senior secondary school teachers experienced high level of job satisfaction; (ii) there is significant independent effect of variables viz. personality and self efficacy on job satisfaction among senior secondary school teachers; and (iii) there is significant two factor interactive effect of variables on job satisfaction among senior secondary school teachers.

Key Words – Job Satisfaction, Gender, Personality and Self –Efficacy.

Introduction-

Education plays extremely significant role in the lives of individuals by empowering them with various competencies, skills, modes of creative thinking and expression and paving the way for enhancing the quality of life. It is the teacher who can inculcate all these qualities in children. On him rests the success or failure of the

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system. If the teacher is efficient, energetic dedicated and effective only then high achievement of the students, moulding them into better citizen and exposing them in the arena of growing competition can become possible. His efficiency and effectiveness is possible only when he is satisfied with his job. Job –Satisfaction is the way an employee feels about his or her job. It is a generalized attitude towards the job, based on evaluation of different aspects of the job. According to Blum and Naylor (1968),

Job-satisfaction is the result of various attitudes possessed by employees. In a narrow sense, their attitudes are related to the job and are concerned with such specific factors as wages, supervision, steadiness of employment, condition of work, opportunities for promotion, recognition of ability, fair evaluation of work, prompt settlement of grievances, fair treatment by employer and other similar things. Hoppock (1935) defines job satisfaction as employees' emotional reactions towards their job (Mercer,1997). Just like any other satisfaction types, job-satisfaction is a talent on which emotions have a strong effect. This effect includes emotions about delectation and aversion. At the same time job satisfaction can be defined as enjoyment in the job (Izgar,2000). Simsek (1998) defines job satisfaction as happiness which is based on creating a work with the colleagues and profit from work. Locke (1983) explains it as an evaluation of experience and job itself and positive emotions based on this evaluation. Job Satisfaction has a strong effect on the quality of the work in organization. That is why in organizations different methods and techniques have been used to promote job satisfaction of employees. As a result of efforts to promote job satisfaction, employees' performances are able to be raised. (Schoderbek, Cosier and Aplin, 1991; Sevimli and Iscan, 2005).

Job Satisfaction has two dimensions; (a) individual variable and experience and (b) organizational variables. These variables interact each other (Spector,1997). Balci (1985) explains job satisfaction in two dimensions as well. Individual variables; age, gender, years of experience, intelligence, personality, self concept, emotional

intelligence, socio-economic status, self efficacy etc. and organizational variables; salary, promotion, supervision and colleagues etc.

One of the elements of the performance that is indicated in most equations related to performance and occupational behaviors is the issue of personality. John Holland commented on the congruity of career choice with personality types assuming that one's interest is in direct relation with one's workplace environment. He believed if the personality of a person is in congruence with his job, it is then that the performance of the workers would change enormously. He suggested that job satisfaction and the tendency to quit a job is dependent on the situations in which people can adapt themselves successfully to their workplace environment (Robins, 2008). People usually seek those jobs in which they are free to display their skills, thoughts, behaviors, values, and talents in such way to recoil incompatibilities.

Yung assumed that human beings will show two different types of attitude and orientation including introversion and extroversion that are inherent and persistent (Ross, 1994). People communicate with outer world in either ways although there is always one alternative way. In case of introversion, the main orientation is inward (Pervin and John, 2002). The introverted one directs much of his attention toward inner and mental elements and is strongly impressed by these elements. There is no doubt that he can also see the outer world whereas the inner world is of prime importance for him (Karimi, 2005). The introverted person is conventional, thoughtful, timid and insecure. The extroverted person is more related to the outer world and is socially involved, active, lively, energetic, outgoing, and valiant (Pervin and John, 2002). In extroversion way of living, the attention is toward the external world and the other basic conditions are also the effect of the exterior domain and not the mental evaluation (Karimi, 2005).

From Eysenck point of view, the introverts respond to sensational impetus stronger than the extroverts and show more sensitivity to low-level forces and have low pain threshold in comparison with the extroverts that is related to the discrepancy in

provocative level of brain. In his findings, the basic level of provocation in the brain of those who are extroverted is lower than the introverted ones. These differences are reflected back to genetics (Sholtz & Sholtz, 2007). The performance of teachers is reliant on various elements that should be identified under close study in order to analyze and fuel their performance. Mental disorders can be either neurotic or psychotic in terms of intensity. They can be classified in terms of differences such as exposing to the reality, understanding and communicating with society along with efficient thoughts and reasoning that used to be accounted on traditionally. Thus, it is likely that the neurotics have the serious feeling of inability but it is not likely to be unable to understand the reality (Azad, 2011). Those psychologists whose interests centered on occupational behaviors believed that the personality of people is related to the type of profession they choose as well as their performance. In other words, those with particular attributes choose specific occupations; hence perform better than the others (Pervin and John, 2002). The findings of Kooshki Shiri, Heydar Ali, and Zahedi, (2010) demonstrated that there is a meaningful relationship between job satisfaction and extroverted qualities and the feeling of responsibility. Also, there is a significant relationship between job satisfactions and the qualities of extroversion, adaptability, as well as responsibility. There is also a significant relationship between job satisfaction and sex whereby the female teachers were more satisfied with their job than the male ones. In a study conducted by NazarPoor Samsami, (2007) the relationship is made between personality traits and job satisfaction of teachers. The findings have shown that the more the degree of introversion in teachers, the less the degree of satisfaction from job promotion and the conditions of workplace. There are numerous studies (Fisher and Hanna,1931: Hoppock,1935; Locke,1976; Judge, Locke and Durham,1997 and Tokar and Subich,1997; Seibert and Kraimer, 2001; Boudreau, Boswell and Judge, 2001; Judge Heller and Klinger,2008) which have shown that a person's personality can serve as a predictor of job satisfaction.

Holland believed that satisfaction and stability and job drives are all part of the personality of individuals and their workplace environment. Mental elements as well as environmental conditions present in institutions and organizations are all the basic factors in creating job satisfaction and occupational progression. A better adaptation between the types of personality and the environment would result in a better adaptation to one's job that finally results in job satisfaction (Shafie Abadi, 1997).

Motzler (2007) in a study "personality types, personnel's satisfaction, and effective commitment" have shown that more than 20% of inconsistencies in job satisfaction of the personnel is because of the differences exist in their personality traits, thus, job satisfaction as a middle agent can affect organizational commitment. Vohra (2010) studied the effect of personality traits on organizational commitment and job satisfaction of the middle managers in India in that all the positive personality traits had an impression on effective organizational commitment, standard commitment, and job satisfaction.

Another important variable for job satisfaction is self efficacy of the teachers. Self efficacy is the belief in one's ability to carry out the necessary action to achieve a certain desired outcomes (Bandura, 1997). Self efficacy belief is an effective process that trigger individual to effective planning and achieving objectives (Aydogan, 2008). In the educational context, where teachers have to meet teaching demands, their efficacy could be an important personal resource in coping with job stress. Teachers' high level of self efficacy shows open mindedness, excellent communication skills, cooperative working desires, willingness to learn, plan and harmony, patient, tolerant, gentle and wise manner of teachers (Goddard and Goddard,2001). The perception of having these talents effects teachers' Job Satisfaction level. Job Satisfaction is emotional expression towards job (Mercer,1997). Previous research has also found that teachers' sense of efficacy is related to their satisfaction with their choice of profession and their competence as rated by school superintendents (Trentham, Silvern, & Brogdon, 1985). Recent

findings have shown that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs have a crucial role in affecting and sustaining their commitment to school and their job satisfaction (Woolfolk&Hoy, 1990;Woolfolk, Rosoff, and Hoy, 1990 Bandura, 1997; Ross,1998; Tschannen-Moran, Woolfolk Hoy, and Hoy,1998; Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy, 2001; Caprara,2003; Caprara, Barbaranelli, Borgogni, Petitta Rubinacci, 2003; Caprara, Barbaranelli, Borgogni, and Steca, 2003; WoolfolkHoy and Davis, 2006). And a teacher with high level of job satisfaction steps up performance and participation for organization. In various theories, self efficacy is put forward as a determining behavior. The expectancy value theory (Vroom,1964; Wigfield and Eccles,2000), for instance, assumes that the likelihood of attaining a valued outcome leads to specific behavior. If a person believes that he or she is capable of gaining positive result, it will be more likely that he or she repeats that behavior. Likewise, within the attribution theory, the beliefs of responsibility for specific outcomes are put forward as guiding a person's subsequent behavior (Weiner,1972). Using an online instrument, Judge et.al. (2005) surveyed 251 employees working in three different organizations and expected a positive relationship between these employees' core self evaluation. SEM analysis revealed a significant relationship between the employees' self efficacy as part of their core self evaluation and satisfaction with their jobs. Caprara et.al. (2006) also used SEM for their studies. They found a positive significant relationship between teachers' self efficacy and job satisfaction of 75 Junior High School teachers. Karabiyik and Korumaz (2013) also found a significant relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and self efficacy perception. According to their study, job satisfaction level increases with the increase in teachers' self efficacy perception. Trentham, Silvern and Brogdan (1995) have also found that teachers' sense of efficacy is related to their satisfaction with their choice of profession and their competence as rated by school superintendents. A strong sense of teacher's self efficacy promotes a firm commitment to the profession and collaborative relationships with colleagues and parents (Coladarci,1992; Imants and

Van Zoelen,1995), contributing fruitfully to the promotion of rich and stimulating learning environment. In line with studies, we can say that teachers' self efficacy contributes to teachers' job satisfaction.

Need of the Study-

Job Satisfaction is indeed of great significance for effective functioning of any teaching institution. Favourable and good performance brings job satisfaction to the teachers. Satisfied workers are the greatest asset to any institution. So, unless and until the workers of a particular organization possess favourable perception of the job, no organization can successfully achieve its goal. Personality is one of the most important variable that contributes to the job satisfaction of the teachers. Recent findings have also shown that teachers' Self Efficacy belief have a crucial role in affecting and sustaining their commitment to school and their job satisfaction (Caprara, Barbaranelli, Borgogni, Petitta and Rubinacci 2003; Caprara, Barbaranelli, Borgogni, and Steca 2003) Hence, the present study has been undertaken to know the influence of personality and self efficacy on job satisfaction of teachers.

Objectives-

- To study the level of Job Satisfaction of teachers.
- To study the influence of gender, personality and self-efficacy and their interaction on job satisfaction of teachers.

Method-

Research Design-

For the purpose of the present investigation, factorial design based upon three independent variable viz., Gender, Personality and Self-Efficacy was followed. The independent variable Gender(A) varied in two ways- Male (A_1) and Female (A_2); the second independent variable Personality (B) varied in two ways- Extrovert (B_1) and Introvert (B_2); the third independent variable Self-Efficacy (C) varied in two ways- high self-efficacy (C_1) and low self-efficacy (C_2); The extreme grouping of self-efficacy was set by using the formula Mean \pm SD. In order to analyze the data, three

ways ANOVA (2X2X2 factorial design) was applied to see the interaction effect of gender, personality and self-efficacy on the job satisfaction of teachers.

Sample and Procedure-

The respondents in this study were teachers who were randomly selected from various senior secondary schools of state Haryana (India). The state Haryana was divided into four zones namely North, South, East and West. Out of each zone, one district was picked up by using the lottery technique. A list of Govt. Sr. Sec. Schools was obtained from the concerned D.E.O of the selected districts and 15 schools from each district were selected at random making total schools to 60. From each school 5-10 teachers were selected.

Initially 400 respondents were chosen. Out of this, the responses of only 315 could be taken for analysis, as only extreme ends were taken into consideration in case of independent variables. As per the requirement of 2x2x2 cells (30 in each cell of the paradigm) the sample of 240 teachers was chosen.

Distribution of Sample (N=240)

Gender	Personality	Self Efficacy	
Male(120)	Extrovert (60)	High Self Efficacy (30)	Low Self Efficacy (30)
	Introvert. (60)	High Self Efficacy (30)	Low Self Efficacy (30)
Female(120)	Extrovert (60)	High Self Efficacy (30)	Low Self Efficacy (30)
	Introvert. (60)	High Self Efficacy (30)	Low Self Efficacy (30)

Figure: 1

Layout of the sample

Tools-

The following tools were used in the present study to obtain reliable data:

Teachers’ Job Satisfaction Questionnaire by S. Mishra

It consisted of 42 items covering six dimensions, namely Security and Accomplishment, Use of Ability, Facilities, Working Conditions, Relationship and Nature of Job. The minimum score of the questionnaire is 42 and the maximum score is 210. Teachers' job satisfaction is classified into five categories according to the range of the scores. The split-half reliability coefficient of the questionnaire was found to be 0.88.

Introversion- Extroversion Inventory by Dr. P. F. Aziz and Dr. Rekha Gupta

The inventory consists of 60 items 30 pertaining to an introvert's characteristics and 30 to an extrovert's characteristics. The test-retest reliability coefficient of the inventory was found to be 0.95.

Occupational Self-Efficacy Scale (OSE) developed by S.Pethe, S. Chaudhary and U. Dhar

This scale consists of 19 items. The range of possible score for this instrument vary from a minimum score of 19 to a maximum score of 95. The odd-even reliability Coefficient for this scale was found to be 98.

Analysis and Interpretation-

In pursuance of the objectives data was analyzed and interpreted under the following heads (1-2):

1. Overall Performance of Senior Secondary School Teachers

Mean and S.D. of 315 teachers of senior secondary schools of Haryana was calculated to assess the level of their job satisfaction

Table 1

Mean and S.D. of Job Satisfaction of senior secondary school teachers.

N	Variable	Mean	S.D.
315	Job Satisfaction	131.68	30

As the obtained mean scores falls in the category 'A' as per the manual of the scale, this can be safely interpreted that Senior Secondary School Teachers of Haryana have been found to be 'highly satisfied' in their job.

2. Influence of Gender, Personality and Self Efficacy and their Interaction on Job Satisfaction of teachers

Table 2
Summary of (2x2x2) Factorial Design ANOVA for Job Satisfaction of teachers.

Gender(A) Personality (B) and Self Efficacy (C)

Source of Variance	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F- ratio	Sig. Level
A	1	777.60	777.60	1.29	NS
B	1	12586.02	12586.02	20.96	.01
C	1	16500.42	16500.42	27.49	.01
AxB	1	16733.4	16733.4	27.87	.01
AxC	1	944.07	944.07	1.57	NS
BxC	1	4018.01	4018.01	6.69	.05
AxBxC	1	504.6	504.6	.84	NS
Error Within	232	139253.86	600.23		
Total	239				

Significant 'F' value according to 'F' table at
.05 Level = 3.87 and at .01 Level = 6.72

Gender-

In case of gender, F- ratio 1.29 (vide Table 2 for df 1/232) is not significant even at .05 level. This indicates that Gender does not have a significant independent effect upon the job satisfaction of teachers.

Personality-

In case of Personality, F- ratio 20.96 (vide Table 2 for df 1/232) is significant at .01 level. This indicates that Personality has a significant independent effect upon the job satisfaction of teachers. In order to interpret this, t-test was applied. The results for the same have been given in the Table 3

Table 3

Mean, S.D and t-ratio of Job Satisfaction of teachers on Personality.

Sr No	Groups	Mean	SD	t- ratio	Sig. Level
1	B ₁	141.83	26.65	4.11	.01
2	B ₂	127.35	27.90		

Table 3 depicts that t-ratio between extrovert and introvert teachers is significant at .01 level. This indicates that significant difference exists in the mean job satisfaction scores of extrovert and introvert teachers. Extrovert teachers got higher scores (M = 141.83) than introvert teachers (M= 127.35). It means that teachers with extrovert type of personality have higher job satisfaction than the teachers with introvert type of personality.

Self- Efficacy-

In case of Self-Efficacy, F- ratio 27.49 (vide Table 2 for df 1/232) is significant at .01 level. This indicates that Self- Efficacy has a significant independent effect on the job satisfaction of teachers. In order to interpret this, t-test was applied. The results for the same have been given in the Table 4

Table 4.

Mean, S.D and t-ratio of Job Satisfaction of teachers on Self -Efficacy

Sr No	Groups	Mean	SD	t- ratio	Sig. Level
1	C ₁	142.88	27.87	4.76	.01
2	C ₂	126.3	26.06		

Table 4. depicts that t –ratio between teachers with high Self-Efficacy and low Self-Efficacy is significant at .01 level. This indicates that significant difference exists in the mean job satisfaction scores of teachers with high self efficacy and low self efficacy. Teachers with high self efficacy got higher scores (M= 142.88) than the teachers with low self efficacy (M=126.3). It means that

teachers with high self efficacy have higher job satisfaction than the teachers with low self efficacy.

Gender (A) X Personality (B)-

Table 2 further reveals that the combined interaction between Gender and Personality of teachers is significant at .01 level (F-ratio 27.87 for df 1/232). This means that there is particular combination of Gender and Personality (AxB) which affects the job satisfaction of teachers. In order to interpret this further, t-test was applied to find out the difference between mean job satisfaction scores of different combination group. The results for the same have been given in Table 5.

Table 5
t-ratio for different combinations of A X B levels for job satisfaction of teachers

Groups	A ₁ B ₁	A ₁ B ₂	A ₂ B ₁	A ₂ B ₂
Mean (S.D)	131.68(25.33)	133.9(25.82)	151.98(23.94)	120.8(28.35)
A₁ B₁ 131.68(25.33)		.47 NS	4.52**	2.22*
A₁ B₂ 133.9(25.82)			3.98**	2.65**
A₂ B₁ 151.98(23.94)				6.52**
A₂ B₂ 120.8(28.35)				

A₁- Male, A₂- Female, B₁- extrovert, B₂- introvert, **- significant at .01 level of significance, *- significant at .05 level of significance, NS – Not Significant.

Table 5 shows that t-ratios for the groups A₁ B₁ vs A₂ B₁ (4.52), A₁ B₂ vs A₂ B₁ (3.98), A₁ B₂ vs A₂ B₂ (2.65) and A₂ B₁ vs A₂ B₂ (6.52) are significant at .01 level and t-ratio for the group A₁ B₁ vs A₂ B₂ (2.22) is significant at .05 level of

significance. This indicates that these combinations differ significantly on mean job satisfaction scores. In order to present the results in brief, these have been arranged in descending order on the basis of their mean scores for different combination groups in Table 6.

Table 6
Groupwise arrangement of mean Job Satisfaction scores in descending order for Gender(A) x Personality (B)

Sr No	Groups	Means
1	A ₂ B ₁	151.98
2	A ₁ B ₂	133.9
3	A ₁ B ₁	131.68
4	A ₂ B ₂	120.8

It may be inferred from Table 6 that female extrovert teachers have the maximum scores on job satisfaction and female introvert teachers have minimum scores on job satisfaction. This shows that female teachers with extrovert personality are more satisfied in their job than the female teachers with introvert personality.

Personality (B) X Self-Efficacy (C)-

Table 2 further reveals that the combined interaction between Personality and Self-Efficacy of teachers is significant at .05 level (F-ratio 6.69 for df 1/232). This means that there is particular combination of Personality and self efficacy (BxC) which affects the job satisfaction of teachers. In order to interpret this further, t-test was applied to find out the difference between mean job satisfaction scores of different combination group. The results for the same have been given in Table 7

Table 7
t-ratio for different combinations of B X C levels for job satisfaction of teachers

Groups	B ₁ C ₁	B ₁ C ₂	B ₂ C ₁	B ₂ C ₂
Mean (S.D)	154.21(24.09)	129.45(23.11)	131.55(26.77)	123.15(28.37)
B ₁ C ₁ 154.21(24.09)		5.75**	4.88**	6.47**
B ₁ C ₂ 129.45(23.11)			.46 NS	1.33 NS
B ₂ C ₁ 131.55(26.77)				1.66 NS
B ₂ C ₂ 123.15(28.37)				

B₁- extrovert, B₂- introvert, C₁- high self efficacy, C₂-- low self efficacy, **- significant at .01 level of significance, *- significant at .05 level of significance, NS – Not Significant.

Table 7 shows that t-ratios for the groups B₁ C₁ vs B₁ C₂ (5.75), B₁ C₁ vs B₂ C₁ (4.88) and B₁ C₁ vs B₂ C₂ (6.47) are significant at .01 level of significance. This indicates that these combinations differ significantly on mean job satisfaction scores. In order to present the results in brief, these have been arranged in descending order on the basis of their mean scores for different combination groups in Table 8.

Table 8
Groupwise arrangement of mean Job Satisfaction scores in descending order for Gender(A) x Personality (B)

Sr No	Groups	Means
1	B ₁ C ₁	154.21
2	B ₂ C ₁	131.55
3	B ₁ C ₂	129.45
4	B ₂ C ₂	123.15

It may be inferred from Table 8 that teachers with extrovert personality and high self efficacy have the maximum scores on job satisfaction and teachers with introvert personality and low self efficacy have minimum scores on job

satisfaction. This shows that teachers with extrovert personality and high self efficacy are more satisfied in their job than the teachers with introvert personality and low self efficacy.

Discussion and Conclusion-

The finding in the present study reveals that there is significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers with respect to personality. Teachers with extrovert personality characteristics have significantly higher level of job satisfaction as compared to teachers with introvert personality characteristics. The present findings are in consistent with the results found by Kavabari, Jirandeh, Kohan, Pashtamsari and Heidari (2013); Ayan and Kocacik, (2010); Kooshki Shiri, Heydar, and Zahedi (2010); Asgari, Naderi and Heykal (2009); Parvaneh Nazarpour Samsami (2007). These results are probably because teaching profession is classified as a social occupational type. People in social occupations tend to be extroverted, receptive and open minded. Extrovert teachers display characteristics like taking their chance in tasks with unknown outcomes, to be very active and continuously be occupied, like changes and being unable to control their feeling completely. They are creative, analytical, logical and intuitively thinking teachers with strong imaginations (Smith et.al., 1993) were more “taking” in using various strategies and technology as compared to sentimental teachers with realistic and social qualities. Such teachers always thinking their job important and meaningful, try to learn new things regarding their job. That is perhaps the reason that they are more satisfied in their job. Results of present study get support from the study of Judge, et.al. 2008; Boudreau,et.al. 2001; Seibert and Kraimer, 2001; Tokar and Subich,1997. These studies also concluded that high extraversion is correlated with high level of job satisfaction.

The finding in the present study also reveals that there is significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers with respect to self efficacy Teachers with

high self efficacy belief are more satisfied in their job than the teachers with low self efficacy. This is because teachers with strong sense of self efficacy exhibit high level of planning and organization (Allinder,1994), are open to new ideas and more willing to experiment with new methods and techniques to better meet the needs of the students (Cousins and Walker 1995; Guskey 1988; Stein and Wang 1988) These teachers also exhibit passion and zeal for teaching (Allinder1994) are more faithful and committed to their profession (Tschannen-Moran and Hoy, 2001). They are also more determined at a task, take more “risks, and are more likely to use innovative elements in their teaching. Another probable reason for this may be that teachers with higher efficacy possess a higher quality of decision making. On the other hand, people with low efficacy give up quickly, have low aspiration of achievement, and experience more anxiety, which leads to stress and burnout (Gibson and Dembo,1984). Another probable reason for this is that teachers with high levels of self-efficacy beliefs are more likely to be able to create the conditions and to promote the interpersonal networks that nourish and sustain their work satisfaction. This seems particularly true today as teachers' job satisfaction is often at risk, due to the many new responsibilities and to the scarcity of external rewards. In this context, it is likely that teachers' perceived sense of competence is a primary source of intrinsic motivation and satisfaction. The relation between teachers' self efficacy beliefs and their job satisfaction further corroborate this reasoning. There may be individual teachers who feel efficacious, although unsatisfied with their job, but this is quite unusual. Thus, it is likely that gathering together efficacious teachers leads to higher satisfaction than gathering together teachers who doubt their capacities. Whereas individual self-efficacy beliefs lead to pursuing the conditions that lead to being satisfied with one's own job, joining schools and associating with other teachers that value their capabilities, unavoidably leads to potentiate the conditions that may bring them satisfaction.

Results of the present study further substantiate the contribution of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs on their job satisfaction (Caprara, et al., 2003; Caprara, Barbaranelli, Borgogni, & Steca, 2003) and provide new elements that attest to the influence that their perceived self-efficacy in the ability to effectively handle various tasks, obligations, and challenges related to their professional role leads to their job satisfaction and students' academic achievement at the school level.

Regarding interactional effects, the joint effect of factors viz., (i) gender and personality on job satisfaction of teacher and (ii) personality and self efficacy on job satisfaction of teacher is found significant. This joint effect of various interactions on dependent variables may be significant due to the reason that factors gender, personality and self efficacy exert significant independent contributing effect in determining the job satisfaction scores. Another probable reason for significant various interaction effects may be due to the two different ways in which each factor is varying viz. male and female teachers extrovert and introvert teachers, teachers with high and low self efficacy.

Implications-

The present study will be very helpful to the education planners, policy makers and administrators in bringing about the job satisfaction by strengthening their self-efficacy and improving their personality the findings of the present investigation bears significant educational implications.

On the basis of self efficacy it was observed that teachers with high level of self efficacy are highly satisfied with their job than the teachers who possessed low level of self efficacy. Our findings have important implications for policies aimed to creating and maintaining an effective learning environment, administering suitable intervention programme and promoting collaboration with colleagues, students and parents.

Again, since teaching profession is classified as a social occupational type and people in social occupations tend to be extroverted, receptive and open minded,

They are able to properly communicate with others in the society and workplace so that these have the ability to act naturally with people in a way that will make them much more successful than introvert because these types are of the requirements of the job, hence, extrovert people should be recruited in teaching profession and can be trained how to deal with work pressure, it is then that the hope can be made to increase the level of satisfaction and as a consequence the effectiveness of teachers.

Reference-

- Asgari, P., Naderi, F, & Heykal, K. (2009). Personality traits Tests, Philip's social support and job satisfaction of JDI. The relations of personality traits and social support with job satisfaction of female teachers of Ahvaz, *the Magazine of Females and Fall Culture*, 19-80. *Job satisfaction 2012*, 4 (19).
- Allinder, R. (1994). The relationship between efficacy and the instructional practices of special education teachers and consultants. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 17, 86–95.
- Ashton, P. T., & Webb, R. B. (1982). *Teachers' sense of efficacy: Toward an ecological model*. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, New York.
- Ashton, P.T. and Webb, R.B. (1986). *Making a difference: Teachers' sense of efficacy and student achievement*. New York: Longman.
- Ayan, S., and Kocacik, F. (2010). The Relation between the Level of Job Satisfaction and Types of Personality in High School Teachers. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 35(1).<http://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2010v35n1.4>
- Aydogan D (2008). Academic procrastination's with self-esteem, selfefficacy and state anxiety will predict. Unpublished MA Thesis. GaziUniversity Institute of Education Sciences Department of Educational Sciences, Ankara.

- Azad, H.(2011). Psychopathology. Tehran: Besat Publication. 11th Ed. 1st Vol
- Aziz, P. F. and Gupta, R. (2002). Introversion Extroversion Inventory. National Psychological Corporation, Agra.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self- Efficacy: The Exercise of Control*. Worth Publishers.
- Blum, M.L. and Naylor, J.C. (1968). *Industrial Psychology* Haper and Row, New York.
- Caprara,G.V., Barbaranelli, C., Borgogni, L, Petitta, L. and Rubinacci, A. (2003). Teachers',school staffs' and parents' efficacy as determinants of attitude towards school. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*,18, 15-31.
- Caprara,G.V., Barbaranelli, C., Borgogni, L and Steca, P.. (2003). Efficacy beliefs as determinants of teachers Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95, 821-832.
- Caprara,G.V., Barbaranelli, C., Steca, P. and Malone, P.S. (2006). Teachers self efficacy beliefs as determinant of Job Satisfaction and Students' Academic Achievement. A Study at the school level. *Journal of School Psychology*, 44,473-490.
- Coladarci,T. (1992). Teachers' sense of efficacy and commitment to teaching. *Journal of Experimental Education*,60,323-337.
- Gibson, S. and Dembo, M. (1984). Teacher efficacy: A Construct Validation. *Journal of Educational Psychology*,76, 569-582.
- Goddard, R.D. and Goddard, Y.L. (2001) A multilevel Analysis of the relationship between Teacher and Collective Efficacy in Urban Schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*. Vol. 17, 807-818.

- Guskey, T. (1988). Teacher efficacy, self-concept, and attitudes toward the implementation of instructional innovation. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 4, 63–69.
- Hoppock, R.(1935). *Job Satisfaction* New York, Ny: Harper and Row Publishing.
- Imants, J. and Van Zoelen, A. (1995). Teachers' sickness absence in primary schools, school climate and teachers' sense of efficacy. *School Organization*,15,77-86.
- Judge,T.A.,Bono, J.E., Erez, A. and Locke, E.A. (2005). Core self evaluation and job and life satisfaction: The role of self –concordance and goal attainment. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 90, 257-268.
- Kavabari, B.A., Jirandeh, H.P.O.,Kohan, R.D, Pashtamsari,M.A.N. andHeidari,F.M.(2013). The Study of the Relationship between the Personality Types (Extroversion, Neurotic, Psychotic) and Job Satisfaction in Teachers of Secondary School in Rasht District I *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research* 3(2)843-847.
- Karabiyik, B. and Korumaz, M. (2013) Relationship between Teachers' Self-Efficacy Perception and Job Satisfaction Level *Science Direct, ELSEVIER Procedia- Social and Behavioural Sciences*
- Karimi, Y.(2005). *Personality Psychology*, 14th Ed. Tehran: Payam-e Noor University Publication.
- Kooshki Shiri, N., Heydar Ali, H., and Zahedi,(2010). NEO's Five-Factor questionnaire, 2011, job satisfaction questionnaire. 2002, Characteristics associated with teachers' job satisfaction factors, Psychological Research. *Job satisfaction*. 8-26.
- Locke, E. (1983). Nature and Causes of Job Satisfaction Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology (ed) Durnette, John Wiley and Sons, USA

- Mercer, D. (1997). Job Satisfaction and the Secondary Head Teacher. The Creation of a Model of Job Satisfaction. *School Leadership and Management*. Cilt 17 Sayı:1
- Motzler. K.(2007). Personality traits, employee satisfaction and effective commitment. *Total quality management & Business*. 18 (5). 589-595.
- Nazarpour Samsami, P.(2007). Eysenck Personality tests and tests made job satisfaction, the relationship of teachers' personality traits with their job satisfaction at elementary, secondary and high school of Masjed Soleiman. *Research and Curriculum* (Knowledge and Research in Education), Curriculum.*JobSatisfaction*. 121-146,
- Pendergast, D. (2011). An investigation of early childhood teachers self-efficacy beliefs in the teaching of artseducation. *International Journal of Education & Arts*. Cilt 12. Sayı 9
- Pervin, L. E., and John, O. P.(2002). Personality: theory and research, translated: Mohammad Jaafar Javadi and Parvin Kadivar, 1st Ed., Tehran: Aaij.
- Robins, S. P.(2008). Organizational behavior, Concepts, Theories and functions, 2 VOL: translated by Ali Parsian and Saied Mohammad Arabi, Tehran; *Cultural research office*.
- Ross A. O.(1994). Personality Psychology (theories and processes), translated by Siavash Jamalfar, 2nd Ed,Tehran: Besat.
- Ross, J. A. (1992). Teacher efficacy and the effect of coaching on student achievement. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 17, 51–65.
- Ross, J. A. (1998). The antecedents and consequences of teacher efficacy. In J. Brophy (Ed.), *Advances in research on teaching*, Vol. 7 (pp. 4974). Greenwich, CT: JAI Press
- Schoderbek, P. P., Cosier, R.A., & Aplin, J.C. (1991). Management.Harcourt Brace Jovanovich Publishers. USA.

- Shafie Abadi, A.(1997). *Guidance and job consultation and professional and theories of job selection*, 16th, Tehran: Roshd Publication.159-161.
- Sholtz, D. P., and Sholtz, S. A.(2007). *Personality theories*, translated by Yahya Saied Mohammadi, 11th Ed, Tehran: Virayesh Publication
- Spector,P.E.(1997). *JobSatisfaction:Application, Assessment,Cause,and Consequences*.California: SAGE Public ations.
- Trentham, L. Silvern, S. and Brogdan, R. (1985). Teacher efficacy and teacher competency ratings. *Psychology in the schools*,22,343-352.
- Tschannen-Moran, M. and Woolfolk Hoy, A. (2001). Teacher efficacy: Capturing an elusive concept. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17, 783–805.
- Tschannen-Moran, M., Woolfolk Hoy, A. and Hoy, W. K. (1998). Teacher efficacy: Its meaning and measure. *Review of Educational Research*, 68, 202–248
- Vohra, N.(2010). Influence of positive characteristics on organizational commitment and job satisfaction of India middle manager submitted to journal of psychology for publication. Available from: <http://www.iimcal.ac.in/res/upd>.Accessed Ague 24.
- Vroom,V.H.(1964). *Work and Motivation*. New York: Wiley.
- Weiner, B. (1972). Attribution theory, achievement motivation and aspirations concerning teaching as a career for different types of beginning teachers. *Learning and Instruction* 18, 408-428.
- Wigfield, A. and Eccles, J.S. (2000). Expectancy-value theory of achievement motivation. *Contemporary Education Psychology* 25,68-81.
- Woolfolk, A. E. and Hoy,W. K. (1990). Prospective teachers' sense of efficacy and beliefs about control. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82, 81–91.
- Woolfolk, A. E., Rosoff, B. and Hoy, W. K. (1990). Teachers' sense of efficacy and their beliefs about managing students. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 6, 137–148.

- Woolfolk Hoy, A. and Davis, H. A. (2006). Teacher self-efficacy and its influence on the achievement of adolescents. In F. Pajares & T. Urdan (Eds.), *Self-efficacy of adolescents* (pp. 117–137). Greenwich, Connecticut: Information Age Publishing.
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2000). Self-efficacy: An essential motive to learn. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25, 82 - 91.

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Paper-10

**An Assessment of Mid Day Meal Scheme in
Primary Schools of Jalpaiguri District
(undivided) in West Bengal**

Manik Aich Sarkar

An Assessment of Mid Day Meal Scheme in Primary Schools of Jalpaiguri District (undivided) in West Bengal

Manik Aich Sarkar¹⁶

Abstract

The Mid Day Meal Scheme (MDMS) in primary schools is an important historical step taken by the government to reduce dropout and increase enrollment in govt. primary schools. The present study tries to make an assessment of the ground reality of the scheme in 40 government aided primary schools from three different blocks of Jalpaiguri district in West Bengal. All the schools performing well, but a lot of problems faced by them in terms of allotment money, water facilities, cooking sheds, storing of cooking materials and utensils, food nutrition and healthcare. After the implementation of MDMS dropout has been reduced and percentage of presence in schools has been increased. A lot of work has to be done to ensure good quality of food to students without disrupting teaching activities and a long way to go.

Introduction-

Universalization of Primary Education is a constitutional provision in India. Primary education is the first step of a child to get entrance into the education system. But the dropout from primary education due to socio-economic conditions of the family can not be ignored. The Mid Day Meal Scheme (MDMS) is a centrally sponsored scheme where cooked meals are provided to all children present in the school. In India during the year 2013-14 about 10.45 crores beneficiary students are taking cooked meal in 11.58 lakhs primary and upper primary schools. The MDMS in West Bengal was first launched in 1100 schools of six districts during the year 2003. Before 2003 children were

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provided dry food like bread, biscuits, uncooked rice etc in an irregular basis. As a result on the day of distribution of dry food and uncooked rice, the presence percentage in school is much more than that of other days. The coverage of schools increased gradually and up to December 2011 the programme has covered 8519472 students of class I to class V of 73841 primary schools and Sishu Siksha Kendra and 3396453 students of class VI to class VIII of 8715 upper primary schools and Madhyamik Siksha Kendras of the state. Most of the primary schools in West Bengal were brought under the coverage of the MDMS before the legislation of the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2009 (the RTE Act). As a result presence percentage in schools has been increased and drop-out rate has been decreased. As per DISE report 2009-10 average provisional drop-out rate was 4.97 percent in primary and 8.22 in upper primary level.

Background and Objectives of the study-

Jalpaiguri is one of the backward districts in west Bengal in terms of education, employment and healthcare. The geographical location and various constraints like communication, mineral resources, fertile land etc. are the main reasons for its backwardness. But in spite of that Jalpaiguri has famous for its natural resources. Economic activities of jalpaiguri are mainly based on three 'Ts' like tea, timber and tourism. Besides, a large number of migrants were coming from Bihar, Jharkhand, Nepal and Bhutan working as a tea worker with a minimum salary in this district. Therefore, poverty still exists and radical changes not yet noticed. Although it is culturally developed and jalpaiguri is the divisional head quarter of jalpaiguri division. As per census 2011 jalpaiguri had a population of 38, 72,846 (37% SC and 19% ST) out of which male were 19, 83,064 and female 18, 89,782. In 2001 census jalpaiguri had a population of 34, 01,173 of which male and female were 17, 51,145 and 16, 50,028 respectively. About 72.62% lives in rural areas and the rest 27.38% lives in urban areas. Average

literacy rate of Jalpaiguri in 2011 were 73.25% as compared to 62.85% in 2001. If things are looked out at gender wise, male and female literacy were 79.95% and 66.23% respectively. For 2001 census, same figures stood at 72.83% and 52.21% in Jalpaiguri District. Sex Ratio (per 1000) 953 in 2011 and 942 in 2001. As per DISE report 2010-11, in Jalpaiguri there were 3178 primary schools out of which 2029 managed by Dept. of School Education, 42 by Municipality, 1088 by Panchayet & Rural Development and 19 by NCLP (National Child Labour Project). The present study is an effort to study the assessment and management of the MDMS in primary schools and try to find out the constraints behind the programme.

Status and Funds Allotment for MDMS in Primary Schools-

It is a comprehensive programme both central and state govts are involved. Food grains/rice allotted to each student is 100 gm. per day and that will be supplied by the govt. of India at free of cost. For procuring cooking ingredients like pulses, vegetables, egg, chicken, salt, condiments, oil and fuel for each student – Rs. 3.69 per day.

For purchases of kitchen devices Rs. 5000/- allotted to a unit. Where the enrolment of students are more, and this fund is insufficient to meet the requirements, the Panchayet Samities sometimes contributed from their own funds to meet the needs.

Honorarium per cook-cum helper is paid @ Rs. 1000/- per month w.e.f. Dec'09.

For 1 to 25 Students – 1 cook-cum-helper.

For 26 to 100 Students – 2 cook-cum-helper.

And for each next 100 Students – 1 each.

Egg once or twice in a month and chicken once or never in a month.

The concerned teacher or and a guardian present in the school should test the food first and afterwards distributed amongst the students.

Methodology-

The present study is an in-depth study for the assessment and management of MDMS in primary school of Jalpaiguri district in the state of West Bengal. The majority of the primary school managed by the Dept. of School Education and the Dept. of Panchayet & Rural Development. The present study is mainly based on two different assessment and analysis - one is infrastructural facilities like cooking room, drinking water, location of school etc and another one is feed-back from students, teachers and cook-cum helpers regarding MDMS. The primary data is collected through the well structured questionnaire and personal interviewed by the researcher in the choosen study areas in jalpaiguri district.

Sampling -

The District of Jalpaiguri, West bengal, has been choosen as the Universe of Study. Out of thirteen blocks, three blocks namely Jalpaiguri Sadar, Dhupguri and Nagrakata have been chosen because of its backwardness, geographical location, infrastructure & communication, education and employment opportunity. Jalpaiguri Sadar is a developed block having District and Divisional Headquater, a large number of offices, banks, schools, colleges, university campus, shops, shoping-mal etc. The main occupations of this block are service, business and agriculture. Dhupguri is a moderately developed block and one of the fastest developing blocks in West Bengal. It is one of the business centres in North Bengal. The main occupations of this block are agriculture and business. Whereas, Nagrakata is a less developed block. It is situated on the foot of the Himalayans and more than 60 percent of the people in this block belonging to SC/ST communities. The main occupations are tea worker with a lower wage rate, collection of fire-wood from forest, live-stock production (cattle, goat, pig, sheep and poultry farming)etc. At first, 40 primary schools have been selected by non-probability quota sampling, 10 from Dhupguri block and 15 each from Nagrakata and Jalpaiguri Sadar block. For the selection of schools, two important different matters have been taken into

consideration- one is location of the schools (whether situated in rural area or in urban area) and another one is communication of schools (distance from main road or road pucca, kaccha, hilly, forest etc). The study has been conducted during Jan'14 to May'14 . Then 40 teachers and 40 cook-cum-helper have been chosen (one each from 40 selected schools) for questionnaire regarding problems faced by them and valuable opinion for proper implementation of the scheme. Similarly, 120 students have been chosen (minimum 2 and maximum 5 students chosen from 40 selected schools) for questionnaire regarding problems, needs and demands and satisfaction of the served meal.

Data Collection and Data Analysis-

Proper permission taken from Head master, Panchayet Pradhan, Samity Education Officer in Block Office to assess the programme. A list of primary schools, their location, distance from road, year of establishment, year of implementation of the scheme have been obtained from Samity Education Officer in Block Office. Sometimes local representatives have been involved to do the work smoothly.

The collected data has been complied into various simple and complex frequency tables, percentages and averages wherever necessary have been computed for a valuable conclusions.

Results and Findings-

Most of the sample schools are located on the road or and within one km. from main road and way of approach to schools is easy as shown in Table:1. Although there are some schools which are located more than one km. and way of approach is difficult due to its location. Most of the schools have two or and three classroom as well as two or and three teachers while a negligible portion of schools where there are more than three classroom as well as more than three teachers. Generally schools which are situated in towns or developed villages are comperatively in better position in respect of collection of rice,

fuel, firewood and vegetables etc. than other schools which are situated in remote areas. About two third of the sample schools are controlled and managed by the Dept. of School Education.

Table: 1
Location and Status of sample schools (N=40)

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Location and Status		
Village	24	60
Town	16	40
Location from main road		
On road	12	30
Within 1 km.	20	50
More than 1 km.	8	20
Way of approach		
Easy	21	52.5
Moderate	15	37.5
Very difficult (hilly, jungle)	4	10
No of class room		
Two	22	55
Three	13	32.5
More than three	5	12.5
No of teachers		
Two	16	40
Three	14	35
More than three	10	25
Controlled and Managed by		
Dept. of School Education	26	65
Dept. of Panchayet & Rural Development	11	27.5
Municipality	3	7.5

Source: Based on Primary Survey.

Most of the schools either have a kitchen shed or have a separate kitchen and also situated inside school premises as shown in Table: 2. Although kitchen is visible to students due to insufficient land area in most of the schools but kitchen is situated far from toilet in major cases keeping in mind about the health and hygienic care of the students.

Kitchen shed or separate kitchen being constructed having door in 95% cases and with the presence of window in 97.5% cases for safety and sufficient air-light purposes respectively.

Table: 2

Condition of cookhouse in sample schools (N=40)

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Type of cook house		
Kitchen shed	16	40
Separate kitchen	24	60
Location		
Inside school building	26	65
Outside school building	14	35
Inside school premises	38	95
Outside school premises	2	5
Cookhouse visible to students	32	80

Cookhouse not visible to students	8	20
Near classroom	28	70
Far from classroom	12	30
Near toilet	8	20
Far from toilet	32	80
Construction of cookhouse		
Kuccha wall	2	5
Pucca wall	38	95
Kuccha floor	24	60
Pucca floor	16	40
Kuccha roof	4	10
Pucca roof	36	90
Door present	38	95
Door absent	2	5
Window present	39	97.5
Window absent	1	2.5
Sufficient light,air	32	80
Insufficient light,air	8	20

Source: Based on Primary Survey.

The provision of water supply is available with in schools or adjacent of schools in 95% cases as shown in Table: 3 and about 90% cases water is available from Municipality tap or and tube well. In few occasion water is available from well in the remote tea garden area. Jalpaiguri is famous for forest and fire wood is available at a cheapest cost. Hence, firewood is used to cook meal in 70% cases, whereas only 10% cases LPG are used and in 20% cases both LPG and firewood are used. The cost and availability of LPG are the major reasons behind its low uses. Although market is situated within one km. from schools in 70% cases but ration shop and FCI godown is situated within one to three km. from schools in 52.5% cases resulting increase in carrying costs which directly affected the quality of meal.

Table: 3
Amenities and Facilities in sample schools (N=40)

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Water available		
Within schools	34	85
Adjacent to schools	4	10
Not adjacent to schools	2	5
Water provision		
Municipality water	8	20
Tube well	28	70
Well	4	10
Washing eating vessels		
Water available in schools	34	85
Water available outside schools	6	15
Fuel used for cooking		
Only LPG	4	10
Only Firewood	28	70
Both	8	20
Storing of food grains		
Separate storeroom	4	10
Cookhouse-cum-storeroom	22	55
Class room	14	35
Distance from schools to Ration shop/FCI		
Less than 1 km	17	42.5
Between 1-3 km	21	52.5
More than 3 km	2	5
Distance from schools to nearest market		
Less than 1 km	28	70

Between 1-3 km	11	27.5
More than 3 km	1	2.5

Source: Based on Primary Survey.

On the day of visit, about 75% of the schools provided rice-dal and rice-vegetables, only 5% of schools provided rice and egg as shown in Table: 4. There is no separate area for feeding meal and about 85% cases students eat meal either in varandha or in the open ground. Most of the cases seating style is linear and extra meal if demanded is distributed among the students.

Table: 4

Meal provided on the day of visit in sample schools (N=40)

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Meal served on the day of visit		
Rice and dal	12	30
Rice and vegetable	18	45
Rice and egg	2	5
Khichudi	8	20
Potato and vegetables		
Included	22	55
Excluded	18	45
Seating provision		
Inside the classroom	6	15
In the varandha	24	60
In the open ground	10	25
Seating style		
Circular	8	20
Linear	26	65
Standing in a line and collect one by one	6	15
Extra meal if demand		
Provided	32	80

Not provided	8	20
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Source: Based on Primary Survey.

Opinion of teachers' in respect of year of introduction, teaching activities, enrolled and dropout of students, accounts of MDM etc. are very important. About three fourth of the total sample schools MDMS has been introduced during 2004 to 2009 as shown in Table: 5. Construction of kitchen-cum-store has been completed in all schools. Although, there is continuous increase in enrollment of students 80% cases and continuous decrease in dropout of students 87.5% cases but teaching activities which are the main activities of primary education have been disturbed in 45% cases due to MDMS. Both presence of students in classes and interest in learning have been increased- it is the good results of MDMS. There is a problem of storing of rice and other cook items in 60% cases and accounts maintained by the cook-cum-helper in 55% cases.

Table: 5

Teachers' Opinion and Responses in respect of the programme in sample schools (N=40)

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Year of introduction of MDM		
Up to 2003	8	20

2004 to 2009	29	72.5
2010 to till survey	3	7.5
Construction of kitchen-cum-stores completed		
Up to 2003	Nil	0
2004 to 2009	22	55
2010 to till survey	16	40
Enrollment of students		
Increase	32	80
Same	6	15
Decrease	2	5
Drop-out of students		
Increase	3	7.5
Same	2	5
Decrease	35	87.5
Students' interested in learning		
Increase	28	70
Same	4	10
Decrease	8	20
Presence of students in classes		
Increase	32	80
Same	6	15
Decrease	2	5
Teaching activities disturbed		
Of course disturbed	18	45
Sometimes disturbed	16	40
Never disturbed	6	15
Problems for storing of rice		
Yes	24	60
No	16	40

Accounts maintained by		
Teachers	8	20
Cook-cum-helper	22	55
both	10	25

Source: Based on Primary Survey.

Cook-cum-helper is appointed through SHGs/NGOs having some criteria in 80% cases as shown in Table: 6 and everybody (cook-cum-helper) has expressed that their honorarium is very low (only Rs.1000/- p.m.). They have argued that cooking amenities are moderate in 70% cases and quality of meal is also moderate in 67.5% cases due to lower allotment per student (only Rs. 3.69 per student). Most of the schools have two cook-cum-helpers in 72.5% cases. If cook-cum-helper taking leave of absence, the mid-day-meal for the day is cooked either by cook's relatives or by the teachers or ready to eat food is served to students for that particular day only.

Table: 6

Cook-cum-helpers' Opinion and Responses in respect of the programme in sample schools (N=40)

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
How appointed		
From SHGs/NGOs	32	80
Panchayet/Municipalities	8	20
Honorarium		

Very low	40	100
Alright	Nil	
Cooking amenities		
Good	8	20
Moderate	28	70
Bad	4	10
Excess meal if any		
Distributed to students	32	80
Distributed to local boy	6	15
Taken to home	2	5
Quality of meal		
Good	5	12.5
Moderate	27	67.5
Bad	8	20
No of cook-cum-helper		
One	6	15
Two	29	72.5
More than Two	5	12.5
If any cook-cum-helper becomes absent, cooking helped by		
The relatives of the cook	16	40
Teachers	18	45
Neighbors/guardians	6	15

Source: Based on Primary Survey.

MDMS is for the students only and assessment of their opinion in respect of satisfaction, quality of meal and interest in learning etc. is necessary. About 93% of students taking meal (68.3% taking regularly). Only 6.7% students never taking meal, they are taking Tiffin from home. 63.3% students never taking Tiffin from home; it indicates that there is poverty in this region. Majority of the students like to eat rice and egg instead of other food items. Regarding quality of food, almost 50% of students' is moderate. There has been a lack of health consciousness among the students; only 46.7% of students always washing of hands before taking meal and the rest of the students washing of hands sometimes or never. Only 30% of students feel illness ever it shows that either they biologically strong or the meal is fresh and health hygienic.

Table: 7

Students' Opinion and Responses in respect of the programme in sample schools (N=120)

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Consume cooked meal		
Always	82	68.3
Sometimes	30	25
Never	8	6.7
Quality of meal		

Good	34	28.3
Moderate	58	48.4
Bad	28	23.3
Preferred meal of the Students'		
Rice and egg	65	54.2
Rice and chicken	15	12.5
Khichudi	16	13.3
Rice and dal	24	20
Feel illness ever after consume meal		
Yes	36	30
No	84	70
Eating vessels washed by		
Self	28	23.3
Cook-cum-helper	92	76.7
Washing of hands before Taking meal		
Always	56	46.7
Sometimes	42	35
Never	22	18.3
Taking Tiffin from home		
Always	8	6.7
Sometimes	36	30
Never	76	63.3

Source: Based on Primary Survey.

Proportion of students taking mid-day meal

Proportion of students taking Tiffin from home

Proportion of Preferred meal of the Students'

Conclusion-

The study has found that there are several positive impacts of MDMS in respect of increase in enrollment, presence in the classes, interest in learning, decrease in dropouts etc. but there are several negative impacts also like disruption of

teaching-learning process, unnecessary shouting during feeding meal, dirty conditions in schools etc. Initially, there are some problems of opposition from guardians of students regarding cook-cum-helpers. Guardians of upper caste has opposed to take meal cooked by backward caste or and minority community. But now it is solved after negotiation with guardians and in some cases changes of cook-cum-helper have been made.

Following are some recommendations that are to be taken into consideration by the govt. to ensure smooth implementation of the MDMS:

1. Kitchen-cum-store rooms are to be completed to all schools with in a specific time limit.
2. Separate pucca shed for eating purpose is to be completed.
3. Allotment per student is to be increased to Rs. 10/- per day.
4. Dal of 50 gm. Per student along with rice of 150 gm. are to be provided from FCI/ Fair Price Shop.
5. Honorarium of cook-cum-helper to be increased to Rs. 2500/- p.m.
6. LPG to be served at a subsidize rate as and when necessary.
7. Drinking water facilities should be improved.
8. Contingency fund to be provided to meet temporary labour for any leave of absence from cook-cum-helper; teachers are not to be involved in cooking process.
9. Egg must to serve at least once in a week and chicken once in a month.
10. Medical team must to visit once in a month.

Reference-

1. Pratchi Trust (2005): The Impact of Mid-Day Meal Programme in West Bengal, Available at www.pratchi.org and. www.righttofoodindia.org.
2. Pratchi Trust (2010): The Pratchi Report on Mid-Day Meal: The Mid-day Meal Programme in Urban Primary and Rural Upper Primary Schools in West Bengal, New Delhi.

3. National Programme of Nutritional Support to Primary Education, 2006 (Mid-day Meal Scheme), Guidelines: Ministry of Human Resource Development, Department of School Education and Literacy, Government of India, Mid-Day Meal Scheme, <http://mdm.nic.in>.
4. “Basic Guidelines for Implementation of Cooked Mid-day Meal Programme for the Primary School Students”, by the Joint Secretary to the Government of West Bengal, School Education Department.
5. Archana Shah and Nisha Shukla. “Mid Day Meal Scheme in Primary Schools of Tehri Garwal in Uttarakhand”, Indian Journal of Social Research Vol.55 (4) (July-Aug, 2014):621-630.
6. Office of the District Magistrate, Jalpaiguri.
7. The District Primary School Council, Jalpaiguri.
8. Office of the Block Development Officer, Jalpaiguri (Sadar), Dhupguri and Nagrakata.

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Paper-11

**National Mission on Higher Education
(RUSA)-What Does It Mean for State
Funded Universities?**

Dr. Neeti Dutta

National Mission on Higher Education (RUSA)-What Does It Mean for State Funded Universities?

Dr. Neeti Dutta¹⁷

Abstract

Indian higher education has expanded phenomenally in quantitative terms since Independence both in terms of number of higher education institutions as well as number of students studying in higher education. Though, these numbers are comparatively less in number than any developed countries in comparison to the age group of 15-29 years. Efforts to increase the number of institutions as well as GER started from University Education Commission. It got impetus in the subsequent five year plans. But with growing number of institutions, the quality of higher education has been deteriorated and it is more so in case of state universities and colleges. State universities are facing myriad of problems today. National Mission of Higher Education (RUSA) has highlighted on four aspects of higher education i.e. access, inclusion, equity and excellence. So, any improvement in state universities/colleges related to access, equity, inclusion and excellence would lead to improvement in higher education. RUSA is a centrally sponsored demand driven scheme. State will develop a plan for its restructuring and expansion of higher education with the help of State Higher Education Council (SEHC) created for growth, expansion and restructuring of universities and colleges. RUSA is actually a plan of rejuvenation of state universities and colleges so that it caters to larger population of students. Moreover, wherever necessary open model colleges at district level especially in Economically Backward Districts (ECB) to increase access, equity and inclusion apart from quality. The funding under RUSA will be norm and performance based. The present paper talks about the key areas where state universities can

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derive benefits from the RUSA scheme especially in the field of research, governance, academics, accreditation etc.

Key Words: Higher education, Universities, Colleges, RUSA, Equity, Inclusion, Quality, Research

Introduction-

Higher Education is always in the helm of affairs. If we start our journey from independence we will find, very first commission which was set up related to education was University Education Commission (1948-49). The main objective of the commission was to expand and enhance the quality of higher education. In the last six decades though, we have grown phenomenally not in terms of number of educational institutions but also in terms of numbers of students enrolled in higher education. Yet, this percentage is well below among the BRIC nation as well as in comparison to many American and European countries. Though, we are among the few nations in the world which have largest network of higher education institutions. But, if we talk about the quality aspects we do not have any institution which is within top 200 in the world ranking. Even within the country there are only a handful of quality education institutions which have been recognized globally. The stage is reached where we need institutions of par excellence not only in teaching, but also in infrastructure, research, faculty etc. The problem with education sector is that it is in concurrent list and it is the responsibility of both the state and central government to look after the affairs of education. As far as school education is concerned it is justified enough as it is impossible to look after the schools from grass root level. Even though, several centrally sponsored programmes were launched to improve the situation of school education. SSA and RMSA are such schemes which have made the school education accessible to vary large population of the country. But, in case of higher education, since universities are face of the nation and provides nationally and internationally highly skilled workforce therefore it is

very important to provide high quality education. If we look at the global scenario, countries like America, UK, Australia, China, Switzerland and many East and South Asian countries have made their impact because of high quality higher education being offered by them. Presently, higher education offered by India is of low quality and myriad with several challenges. Firstly, in the name of excellence we have handful of institutions. These institutions are centrally funded and their coverage is limited. Second, bulk of the state universities are state controlled and managed though many of them receive financial assistance from central government through UGC. These universities are reeling under plethora of scarcities which resultant in pathetic conditions mostly in terms of human resources, infrastructure, high teacher student ratio, poor library facilities, poor research facilities etc. Third, most of the state universities are affiliating in nature and some of them have almost 5000 colleges affiliated with them resulting in poor educational management and low creditability. Fourth, state universities are the highest in terms of number of the student's enrolment but, they face severe starvation from finance. As per the RUSA Report (2013) the centrally-funded institutions receive generous funding from the centre, they have a limited coverage in terms of enrollment. About 94% of the students enrolled in government funded (48% of total enrolments) or government controlled private institutions come under the state higher education system. It is worth noting that most private education institutions (52% of all enrolments) are affiliated to state universities and come under their academic and administrative control. The fifth challenge is the low gross enrolment ratio. Indian higher education has GER of 19.4% in comparison to the size of the total population enrolled in higher education institutions, the GERs for SCs, STs and OBCs are far below the average GER and those of other social groups. There is also a wide gender disparity; GER for males is 20.9% while that for females is only 16.5%. The educationally backward districts which have been identified 374 in numbers

have GER of 12.6. There are also differences in the quality of institutions and enrolments between rural and urban areas and between developed states and not so-developed ones (RUSA, 2013). Sixth, the uneven distribution of these universities and colleges has created the problem of equity and access of higher education to masses. The states like Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Chennai, Maharashtra, Delhi has high concentration of higher educational institutions whereas state like Bihar, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand and North-East have low concentration of higher education institutions'. Apart from it the problems of higher education are many like shortage of faculty, infrastructure, research facilities etc. all these deficiencies are more pronounced in state institutions than in the central institutions. To improve the condition of state universities and colleges under state universities, central government has launched "The National Mission on Higher Education" commonly known as Rashtryia Ucchar Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA). It is a centrally sponsored scheme initiated in the beginning of 12th five year plan (2012-2017) and expected to continue till the end of the 13th five year plan (2018-2023) and target to improve the condition of the state funded universities and their affiliated colleges as it is felt by the government that improvement in the quality of the state universities will definitely improve the access, equity and quality of higher education. The scheme is innovative of its kind as it talks about the performance based funding to the state institutions. It also provides incentives to those state institutions who can upgrade themselves from non-performing to high performing institutions. RUSA also aim to provide greater autonomy to universities as well as colleges and have a sharper focus on equity-based development, and improvement in teaching-learning quality and research.

Present Status of Higher Education in India-

The higher education is offered by the central universities, deemed universities, state universities and its affiliated colleges along with large number of private

technical and professional institutions including universities created through act of state legislature. The Table No.1 given below shows the table of different category of institutions and their numbers along with the percentage of share in the total number of institutions.

Table No.1 Types of Higher Education Institutions and their Numbers

S.No	Type of Higher Education Institutions	Number of Institutions	Percentage
1	Central Universities	45	6.08%
2	State Universities	318	43.03%
3	Deemed Universities	129	17.45%
4	Private Universities	185	25.03%
5	Institutions of National Importance & other University level Institutions	55	7.44%
6	Total	739	100%

Source: MHRD Website, 16th June 2015

Out of the five types of higher educational institutions, the centrally funded institutions comprises of almost 6% which is a miniscule in percentage and caters only to a small percentage of the population of the students going for higher education. The major share of the higher educational institutions is of state universities and its affiliated colleges where the bulk of the population receives higher education. These state universities and its affiliated colleges are offering substandard quality of education to their students. It has been often been cited in the national reports that state universities are suffering from crippling and delayed academic sessions, poor infrastructure, shortage of faculty, poor and un-updated curriculum, lack of research and development activities and all these has been attributed to the severe fund crisis in the state funded institutions. The problem is further worsened when we talk of its affiliated colleges. One of the major problems of the affiliating colleges are that though they are affiliated by the state universities and it's the apex body as far as all their academic activities

but when it comes to funding related to the developmental and maintenance grants it is being controlled by the Department of Higher Education of the State and still worse their recruiting agency is the State Public Service Commission. Thus, control over colleges is done by the multi agencies of the state which makes the situations further worsen. This affect can be seen in the quality of products being produced from affiliated colleges. One major drawback of the state universities is that they are affiliating-cum-teaching universities. The work of affiliation and administrative over weighs the teaching in the universities. The university resources and systems are diverted towards management and conduct of exams with consequent dilution of focus on academic quality and research. If we look at the table we will find that some of the universities have large number of affiliated colleges are:

Table No.2 Number of Affiliated Colleges associated with State Universities

S.No	Universities	Number of Affiliated Institutions
1	Osmania University, Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh	901
2	Pune University, Pune, Maharashtra	811
3	Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj, Nagpur, Maharashtra	800
4	Rajasthan University, Jaipur, Rajasthan	735
5	Bangalore University, Karnataka	687
6	Mumbai University, Mumbai, Maharashtra	711
7	Tamil Nadu Teachers' Education University, Tamil Nadu	661
8	Gautam Buddha Technical University, Uttar Pradesh	614
9	Andhra University, Andhra Pradesh	614
10	Rajeev Gandhi Health Sciences University, Karnataka	560
11	M.L.C National Journalism & Communications, Madhya Pradesh	549
12	Kakatiya University, Andhra Pradesh	480
13	Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Andhra Pradesh	451

14	Maharishi Dayanand University, Haryana	448
15	Kurukshetra University, Haryana	435
16	Sant Gadge Baba University, Maharashtra	401
17	Dr. NTR Health Sciences University, Andhra Pradesh	400

Source: RUSA Document, 2013

Another concern related to state universities and its affiliated colleges enroll 89.3% of the undergraduate students, about 72.2% postgraduates and 20.6%⁸⁸ of doctoral students. This large force of human resources neither get any kind of substantial input in terms of quality of teaching, educational resources and infrastructural facilities nor they are polished enough to get good jobs or trained in entrepreneurship result in sheer wastage of human resources. For universities this large force of human resource serves merely as income generation for the affiliating universities therefore; it is of paramount importance that the financial position of the state universities should improve either by state funding or by other means rather than through affiliation. There is hardly any incentive for the affiliated colleges to undertake any meaningful quality improvement programme in teaching and research. Therefore, it is mandatory the overhauling of the state universities and its affiliated colleges needs to be done. Though, the State Universities are provided funds from through the University Grants Commission. However, UGC's mandate allows it to fund only a limited number of institutions that are under Section 12B and 2(f) (UGC Act) compliant. As of March 2012, about 33% of the universities are not covered under it and also almost 83% of government colleges are covered under 12(B). Since UGC directly funds the state universities sometimes it is impossible to keep a tab on the needs of the state universities. Moreover, state also complains that they are unaware of the funds being available to the state universities. It is imperative that a comprehensive program needs to be designed and implemented jointly by central and state governments for promoting strategic planning and recognizing performance at the university level. Such a program should address gaps at all

levels, spatial, academic and infrastructural. It must take into account the quality gaps, institutions-industry linkages, skill provision and curricular up-gradation. It is, therefore, imperative for each state to prepare a comprehensive State Higher Education Perspective Plan, which will effectively assess the needs and requirements of state institutions for a better, equitable and balanced allocation of resources (RUSA, 2013).

RUSA-Implications for State Universities/Colleges-

RUSA scheme has some major benefits especially in the given areas. They are as follows:

❖ **Administrative Reforms (Governance):** The biggest bottleneck or hurdle in improving the efficiency of state universities and its affiliated colleges is the beaucratic model under which these institutions are running. Though universities are autonomous in nature, yet it has been found out that there is too much intervention from the higher education department of the state. In one of the recent case one State University advertised faculty post for opening new departments, candidates were shortlisted and selected through proper selection committee but unfortunately it was being cancelled as university has not taken permission from the state education departments. Moreover, RUSA has cited that in the XI plan UGC has kept Rupees 22891 crores for development of university but only Rupees 7652 crores universities are able to spend (RUSA, 2013). This indicate that in spite of having large amount of funds at the disposal of UGC, due to deep rooted beaucratization in the higher education, many times universities has to depend upon the state mechanism which slow down or delayed the process of decision making or sometimes anarchic decision were made which effect the running of the university system. RUSA has categorically asked the state governments to set up State Higher Education Councils as Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) and en-route for all the proposal of funding through it as it will reduce the unnecessary hurdles and help the university and the colleges to access

the funds more easily. RUSA, thus talks about the administrative reforms or good governance so that optimal and timely utilization of funds takes place.

❖ **Better Infrastructural Facilities:** State universities and colleges accounts for around 94% of student's enrollment. If we want to create knowledge based society, it is imperative that state universities and colleges are potential catchment area where large mass of students in state sector cannot remain cut off from good quality education and hence this trend need to be reversed and we have to take state universities and colleges under the fold of reform. As, majority of the state universities are reeling under financial crunch therefore, it is necessary state universities starved off funds should be provided funds so that basic infrastructural facilities of the universities and colleges should improved. The better infrastructural facilities always create good support services systems which act as a catalyst to attract best of the talents (teachers and students) in the universities like well stocked and better library facilities, modern equipped laboratories, technology integrated classrooms and many more. Since, RUSA is the demand driven approach of funding wherein State universities and colleges in consonance with state departments of higher education or State higher Education councils should asked for funds especially to improve the existing infrastructural facilities of universities/colleges or create new colleges or university as huge amount of money is required for development of infrastructural facilities. Majority of the private colleges and state universities opened by the private entrepreneurs are investing huge amount of money on building infrastructural facilities as it holds the key in the entire system of education.

❖ **Examination Reform:** Another key area which RUSA has pointed out that examination system in the state universities and colleges. At present in most of the state universities and colleges especially at undergraduate level and to some extent at post- graduate level annual examination system is operational wherein

UGC has time again focuses on semester pattern of examination system. Moreover, UGC has emphasized on internal evaluation and external evaluation wherein tools of evaluation for internal and external evaluation could range from individual to group; oral to task based; non-skilled to skill based; scholastic to non-scholastic domain etc. so that students could be evaluated on each and every parameters which could make him more skillful and employable. Internal and external evaluation should be integrated and continual. Assessment through marks should be discouraged and more scientific and acceptable grades should be assigned. It is pertinent to mention here that in most of the universities mechanism of running the examination system runs on old pattern right from organizing, conducting, evaluating and declaring the results. Technology has made great advancements and has almost permeated every field of education. Many of the state universities have used these technologies to revamp the system of examination like University of Pune, SNDT University, Mumbai University, GGSIP University, IGNOU, Delhi University, Jamia Millia Islamia etc. It is necessary that the best practices from these universities could be utilized to reform the examination system.

❖ **Academic Reforms:** It is the most concerned area of reforms as documented in RUSA. RUSA has pointed out that “academic reforms are key towards imparting better quality education that is oriented towards employability and innovation”. It means such changes need to be introduced which would make system more flexible and students friendly. Some of the changes recommended by RUSA are switching over to semester pattern which includes curricular reform, deciding contact hours of program, credit earned, time distribution for classroom, field work, laboratory, tutorial, workshop etc., Choice Based Credit System (CBCS), Admission procedure, Curricular Reform. Another major academic reform on high agenda of RUSA is implementation of Choice Based Credit System (CBCS). According to RUSA document(2013):

“CBCS it will create enhanced learning opportunities, match students’ scholastic needs and aspirations, inter-institution transferability, part completion of an academic program in the institution of enrolment and part completion in a specialized institution, improvement in educational quality and excellence, flexibility for working students to complete the programme over extended time period, standardization and comparability of educational programmes across the country etc”.

Admission procedure is another crucial area of academic reform and rest on the pillar of access, inclusion, equity and quality. Admission to the courses and programs will be the first step to meet the pillars of access, inclusion, equity and quality and it will happen only if the admission process will be transparent and objective. To ensure all the four pillars of higher education state universities should widely publicize both in print as well as through various electronic media not the courses/programs they are offering but also the number of seats allocated to each course along with distribution of seats in terms of reservations to differently disadvantaged sections. It is important to mention here that as far as possible technological help should be put to use not in entire admission process right from online filling of forms to online examinations and declaration of final results to online admission so to reduce wastage of various resources and better time management. It is here to note that India is a country where majority of the students come from rural areas where the facility of technology might not be available round the corner nor they are digitally literate therefore, offline mode should be opened for those sections of children so meet the goal of access, equity, inclusion and quality. Merit should be given top priority in giving admission and ethics of professionalism should be key for every person involved in the admission process. Students belonging to the disadvantaged sections of society should be made aware about the various scholarships programme or incentives on being offer from the state and central funds so it will help them to

pursue their courses easily. It is necessary that faculty should play a proactive role to decide only needy students should get scholarships rather than those who belong to the disadvantaged but affluent sections of the society.

Curricular reform is another major area where RUSA has proactively indicated that curricular revision should be an ongoing academic activity which “*endows academic programme with quality but also adds to its contemporariness and relevance*”. It means curricular revision can be carried out in terms of current knowledge, national and international developments, relevance of new ideas, concepts and knowledge in the concerned discipline. Often it has been found out that state universities do not periodically revise their curricula and even if they do, they do it in a manner which is more cosmic in nature i.e. “old wine in new bottle”. Therefore, they teach those ideas, concepts or knowledge which has lost its market relevance. It is necessary that curricular modification should help the students to equip them with certain skills or some skill based courses should be attached with their main courses which help them to be employable or make them entrepreneur.

Affiliation Reforms: In India, most of the state universities function as teaching-cum-affiliating university where bulk of the enrollment takes place. This structure has burdened many universities with the management of academic content, examination, and quality of these colleges. In addition, while better colleges feel stifled by the university bureaucracy – delays, controls, and inadequate support – the better universities are affected by the limited thinking of the college leadership and their negative role in university processes. It is obvious that the better institutions are suffering and creativity is a casualty (Yashpal Committee, 2009). In recent RUSA report it has documented there are almost 17 state universities (Table No.2) which has more than 400 affiliated colleges. These affiliating colleges are rich source of revenue for state universities as a result they do not want easily to forego this huge sum of money.

These universities neither have any quality control cell to check the quality of academic standards, infrastructural facilities, facilities provided to the students or teachers. Grant which are provided from the state education department or from UGC under 12(B) are hardly been audited. Strictly speaking University has no control over these affiliated colleges. Matter become further worsen in case of private colleges who once affiliated to the state universities (through any means) charges fees from the students in an unregulated manner, pays minimum salary (mostly in the form of wages), no facilities to students and teachers, and sometimes to the extent that no classroom transaction in a whole year and students appear in the final examinations. Since state universities are already reeling under starvation of human resources (faculty) therefore, they act as more of an administrative burden to the universities. RUSA has proposed for affiliation reforms to the state universities:

- Limit the number of affiliated colleges to 100 so that university could monitor the quality of education being offered by the colleges along with serving as a mentor to expand horizontally and vertically. Moreover, increase the number of affiliating universities.
- Sometimes geographical distance between the affiliating colleges and the university is large in such case convert the disciplined wise colleges of proximate areas into a university with enhanced capacity and resources.
- Convert the old colleges into autonomous and autonomous into universities.
- State universities should focus on converting the affiliated colleges into constituent colleges which will be under direct control of university.
- While giving affiliation to any new college it is necessary to go for proper mapping and need assessment. Encourage to open colleges at district and rural level rather than at urban centre.

- The act and statues of university must be amended suitably to accommodate the four pillars of higher education-access, inclusion, equity and quality. The University should frame a Model of Affiliation based on the four aspects of higher education as envisioned in RUSA.
- While giving affiliation to private institutions, it is imperative that state universities should made stringent rules and any college violating the norms laid down in the affiliation policy would be taken seriously. It means state universities should be proactive whether colleges are functioning as per the standard or norms.
- Establish new centre, open new programmes and open self financing courses in the university departments within the university campus to enhance the capacity of the university. If possible start double shift in the existing colleges/universities as it will also help in enhancing the capacity which would increase the GER and also provide students of economically weaker sections to go for “earning while learning” simultaneously.

❖ **Accreditation of Universities and Quality Education:** The RUSA entire funding to the University/College is basically based on one of the criteria i.e. it should be accredited by NAAC or NBA or any other agencies. It means that universities and colleges go for mandatory accreditation. Unfortunately, in India accreditation is not very popular. As of June 2015, only (%) one-third of all universities and only (%) colleges have been accredited so far. Private universities and colleges are reluctant to go for accreditation. This means that there is effectively no standard national level monitoring in terms of quality for most of the educational institutions. But, the accreditation of the institute synonymously means institute is offering quality education. Accreditation is seen as necessity in order to attract good students. It provides a common frame of reference for students and others to obtain credible information on academic quality across the institutions thereby assisting student mobility across

institutions, domestic as well as international. Accreditation of the universities and colleges would enable global quality assurance system. RUSA ensures that higher education institutions would go for accreditation which would enable the universities and colleges to attract more funds from central and state agencies. It means acquiring better facilities and resources for students and teachers, thus involving overall improvement in the existing status. Thus, the presence of one or many independent quality assurance mechanism is a sine qua non for quality and excellence. (RUSA, 2013). It has been further pointed out in document *any new scheme planned by the government must ensure that accreditation becomes mandatory and sufficient incentives and disincentives are built into the system to ensure that every higher education institutions obtain accreditation (RUSA, 2013).*

❖ Enhancing Research and Development & Academic-Industry Interface:

India lags way behind in term of research and development. Many of the small countries are listed in QS ranking because of reasons: (i) majority of the teachers in the universities are involved in quality research and thus contributing to the knowledge (ii) producing large number of good quality research (iii) large collaborative researches among faculty members (iv) High private investment in University R&D work (v) Presence of Research Institutions/ Universities. As far as international standards we have inadequate funding for researches as well as we are well below the global standard. The reason is obvious the structural organization of our universities/colleges do not promote research. In India majority of the state universities research is confined only to awarding of degrees (which is also low in comparison to BRICS and other European nations). In colleges faculty gets hardly any opportunity to do research as facilities are unavailable there. In short, one can say the culture of research is missing from the state universities/colleges. That's why to promote research even in promotion (under CAS), research has been accorded the highest priority. It is not that UGC

and other sponsoring bodies' institutions are starved of funds, but it has been often reported that universities/colleges are unable to utilize the funds available under the head of projects (researches). In India except for the handful institutions especially central institutions where majority of the researches are being carried out, rest presents a very gloomy picture. Even the picture from the Industry is not very encouraging. Industry-academia interface is the weakest link especially related to state university and colleges. State universities/colleges seldom forge into the partnership where industry driven researches could be carried out in universities and entire research is being funded by the industry. Moreover, the researches carried out are of little significance to the industry. Therefore, to encourage research in universities/colleges idea of creating a research university is floated through RUSA wherein those universities/institutions who are doing exemplary work in research and have been acknowledged globally, have memorandum of understanding with industries, large number of students engage in research with senior academia should be upgraded to research university. RUSA would encourage of creating research university by providing infrastructure, creating enabling governance structure which would help achieve academic excellence, attract high quality talent, forge linkages with industry, peer institutions, the academia and other stakeholders and facilitate resource mobilization for continued enhanced research activities.

❖ **Filling up the Strength of Faculty:** Another key implication of the RUSA for universities and colleges are filling up the vacant positions or creating faculty strength as well as faculty improvement in various disciplines. It is estimated that around 50% of the faculty strength in most of the state universities/colleges are lying vacant. In many state universities there is ban on faculty recruitment. In many state universities/colleges recruitment process has not held for almost for decades because of the procedural tangle which delays the decision making and

thus sometimes stalled the process of recruitment. In some universities even if the posts are advertised they are drag into the litigation process because of violation of laid regulatory norms. The process of recruiting faculty in the state universities or colleges is never apolitical. In many cases selection process is being influenced by political or beaucratic people. RUSA has pointed out that at most 15% of the sanctioned strength of the faculty should remain vacant in a university/college otherwise the grant of RUSA will be stopped. It means that RUSA is in favour of appointing competent faculty as teacher is the backbone of any educational institution. So, state universities/colleges must use this opportunity to fill their backlog vacancies as RUSA will support the states in this aspect too.

❖ **Diversification of Courses/Programmes:** In the present era of globalization what is required is the skilled manpower. India has the largest workforce of especially in the age group of 18-35 which can pay rich dividends in terms of productivity. What is required is to prepare them to reap the benefit. Present government has specially created a department named as National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) wherein target is to train 500 million young generation students. The universities/ colleges can play a bigger role here. They can offer courses (diploma, certificate or degree) so that they can generate a skilled force. For offering such programmes, RUSA will provide special grants to universities/colleges. Even within the existing curriculum, universities can offer such courses under CBCS and thus get grants from the RUSA.

❖ **Autonomy of the Universities (Institutional Governance):** Normally, the state universities are under severe clutches of the state governments and its functionaries. Interference, from various political or commercial vested interests, in the functioning and priorities of the universities comes in many different forms and intensities. It touches all aspects of higher education and involves improper admission of students, pressures in selection of teachers, manipulation

in appointment of senior functionaries like registrars and deans, purchase of equipment and allotment of construction contracts and so on. Even the vice-chancellors, the academic and administrative head of the university appointment was seldom apolitical. The executive council and academic council members are appointed more on political grounds. In such a case, universities functioning (governance) and its decision are taken more on political grounds rather than on academic grounds. The governance structures are archaic and have not changed with changing environment to meet the expectations of its various stakeholders. To run a university smoothly it is necessary that universities should be given enough freedom as *“only an autonomous institution, free from regimentation of ideas and pressure of party or power politics, can pursue truth fearlessly and build up in its teachers and students, habits of independent thinking and a spirit of enquiry unfettered by the limitations and prejudices of the near and the immediate which is so essential for the development of a free society (Kothari Commission, 1964-66).*

While recognizing the importance of autonomy, Kothari Commission (1964-66) states that, “the autonomy of universities is eroded by interventions from government and intrusions from political processes.” It further adds that, “experience suggests that implicit politicization has made governance of universities exceedingly difficult and much more susceptible to entirely nonacademic interventions from outside. This problem needs to be recognized and addressed in a systematic manner within universities but also outside, particularly in governments, legislatures and political parties”. Thus, autonomy is the essence as Yashpal Committee (2009) recognized autonomy as:

“Autonomy is arguably the lifeline of any institution that deals with education, creation of knowledge and learning of all kinds..... Hard rules that were framed for a past era still dominate rather than soft-processes and collegial consensus making. All of these have led to centralization of

decision-making and low involvement of faculty and students in most policy decisions affecting academics. These may have been the direct outcomes of low autonomy as well as low management skills amongst administrators at these institutions”.

RUSA has emphasized for three the kinds of autonomy: academic, financial and administrative. Though, majority of the universities enjoy academic freedom as far as possible but it is the other two where state universities faces the most constraint. RUSA has called for giving financial autonomy to the state universities wherein universities can maintain their own budgets; generate their own source of funds. In areas of administrative autonomy universities should be given full freedom to take their own decisions related to recruitment of human resources (both teaching and non-teaching).

Conclusion-

The national mission of higher education rests on four pillars i.e. equity, access, inclusion and excellence and can be achieved only if there is shift in state's focus on higher education and its importance in creating knowledge society. It is necessary that state a major player in RUSA should direct universities/colleges to prepare their own plan. The state should act as a facilitator organ rather than act as obstruction for the promotion of higher education. State should direct each universities and colleges to prepare their own plan of expansion and improvement. Universities too taking the privilege of autonomy should plan at micro level i.e. each department in the state universities should be the unit of planning (infrastructure, human resources (academic and non-academic), technological requirements, increasing the capacities, vocationalization of education and fixing the priorities within the university. College as whole acts as a unit and prepares plans for its reform and rejuvenation. It is important to mention that those units need immediate attention should be given high priority. Planning should be realistic and achievable as unrealistic targets would do more

damage to the universities as prerequisite is the norm and performance based funding. Thus RUSA is an opportunity for state universities to improve their infrastructure and other aspects and thus provide quality education otherwise they will be cornered by the private universities or colleges.

References-

- MHRD(2009) Renovation and Rejuvenation of Higher Education, New Delhi accessed on www.mhrd.ac.in 25th July 2015
- MHRD(2011) Measures to Regulate the Standard of Education Imparted through Distance Mode, New Delhi www.mhrd.ac.in accessed on 26th July 2015
- MHRD(2013) Policy Document of Rashtriya Uchhatar Shiksha Abhiyan New Delhi accessed www.mhrd.ac.in on 24th July 2015
- Ministry of Education (1964-66) National Commission on Higher Education www.nuepa.org accessed on 26th July 2015
- UGC(2012) Annual Report on Higher Education, New Delhi accessed on www.ugc.ac.in on 24th July 2015

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Paper-12

**Problems of Education in India: Theory or
Practical**

Dr. Ritu Bala

Problems of Education in India: Theory or Practical

Dr. Ritu Bala¹⁸

Abstract

“Produce Educated Human Beings not the Literate Persons!”

Since ancient times, it is said “Sa Vidya Ya Vimuktaye” which means with education, we finally attain salvation. It strongly advocates overcoming evils through the mean of education. We are spending millions and billions to educate our children to make India a developed nation. But to what use? We are producing literate machines with no humanity, no feelings and no emotions. We are producing just literate persons but not educated human beings. In this paper, I would like to through light on some very important issues, need to be addressed at the earliest, through the channel of review of movies presented by our Bollywood.

Keywords: Education, Literacy, Humanity, Movies

Introduction-

I use to do a lot of research work to make and standardize tests, to explore the problems of education and search their probable solutions. And to do this, the steps of the scientific research from the identification of the problem to the conclusions and suggestions for research are always followed. When I was writing a paper based on empirical studies on this issue of problem of education in India, I have started following the same steps. But after doing a lot of research work – analyzing constituents, issues, reviews, policies and frameworks, I started to write the report of the research. But I was not satisfied with my work. Therefore I discussed the topic with one of my senior colleagues and after getting her suggestions I revised my research criterion and again

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started writing the paper. However I prepared an article for this endeavor. Suddenly something very crucial in my life as a teacher educator has happened. And I again read my previous two papers written after a lot of research work and to my shock not a single word I found to be the new contribution to this world. So I kept it aside and to let my mind relax I decided to watch a randomly selected movie. And after watching the movie, I feel enlightened to write this article.

In my earlier version for this topic, I have empirically studied the problem of education e.g. problems related to teachers, students, teaching-learning environment, educational objectives, teaching-learning process, evaluation and problems at elementary, secondary and tertiary levels etc. But after watching the movie I was directed to think over this issue in a practical manner.

I was surprised to see how the film industry, once considered to inferior to all other industry especially education, being apart not only is trying hard to present to us the present scenario of education and necessity to take serious steps but also to motivate us to be human and know the real meaning of education.

We are spending millions and billions to educate our children to make India a developed nation. But to what use? We are producing literate machines with no humanity, no feelings and no emotions. We are producing just literate persons but not educated human beings.

Education – a philosophy, a process of life to become an enriched and productive human being has today become just a process to get degrees and jobs. We are lacking the utmost required virtue of humanity. We have made man for education. The collected facts from scriptures, thoughts of philosophers, educationists conclude that “Education is for Human beings, Human beings are not for Education.”

Since ancient times, it is said “Sa Vidya Ya Vimuktaye” which means with education, we finally attain salvation. It strongly advocates overcoming evils through the mean of education.

In this paper, I would like to through light on some very important issues, need to be addressed at the earliest, through the channel of review of movies – 3 Idiots and Hawa- Hawai presented by our Bollywood.

In the movie 3 Idiots, it is clearly shown that our education system has worthless practical value. A person with a strong desire to learn will not only learn but can also gain name and fame without degrees. People will criticize this fact by saying that it’s all imagination. But we can see many people who have excelled in their fields without having bundles of degrees. The movie has enlightened the following four facts of education system:

1. **One should learn what one wants to learn:** We usually discuss about attitude and aptitude of a person. But to what use? In India we are scoring degrees to get jobs without having any attitude or aptitude for that profession. Our target is not learning according to our attitude but our target is to get degrees to earn livelihood. No doubt, to earn livelihood id the first duty to satisfy the basic needs of self and family. If we do what we want to do and for which we have interest, attitude and aptitude, then the quality of the output will match no boundaries of success. After implementing so many policies in this direction, what we getting – just a points increase/ decrease in the figures. We need to think over this. It will not only stop brain –drain but will also bring to true prosperity to the nation. Education system is based on experiments. Let us start an experiment and let our children – the future of the nation learn what they want to learn, for what they have the interest, aptitude and attitude and see the output.

2. **Knowledge:** There is no doubt that books, scriptures and internet in this modern era of science and technology are a great source of knowledge. Now the question arises is, “Is to cram some facts, principles and to master their application is knowledge?” This movie has very effectively thrown light on this issue. The scenes of classroom clearly elaborate this phenomenon and its adverse effects.
3. **Confidence:** Education system aims at producing confident citizens. But the figures of rate of suicides by the students, declining stamina, higher levels of stress, emotional outbursts say another story. We have to check this situation before it’s too late.
4. **Learning Experiences:** Learning experiences should be given in line with the life experiences to complement them. Ask a post graduate in Mathematics a very simple question, “ If you have bought a packet of 20 items for 20 rupees and another similar packet for 30 rupees, then how much more you have to pay for each item?” I hope to get the answer at least. Now note the time taken by the candidate to solve the problem. Now ask the same question to an illiterate vendor, and his/her speed of answer will surely surprise you. S/he will answer before you fully complete the question.What does it show? The skill and competencies developed by our education system is much less than the skills and competencies developed by illiterate person to another illiterate person. Second movie ‘Hawa-Hawai’ is also a great effort to highlight the following three issues:
5. **Educate those who are Capable:** The movie has clearly shown how a small boy who is working in a garage make skates for his friend. It clearly indicates the talent for which India is called ‘ Sone ki Chidya’- The Golden Bird. The reality shows on T.V. also support this fact. We need to recognize such talent and nourish it with love and care.

6. **A Learner has no Limits:** A learner who is derived to learn knows no boundaries of buildings, and money. The main lead in the movie learns skating even of all the odds. The education system lacks this “derive/will to learn”. Students do not learn for learning. They learn to get certificates.
7. **Access to Education:** These are millions of children who cannot afford to go to school. Though we have made provisions in the form of no-formal education, yet these are nothing more than a few drops for drought dead field. We need to walk long miles, see the actual figures and analyze what is the realistic picture.

These are not only facts that have been highlighted in Bollywood movies. Many attempts have been made to give humanistic direction to education.

The problems of education in India have a very broad view. We cannot conclude them in few words in a single article. We have to do a reality check on ground level, not only in the form of data and its interpretation but in the form of human beings and their humanity.

We have machines and technology to exploit, so let us exploit these not the human beings and humanity. There is an essential and great need to regenerate the virtue of humanity- the unique virtue of Humans over animals. Education has to be for humans and not human beings for education.

“Produce Educated Human Beings not the Literate Persons!”

References-

- Aggarwal, Ritu Bala (2014). *Mathematics from Daily Life*, Education India Journal, 3(2), May 2014.
- Bhave, Vinoba (1985). *The Steadfast Wisdom*, Sarva Seva Sangh Prakashan, Varanasi.
- Fernandez, Angelo (1981). *Towards Peace with Justice*, Indian Social Institute, New Delhi.
- Gupte, Amole (2014). *Hawa Hawaii*, Bollywood, India.

- Hirani, Rajkumar (2009). 3 Idiots, Bollywood, India.
- Kumar, Ravinder (2012). *Education, Peace and Development*, Kalpaz Publication, New Delhi.
- Kumar, Ravinder (2013). *Facts of Education in Global Perspectives*, The Institute of Indology and Oriental Studies, Shridhar University, Pilani.

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Paper-13

**Primary Education System in
Lakshadweep**

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Primary Education System in Lakshadweep

Dr.Baiju K.Nath¹⁹

Farsana A.K.²⁰

Introduction-

Education in the islands in earlier periods was confined to the teaching of *Koran* and the elements of Islamic theology in religious schools attached to mosques. In these schools called *Madrasas*, the Malayalam Language was also taught in Arabic scripts. Only few could read and write and neither their isolated position nor any of their avocations made much call for education. On the whole they were apathetic towards education and they were contented with what little they could learn from the schools attached to the mosques.

In the earlier years of British administration, the people were considered to be too backward to realize the value of modern education and no serious attempts were made to start schools in the islands till the latter half of the 19th century. The question of providing education to the people of Amindivi islands, which came under the British Government as early as 1799, was taken up only in 1871. But the people were not willing to show interest for the education to be provided by government and it was that the time had not come for forcing education on the islanders.

At the time of independence, there were only 9 primary schools in the territory, one in each inhabited islands except Bitra. In the Amindivi group a lower elementary school has been in existence in each of the islands.

General Education now includes education from the Nursery to the University stage. As stated elsewhere, there has been an enormous expansion of education after 1956. The number of institution increased from 9 primary schools in 1956

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to 15 primary schools and one high school by the end of the Second Five Year Plan, while the number of students on roll rose from 1500 in 1956 to 3700 by the end of the Second Plan. The number of schools and students further increased to 35 (including three high schools) and 5328 respectively by the end of the Third Five Year Plan. Similarly the number of teachers increased from 28 in 1956 to 268 by the end of the Third Five Year Plan. By 2009, there are 56 different educational institution under Lkashadweep Administration. In addition to this there are no Navodaya Vidyalaya at Minicoy and one Kendriya Vidyalaya at Kavaratti. Similarly the total number of teachers has risen to 968. The statement below gives the figures of enrolment for each type of institutions.

Primary Education-

Primary education is the first stage of compulsory education. It is preceded by pre-school or nursery education and is followed by secondary education. In North America this stage of education is usually known as **elementary education** and is generally followed by middle school.

In most countries, it is compulsory for children to receive primary education, though in many jurisdictions it is permissible for parents to provide it. The transition to secondary school or high school is somewhat arbitrary, but it generally occurs at about eleven or twelve years of age. Some educational systems have separate middle schools with the transition to the final stage of education taking place at around the age of fourteen.

The major goals of primary education are achieving basic literacy and numeracy amongst all pupils, as well as establishing foundations in science, mathematics, geography, history and other social sciences. The relative priority of various areas, and the methods used to teach them, are an area of considerable political debate.

Typically, primary education is provided in schools, where the child will stay in steadily advancing classes until they complete it and move on to high

school/secondary school. Children are usually placed in classes with one teacher who will be primarily responsible for their education and welfare for that year. This teacher may be assisted to varying degrees by specialist teachers in certain subject areas, often music or physical education. The continuity with a single teacher and the opportunity to build up a close relationship with the class is a notable feature of the primary education system.

Madrasas-

Lakshadweep has come a long way from the days when education in the union territory was limited to the sacred instructions of the Koran. The various lessons of Islamic theology were imparted in the islands mosques or madrasas.

Anganwadi Centres in Lakshadweep-

In the Integrated Child Development Scheme there are 67 Anganwadies working to improve the nutritional status of the vulnerable group with implementation of non-formal education for pre-school children.

Sl. No.	Island	J.B. Schools
1	Agatti	12
2	Amini	13
3	Andrott	20
4	Bitra	1
5	Chetlat	4
6	Kadmat	10
7	Kalpeni	9
8	Kavaratti	16
9	Kiltan	8
10	Minicoy	14
Total		107

Nursery Schools-

The Nursery Schools which are intended for children in the age-group three to five is of recent growth in the territory. The emphasis in nursery education is

one hygiene and health habits, besides teaching the child informal school practices. There are seven Nursery Schools including a Balavady at Chetlat. The first among them was established at Kavaratti in 1964, and the other schools were started in quick succession at Kalpeni, Androth, Agatti, Amini and Minicoy in 1965. The Balvady at Chetlat was started in 1970-71. Specially trained teachers are appointed at these schools. The curriculum of studies include action songs, stories, drawing, games etc. The hours of instruction extend from 10.30 to 12.30 in the morning and from and from 3 to 4 in the afternoon. There were 259 boys and 262 girls in these seven Nursery Schools during 1973-74.

Junior and Senior Basic Stage-

Junior Basic Schools impart education from Class I to Class IV. Admission to Class I is open to children who have completed 5 years. At the time of reorganization in 1956, all the island schools had only classes up to the Primary There are many theories on the formation of the islands but the most attributed one is to Sir Charles Darwin, the renound evolutionist. He opined that the base of islands below the reef is a volcanic layer over which corals settled and turned into atolls over a period of time. The atolls consisting of the islands and lagoons are virtually filled with sediments. The larger ones are deeper in range of 10-16 meters. The enchanting aspect of these islands is de to the coral reef, biologically formed over many centuries. As of now extends along the cost, giving Lakshadweep its unique stature.

Institution and Enrolment in 2009-10-

Institutions	No. of Institutions	No. of Students		
		Boys	Girls	Total
Nursery Schools	10	397	345	742
Primary Schools	20	3387	3404	6791

The class wise student population from I Std to VI for the year 2010-11 as follows:

Class	Boys	Girls	Total
I	583	537	1120
II	614	600	1214
III	664	671	1278
IV	671	676	1347
V	861	985	1846
VI	612	665	1277
Total	4005	4134	8082

Distribution of Elementary Classes in various Schools of Lakshadweep island wise as follows.

Sl. No.	Island	J.B. Schools	S.B. Schools
1	Agatti	3	1
2	Amini	4	1
3	Andrott	4	2
4	Bitra	0	1
5	Chetlat	1	0
6	Kadmat	3	1
7	Kalpeni	1	1
8	Kavaratti	2	1
9	Kiltan	1	1
10	Minicoy	2	1
Total		21	10

Only women with Secondary School Leaving Certificate and Nursery Teachers' training are appointed as teachers in Nursery Schools. For Primary School Teachers for teaching in Junior Basic Schools, essential qualifications are Senior Secondary School Level Certificate with two years teacher training certificate with not less than 40% marks in both.

Preparation/Adoption of Textbooks-

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Kerala pattern of education is followed in Lakshadweep from the very beginning of formal education. The Lakshadweep Administration has prepared textbooks for standard I to IV under Primary Education Curriculum Renewal Scheme.

Admission and Withdrawal of Students-

1. Headmasters are authorized to admit pupils to various classes and issue transfer certificates for admission to mainland schools.
2. 3 ½ years is the minimum age for admission to Nursery Schools.
3. 5 ½ years is the minimum age for admission to 1st standard.
4. Inter State Transfer Certificates are countersigned by concerned Education Officers/Director of Education.

Midday Meals Scheme-

The Mid-Day meals scheme is being implemented in all Lakshadweep Schools. The benefit of Midday meal Scheme is extended for all the children in Primary Schools up to VII Standard. The Lakshadweep Administration provides cooked meals in all the schools with a minimum content of 300 calories & 8-12 grams protein to each student each day of school for minimum of 220 days.

Xith Five Year Plan 2007-12-

Tremendous progress has been witness in the field of education after Lakshadweep became a Union Territory in the year 1956. during the decade of 50's only 300 pupils attended schools and whereas the student population in Lakshadweep risen to seventeen thousand now with a setup of 53 Educational Institutions ranging from Nursery to Degree level functioning in Lakshadweep. At present in Lakshwadweep 10 Nursery schools, 21 Junior Basic Schools, 4 Senior Basic Schools.

Proposed Outlay At A Glance (Rs. in Lakhs)-

Sl. No.	Name of the Scheme	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	Total

1	Early Child Hood Care and Education	58.00	60.00	66.26	68.85	75.85	328.96
2	Primary Education	350.10	364.65	379.80	395.90	417.60	1908.35
Total		2407.1	2423.65	2445.06	2463.75	2492.45	2237.31

Early Childhood Care and Education-

The scheme aims at moulding a child both physically and mentally to take up Primary Education. Lakshadweep being a very remote area, the children of these islands deserve very much care and attention in all respects. In the Nursery schools of Lakshadweep emphasis has been laid on games songs, stories, good health, good habits etc only till date. Now, as a part of improving the quality of Education the department plans to introduce LKG and UKG classes in Nursery schools from XIth Five year plan period onwards. The programme of childhood care and Education is of two years duration. Children who have completed three years of age will be admitted to these classes.

At present only one Nursery school each exists in each of the inhabited islands except Minicoy where there are two Nursery Schools. This is very much insufficient to accommodate all the pre-school going children of the Islands. Besides, the children of 3 years find it very difficult to walk even beyond 3 kms to reach a Nursery schools and such children are either enrolled in Madrasa Nurseries or not availing the facilities at all. Hence one each additional Nursery school for each island with supporting staff is proposed during XIth five year plan. Strengthening Pre-Primary Education is also a part of improving the quality of education as emphasized by the Planning Commission of India in the approach paper to XI five year plan.

Reference-

- Carnoy, M., Dossani, R., (2013), Goals and Governance of Higher Education in India: The International Journal

of Higher Education and Educational Planning, 65, 595-612. Erik Document Service Number (EJ1000490).

- Department of Information Publicity and Tourism.(2002). *Lakshadweep and Its People*.DC:Author
- Directorate of Planning and Statistics Administration of the Union Territory of Lakshadweep Kavaratti. (2007) *Basic Statistics 2007*. DC: Author
- Hamzakoya, (2006)*Education Policy of Lakshadweep*.
- Mannadiar.N.S. (Ed.) (1977).*Gazetteer of India: Lakshadweep*. Coimbatore: Govt.Press
- www.lakshadweep.nic.in
- www.studyguideindia.com
- www.entrance.exam.net
- www.lakshadweepeducation.net

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Paper-14

**Psychological predictors of academic
achievement in adolescent students of XI
grade.**

Honey Premendra

Psychological predictors of academic achievement in adolescent students of XI grade.

Honey Premendra²¹

Abstract

This study is an attempt to investigate the extent to which some of the essential psychological variables like Scientific Creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits contribute in the academic achievement at the senior secondary school level, adolescent students. The preliminary aim of the study is to identify the extent (if any) to which these prime psychological variables which are equally helpful in maintaining equilibrium with changing situations of life, along with their prime requirement to achieve high in academics, and which is found evenly in male and female students. Analysis of data achieved was done separately for male and female students and then collectively to have a much clearer and detailed understanding of the predictive relationship in between all these variables on gender basis. The descriptive research design is adopted for the investigation which includes Doolittle method of multiple regression to estimate predictive relationship in between dependent and independent variables described in the study. A sufficient large sample of 150 senior secondary students (75 male; 75 female) was drawn from Eastern, Central and Western zone of Uttar Pradesh using simple random sampling technique. A major hypothesis was raised to estimate collective relation (if any) in between variables of the study and also for overall students of XI grade. Only mean and Standard deviation (SD) were estimated for all these four variables with the help of SPSS software and then Doolittle method of multiple regression was implied by the researcher manually

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for male and female students separately and then collectively for overall students for XI grade.

A retrospective overview of data thus obtained on the basis of intercorrelation found in between these variables indicates a significant variable correlation in male students of XI grade, which also correlates positively for the female students of XI grade. Overall intercorrelational pattern in between the mentioned variable for overall XI grade students indicates a strong co-relationship (at the significance level of 0.01 level) for overall adolescent students of XI grade. A detailed values of all the values calculated for Doolittle method are mentioned in a tabular form which also indicates the extent and predictive capacity of independent variables in prediction of dependent variable.

Keywords: Academic achievement, Study habits, Intelligence, senior school students, adolescents etc.

Introduction-

Every article, process or phenomenon is evaluated on the appropriateness and desirability of the result which it produces after its implication. Not only its adapting desirability but also its appropriateness to fulfill some objective is assumed before it is actually practiced in a real life situation. Similarly the process of teaching-learning is also evaluated on the extent to which it facilitates or enhances the academic achievement of the childrens involved in the process. Not only the children's ability to learn and assimilate is evaluated on how they achieves in its academics, but whole teaching-learning process along with the capability and effectiveness of teacher is also evaluated by the academic achievement of the students. Along with the effective and appropriate teaching learning experience which is provides to students to achieve academically, there are number of factors which also effects academic achievement of students. One of the most important factor which effects not

only academic achievement of students but each and every aspect of children's life is their adolescence stage of life, where they start experiencing drastic changes physiologically, psychologically, socially, emotionally etc. Along with this, adolescent students also have to face severe stress to achieve good in academics along with their biological and psychological stress of their adolescence, which can be counter balanced by some specific psychological capabilities of which any student possess.

Some psychological capabilities not only help adolescent students to deal up with changing situation of life but also achieve good in their academics too. Some of the essential psychological variables which enables childrens to deal with adolescent problems along with achieving good in academics are their creativity, intelligence, personality, reasoning, understanding capabilities, intuitive thinking, their abilities to pursue any operations, their habits etc. Some of the essential variables which helps students to achieve good in academics and helps in maintaining equilibrium in their adolescence like Scientific creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits are considered as the variables of this study and as these variables are assumed to maintaining equilibrium and high achievement in their life, they are generally pre-assumed to be as significant variable to achieve success in their academic achievements too. *Crow and Crow* (1969) described academic achievement as the extent to which a learner is profited from instructions in a given area of learning i.e., achievement is reflected by the extent to which skill or knowledge is been imparted to the students.

Similarly scientific creativity is one of the most important factor which affects to each and every part of life directly or indirectly. Scientific Creativity can be defined as the process of becoming sensitive to problem, related to science; deficiencies, gaps, missing elements, disharmonies and so on in scientific knowledge, identifying the difficulty; searching for solutions, making guesses or formulating hypothesis about deficiencies, testing and retesting of these

hypothesis and possibly modifying and retesting them, and finally communicating the results, which indicates that it includes needed presence or absence of replicated studies, follow up investigation, conceptual and somatic agreement, adequacy of sample, precision of measuring tools, unanimity about problem of criteria and predictors and longitudinal studies, the construct of scientific reactivity is in a developing stage which needs to be refined through persistent efforts to create something novel and constructive in the regime of scientific field (Bennett et-al, 1968). Magnani (1999) discussed the role of inconsistency, which acts in the advancement of a scientific theory and the part that scientific creativity plays in generating and maintaining itself and thus it becomes necessary to predict the extent to which scientific creativity can contribute in the academic achievement of students along with developing a strong measure to deal with the changing situations of life.

Encyclopedia of Educational Psychology defines creativity as the interaction among aptitude, process and environment by which an individual or group is able to produce original (unique, novel, unusual) and adaptive (useful, appropriate, meaningful) interpretations, ideas, behavior, solution or product, which is effected by other psychological aspects of any individual. Another prominent variable which effects academic achievement along with scientific creativity and also ensures psychological well being of any individual is their *intelligence*, which is considered as the second independent variable of the study to be as predictor of students' academic achievement. Intelligence can be defined as the ability to learn, to understand and to think in a logical way about things, this capability is reflected in behavior. Intelligence are the abilities demanded in the solution of problem which requires the comprehension and use of symbol, i.e. words number, diagrams equations and formulae (Garrett, 1947). Intelligence refers to the whole class of cognitive behaviors which reflect an individual's capacity to solve problems with insight, to adapt himself to new

situations, to think abstractly and to profits from his experiences (*Robinson and Robinson,1965*). The last factor which is assumed to be the independent variable of the study is the habits which students adopts during their learning process. Habits as defined by *Introduction to Psychology* is, '*a learned or fixed way of behaving to satisfy a given motive*'. It indicates the predictable response which a person gives in a particular situation to achieve any desirable goal.

Thus a specific, defined and assumptive feedback of behaviors which is adopted by learners to fulfill or to satisfy their desired objectives in the field of study are termed as '*study habits*'. In simple words, Study habits are study routines which include, but not restrict the frequency of studying sessions, review of material, self-testing, rehearsal of learned material, and studying in a conducive environment. Students' attitudes toward the act of studying are referred to as 'study attitudes'.(*Crede and Kuncel, 2008*). Study habits are '*the adopted way and manner a student plans his private readings, after classroom learning so as to attain mastery of the subject.*'(*Azikiwe, 1998*).Thus the study comes out to be as a exploratory-predictive research to explore the extent to which psychological variables of Scientific creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits contributes in to the academic achievement of male and female adolescent students separately and collectively.

Objective of the study-

The present study was taken up with the following objective-

1. To find out the extent to which Scientific Creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits helps in to predict academic achievement of XI grade male students.
2. To find out the extent to which Scientific Creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits helps in to predict academic achievement of XI grade female students.

3. To find out the extent to which Scientific Creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits helps in to predict academic achievement of XI grade students collectively.

Hypotheses-

Following hypotheses were tested-

1. There is a significant contribution of Scientific Creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits in prediction of academic achievement of XI grade male students.
2. There is a significant contribution of Scientific Creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits in prediction of academic achievement of XI grade female students.
3. There is a significant contribution of Scientific Creativity, Intelligence and Study Habits in prediction of academic achievement of XI grade students.

Sample-

Researcher had decided to adopt *random purposive* data collection procedure from all the three regions of Uttar Pradesh viz. Eastern region, Central region and Western region comprising the students from the cities of Allahabad and Varanasi in Eastern region, Lucknow and Sitapur in Central region and, Bareilly and Sahjahanpur in Western region. 25 male students and 25 Female students were selected from UP board, hindi medium schools of these region, which collectively results in to 150 students (75 males and 75 females) for the study. The distribution of students taken as sample from different regions in the study can be summarized as follow:

Table-1.

Table showing distribution of students taken as sample from different regions in the study.

Region	Students from District	Males	Females	Total Students
Eastern Region	Allahabad, Varanasi.	25	25	50
Central Region.	Lucknow, Sitapur.	25	25	50
Western Region.	Bareilly, Sahjahanpur.	25	25	50
Total	3x2 districts	75	75	150

A total of 150 secondary school students with biology in their science stream were selected and data was collected from them. This sample being sufficiently large and drawn in random manner may be reasonably considered representative of the total population of male and female secondary schools students constituting Eastern, Central and Western region of Uttar Pradesh.

Tool used-

Following tools were used in the study to collect data of the selected variables in the study-

1. Standardized test of academic achievement developed by *researcher himself* comprising subjects of XI grade curriculum.
2. Test of Scientific Creativity developed by *K.S.Misra*.
3. Test of Intelligence developed by *R.K.Ojha and K.Ray Raychaudhary*.
4. Test of Study Habit developed by *M.Mukhopadhyay and D.N.Sansanwal*.

Data Analysis-

Data was analyzed by calculating Mean, Standard deviation and Regression coefficient by Doolittle method of multiple regression for students for Male and Female students separately and collectively as per need of the study.

Results and Discussion-

The data collected by the above mentioned psychological test was analyzed separately and following and results were obtained which can be summarized as follows-

(I) To find out the extent to which Scientific Creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) helps in to predict academic achievement (X_1) of XI grade male students.

Table – 2

Mean (M), Standard deviation(s) and Co-relational values for variables X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 of academic achievement of male students of XI grade.

Mean(M)	SD(s)	Variable	Correlation Coefficient (r)			
			X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4
83.82	12.747	X_1	1.0	0.343**	0.288**	0.503**
77.31	11.068	X_2	0.343**	1.0	0.176*	0.316**
83.06	10.033	X_3	0.288**	0.176*	1.0	0.180*
182.18	18.953	X_4	0.503**	0.316**	0.180*	1.0

(**significant at 0.01 level of significance, * significant at 0.05 level of significance)

The above table shows the Mean (M), Standard deviation (s) and correlation coefficient in between the dependent variable, academic achievement (X_1) and other three independent variables, Scientific Creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) of male students of XI grade. The mean and standard deviation for academic achievement (X_1) is found to be 83.82 and 12.747 whereas, those of scientific creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) are found to be 77.31,11.068; 83.06,10.033 and 182.18,18.953 respectively.

Table – 3

Solution of the Multiple Correlations, the Regression Coefficient and the Constant for male students of XI grade.

Variable	β_i	r_{ii}	$\beta_i r_{ii}$	s_i	s_1/s_i	b_i	M_1	$M_i b_i$
X_2	0.1803	0.343	0.0618	11.068	1.151	0.2075	77.31	16.0418
X_3	0.2034	0.288	0.0585	10.033	1.270	0.2583	83.06	21.4543

X_4	0.6404	0.503	0.3222	18.953	0.672	0.4303	182.18	78.3920
$\Sigma b_i r_{ii} = 0.4425$				$\Sigma M_i b_i = 115.8881$				
$M_1 = 83.82$	$R^2_{1.234} = 0.4425$			$K = M_1 - \Sigma M_i b_i$				
$s_1 = 12.747$	$R_{1.234} = 0.6652$			$= 32.0681$				
Regression Equation: $X_1 = 0.0275X_2 + 0.2583X_3 + 0.4303X_4 + 32.0681$.								

Above table shows the solution of multiple correlations, the regression coefficient and the constant(K) to predict the dependent variable academic achievement (X_1) with the help of other three independent variables viz. scientific creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits(X_4) of male students of XI grade. The sum total of all the three independent variables X_2 , X_3 and X_4 , β -coefficient correlation and their relational coefficient ($\beta_{ir_{ii}}$) is found to be 0.4425 whereas the sum total of mean and b-value (M_{ibi}) of all the three variables was found to be 115.8881. The multiple correlation coefficient of all the independent variable with the dependent variable ($R_{1.234}$) is found to be 0.6652 and the constant (K) value is found to be 32.0681.

Thus on the above calculation the predicting equation of dependent variable(X_1) i.e. academic achievement is estimated to be $X_1 = 0.0275X_2 + 0.2583X_3 + 0.4303X_4 + 32.0681$, which indicates that in predicting the value of academic achievement of male students of XI grade the independent factor(X_2) i.e. Scientific creativity contributes to a value of 0.0275, whereas the independent factor (X_3) i.e. Intelligence contributes to a value of 0.2583 and that of factor (X_4) i.e. Study Habits contributes to the value of 0.4303 and the value of regression constant (K) is found to be 32.0681, which correlates positively in the prediction of dependent variable with the help of regression equation.

Overall the significant intercorrelational pattern is found in between the variables Scientific creativity (X_2), Intelligence(X_3) and Study Habits(X_4) with academic achievement (X_1) inferred that the independent variables contributes significantly in the prediction of academic achievement of male students of XI grade.

(II) To find out the extent to which Scientific Creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) helps in to predict academic achievement (X_1) of XI grade female students.

Table-4.

Mean(M), Standard deviation(s) and Co-relational values for variables X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 of academic achievement female students of XI grade.

Mean(M)	SD(s)	Variable	Correlation Coefficient(r)			
			X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4
81.34	13.947	X_1	1.0	0.120	0.249**	0.309**
73.39	11.463	X_2	0.120	1.0	0.039	0.115
78.53	9.955	X_3	0.249**	0.039	1.0	0.184*
177.02	16.163	X_4	0.308**	0.115	0.184*	1.0

(**significant at 0.01 level of significance, * significant at 0.05 level of significance)

The above table shows the Mean (M), Standard deviation (s) and correlation coefficient in between the dependent variable, academic achievement (X_1) and other three independent variables viz. Scientific Creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits(X_4) for female students of XI grade. The mean and standard deviation for academic achievement (X_1) is found to be 81.34 and 13.947 whereas, those of variables Scientific Creativity (X_2), Intelligence(X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) are found to be 73.39,11.463; 78.53,9.955 and 177.02,16.163 respectively.

Table – 5.

Solution of the Multiple Correlations, the Regression Coefficient and the Constant for academic achievement for female students of XI grade.

Variable	β_i	r_{li}	$\beta_i r_{li}$	s_i	s_i/s_i	b_i	M_1	$M_i b_i$
X_2	0.0819	0.120	0.0098	11.463	1.216	0.0995	73.39	7.3023
X_3	0.1989	0.249	0.0495	9.955	1.401	0.2786	78.53	21.8784
X_4	0.2902	0.308	0.0893	16.163	0.862	0.2501	177.02	44.2727
$\Sigma b_i r_{li} = 0.1486$				$\Sigma M_i b_i = 73.4534$				

$M_1 = 81.34$	$R^2_{1,234} = 0.1486$	$K = M_1 - \sum M_i b_i$
$s_1 = 13.947$	$R_{1,234} = 0.3854$	$= 7.8866$
Regression Equation: $X_1 = 0.0995X_2 + 0.2786X_3 + 0.2501X_4 + 7.8866$		

Above table shows the solution of multiple correlations, the regression coefficient and the constant (K) to predict the dependent variable academic achievement (X_1) with the help of other three independent variables scientific creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) of female students of XI grade. The sum total of all the three independent variables X_2 , X_3 and X_4 , β -coefficient correlation and their relational coefficient ($\beta_{r_{ij}}$) is found to be 0.1486 whereas the sum total of mean and b-value ($M_i b_i$) of all the three variables was found to be 73.4534. The multiple correlation coefficient of all the independent variable with the dependent variable ($R_{1,234}$) is found to be 0.3854 and the constant (K) value is found to be 7.8866.

Thus on the above calculation the predicting equation of dependent variable (X_1) i.e. academic achievement is estimated to be $X_1 = 0.0995X_2 + 0.2786X_3 + 0.2501X_4 + 7.8866$, which indicates that in predicting the value of academic achievement of female students of XI grade the independent factor (X_2) i.e. scientific creativity contributes to a value of 0.0995, whereas the independent factor (X_3) i.e. Intelligence contributes to a value of 0.2786 and that of factor (X_4) i.e. Study Habits contributes to the value of 0.2501 and the value of regression constant (K) is found to be 7.8866, which correlates positively in the prediction of dependent variable with the help of regression equation.

Overall the significant intercorrelational pattern is found in between the variables scientific creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) with academic achievement (X_1) inferred that the independent variables contributes positively in the prediction of academic achievement of female students of XI grade.

(III) To find out the extent to which Scientific Creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) helps in to predict academic achievement (X_1) of XI grade students.

Table – 6.

Mean(M), Standard deviation(s) and co-relational values for variables X_1 , X_2 , X_3 and X_4 of students of XI grade.

Mean(M)	SD(s)	Variable	Correlation Coefficient(r)			
			X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4
82.92	13.522	X_1	1.0	0.293**	0.214**	0.369**
76.29	11.169	X_2	0.293**	1.0	0.197**	0.272**
80.93	10.227	X_3	0.241**	0.197**	1.0	0.209**
178.59	19.252	X_4	0.396**	0.272**	0.209**	1.0

(** significant at 0.01 level of significance)

The above table shows the Mean (M), Standard deviation (s) and correlation coefficient in between the dependent variable, academic achievement (X_1) and other three independent variables Scientific Creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) for overall students of XI grade. The mean and standard deviation for academic achievement (X_1) is found to be 82.92 and 13.522 whereas, those of variables Scientific Creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits (X_4) are 76.29,11.169; 80.93,10.227 and 178.59,19.252 respectively.

Table – 7.

Solution of the Multiple Correlations, the Regression Coefficient and the Constant for students of XI grade.

Variable	β_i	r_{li}	$\beta_i r_{li}$	s_i	s_1/s_i	b_i	M_1	$M_i b_i$
X_2	0.1861	0.293	0.0545	11.169	1.210	0.2251	76.29	17.1728
X_3	0.1467	0.241	0.0353	10.227	1.322	0.1939	80.93	15.6923
X_4	0.3197	0.369	0.1179	19.252	0.702	0.2244	178.59	40.0755
$\Sigma \beta_i r_{li} = 0.2077$				$\Sigma M_i b_i = 72.9406$				
$M_1 = 82.92$		$R^2_{1,234} = 0.2077$			$K = M_1 - \Sigma M_i b_i$			

$s_1 = 13.522$	$R_{1,234} = 0.4557$	$= 9.9794$
Regression Equation: $X_1 = 0.2251X_2 + 0.1939X_3 + 0.2244X_4 + 9.9794$		

Above table summarizes the solution of multiple correlations, the regression coefficient and the constant(K) to predict the dependent variable academic achievement (X_1) with the help of other three independent variables scientific creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits(X_4) for overall students of XI grade. The sum total of all the three independent variables X_2 , X_3 and X_4 , β -coefficient correlation and their relational coefficient ($\beta_i r_{ij}$) is found to be 0.2077 whereas the sum total of mean and b-value ($M_i b_i$) of all the three variables was found to be 72.9406. The multiple correlation coefficient of all the independent variable with the dependent variable ($R_{1,234}$) is found to be 0.4557 and the constant (K) value is found to be 9.9794.

Thus on the above calculation the predicting equation of dependent variable (X_1) i.e. academic achievement is estimated to be $X_1 = 0.2251X_2 + 0.1939X_3 + 0.2244X_4 + 9.9794$, which indicates that in predicting the value of academic achievement of overall students of XI grade the independent factor (X_2) i.e. scientific creativity contributes to a value of 0.2251, whereas the independent factor (X_3) i.e. Intelligence contributes to a value of 0.1939 and that of factor (X_4) i.e. Study Habits contributes to the value of 0.2244 and the value of regression constant (K) is found to be 9.9794, which correlates significantly in the prediction of dependent variable with the help of regression equation.

Overall the significant intercorrelational pattern (all at the significance level of 0.01) is found in between the variables Scientific creativity (X_2), Intelligence (X_3) and Study Habits(X_4) with academic achievement (X_1) inferred that the independent variables strongly contributes in the prediction of academic achievement for overall students of XI grade.

References-

- **Anna, Vedel (2014).** The Big Five and tertiary academic performance: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Personality and Individual Differences* 71 (2014) pp.66–76.
- **Azikiwe, U. (1998).** Study approaches of university students. *WCCI Region II Forum*. Vol. 2, Lagos. pp.106-114.
- **Cropley, A.J. (1966)** Creativity and Intelligence, *Senior Journal of Educational Psychology*, 36, 3 : 259-66.
- **Cropley, A.J.(1967)** Creativity: A new kind of Intellect. *Australian Journal of Education*, 2, 2 : 120-25.
- **Jauk, E., Benedek, M., and Neubauer, A. C. (2014).** The road to creative achievement: A latent variable model of ability and personality predictors. *European Journal of Personality*, 28, pp.95-105.
- **Julie A. Pozzebon, Michael C. Ashton and Beth A. Visser(2014).** Personality, Ability and Congruence in the Prediction of Academic Outcomes. *Journal of Career Assessment*. Feb 2014. Vol.22 no.1 pp.75-88.

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Paper-15

**Relation between Substance Use and
Parental Control among undergraduate
students**

Suvashree Roy Chowdhury

Relation between Substance Use and Parental Control among undergraduate students

Suvashree Roy Chowdhury²²

Abstract

*Substance use is a burning issue throughout the world. Substance use generally refers to the use psychotropic substances for the purpose of alternating one's mental condition either by sedating the mind or by making the mind excited. In this present study five hundred students were chosen from colleges catering engineering course of study. Keeping in view the cases of suicides taking place among the engineering students due to drug intake, it is inevitable to study the matter on a serious note. Students' college life often lack parental proctoring and supervision which often become dangerous. Many own up diversions into things that are harmful and injurious to the society as well. Substance use is one such heinous practice that often triggers danger and crime committing acts by the students. Thus, the paper aims at finding out significant relation between substance use and parental control. **Objective:** To find out relation between personal substance use and parental control. **Sample:** Five hundred students were randomly chosen to participate in the study. **Research design:** Descriptive survey approach was implemented. **Data Analysis:** Descriptive statistics (mean and SD) and Pearson Correlation. **Conclusion:** The result showed that there is a significant negative correlation between substance use of the students and parental control. **Educational Implication:** The study showed that parental control seems to play a very important role in shaping up personal substance use behaviour. Thus, not only from the familial end, but the educational institutions are to be more alerts in spreading the awareness about*

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drug addiction and arrange for programs where the parents would be oriented about the various ways by which they can track their children on substance use.

Keywords: Substance use; undergraduate students, parental control.

Introduction-

This study focuses to detect substance use among the engineering students. The study involves cigarette, alcohol and drug use among the students pursuing engineering course of education. Often it has been found that students are into substance use due to lack of parental monitoring. In some cases it was also found that parents are quite oblivious about their child's substance use and it was quite casual matter for the parents to allow their child to use alcoholic beverages with no glitches at all (Moore, Rothwell, & Segrott, 2010; Muñoz-Rivas & Graña, 2001). It was the same case with tobacco usage as well (Muñoz-Rivas & Graña, 2001). Cannabis, another kind of substance used for addiction, was found to be quite casually used by the youths with parents having no problem at all. (Olsson et al., 2003). Substance use is not only a social menace but individually it has adverse psycho-somatic fall outs. It was also found out that parenting style and control helped in reducing the initiating age of substance use among the youths especially the adolescents (Velleman et al., 2005). The present world scenario also shows escalation of drug use among the youths and many students are meeting death due to drug dependency and its overdose.

The present study aims to find substance use of the engineering students and its relation to parental control. It is the home, the primary agent of socialisation, nevertheless play a very vital role in shaping up an individual's behaviour and thus it is imperative to see the extent to which the correlation between personal substance use and parental control is significant.

Objectives-

Thus, the **objectives** of the study were constructed as-

1. To find out significant relation between personal cigarette use and parental control.
2. To find out significant relation between personal alcohol use and parental control.
3. To find out significant relation between personal drug use and parental control.

Hypotheses-

Basing on the objectives constructed the null hypotheses were framed as-

H₀1: There is no significant relation between personal cigarette use and parental control

H₀2: There is no significant relation between personal alcohol use and parental control.

H₀3: There is no significant relation between personal drug use and parental control.

Operational definition-

Substance Use: The study operationalized the term 'Substance Use' as consumption of substances of addiction that are mainly used to alter an individual state of mind especially the nervous system. Substances are consumed to relieve stress and remove psychological distress for a time being.

Parental Control: Monitoring and supervision of the parents over their children to combat their harmful diversions and bad habits like substance use.

Review of Related Literature-

It has been seen that the parents who themselves are into substance use practice are likely to lack supervision over their children in matters of substance use (Jacob and Johnson, 1997). There have been researches where faulty parenting style was directly related to substance use among their children (Ham and Hope, 2003). Parents into substance use often project to be model themselves in front of their children (Kandel and Andrews, 1987). In another

study it showed that disruptive families' had children less parental control over their children. Often children from these lack parental control and get into the practice of drug intake(Wills *et al.*, 2004). Psychological distress due to parental problems and weak parent–child bonding is a lead their wards to get addicted to substances. It was observed that strong parental control and strong attachment to parents considerably reduced substance use among the adolescent students (Adalbjarnardottir and Hafsteinsson, 2001).Contrasting the above studyanother research finding concluded that poor parental control led to increased substance use among the adolescents(Barnowet *al.*, 2002). But speaking from the view point of extreme parental control, it was found that too much of control produced psychological distress among the adolescents (Barber, 1996). On the more a research finding also said that substance use more or less depends on personal disposition. One is capable of handling it by the dint of self-control as well. Disruption in parental control has negative effect on adolescent substance use.

One of the interesting studies on substance use showed that over strictness and control on children eventually leads to addiction to illicit substances. The children who remains under strictest supervision often become more prone towards substance use more than the ones whose parents were not very strict (Schucksmith, Glendinning, & Hendry, 1997).

The aim of the present study thus lies in analysing the use of substances by the young students and whether parental control is at all a factor to regulate such habit.

Methodology-

Research Design: Descriptive research design was implemented to conduct the study. Survey approach helped to collect data from the engineeringstudents and meet the research objective.

Sampling: Simple random sampling was used to collect the data.

Data Collection and Instrument: Data was collected from hundred engineering students (n=100), pursuing engineering course of study from a public engineering in Kolkata in West Bengal. The students were randomly chosen irrespective of the branches they hailed from. The students of B.Tech (Bachelors in Technology and B.E degree (Bachelors in Engineering) were the target group.

Two tools were mostly used -1) Personal Substance use questionnaire, where questions pertained to personal cigarette use (PSUP-C); personal alcohol use (PSUP-A) and personal drug use (PSUP-D).

For personal cigarette use the answering options ranged from 'No usage of cigarettes' to 'Fifteen to twenty cigarettes per day' in the last thirty day. The scoring ranged from 1-6. The second item was on personal alcohol use. Here, the answering option ranged from 'No use of alcohol' to 'More than then times fives drinks at a row in the last thirty days'. Here the score ranged from 1-6. The third item in this questionnaire pertained to drug use, and the answering options were given in 'Yes' and 'No'. The total weightage of this item was 5, where Yes=1 and No=2.

A four point Likert scale on parental control was used to procure responses from the participants. The questions pertained to questions related to parental supervision and control into three sections. Each section queried about different kinds of supervision provided by their parents. The answering options ranged from 'Definitely true for you' to 'Not at all true for you and the score ranged from 1-4.

Data Analysis: For analysing the data, statistical procedures were used. Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Correlation were implemented. **Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)** version 17.0 was used to compute the data.

Result and Discussion-

Illustration of the result is shown in the table 4.1 below

4.1: Correlation matrix.

	PSUP-C Mean =2.09 S.D=1.58 N=100	PSUP-A Mean=1.79 S.D=1.37 N=100	PSUP-D Mean=0.054 S.D=0.132 N=100	PTC Mean=0.53 S.D=0.23 N=100
PSUP-C	1			
PSUP-A	0.822	1		
PSUP-D	0.476	.564	1	
PTC	.082	-.037	-.037	1

The result outcome showed no significant correlation between with personal; personal alcohol use; and personal drug use. The result outcome thus defies the previous conducted researches which showed that parental control is very much related to personal use of substances.

The null hypothesis constructed in the beginning of the study are all refuted as because there no significant relation was observed between personal substance use (cigarettes, alcohol; drugs) and parental control

Conclusion and Educational Implication-

The study affirms to a large extent that it is not only parental control that regulates substance use among students but it is rather self-control and self-efficacy that shapes up such behaviour. Even though a lot of times disruptive homes, broken family and frivolous lifestyle tends to give rise to such habits, but it depends on one's own disposition to accept or refute substance use. There are various preventive programs that have been taken under the stride of our Indian Government and many other international agencies throughout the globe are fighting the curse of substance use where ever possible. World Health Organisation is a robust acting body concerned about the problem of substance use, but hand in hand there are other national and regional level agencies that are trying still to spread the awareness program and preventive measures. Only a small group of sample's result is not all to tame the problem of substance use, but if not generalized, it is still a stubborn problem that is nibbling every society of the world.

- References-Barber BK (1996) Parental psychological control: Revisiting a neglected construct. *Child Dev* 67:3296–3319
- Barber BK, Harmon EL (2002) Violating the self: Parental psychological control of children and adolescents. In: Barber BK (ed) *Intrusive parenting: How psychological control affects children and adolescents*. American Psychological Association, Washington, D C, pp 15–52
- Barnow S, Schuckit MA, Lucht M, John U, Freyberger HJ (2002) The importance of a positive family history of alcoholism, parental rejection and emotional warmth, behavioral problems and peer substance use for alcohol problems in teenagers: A path analysis. *J Stud Alcohol* 63:305–315.
- Glendinning, A., Schucksmith, J., & Hendry, L. (1997). Family life and smoking in adolescence. *Social Science & Medicine*, 44, 93-101.

- Ham LS, Hope DA (2003) College students and problematic drinking: A review of the literature. *ClinPsychol Rev* 23:719–759
- Jacob T, Johnson S (1997) Parenting influences on the development of alcohol abuse and dependence. *Alcohol Health ResWorld* 21:204–210
- Muñoz-Rivas, M.J., &Graña, J.L. (2001).Factoresfamiliares de riesgo y protecciónpara el consumo de drogas en adolescentes [Family risk and protection factor for drug use by adolescents].*Psicothema*, 13, 87-94.
- Olsson, C.A., Coffey, C., Toumbourou, J.W., Bond, L., Thomas, L., &Patton, G. (2003). Family risk factors for cannabis use: A population based survey of Australian secondary school students. *Drug andAlcohol Review*, 22, 143-152.
- Schucksmith, J., Glendinning, A., & Henry, L. (1997). Adolescent drinking behaviour and the role of family life: A Scottish perspective. *Journal ofAdolescence*, 20, 85-101.
- Velleman, R.D.B., Templeton, L.J., &Copello, A.G. (2005). The role of the family in preventing and intervening with substance use and misuse: Acomprehensive review of family interventions, with a focus on young people. *Drug and Alcohol Review*, 24, 93-109
- Wills TA, Dishion TJ (2004) Temperament and adolescent substance use: A transactional analysis of emerging self-control. *J Clin Child AdolescPsychol* 33:69–81
- Wills TA, Resko JA, Ainette MG, Mendoza D (2004) Role of parent support and peer support in adolescent substance use: A test of mediated effects.*Psychol Addict Behav* 18:122–134

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Paper-16

**A Study of Scientific Temperament among
Higher Secondary Students**

Dr. Vinod Kumar Singh
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A Study of Scientific Temperament among Higher Secondary Students

Dr. Vinod Kumar Singh²³

Raghavendra Pratap Shukla²⁴

Abstract

The newer technological developments have become a routine in day-to-day and we are becoming dependent more and more upon the scientific temperament. In such condition, it is rather more necessary that the people are oriented and educated for scientific attitude and temperament. This study looks at the scientific temperament of higher secondary students. To achieve the objective of the study 56 students were filled up the scientific temperament inventory. Result of the study revealed that the condition of scientific temperament among higher secondary students is not up to the mark. There is significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary students and there is no significant difference between male and female higher secondary students.

Key-words- Scientific, Temperament, Scientific Temperament, Scientific Attitude, Scientific Literacy, Scientific Thinking, Scientific Method, Scientific Habit.

Introduction-

The present world is a world of science and technology. Every event happening around us demands some knowledge of simple scientific facts or principles. Science is now a part of life of everyday for everybody. The achievements and the benefits of science touch all sectors and all levels of modern society. Science has made a tremendous impact on the cultural life of the present day society which

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is a product of science. The thinking, feelings and actions of a modern man are practically guided by the effects of science. Our habits and attitudes have also been affected by science. In society, there will always be problems to be solved. One of the very useful outcomes of learning science is the development of problem solving skill. Hence with the help of this skill, one can solve the problems in his personal or social life.

Scientific temperament is a spirit of enquiry and involves the process of logical reasoning (sharma 2013). It is the way we look at the world in a scientific manner. According to C. Jinarajadasa (1958), the scientific temperament means a careful training of the mind to observe facts “as they are”, again and again, before constructing any theories about them. But to observe facts rightly requires a preliminary training of the senses to report correctly and this is a difficult process, though others can acquire it, especially if they happen to be influenced by a really scientific observer and inspiring teacher. Bishop Leadbeater made a special point of trying to “see” a fact as accurately and dispassionately as possible; he had an innate reverence for a fact, that is, for the “thing-as-it-is”, which characterizes the scientist.

By Anita Singh (1988) Scientific Temperament connotes an individual’s mental disposition related to the items pertaining to six areas of human behavior; Scientific attitude, Scientific habit, Scientific thinking, Scientific perception, Scientific literacy and Scientific method. For present study these six areas have been concerned. All six areas are discussed below:

Scientific Literacy - According to the United States National Center for Education Statistics, "Scientific literacy is the knowledge and understanding of scientific concepts and processes required for personal decision making, participation in civic, cultural affairs and economic productivity".

Scientific Attitude - Scientific attitude is used to denote opinions, feelings, beliefs and appreciations which individuals have for and about science and general orientation of individuals towards dealing with facts, evidence and objects of science.

Scientific Thinking- Scientific thinking is also an important dimension of scientific temperament. Scientific thinking means an experience and the purpose of which to invent the intellectual tools for the use in common sense thinking. By Kevin Dunbar and Jonathan Fugelsang, scientific thinking involves many general purposes, cognitive operations that human beings apply in nonscientific domains such as induction, deduction, analogy, problem solving, and causal reasoning. R.K. Coll and others in their study “Understanding Scientific Thinking”, described that one feature of scientific literacy is the ability to make credibility, judgments of peoples’ and scientists’ testimony. Scientific literacy is important in modern society as people encounter debates and issues of a scientific and technological nature, including science curriculum matters. John Dewey (1933) says that scientific thinking is a process of analysis and synthesis.

Scientific Method- Scientific method is another important component of scientific temperament. It is the only way to increase the general body of tested knowledge and to eliminate arbitrary and ambiguous opinion. Scientific method springs from the desire to acquire knowledge and it is beyond a narrow and subjective elements.

Scientific Habit- Scientific habit is also a main feature of scientific temperament. A person having scientific habit always keeps on thinking that every work is governed by scientific laws and there is some reason behind every work. Scientific creativity or creative ability is one of the most important dimensions of scientific habit.

This is the era of scientific achievements. The newer technological developments have become a routine in day-to-day and we are becoming dependent more and more upon the scientific temperament. In such condition, it is rather more necessary that the people are oriented and educated for scientific attitude and temperament. The findings of study will be useful to increase scientific temperament among higher secondary students.

Objectives of the Study –

The present study was undertaken to achieve the following objectives:

1. To assess the present status of scientific temperament among higher secondary students.
2. To find out the difference of scientific temperament among rural and urban higher secondary students.
3. To compare the scientific temperament among male and female students of higher secondary.

Hypotheses of the Study-

Hypotheses for the present study are framed to list the objectives of the study.

H01 There is no significant difference in scientific temperament between rural and urban students of higher secondary at 0.01 level of significance.

H02 There is no significant difference in scientific temperament between male and female students of higher secondary at 0.01 level of significance.

Methodology-

The proposed study was carried on by quantitative research method. The population of the present study confined to as the higher secondary students studying in various Intermediate colleges of Allahabad district. Five senior secondary schools of Allahabad district were randomly selected, out of which three schools were from urban areas and two from rural areas. There were total 56 students as sample, 35

students from rural areas and 21 students from urban areas. A Scientific Temperament Inventory (S.T.I.) which was constructed and standardized by Anita Singh (1988) a research scholar, has been used to collect data. It consists of 70 items according to their area of scientific temperament. The reliability coefficient is 0.97 and validity is 0.87. In the study t-test was used to compare the scientific temperament of different groups of higher secondary students.

Analysis and Interpretation-

Hypotheses wise analysis and interpretation has been given below.

1. To assess the present status of scientific temperament among higher secondary students.

From the table 1 the mean score obtained for the sample was 95.09. The value of median & mode was 94 and 95.29 respectively. The distribution is negative skewed, which is evident from the calculated value of skewness i.e. -0.02.

Table 1

Distribution of Scientific temperament scores of higher secondary students

S. No.	Class Interval	Mid Values	Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Descriptive Statistical details
1.	70-79	74.5	6	56	Mean=95.09 Median=94 Mode=95.29 Standard Deviation=9.98 First Quartile (P25)=87 Third Quartile (P75)=102 Quartile
2.	80-89	84.5	11	50	
3.	90-99	94.5	20	39	
4.	100-109	104.5	12	19	
5.	110-119	114.5	6	7	
6.	120-129	124.5	1	1	
			N=56		

					Deviation=7.5 Skewness= -0.02 Maximum=124 Minimum=75 Range=50
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The range of the distribution of scores is 50 (highest score=124 and lowest score=75). The standard deviation and quartile deviation are 9.98 and 7.5 respectively. These measures dispersion reveal that the spread in the distribution is normal.

Table 2

Distribution of higher secondary students in different category of scientific temperament

Status of scientific temperament	Score	No. of students	Percentage of Distribution
Poor/Unsatisfactory	Below 80	7	12.5
Below Average	81-90	10	18.25
Average	91-100	22	38.50
Above average	101-110	10	18.25
Good	Above 111	7	12.5

The table 2 shows the percentage of higher secondary students in different status related to scientific temperament. It infer that 12.5% students were found in poor level, 18.25% students were found in below average level, 38.5% students were found in average level, 18.25% students were found in above average level and 12.5% students were found in the good level of scientific temperament.

2. H01 There is no significant difference in scientific temperament between rural and urban students of higher secondary at 0.01 level of significance.

Table 3

The means, SD and t-value between Rural and Urban higher secondary students on STI

Group	No. of Sample	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P(.01)
Rural	35	89.57	8.89	54	4.94	Significant
Urban	21	102.68	9.33			

The interpretation of table 3 speaks that the Mean and S.D. of Rural and Urban higher secondary students were 89.57, 8.89 and 102.68, 9.33 respectively. The calculated 't' value to be 4.94, is more than the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence our research hypothesis is accepted.

($t_{0.01} = 2.66$, for $df = 54$)

3. H02 There is no significant difference in scientific temperament between male and female students of higher secondary at 0.01 level of significance.

Table – 4

The means, SD and t-value of male and female higher secondary students' respondent on STI

Group	No. of sample	Mean	SD	df	t-value	P(.01)
Male	26	94.96	21.06	54	.439	Not Significant
Female	30	92.06	27.35			

From the sample of 56 higher secondary students the score of 26 male students and 30 female students were tabulated in table 4. The Mean and S.D. of Male and Female students of higher secondary were 94.96, 21.06 and 92.06, 27.35

respectively. The calculated t-value to be 0.439, which is less than the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence our research hypothesis is rejected.

($t_{0.01} = 2.66$, for $df. = 54$)

Findings and conclusions-

The study was properly conceptualized, operationalized, hypothesized and conducted on scientific lines leads to worthwhile results and conclusions. The conceptual frame of the study is based on the comprehensive survey of related areas. On a whole, it was observed that near about 2/3rd students have satisfactory scientific temperament. On the basis of this it can be concluded that maximum students of the sample have some extent of scientific temperament. Rural and urban students vary significantly in regard to their mean scientific temperament scores. Urban students secured higher mean score than rural students. When comparison of rural and urban students was made, the urban students differ significantly in their scientific temperament. It shows that habitation is a determining factor of scientific temperament. It is because of different environment in rural and urban area. Male and female students do not vary significantly in regard to their mean scientific temperament scores. Male and female students secured near about equal mean. When a comparison of male and female students was made, the students do not differ in scientific temperament. According to this study it may be proved that gender is not a determining factor of scientific temperament. It is because of same environment provided to male and female higher secondary students.

Implications of the study-

It was found that 1/3rd of the students have poor scientific temperament so that it is alarming for us. Hence, Popular educational packages and models may be

developed to enhance scientific temperament of higher Secondary students. A well structured programme is evolved so as to encounter the deep rooted obscurantism. Different channels of mass communication and mass media may be utilized for the promotion of scientific temperament. Programs of educations in rural areas should be enriched to scientific temperament. An integrated approach of curriculum development should be adopted strategically so as scientific temperament may be inculcated reasonably at every stage. To improve scientific temperament among students of senior secondary there is an urgent need of modification in school curriculum, textbooks and pedagogy etc. keeping in mind six components namely scientific attitude, scientific habit etc. of scientific temperament. An exposure should be provided to rural students to increase scientific temperament.

References-

- Dewey, John (1933); How We Think, D. C. Heath and Company, Boston.
- Dunbar, K., and Fugelsang, J. (2004). Causal Thinking in Science: How Scientists and Students Interpret the Unexpected. In M. E. Gorman, A.Kincannon, D. Gooding, and R. D. Tweney (Eds.), New Directions in Scientific and Technical Thinking. Lawrence Erlbaum. Hillsdale.
- Jinarajadassa, C. (1958); Helping Students Develop a Scientific Temperament, The Science Teacher, Vol. 25.
- Leadbeater, B.(1928); “Elements and Safeguards of Scientific Thinking”. In Harris C. W. (ed.); Encyclopedia of Education research, Third edition, The Macmillan Company.
- [National Center for Education Statistics](http://www.nap.edu/readingroom/books/nse) (2011). National Science Education Standards (Report). National Academy Press.
www.nap.edu/readingroom/books/nse

- Singh, Anita (1988); Scientific Temperament among postgraduate students of deferent religious in India . Ph.D. Thesis, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.
- Sharma, Suman (2013). A Study of Scientific temprament among science students at higher secondary level. Review of research vol 2, issue 8 retrived from www.reviewofresearch.net on 15.07.2015

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Paper-17

**Enhancement of Creative Writing Ability
in Poetry through Participatory Approach**

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Enhancement of Creative Writing Ability in Poetry through Participatory Approach

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Abstract

This paper reports a study on students' classroom-based participatory approach creative writing. The central aim of the research was to contribute to creative writing ability in poetry through participatory approach. The study drew on longitudinal observations of ongoing creative writing session. The participatory approach creative writing sessions were observed and recorded. Based on the analysis of composed poem by a student before and after using the participatory approach it has been found that the peer editing of the poems of one another worked much better than solo creative writing. The study has identified discourse patterns and participatory strategies which facilitate creative composition.

Introduction-

Creativity has been defined in many contexts, but can be simply described as “successful personal activity intent on producing an appropriate new idea or object” (Newton and Newton, 2009: 45). Within the domain of student learning, teachers can serve as facilitators or inhibitors of creativity and therefore, play an important role in the development of creative skills within the educational system (Sternberg, 2003). At the classroom level, the incorporation of teaching practices that promote creativity can lead to positive changes in student behaviour, social

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skills, self-esteem, motivation and academic achievement (Qualifications and Curriculum Authority, 2005).

Poetry-

Poetry has a long history, dating back to back to Vedic times. They were written in various Indian languages such as Vedic Sanskrit, Classical Sanskrit, Oriya, Tamil, Kannada, Bengali and Urdu. Poetry in foreign languages such as Persian and English also has had a strong influence on Indian poetry. The poetry reflects diverse spiritual traditions within India. In particular, many Indian poets have been inspired by mystical experiences. Poetry is the oldest form of literature and has a rich written and oral tradition. Poetry has sometimes been more generally regarded as a fundamental creative act employing language. The use of ambiguity, symbolism, irony and other stylistic elements of poetic diction often leaves a poem open to multiple interpretations. Similarly, metaphor, simile and metonymy (Strachan 2000) create a resonance between otherwise disparate images—a layering of meanings, forming connections previously not perceived. Kindred forms of resonance may exist, between individual verses, in their patterns of rhyme or rhythm. Some poetry types are specific to particular cultures and genres and respond to characteristics of the language in which the poet writes. Much modern poetry reflects a critique of poetic tradition, (Eliot 1999) playing with and testing, among other things, the principle of euphony itself, sometimes altogether forgoing rhyme or set rhythm. (Longenbach 1997) and (Schmidt, 1999). In today's increasingly globalized world, poets often adapt forms, styles and techniques from diverse cultures and languages.

Creative writing is a new subject here and is stated to anything where the purpose is to express thoughts, feelings and emotions rather than to simply convey information. Creative writing can technically be considered any writing of original

composition. In this sense, creative writing is a more contemporary and process-oriented name for what has been traditionally called literature, including the variety of its genres.

Reflections on the Review of Related Studies-

The brief review of research studies indicate that, Pathak, U.(1983). studied personality variables associated with creative writing of Writers, Chitambar (1981) studied creative ability, reading interests, and creative writing of Std. VII to IX students and Prabhavathamana (1987) studied creative writing process and identification of creative writing in English in student-teachers in intercultural connotation.

The success of developing creativity depends on enthusiastic and careful transaction by the teacher in the classroom. Bush, Harold, K, (1993) indicated that poetry may be the ideal arena for fostering figurative language skills at virtually any reading level.

Bailey, Margaret, and others (1995) found that some of the computer applications enhanced length and quality of compositions; increased students' self-esteem; helped students organize their thoughts via storyboarding; and got good overall reaction from the students.

Hollander John (1997) described that the enduring force of poetry is championed against the incursion of fashionable writing. It revolts against the college and university literature and writing programs that offer only "little blots of condensed contextualization" scarcely touching poetry's legacy.

According to Bartscher, Mark A, et.al. (2001), low achievement affects behaviour, attitudes, and peer interaction. The probable cause for lack of writing skills has been attributed to lack of feedback from teacher to pupil and unpredictable

lifestyles of some students. The solution strategy involves cooperative learning, journalizing, and creative writing.

Reid, Laura, (2009) Webb, Pam (2009) stated that through poetry, a teacher may find a way to entice children in wondrous ways not before realized.

Some of the studies were conducted on the creativity in education and language teaching, writing of poetry and teaching of poetry, such as, Sue Dymoke & Janette Hughes (2009), Hosseini, A.S. and Watt, A.P. (2010), Tin Tan Beo, et.al. (2010), Welch Kristen Dayle (2010), Cetinavic, U.R. and Tutunis, B. (2012), Vala, J.et.al. (2012), and Jaffar, Z.B. et.al.(2014).

Hennessy, J. et.al. (2010) and Krikgoz, Y. (2014) conducted a study about exploring poems to promote language learners' creative writing and found that the presence of familiar topic could lead students to retrieve known meaning rather than generating imaginative responses, constructing new and surprising meaning as in the poems composed by the students. While Myhill, D. and Wilson, A. (2013) explained the playing it safe: Teachers' views of creativity in poetry writing.

From the review, it is evident that some of study by Chitambar (1981), Jaffar, Z.B. et.al. (2014) were conducted in the area of creative writing in English language at Secondary level. Some studies were conducted in the field of teacher education by Prabhavathamana (1987), Hennessy J. et.al. (2010) Myhill, D. and Wilson, A. (2013), Krikgoz, Y (2014), were on creative writing process and identification of creative writing in English in student-teachers in intercultural connotation. However, the germination of creative ideas takes place individually but its expression through appropriate lexicon can be facilitated by the peers. Also, the individual can be motivated by the group through appreciation of creative production. So, it is highly desirable to take up a research study on creative writing through participatory approach.

Rationale for the Study-

Every individual is creative in some respect or the other. Due to the phenomenal complexity of our genetic makeup and the uniqueness of each life experience, we are as distinct as snowflakes. This dissimilarity is the basis for our creativity. We each have unique perspective to express, a completely different set of talents and experiences to translate through our individual skills. It is this process of finding and listening to that individual's perspective, which results in the expression of our creativity. Creativity thus is the translation of our self into tangible expression. Accordingly, works of art, music, solutions to problems in our careers, style in dress, hobbies, dance or other expressive activities are all acts of creativity.

All have their own ideas of their environment. In early childhood, every individual expresses thoughts in small sentences. At times, it is in the form of rhyme. Because, children find it easy to express their thoughts in the rhymes and songs. But after childhood or in the middle of adolescence stage, all the attitudes of composing words in the shape of poems are not sustained among the children.

Classroom teaching today offers a little scope for creative works. It is mostly concerned with teaching the content than nurturing the creative abilities, instead of being centers of inquiry, classrooms still continue to be lesson hearing and note taking rooms. The activities in the classroom are generally centered on teacher and s/he is dominating the activities most of the time. The material provided to the pupils is a polished, finished product which provides a little scope to choose, think, infer or evaluate. Thus, classrooms provide a little scope for novelty, originality or innovations. The pupils have been, thus, taught to find the 'right' answer and until recently, schools provided a little opportunity to exercise imagination and alternative thinking skills (Joseph, 2001).

A language is a skill-oriented subject. It has got two dimensions- the practical and the creative. Overall, the language goals, curriculum, and methodology are centered round the practical communicative level, and mastery of the language, which consists of acquisition of the basic skills- listening, speaking, reading and writing. There is some provision for literature teaching. But it stops at the appreciation level only. Least importance is given to self expression. Students do learn certain essays, answer and reproduce them in the examination. Lesser scope is given for original expression; the compositions are teacher-dictated, little encouragement is given for original thinking and ideas. The prosody, and figures of speech teaching is only for examination purpose; rarely an opportunity is given to compose a poem using these elements. That's why students lose interest in language. The present goals, curriculum and methods of language teaching do not allow the students to reach the higher goal of creative-writing. They are putting restraints on the creative urge of impulse or self-expression of the students. The students should be given an opportunity for self-discovery, and expression of their own ideas, feelings and emotions, joy and sorrow, anger and sympathy, hatred and love. There can be some creative exercises through which their aesthetic sense is triggered up and get to a start of writing creatively. The ultimate aim of teaching creative writing is to enable the child to express his thoughts and ideas correctly in a logical sequence. He should be able to present his emotions, feelings, accurately and judiciously, either orally or in writing. For this teachers should be oriented on how to teach poetry effectively. The poetry teaching, particularly for older students, has been to teach poetry through print text and to focus on finding one meaning to be dissected. In contrast, poets emphasize the importance of hearing the poem read aloud engaging with it, and probing for deeper meaning through discussion with others. If we want our students to understand how literature, and

poetry in particular, brings them to a deeper understanding of life, we need to find meaningful ways to engage them with poetry. (Janette Hughes, 2007).

It has been observed that, generally, only a few individuals have both imagination and word power. One having only imagination power and lacking word power cannot present ideas. If one gets proper guidance for suitable expression of imagination power, h/she will be able to manifest well. The participatory approach could be a suitable approach for enhancing the creative ability of the students as well as student-teachers. Through the participatory approach, student-teachers are likely to get compatible feedback for expressing their imagination effectively. At the same time, the presentation can be made precise. What we expect our student-teachers to do is that they should not find any difficulty in communicating their creative ideas in the society freely. The creative writing abilities of the student-teachers ought to be developed through participatory approach through poems. The logical arrangement of the ideas regarding a particular topic, the vivid description of Rasas within the experience, the reasonably correct and prompt conversation, conveying a message, specifically, ventilating one's personal thinking, are some of the aspects of composition. Student-Teachers ought to be groomed in the Science & Art of creative composition & poetic expression.

Statement of the Problem-

Enhancement of Creative Writing Ability of Student -Teachers in Hindi Poetry through Participatory Approach

Research Questions-

1. To what extent does the creative writing ability exist in the Student-Teachers?
2. Can the creative writing ability of the Student-Teachers be enhanced?
3. Can Participatory approach facilitate Creative Writing?

Objectives of the Study-

1. To analyze selected poems of Hindi in terms of components of creative writing.
2. To identify the creative writing ability of the Student-Teachers.
3. To enhance the creative writing ability of the Student-Teachers through participatory approach.
4. To study the extent of enhancement of creative writing ability among Student-Teachers.
5. To study the reactions of the Student-Teachers towards Participatory Approach.

Assumption-

1. Participatory Approach presumes that team mind is very often better than the individual mind.
2. Creative Writing ability, particularly, composing poems can be enhanced through participatory approach.
3. Germination of idea is done by an individual, whereas, its incubation and enhancement can be done through participatory approach.

Hypotheses of the Study-

1. There will be no significant difference in the frequencies against 5 point scale at the pre test level and post level with respect to the various components of creative composition of the poems composed by a pupil teacher as follows-
 - i. Organization
 - ii. Originality
 - iii. Richness/ Elaboration
 - iv. Assonance

- v. Repetition
- vi. Rhyme
- vii. Simile
- viii. Metaphor
- ix. Hyperbole
- x. Tautology
- xi. Alliteration
- xii. Personification
- xiii. Onomatopoeia
- xiv. Litotes
- xv. Oxymoron
- xvi. Transferred Epithet
- xvii. Antithesis
- xviii. Anaphora
- xix. Phrase
- xx. Paradox

Delimitation of the Study-

The present study was delimited to D. El. Ed. Student-Teachers of the M.B. Mahila Teacher Training School, Dungarpur (Raj.).

Methodology-

The present study employed participatory approach for enhancement of creative writing ability of student teacher.

Population-

All the D. El. Ed. Student-Teachers (2014-2015) of Rajasthan constituted the population for the present study.

Sample-

All the D. El. Ed. Student-Teachers (2014-2015) of the M. B. Mahila Teachers Training School, Dungarpur (Rajasthan) constituted the sample for the study. The sample was selected purposively.

Tool for the present Study-

The following tool was used for the study-

1. Rating Scale on the Components of Poems (RSCP)

Rating Scale on the Components of Poems (RSCP)-

A Rating Scale on the Components of Poems was developed by the investigator for identification of creative writing ability of the D. El. Ed. Student-Teachers. Validity of the tool was established by the experts.

Data collection-

The data were personally collected by the investigator. Orientation of the D. El. Ed. student-teachers to different components of Creative Writing in poetry was done. One of the Hindi Poems written by HARIVANSH RAI BACCHAN “*DEKHO TOOT RAHA HAI TARA*” was selected as a model poem.

The procedure adopted by the investigator for enhancement of creative writing ability is presented as follows-

The Students-Teachers were oriented to different components of Creative Writing in Poetry by the Researcher. The Researcher made a Power Point Presentation and explained the various components of Creative Writing in Poetry with suitable examples.

After orientation of the D. El. Ed. Student-Teachers, the Researcher recited the model poem “*DEKHO TOOT RAHA HAI TARA*” with rhythm in class situation by presenting the power point presentation of poem.

After identification of creative writing components of the poem, the student-teachers were asked to compose a poem on the theme- ‘Beauty of Nature’. The

student-teachers were asked to compose a poem individually. After the poem was composed by the student-teacher, it was presented by him/her in the in class situation. The investigator and the student-teachers discussed the poem composed by the student-teacher, individually, in the context of creative writing components of poems. The student-teachers and the investigator suggested to improve the poem with appropriate words and figures of speech. The Student-Teacher modified the poem as per suggestions given by the investigator and the peer groups of student-teachers. After modifying the composed poem, the student-teacher was asked to recite the poem. Then student-teachers were given Rating Scale on the Components of Poem (RSCP) to assess the creative writing components. Then the Rating Scale on the Components of Poem was collected from Student-Teachers by the investigator after rating on the composed poem was done by them. The scoring of the tool was done according to the pre-planned scoring procedure.

Statistical Techniques used-

Collected data were analyzed using quantitative techniques. Quantitative data were collected through the Rating Scale on the components of poem. Collected data were analyzed using, frequency, percentage and Chi-Square.

Findings and Discussion-

In analyzing the students' poem, the investigator was primarily interested in exploring how the student created poem individually and intervened in each others in peer-group discussions. The findings and discussion of the study are as given below-

Table 1: Frequencies, percentage, chi-square and responses of the students on the rating scale against various components of a Poem- "PRAKRITI MAHA GRANTH HAI" composed by a student prior to Participatory Approach

Components	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Poor	Very Poor	Chi-Square	df	Level of Significance
1.Organization	2(6.67%)	25(83.33%)	3(10%)	0	0	70.2	4	.01
2.Originality	11(36.67%)	8(26.67%)	8(26.67%)	3(10%)	0	21.08	4	.01
3.Richness/ Elaboration	10(33.33%)	11(36.67%)	7(23.33%)	2(6.67%)	0	12.54	4	.05
4.Assonance	3(10%)	12(40%)	13(43.33%)	2(6.67%)	0	20.2	4	.01
5.Repetition	1(3.33%)	9(30%)	17(56.67%)	3(10%)	0	28.86	4	.01
6.Rhyme	8(26.67%)	17(56.67%)	3(10%)	2(6.67%)	0	26.88	4	.01
7.Simile	8(26.67%)	12(40%)	8(26.67%)	2(6.67%)	0	12.88	4	.05
8.Metaphor	0	0	5(16.67%)	9(30%)	16(53.33%)	26.2	4	.01
9.Hyperbole	4(13.33%)	12(40%)	10(33.33%)	4(13.33%)	0	12.88	4	.05
10.Tautology	0	0	5(16.67%)	13(43.33%)	12(40%)	22.2	4	.01
11. Alliteration	1(3.3%)	14(46.67%)	15(50%)	0	0	34.88	4	.01
12.Presonification	17(56.67%)	8(26.67%)	5(16.67%)	0	0	28.88	4	.01
13.Onomatopoeia	0	0	2(6.67%)	16(53.33%)	12(46.67%)	32.2	4	.01

14.Litotes	3(10%)	8(26.67%)	13(43.3%)	6(20%)	0	13.54	4	.01
15.Oxymoron	8(26.67%)	11(36.67%)	9(30%)	2(6.67%)	0	11.88	4	.05
16.Transferred Epithet	0	0	8(26.67%)	17(56.6%)	5(16.67%)	56.88	4	.01
17.Antithesis	0	6(20%)	5(16.67%)	12(46.67%)	7(23.33%)	10.2	4	.05
18.Anaphora	0	0	5(16.67%)	17(56.67%)	8(26.67%)	28.88	4	.01
19.Phrase	0	3(10%)	12(46.67%)	8(26.67%)	7(23.33%)	11.54	4	.05
20.Paradox	0	5(16.67%)	10(33.33%)	7(23.33%)	8(26.67%)	7.54	4	NS

It is evident from Table-1 that the computed Chi-Square values against the components organization, originality, assonance, repetition, rhyme, metaphor, tautology, alliteration, personification, onomatopoeia, litotes, transferred epithet, anaphora and paradox have been found to be greater than the Table value of Chi-Square of 13.277 against 4 degrees of freedom at .01 level, whereas against components richness/elaboration, simile, hyperbole, oxymoron, antithesis and phrase at .05 level. So, the null hypotheses that there will be no significant difference between the observed frequencies and frequencies expected against equal probability is rejected against all these statements against the respective levels. The computed Chi-Square values against the component paradox has been found to be lesser than the corresponding table Chi-Square values against 4 degrees of freedom at .05 level. So, the null hypotheses that there will be no significant difference

between the observed frequencies and the frequencies expected against the equal probability is not rejected.

A large majority (83.33%) of respondents have rated the organization of poem including balance, arrangement, consistency and clarity of words as very good, 6.67% excellent, whereas, 10% rated good.

Originality in the poem including choice of topic, sense of humor, and uniqueness of the idea composed by the student teacher was rated excellent by 36.67%, very good and good by 26.67%, respectively, whereas, poor by 10% of the respondents. The element richness/elaboration including expression, emotion, fluency and communication was rated very good by 36.67%, excellent by 33.33%, good by 23.33%, whereas, poor by 6.67%.

A large majority (43.33%) of respondents rated assonance in the poem good, 40% very good, 10% excellent, whereas, 6.67% poor.

A large majority (56.67%) of respondents rated repetition of words in the poem good, 30% very good, 3.33% excellent, whereas, 10% poor.

A large majority (56.67%) of the respondents have rated that the rhyme including repetition of similar sounds in two or more words is very good, 26.67% excellent, 10% good, whereas, 6.67% poor.

A large majority (40%) of respondents have rated Simile of the poem as very good, 26.67% good and excellent, respectively, whereas, 6.67% poor.

A large majority (53.33%) of respondents have rated metaphor of the poem as very poor, 30% poor, whereas, 16.67% good.

Hyperbole in the poem was rated very good by 40% of the respondents, good by 33.33%, excellent by 13.33%, whereas, poor by 13.33%.

Tautology in the poem was rated poor by 43.33%, very poor by 40%, whereas, good by 16.67% .

Alliteration in the poem was rated good by 50% of the respondents, very good by 46.67% , whereas, excellent by 3.33% of the respondents.

A large majority (56.67%) of respondents have rated that personification in the poem excellent, 26.67% very good, whereas, 16.67% good.

A large majority (53.33%) of respondents have rated onomatopoeia in the poem as poor, 46.67 very poor, whereas, 6.67% good.

A large majority (43.33%) of respondents have rated that litotes including impact by denying the opposite of what is true in the poem is good, 26.67% have rated that it is very good, 20% have rated that it is poor, whereas, 10% respondents have rated that it is excellent.

A large majority (36.67%) of respondents have rated that oxymoron in the poem as very good, 30% good, whereas, 26.67% excellent, whereas, 6.67% poor.

A large majority (56.67%) of respondents have rated that transferred epithet in the poem as poor, 26.67% good, whereas, 16.67% very poor.

A large majority (46.67%) of respondents have rated that antithesis in the poem as poor, 23.33% very poor, 16.67% good, whereas, 20% very good.

A large majority (56.67%) of respondents have rated that anaphora in the poem is poor, 26.67% very poor, whereas, 16.67% good.

A large majority (46.67%) of respondents have rated that phrase in the poem is good, 26.67% poor, 23.33% very poor, whereas, 10% very good.

A large majority (33.33%) of respondents have rated that paradox in the poem as good, 26.67% very poor, 23.33% poor, whereas, 16.67% very good.

Table 2: Frequencies, percentage, chi-square and responses of the students on the rating scale against various components of Creative Writing on the “PRAKRITI MAHA GRANTH HAI” composed by a student after participatory approach.

Components	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Poor	Very Poor	Chi-Square	df	Level of Significance
1.Organization	22(73.33%)	8(26.67%)	0	0	0	55.54	4	.01
2.Originality	17(56.67%)	10(33.33%)	3(10%)	0	0	31.54	4	.01
3.Richness/ Elaboration	17(56.67%)	11(36.67%)	2(6.67%)	0	0	33.88	4	.01
4.Assonance	20(66.67%)	5(16.67%)	5(16.67%)	0	0	40.54	4	.01
5.Repetition	11(36.67%)	18(60%)	1(3.33%)	0	0	38.88	4	.01
6.Rhyme	17(56.67%)	11(36.67%)	2(6.67%)	0	0	33.88	4	.01
7.Simile	15(50%)	13(43.33%)	2(6.67%)	0	0	31.2	4	.01
8.Metaphor	13(43.33%)	16(53.33%)	1(3.33%)	0	0	35.54	4	.01
9.Hyperbole	11(36.67%)	16(53.33%)	3(10%)	0	0	29.54	4	.01
10.Tautology	10(33.33%)	9(30%)	6(20%)	5(16.67%)	0	8.2	4	NS
11. Alliteration	19(63.33%)	6(20%)	4(13.33%)	1(3.33%)	0	14.88	4	.01
12.Presonification	17(56.67%)	9(30%)	4(13.33%)	0	0	29.88	4	.01
13.Onomatopoeia	9(30%)	16(53.33%)	4(10.33%)	1(3.33%)	0	24.88	4	.01

14.Litotes	11(36.67 %)	16(53.33 %)	3(10%)	0	0	29.54	4	.01
15.Oxymoron	13(43.33 %)	14(46.67 %)	2(6.67%)	1(3.33%)	0	26.88	4	.01
16.Transferred Epithet	7(23.33%)	17(56.67 %)	6(20%)	0	0	28.54	4	.01
17.Antithesis	11(36.67 %)	10(33.33 %)	6(20%)	3(10%)	0	11.54	4	.05
18.Anaphora	10(33.33 %)	10(33.33 %)	7(23.33 %)	2(6.67%)	1(3. 33%)	9.54	4	.05
19.Phrase	11(36.67 %)	7(23.33%)	9(30%)	3(10%)	0	10.54	4	.05
20.Paradox	9(30%)	10(53.33 %)	3(10%)	0	2(6. 67%)	24.2	4	.01

It is evident from Table No.2 that the computed Chi-Square values against the components organization, originality, richness/elaboration, assonance, repetition, rhyme, simile, metaphor, hyperbole, alliteration, personification, onomatopoeia, litotes, oxymoron, transferred epithet, and paradox have been found to be grater than the Table value of Chi-Square of 13.277 against 4 degrees of freedom at .01 level, whereas against components antithesis, anaphora, and phrase at .05 level. So, the null hypotheses that will be no significant different between the observed frequencies and frequencies expected against equal probability is rejected against all these statement against the respective levels. So, the participatory approach of creative composition of poetry has been found to be significantly effective with respect of the all the components of creative writing. The computed Chi-Square

values against the component tautology has been found to be lesser than the corresponding table Chi-Square values against 4 degrees of freedom at .05 level. So, the null hypotheses that there will be no significant difference between the observed frequencies and the frequencies expected against the equal probability is not rejected.

Table 3: Frequencies & percentage responses of the students on the rating scale against various components of Creative Writing on the “PRAKRITI MAHA GRANTH HAP” composed by a student with & without participatory approach.

Components	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Poor	Very Poor
1.Organization (Without PA)	2(6.67%)	25(83.33%)	3(10%)	0	0
1.Organization (With PA)	22(73.33%)	8(26.67%)	0	0	0
2.Originality(Without PA)	11(36.67%)	8(26.67%)	8(26.67%)	3(10%)	0
2.Originality (With PA)	17(56.67%)	10(33.33%)	3(10%)	0	0
3.Richness/ Elaboration(Without PA)	10(33.33%)	11(36.67%)	7(23.33%)	2(6.67%)	0
3.Richness/ Elaboration (With PA)	17(56.67%)	11(36.67%)	2(6.67%)	0	0
4.Assonance	3(10%)	12(40%)	13(43.33%)	2(6.67%)	0

(Without PA)			33%)		
4.Assonance (With PA)	20(66.67 %)	5(16.67%)	5(16.6 7%)	0	0
5.Repetition (Without PA)	1(3.33%)	9(30%)	17(56. 67%)	3(10%)	0
5.Repetition (With PA)	11(36.67 %)	18(60%)	1(3.33 %)	0	0
6.Rhyme (Without PA)	8(26.67%)	17(56.67 %)	3(10%)	2(6.67%)	0
6.Rhyme (With PA)	17(56.67 %)	11(36.67 %)	2(6.67 %)	0	0
7.Simile (Without PA)	8(26.67%)	12(40%)	8(26.6 7%)	2(6.67%)	0
7.Simile (With PA)	15(50%)	13(43.33 %)	2(6.67 %)	0	0
8.Metaphor (Without PA)	0	0	5(16.6 7%)	9(30%)	16(53.33%)
8.Metaphor (With PA)	13(43.33 %)	16(53.33 %)	1(3.33 %)	0	0
9.Hyperbole (Without PA)	4(13.33%)	12(40%)	10(33. 33%)	4(13.33%)	0
9.Hyperbole (With PA)	11(36.67 %)	16(53.33 %)	3(10%)	0	0
10.Tautology	0	0	5(16.6	13(43.33%)	12(40%)

(Without PA)			7 %)		
10.Tautology (With PA)	10(33.33 %)	9(30%)	6(20%)	5(16.67%)	0
11. Alliteration (Without PA)	1(3.3%)	14(46.67 %)	15(50 %)	0	0
11. Alliteration (With PA)	19(63.33 %)	6(20%)	4(13.3 %)	1(3.33%)	0
12.Presonification (Without PA)	17(56.67 %)	8(26.67%)	5(16.6 %)	0	0
12.Presonification (With PA)	17(56.67 %)	9(30%)	4(13.3 %)	0	0
13.Onomatopoeia (Without PA)	0	0	2(6.67 %)	16(53.33%)	12(46.67%)
13.Onomatopoeia (With PA)	9(30%)	16(53.33 %)	4(10.3 %)	1(3.33%)	0
14.Litotes (Without PA)	3(10%)	8(26.67%)	13(43.3 %)	6(20%)	0
14.Litotes (With PA)	11(36.67 %)	16(53.33 %)	3(10%)	0	0
15.Oxymoron (Without PA)	8(26.67%)	11(36.67 %)	9(30%)	2(6.67)	0
15.Oxymoron (With PA)	13(43.33 %)	14(46.67 %)	2(6.67 %)	1(3.33%)	0
16.Transferred Epithet (Without PA)	0	0	8(26.6 %)	17(56.6%)	5(16.67%)

16. Transferred Epithet (With PA)	7(23.33%)	17(56.67%)	6(20%)	0	0
17. Antithesis (Without PA)	0	6(20%)	5(16.67%)	12(46.67%)	7(23.33%)
17. Antithesis (With PA)	11(36.67%)	10(33.33%)	6(20%)	3(10%)	0
18. Anaphora (Without PA)	0	0	5(16.67%)	17(56.67%)	8(26.67%)
18. Anaphora (With PA)	10(33.33%)	10(33.33%)	7(23.33%)	2(6.67%)	1(3.33%)
19. Phrase (Without PA)	0	3(10%)	12(46.67%)	8(26.67%)	7(23.33%)
19. Phrase (With PA)	11(36.67%)	7(23.33%)	9(30%)	3(10%)	0
20. Paradox (Without PA)	0	5(16.67%)	10(33.33%)	7(23.33%)	8(26.67%)
20. Paradox (With PA)	9(30%)	10(53.33%)	3(10%)	0	2(6.67%)

It is evident from Table-3 that Ratings by the respondents on the Rating Scale are significantly greater on the higher points of the Rating Scale with Participatory Approach than without Participatory Approach on all the components of creative composition (1 to 20). So, composition of the Poem- PRAKRITI MAHA GRANTH HAI has been found to more effective with the participatory approach than without participatory approach.

Concluding Remarks-

Beginners were found to face some difficulty to compose a poem using creative writing components, but, progressively they gained a lot in terms of various components of creative composition through participatory approach. There is a dire need to tease the creative faculties of the learners by facilitating participatory approach. Let our silent potent learners realize creative composition & expression.

Reference-

- Auerbach, E. (1992). *Making meaning, making change: Participatory curriculum development for adult ESL literacy*. McHenry, IL and Washington, DC: Delta Systems and Center for Applied Linguistics.
- Bailey, M., et.al. (1995). *The Impact of Integrating Visuals in an Elementary Creative Writing Process*. Retrieved from ERIC Database.
- Bartscher, Mark A, et.al. (2001). *Improving Student's Writing ability through Journals and Creative writing Exercises*: Retrieved from ERIC Database.
- Bush, H. K. (1993). *Poetry and the Teaching of Figurative Language Skills*: Retrieved from ERIC Database.
- Carter, R. & Long, M.N. (1987). *The Web of Words*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Chitambar, S. (1981). *A study of the creative ability, reading interest and creative writing of children in std. VII-IX in selected English medium schools*, A unpublished M. Sc.(Home science) dissertation, Faculty of Family and Community, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara.
- Eliot, TS (1999). "The Function of Criticism". Selected Essays. Faber & Faber. pp. 13–34. ISBN 978-0- 15-180387-3.

- Fingeret, A. (1989). The Social and Historical Context of Participatory Literacy Education. In A. Fingaret and P. Jurmo (Eds.), *Participatory Literacy Education*. (pp.5-15). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. New York: Seabury Press.
- Freire, P. (1985). *The Politics of Education: Culture, Power and Liberation*. MA: Bergin & Garvey Publishers, Inc.
- Giquere, M. (2006). [Thinking as They Create: Do Children Have Similar Experiences in Dance and in Language Arts?](#) Retrieved from ERIC Journal.
- Hollander, John, (1997). [The Work of Poetry](#). Retrieved from ERIC Journal.
- Hughes, J. (2007). *Poetry: A Powerful Medium for Literacy and Technology Development*. The literacy and Numeracy Secretariat, Ontario.
- Joan Franklin Smutny, *Creative Writing For Gifted Students (1-6)*: Illinois Association for Gifted Children Journal, 2002.
- Joseph, K. (2001). *Learning to Educate*. Vadodara: Gold Rock Publication.
- Katrina C.(2013, July16). *Creative Writing*. [Web log Message] Retrieved from <http://custom-research-papers.blogspot.com>
- Longenbach, J. (1997). *Modern Poetry After Modernism*. Oxford University Press. pp. 9, 103. ISBN 0-19-510178-2.
- Magarray, M.L. (2003). Participatory teacher evolution: A vehicle for professional development. (Ph.D. thesis, University of Toronto (Canada). In *Dissertation Abstracts International*, Vol.(63). No.12.
- Newton DP, Newton LD (2009). Some student teachers' conceptions of creativity in school science. *Res. Sci. Technol. Educ.* 27(1): 45-60.
- O' Dell, F. (1998). *English Panorama 2*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Patel, M.F. (2011). *Indian writing in English*. Jaipur: Sunrise Publication.
- Pathak, U.,(1983). Identification of Personality Variables Associated with Creative Writing in Hindi. In M.B. Buch,(Edu.), : *IV Survey of Research in Education*, 1983-88, New Delhi: NCERT.
- Prabhavathamana K. (1987). *An investigation into the creative writing process and identification of the creative writing ability in English, in student-teachers in inter-cultural connotation*. (An unpublished Ph.D. thesis), CASE, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara.
- Qualifications and Curriculum Authority (QCA) (2005). *Creativity: Find it! Promote it!* London: QCA/DFEE.
- Reid, L. (2009). [*Follow the Poet: Poetry in the Montessori Classroom*](#). Retrieved from ERIC Journal.
- Ross, D. (1995). A review of Aurbach's Making Meaning, Making Change: Participatory Curriculum Development of Adult ESL Literacy. *Teaching Language as a Second or Foreign Language*. 1(3), n.p.
- Sachdeva, M.S. (2007). *Teaching of English: Twenty First Century*. Patiala: Patiala Publication.
- Schmidt, M. I, ed. (1999). *The Harvill Book of Twentieth-Century Poetry in English*. Harvill Press. pp. xxvii–xxxiii. ISBN 1-86046-735-0.
- Sharma, R. (2013). *Rashtra Bhasha Hindi Shikshan*. Agara:Radha Publication.
- Spencer, D. (1992). The Freirean Approach to Adult Literacy Education. *Center for Adult English Language Acquisition*. Retrieved from: http://www.cal.org/caela/esl_resources/digests/FREIREQA.html
- Stone, R. (2001). *Teaching Creativity Creatively*: Retrieved from ERIC Database.

- Strachan, John R; Terry, Richard, G (2000). Poetry: an introduction. Edinburgh University
- Sue D. & Janette H.(2009). *How can the medium support pre-service teachers of English in their professional learning about writing poetry and teaching poetry writing in a digital age?* Retrieved from ERIC Database. <http://www.education.waikato.ac.nz/research/files/2009v8n3art6.pdf>.
- Tin, T. B., Manara, C. & Ragawanti, D. T. (2010). [Views on Creativity from an Indonesian Perspective](#): Retrieved from ERIC Journal.
- Webb, P. (2009). [Innovative Writing Instruction: Sophomore Boys and Poetry](#): Retrieved from ERIC Journal.
- Welch, K. D. (2010). [Poetry, Visual Design, and the How-To Manual: Creativity in the Teaching of Technical Writing](#): Retrieved from ERIC Journal.

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Paper-18

**Impact of Socio-Emotional Adjustment on
Academic achievement of Adolescent Girls
in Jammu and Kashmir**

Dr. Showkeen Bilal Ahmad Gul

Impact of Socio-Emotional Adjustment on Academic achievement of Adolescent Girls in Jammu and Kashmir

Dr. Showkeen Bilal Ahmad Gul²⁷

Abstract

The study examined the impact of socio-emotional adjustment on academic achievement of adolescent girls of Jammu and Kashmir. The purpose of the investigation was to study the relationship and effect of socio-emotional adjustment on academic achievement among adolescent girls. The descriptive survey research method was used for the study and the sample of 250 participants were randomly selected from ten higher secondary schools. The socio-emotional adjustment scale developed by Najam and Simeen (1991) adopted and revised by the investigator, and the academic achievement of previous year examination was used. The finding of the study revealed that: (1) there is a positive and significant correlation between socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement of adolescent girls; (2) The socio-emotional adjustment of adolescent girls has a significant effect on their academic achievement; and (3) there was significant difference between rural and urban adolescent girls in their socio-emotional adjustment.

Key words: Impact, Socio-emotional, Adjustment and Academic Achievement

Introduction-

Jammu & Kashmir State is one of the disputed States of India. It is also well known as paradise on the earth is the northern state of India with population more than one crore as per Census 2011 and covers the area of approximately 2,22,236 sq. Kms (Ahmad Gul and Khan, 2014). The J&K has three regions namely,

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Kashmir, Jammu and Ladakh and further divided into 22 districts for administration and carrying out developmental programmes. The J&K has its own Constitution besides the Constitution of India and adores the special status under article 370. Topography of the State comes in the way of rising satisfactory infrastructure and is further compounded by armed conflict and militancy, which have taken a heavy toll of life and public property besides throwing normal life out of gear (Ahmad Gul and Khan, 2014). Education system could not run away from this calamity as most of the schools and colleges in urban and rural areas were destroyed and loss of schooling hours enormously affected the learning outcomes. Girl's education could not run from this calamity. As, most of the parents restrain their daughter from getting education, because of their physical security. Especially girls are forced to stop education, when they reached to puberty or adolescence period.

Adolescence period of life is one of the crucial stages of life which needs proper care and development. This stage of life is very sensitive as the children lack decision making powers because of their being underdeveloped (Adams & Bennion, 1990). Girl children are not aware of the real life situations. At this juncture of life, proper counselling and guidance to the girl children is the need of the hour. The period of adolescence is a very critical period of life. The problems of adolescents, which if not addressed properly, will lead our adolescents to psychological disturbance, mental imbalance and physical disorders (Berndt & Keefe, 1995).

The families in general and parents in particular, have often been deemed to be the most important support system available to the girl child. The strongest factor in moulding a girl child's personality is his relationship with his parents (Mohanraj & Latha 2005). The family in its most common forms is a lifelong commitment

between man and women who feed, shelter and nurture their children until they reach maturity. It is a primary socialization context and is, therefore, considered to be a very important factor influencing child development (Ozcinar, 2006). Family members are very important for survival, thus, strong emotional bonds evolved to foster long term commitment among parents, children and other relatives. The experience that the adolescent girls gain from the family decide the future adjustment of adolescent girl within society and her peer group which eventually reflect the social maturity of adolescent girls (Unisa, 1995). Family environment continues to be of crucial importance throughout adolescence and young adulthood (Van Wel, 2000). Because of the important role of psychological functioning for youngsters' daily lives and their further social adaptation, it is apparently relevant to study the effect of the family environment on the emotional adjustment of adolescents (Mc Farlane et al. 1994). During adolescence, well-being decreases and psychological problems increase.

One of the aspects that play a pertinent role in promoting adolescents healthy development is socio-emotional development. It reflects an individual's well-being in emotions, personality, relationships with other people and within the social contexts (Bronstein, et al, 1993). In studying developmental psychology, the emotion domain should not be viewed as interdependent from the social domain. Putting these two domains together, socialization is achieved through communication which loaded with emotions; meanwhile, adolescent girls adjust their relationships with others to fulfil the emotion needs. Being a socio emotional competent individual was found to engage fewer in defiant activities, antisocial and misconduct behaviour (Jewell & Stark, 2003). Hence, it is deemed necessary to focus on healthy growth and development of adolescents to produce socially and emotionally well-adjusted young generation. As socio emotional maladjustments

have been notoriously hard to treat, there is a growing attention on prevention and early intervention. Socio-emotional adjustment is on the main factor in academic achievement.

The term “achievement” refers to indicate the degree of level of success attained in some general and specified area. It represents to the acquirement of knowledge as skills and may imply ability to make appropriate use of such knowledge or skill in a variety of present and future situations. Achievement is an end prudent of learning and its level and performance are affected by various conditions existing at the time of learning and its use (Mohanraj & Latha, 2005). It has been a matter of concern since long and its prediction has assumed enormous in view of its practical effective value. Attempts have been made to identify the main determinants of achievement, which led to the studies involving both socio-emotional variables. Academic achievement is not a uni-dimensional function but a multidimensional activity. In other words, academic achievement has to be studied in terms of Psychological correlates in order to identify the factors which are important in affecting the academic achievement at school level among girls.

Objectives of the Study-

1. To study the relationship between socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement of adolescent girls.
2. To determine the effect of socio-emotional adjustment on academic achievement of adolescent girls.
3. To study the difference between rural and urban adolescent girls in their socio-emotional adjustment.

Hypotheses-

1. There exists no relationship between socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement of adolescent girls.
2. There exists no significant contribution of socio-emotional adjustment to academic achievement of adolescent girls.
3. There exists no difference between rural and urban adolescent girls in their socio-emotional adjustment.

Method and Sample-

Descriptive survey method was used by the investigator to collect the relevant information for the research. In the present study the sample consisted of 250 adolescent girls (144 rural girls and 106 urban girls) selected through stratified random sampling technique. Whereas, for the data collection, investigator used the scale developed by Najam and Simeen (1991) adopted and revised by the investigator and the academic achievement of previous year examination.

Results and Interpretation-

The data was analyzed by used statistical techniques like, Pearson's product moment correlation, linear regression and t test.

1. Relationship between Socio-Emotional Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Adolescent Girls.

Results pertaining to relationship between socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement of adolescent girls have been shown in table 1

Table 1

Variables	N	Mean	S.D	Correlation Value	Significance level
Academic Achievement	250	55.94	3.47	.625*	0.00
Socio-emotional Adjustment					

		71.12	13.63		
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Interpretation-

It is revealed from table 1 that the value of mean for academic achievement of adolescent girls turned out to be 55.94, whereas their mean for socio-emotional adjustment is 80.37 respectively. After calculating the mean, the coefficient of correlation was calculated to find the relationship among the variables. The value of correlation turned out to be 0.625 which interprets that there is a significant and high positive correlation between the socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement as significance value calculated by using SPSS is 0.00. This makes clear that the socio-emotional adjustment have a significant positive relationship with academic achievement, which indicates that the relationship is real and meaningful. Thus hypothesis No.1 that “there exists no relationship between socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement of adolescent girls” is rejected.

2. Predicting Academic Achievement by Socio-Emotional Adjustment of adolescent girls.

Results pertaining to the effect of socio-emotional adjustment to academic achievement of adolescent girls have been shown in table 2

The linear regression analysis of academic achievement (dependent) to socio-emotional adjustment (independent variable) was made. Table 2 presents the regression analysis suggested by the model.

The analysis in table 2 shows a regression coefficient (R) of 0.625, which suggests a relation between independent variable (socio-emotional adjustment) and dependent variable (academic achievement). The coefficient of determination (R^2) of .391 indicates that 39.10% of the observed variability in academic achievement of adolescent girls is explained by the independent variable (Socio-emotional adjustment).

Table 2: Model Summary^a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.625	.391	.388	.388
Predictor: (constant) Socio-emotional Adjustment				
Dependent variable: Academic Achievement				

Table 2.1: ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	304665.77	1	304665.77	159.17	.000 ^a
	Residual	474672.12	248	1914.00		
	Total	779337.90	249			

Predictor: (constant) Socio-emotional Adjustment

Dependent variable: Academic Achievement

The ANOVA test in table 2.1 shows an F value of 159.17, and strong significance level of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) indicates that the regression model is statistically significant, valid and fit; and could be used to predict the dependent variable- Academic Achievement. Thus hypothesis No.2 that “there exists no significant contribution of socio-emotional adjustment to academic achievement of adolescent girls” is rejected.

The tolerance value of less than 0.20 or 0.10 suggests a multicollinearity problem. In table 2.3, the independent variable have tolerance value greater than 0.20 which shows that the tolerance is moderate and good. Furthermore, as shown in the same table, Socio-emotional adjustment have significant influence towards academic achievement ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2.3: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics
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		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1		165.43	14.72		11.23	.000		
	Home Environment	2.56	.203	.625	12.61	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement

3. Comparison between the rural and urban adolescent girls in their socio-emotional adjustment.

Results pertaining to study the significant difference between the rural and urban adolescent girls in their socio-emotional adjustment have been shown in table 3.

Table 3

Socio-emotional Adjustment	N	Mean	S.D	SEd	t-value	Significance
Rural Adolescent Girls	144	70.45	15.47	1.28	7.10	0.01
Urban Adolescent Girls	106	102.06	10.65	1.03		

***Significant at 0.01 level of significance**

Interpretation-

The table 3 depicts that the difference between the mean scores of rural and urban adolescent girls in their socio-emotional is very high that is (70.45) and (102.06) respectively .The urban adolescent girls (102.06) shows high socio-emotional adjustment as compared to rural adolescent girls (70.45). Therefore the hypothesis No.3 that is, “there exists no difference between rural and urban adolescent girls in their socio-emotional adjustment” is rejected.

Discussion and Conclusion-

An insight into the investigation about the impact of socio-emotional adjustment on academic achievement of adolescent girls of Jammu and Kashmir, it can be deduced that there is positive and significant relationship between socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement in adolescent girls. Because, adolescence period is a time of growth, development and change. The teens are developed emotionally and socially as well as physically. This development may seem seamless, but there are distinct things happening in teenager's social and emotional development that are helping them become who they are going to be - helping them to form their identity. Social and emotional changes are part of girl child's academic achievement in the schools. Parents have a big role to play in helping girl children to develop grown-up emotions and social skills. The present study focused on the association between socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement. Contributing to a growing body of research showing a significant impact of socio-emotional adjustment on academic success, results show significant correlation between socio-emotional adjustment and academic achievement. The literature has consistently suggested that academic achievement is associated with socio-emotional adjustment (Masten et al., 1995). The results of the present study further indicated that, urban adolescent girls having high socio-emotional adjustment as compared to rural adolescent girls. It is because urban girls having lot of exposure towards modern technological and scientific world. The parent belonged to urban areas showing good support and care towards their daughter as compared to rural areas, which leads them towards proper socio-emotional adjustment.

References-

- Adams GR, Bennion, D. P. (1990). *Parent-adolescent relationships and identity formation*. Parent-Adolescent Relationships. Lanham MD: University Press of America, pp. 1-6.

- Ahmad Gul, S.B & Khan. Z. (2013). Interventions For Promoting Gender Equity At Elementary Education Level In South Kashmir: An Evaluative Study, *International Refereed Research Journal*, Vol.– IV, Issue–3, July 2013 [130].
- Berndt T. J., & Keefe, K. (1995). Friends influence on adolescents adjustment to school. *Child Dev*, 66: 1312-1329.
- Bronstein, P., Fitzgerald, M., Briones, M., & Pieniadz J. (1993). Family emotional expressiveness as a predictor of early adolescent social and psychological adjustment. *The Journal of Early Adolescence*, 13: 448- 471.
- Jewell, JD. & Stark, KD. (2003). Comparing the family environments of adolescents with conduct disorder or depression. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 12: 77–89.\
- Lengua, L.J., et al. (2000). The additive and interactive effects of parenting and temperament in predicting adjustment problems of children of divorce. *Journal of Clinical Child Psychology*, 29: p. 232-244.
- Masten, A., Coatsworth, J. D., Neemann, J., Gest, S. D., Tellegen, A., & Garmezy, N. (1995). The structure and coherence of competence from childhood through adolescence. *Child Development*, 66, 1635- 1659.
- Mohanraj, R. & Latha (2005). Perceived family environment in relation to adjustment and academic achievement. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 31: 18-23.
- Najam, N., & Simeen, A. (1991). Comparative study of social and emotional development of children living in orphanages in SOS villages and children living with parents. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological research*, Vol. 23, No. 3-4, 93-105.

- Ozcinar, Z. (2006). The instructional communicative qualification of parents with students. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences, 1: 24-30.*
- Santrock, J.W. (2008). *Adolescence.* New York: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- Unisa, S. (1995). Demographic profile of the girl child in India. *Journal of Social Change, 25: 30-37.*
- Van Wel, F. (2000). The parental bond and the well-being of adolescents and young adults. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence, 28: 307-318.*

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Paper-19

**Role of Education in Knowledge-based
Economy**

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Role of Education in Knowledge-Based Economy

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Omid Arad²⁹

Abstract

Many institutions and organizations recently have identified knowledge as a factor of production, main driver of growth, creation of wealth and employment and considered its role in global competitions as an important factor. Knowledge reaches its full capacity when it can create economic value when organizational procedures and processes are included and internalized in products. Knowledge-based economy is also created through training in persons. For this reason, human capital is an essential and valuable element in Knowledge-based economy. To create suitable human capital, it is necessary to invest in education, research and development. It should be noted that suitable manpower in knowledge-based economy is a person who has been trained based on needs of market. Therefore, considering that role of education in knowledge-based development strategy is important, this paper tries to elaborate relationship between education and knowledge-based economy.

Key words: Education, knowledge-based economy

Introduction-

Schools and universities are always regarded as one of the main bases of strategic plans of the countries. Their fair frequency distribution in different regions not only increases prosperity of the research and training of efficient and creative forces based on entrepreneurship along with scientific and technical skills but also reduces excessive immigrations and localization of different sciences and develops

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society with increasing scientific and educational awareness level. In this regard, it has cultured entrepreneurs in addition to employment and job opportunities in different levels.

The third millennium is called knowledge era. Thus, speed of knowledge production and scientific research along with its applicability proves caused considerable changes in new era civilization. Since human as the most valuable capital assumes serious tasks in development trend in the present changing society and educational centers in the countries should train efficient manpower. It is necessary that the educational pacemakers necessarily utilize all potential and actual forces through deliberation and awareness with trend of affairs in university and solving its problems. The term "knowledge-based economy" was first raised by economic organization of the developing countries (APEC) and indicates the important role of knowledge and technology in economy in the past two decades and it can be said that it refers to two features of new economy. Knowledge economic resources depend on skill level of labor force and human capital. Commercial interest resulting from application of knowledge gives new round of innovation and absorption of knowledge by sending feedback for knowledge production.

Therefore, it can be said that investment in human capital through education, state protective policies, information and communication technology, the presence of suitable social, political, economic and legal environment for investment and production and trading are the prerequisites of knowledge-based economy.

What is knowledge-based economy?

According to OECD, knowledge-based economy is the economy which has been directly formed based on production, distribution and utilization of knowledge and information (OECD, 2001). In knowledge-based economy, knowledge is the main

driver of growth, creation of wealth and employment in all fields of activities. Based on this definition, knowledge-based economy only depends on limited number of industries based on very advanced technology but all economic activities are based on knowledge in this type of economy. Even activities such as mine and agriculture are called old economy. The required knowledge for construction of knowledge-based economy is not of technology and pure type and also includes cultural, social and managerial knowledge (Vahidi, 2001).

Specifications of knowledge-based economy-

- All sections of economy are knowledge –intensive.
- In knowledge-based economy, there is the attitude that knowledge and information are the sources which belong to the public.
- Cheap labor force doesn't determine advantage of knowledge-based economy.
- This type of economy is flexible against rapid changes of knowledge.
- Knowledge-based economy has knowledge-based companies.
- In knowledge-based economy, industry is also knowledge-based.
- In knowledge-based economy, a resource is able to perform all types of services.

Main processes in knowledge-based economy-

Processes of knowledge production, knowledge distribution, transfer and application are four main processes in knowledge-based economies. Volume and manner of relation of these processes differentiate between modern economies and traditional economies. In traditional economies, volume of these processes is low and their relation is linear. It means that knowledge is first produced and then distributed and transferred and finally used. There is no direct relationship between use of knowledge and production but a unilateral indirect relationship has been formed due to knowledge transfer which doesn't assure any dynamicity.

Source:(Heng& Other, 2002)

In knowledge-based economy, the first three processes interact with each other to form knowledge and expand it and the fourth process deals with consumption of industries and modern economic sections. In fact, dynamicity of the fourth process and its interaction with the first three processes indicate emergence and development of knowledge-based economy. Knowledge flows through two channels from knowledge process to knowledge distribution and conversion. The knowledge which flows to the conversion process flows into process of knowledge use after enrichment. The knowledge which flows to distribution process is disseminated among people in society through different educational levels.

Knowledge-based economy has feedback flows from knowledge that is knowledge also flows from other processes to knowledge production process. In fact, one of the main channels of knowledge flow is knowledge flow from production process.

The knowledge which flows in this channel is the knowledge related to issues of

the utilization process. This flow is dynamicity of economic system and differentiates between traditional economies and knowledge-based economies (Emadzadeh and Shahnazi, 2007).

Measurement indices of knowledge-based economy-

Two important indices for size of knowledge-based economy have been presented as follows:

A: knowledge-based economy index (APEC): knowledge-based economy provided by APEC includes four main parts of knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge learning, knowledge dissemination and knowledge application. It is evident that knowledge creation is specified based on system of national innovations, knowledge acquisition and learning by developing human resources , knowledge dissemination considering infrastructures of ICT and knowledge application considering business environment(APEC , 2001).

Table 1- Components of APEC’s knowledge-based economy index

<p>B- knowledge acquisition and learning</p> <p>1- Share of technology import out of total import</p> <p>2- FDI percent from GDP</p> <p>3- Size of knowledge-based commercial services</p>	<p>A- Knowledge creation</p> <p>1- R&D expenditure percent from GDP</p> <p>2- per capita of researchers</p> <p>3- patent per capita</p>
<p>D- Knowledge application</p> <p>1- Percent of labor force with academic educational level</p> <p>2- percent of knowledgeable labor force to total labor force</p>	<p>C- knowledge dissemination</p> <p>1- ICT expenditure percent from GDP</p> <p>2- Cost of access to internet through per capita</p> <p>3- labor force percent with education</p>

3- rate of entrepreneurs

below the second educational level

B- Knowledge assessment methodology: World Bank has presented an index as Knowledge Assessment Methodology which includes five main parts of economic performance, economic incentives and institutional regime, education and human resources, innovation system and information infrastructures (World Bank,1998). Subsections of this index are given briefly in Table 2.

Table 2- Components of Knowledge Assessment Methodology of World Bank

B- economic incentives and institutional regimes Tariff and non-tariff barriers Quality of order Laws and regulations	A- Performance indicator Average Annual growth of GDP Human development index
D- innovation system Per capita of researchers for 1 million people Patent per capita for 1 million people scientific and technical articles and journals for 1 million people	C- Educational and human resources Literacy rate of adults above 15 years Enrollment in the second educational level Enrollment in the third educational level
	D: Information infrastructures Telephone per capita in 1000 persons Computer per capita in 1000 persons Per capita of internet users in 10000 persons

Knowledge-based economy and education-

As observed in the above Table, education has been considered in measurement of knowledge-based economy as index. Therefore, education and higher education are regarded as the main infrastructures of development in any country. For this reason, issues of education have been considered by decision makers and planners. Missions of schools and university are so extensive that they cannot be regarded as a segmental activity. For example, the following cases can be mentioned as follows:

- Education mission related to value system of society
- Education mission for production and enrichment of knowledge and culture of country
- Education mission for training of specialized human resources in the country
- Education mission for accelerating and facilitating economic , social and cultural development process of the country
- Education mission for creating and facilitating establishment of scientific , cultural , political and economic relations in regional and international level

Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to education in planning system of countries and to provide necessary space, equipment and financial resources as far as possible beyond other sections and solve its problems and bottlenecks faster than other sections.

Conclusion-

Education and investment in human capital is a long-term investment without which knowledge-based economy will be unstable. In a developed economy, extensive provision of qualitative educational services is the main priority of society without which other elements of national knowledge bases such as research and development cannot achieve the required level. In knowledge-based economy, science and technology, innovation and entrepreneurship are

the main elements of economy all rooted in accumulation of knowledge. For this reason, it can be said that knowledge has become more important quantitatively and qualitatively. In other words, drive of economic growth in knowledge –based economy, production of new knowledge through research, its transfer through education and skill learning, its dissemination through information and communication technology and use through technological innovation. Therefore, schools and universities can play considerable role in performance of these processes through industrial cooperation and reproductive companies, education and skill learning particularly creation of human capital.

References-

- Vahidi, Pridokht(2001), knowledge –based economy and role of research and development in it ; conference on challenges and visions of development in Iran, Tehran. March 2002.
- APEC (2000) Toward Knowledge Based Economies in APEC, November <http://www.apecses.org.sg/pubs/freepubs.html#2000>
- OECD (2001) Sciences, Technology and Industry scoreboard, Paris:OECD
- Emadzadeh, Mostafa, Shahnazi, Roohollah(2007). Studying fundamentals and indices of knowledge –based economy and its place in selected countries compared with Iran. Journal of Economics Science. Winter 2008. No. 27.

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Paper-20

**Teaching in the Knowledge Age:
Challenges for Teachers and Schools of
India**

Dr. Sutapa Bose

Teaching in the Knowledge Age: Challenges for Teachers and Schools of India

Dr. Sutapa Bose³⁰

Abstract

The onus is on the schools and therefore on teachers to develop knowledge workers capable of functioning effectively in a knowledge society. This article argues that for this expectation to be considered as realistic, a close examination of two aspects is warranted. One comprises the way teachers are prepared for shouldering this responsibility by teacher education institutions. The other comprises the realities that beset the situation within which the teaching-learning processes of schools are embedded. In the perspective of these aspects, the article first underlines the competencies required by knowledge workers and then articulates the pedagogies suitable for fostering them. Thereafter it critically views pre-service teacher education programmes of India in terms of their approach to teacher preparation. Next it focuses on India's school based realities in terms of their suitability for the adoption of the pedagogies relevant to a knowledge society. Subsequently it infers that these aspects pose serious challenges to the instructional procedures, required in a knowledge society school.

Key words: knowledge society competencies; schools; challenges; teacher education; school based realities

Introduction-

In a knowledge society knowledge base doubles every year (UNESCO, -2002) and information, ideas and knowledge gain importance over land, labour and capital, the mainstay of the industrial age. Therefore, information and knowledge are at the

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centre of economic growth and development and the ability to produce and use information effectively is vital for knowledge workers (OECD, 2000e). The knowledge society is also highly interrelated and interdependent since it is shaped by Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) (Pons, 2010) that supports the flow of information across interrelated structures, permeating geographical boundaries. The characteristics and accordingly the needs of a knowledge society are thus different from that of the industrial society.

A school being a societal agency, the societal context determines its practices. Consequently the onus lies on schools to develop future knowledge workers with grounding in practices like reflection, innovation and collaboration (New Zealand Council for Educational Research, 2009). India's National Knowledge Commission in its Report to the Nation (2006) also says that knowledge workers will be developed in today's educational institutions, especially schools. Hence, educational systems, especially those operating at the foundation level need to be manned by teachers competent to teach children to advance knowledge (Moreno, 2005; Tan Hung & Scardamalia, 2006). Educational systems around the world are therefore under increasing pressure to use the new information and communication technologies (ICTs) to teach students the knowledge and skills they need in the 21st century and function in an information rich, dynamic environment (UNESCO,2002). Education in fact has to be aligned with the factors that determine the socio-economic productivity in a knowledge society (UNESCO, 2011).

Educational practices during the knowledge age are therefore not supposed to be the same as that during the industrial age (Tuomi, 2008; UNESCO, 2002) and teachers need to shift towards teaching-learning processes that are in the context of the knowledge society needs. This calls for an identification of the competencies to

be developed in children of the knowledge age and the pedagogies that are suitable for developing them so as to structure teaching-learning processes in schools. There is also the necessity to critically view the preparedness of teachers as well as the realities that beset the situation in which teaching-learning processes are embedded vis a vis the pedagogies to be adopted. In the perspective of these prerequisites, this article underlines the competencies required in a knowledge society and the pedagogies suitable for developing them. Following a critical view of teacher preparation and the situation commonly prevailing in schools, it underscores the challenges to the teaching - learning procedures required in a knowledge society.

Competencies required in a knowledge society-

Children need to learn to advance knowledge with processes like theorizing, inventing, innovating and designing in collaborative way (Moreno, 2005; Tan, Hung & Scardamalia., 2006) and as future knowledge workers they need to develop abilities like autonomy, innovation, lifelong learning, abilities for collaboration and use of technology for creating shared understanding (Drucker, 1999; Tan, Hung & Scardimalia, 2006). As collaboration gains significance over competition and individualised functioning in the knowledge age, Stasz (2000, as cited in OECD, 2000e) says that there is a strong need for interpersonal skills for effective team work, ability to collaborate for pursuing common objectives, leadership abilities; intrapersonal skills with the motivation and the ability to learn, problem solving skills, capacity for effective communication, analyzing information; and technological or ICT skills. ICT skills are indispensable because ICT mediated interconnectedness is central to a knowledge society. Therefore, the competencies required in the knowledge age include technical capabilities. For example, the competence for collaboratively creating and sharing knowledge

assumes ICT use for these processes and that too in ethical and legally correct ways. India's national policy on ICT in schools (2012) also envisions ICT use for carrying out the functions required in a knowledge society.

The vision of India's national policy on ICT in schools is that "the youth is prepared to participate creatively in the establishment, sustenance and growth of knowledge society leading to socioeconomic development of the nation and global competitiveness" (p.3). In order to fulfill the vision, the Policy has many requirements like optimum utilization of ICT for collaborative activities leading to the creation and sharing of localized and digitized resources, the development of professional networks of teachers, resource persons and schools to catalyse and support resource sharing, continuing education of teachers and for providing support to students. Since the competencies to be built are those required in a knowledge society and ICT use is conceptualized in the back drop of the knowledge society needs, the national policy of India and the UNESCO (2002; 2011) documents are fundamentally similar in respect of the competencies required and the rationale of ICT use in schools.

Pedagogies for developing knowledge society competencies-

Education is traditionally conceptualized as an instructional process that leads to individualized knowledge acquisition, devoid of the social context. The instructional process mainly comprises transmission of information in situations that lack authentic contexts with real world problems. However, in a knowledge society the focus of education needs to be on learning as development of human capabilities that are fundamentally social and socio-technical where innovation, knowledge creation and communication are the key to individual as well as social development, against the tradition of transmitting knowledge into the minds of the learners followed during the industrial age (Tuomi, 2008). The social and socio-

technical contexts with learner engagement being central to knowledge construction, ICT use that can draw in the social context into educational processes through technology enabled interactions, discussions and collaborative processes, is naturally crucial. The UNESCO (2002) also considers the traditional approach to teaching and learning unsuitable in the present age and refers to the tradition of teaching through lectures as the factory model of education whereby huge numbers of learners are prepared for low skilled jobs by teachers who act as knowledge repositories and are transmitters of information for filling up the deficits in knowledge. In the knowledge age, education needs to overcome such 'mind-as-container' metaphor and acknowledge the capability of mind of sustaining knowledgeable, intelligent behaviour without amassing information and the need for knowledge building along with learning (Bereiter, 2002). Thus there is an epistemological shift as knowledge is no longer considered as a fixed product for filling minds through didactic linear transmission but is conceived as a dynamic entity which is continually constructed and reconstructed through experience (Dewey, 2015). Pons says that traditional education causes educational engineering, whereby learning is conceived as a closed, manipulable and evaluable process and teachers have all the authority and responsibility for education, while the constructivist view of learning sets a different educational culture with initiative and authority being shared by teaching staff and students for knowledge construction. Therefore, learner centered pedagogies that engage learners in activities for collaboratively accessing, selecting, organizing, processing, presenting, sharing and creating knowledge are required in the knowledge age. ICT has to be integrated into teaching-learning processes comprising these activities by teachers of all disciplines instead of the computer teacher teaching computer skills and the rest teaching traditionally the other subjects.

As per UNESCO (2002) in a technology based globalised economy, there is a need to shift from traditional approach of teaching and learning towards learner centered approaches that employ the new digital technologies for creating learning environments in which students are engaged learners, able to take greater responsibility for their own learning and construct knowledge as an integrative and contextualised process. This calls for pedagogies that as per the UNESCO create a constructivist environment with learning communities comprised of students, teachers and experts and learners, who can provide multiple perspectives and learners negotiate meaning and develop shared understandings. The constructivist learning environment also emphasizes authentic assessment of learning rather than the traditional paper/pencil test. During this type of teaching-learning activities, learners refer to various sources of information, digital as well as human through ICT enabled networks, apart from their teachers.

The learner centered pedagogies require ICT use to help learners access vast knowledge resources, collaborate with others, consult with experts, share knowledge, and solve complex problems using cognitive tools and also provide learners with powerful new tools to represent their knowledge with text, images, graphics, and video (UNESCO, 2002). This is distinctly different from ICT use in traditional approaches. ICT use in such cases only supports the transmission. This method only alters the source of information and replaces the teacher with a technology and this kind of use encourages individualised learning, failing to tap the potential of technology for interactive and collaborative learning (Laurillard, 1993; 2000; Oliver & Herrington, 2003). Therefore it is not enough to shift to ICT from chalk and the blackboard while retaining traditional pedagogies but there is a need for the recognition of the potential of ICT, which as per Dias (1999); Jarvela, Hakkarainen, Lipponen, & Lehtinen (2001) can support collaborative

knowledge construction. For example, Web 2.0 technologies if effectively deployed can enhance learning experiences, and deepen levels of learners' engagement and collaboration within digital learning environments (Boulos, Inocencio, & Wheeler, 2006) as the sociability aspects of Web 2.0 tools built through their social soft wares make them ideal for supporting conversational interaction, feedback and social networking in educational processes (McLoughlin & Lee, 2007).

Teacher preparation and the ground realities of schools-

The expectation that teachers adopt constructivist pedagogies using ICT can be considered as realistic only when teacher preparation is in sync with it and the ground realities are not contrary to it.

Teacher preparation-

Didactic practices are common in teacher education institutions (Scott, 2008). The National Curriculum Framework for teacher Education (NCFTE), (2009) of India too expresses concern over the prevalence of didactic approaches during teacher education. Since teachers teach the way they have been taught (Bigge & Hunt, 1980; Hargreaves, 2003) unless teacher education programmes switch over to the pedagogies they expect teacher to adopt in knowledge age schools, it is unlikely that teachers prepared through behaviouristic approaches would be actually in a position to practice pedagogies for situated learning, reflective practices, problem solving and other such knowledge construction processes.

Teachers are also expected to use ICT for teaching and pre-service teacher education programmes are supposed to prepare them for it. The UNESCO (2002) recommends that ICT be infused into the entire teacher education programme in order to enable teachers to develop the ability to integrate ICT. It is also strongly critical of attempting to develop such abilities through an isolated course on ICT.

UNESCO (2011) therefore conceptualizes ICT competencies in the context of the major activities carried out by teachers. The ability to use ICT is thus to be developed through ICT use while applying concepts learnt to complex and real-world problems, accessing, managing and communicating information, integrating appropriate tools, applications, digital resources and networks and managing own learning. Development of ICT skills is thus integrated with the development of other skills. However in India the approach has been to teach courses on educational technology with lectures on technology during pre-service teacher education, while the curriculum is transacted through traditional approaches. The UNESCO (2002) labels it as teaching for ICT rather than through ICT and considers it as an approach of limited use for preparing teachers to effectively integrate ICT in teaching.

Reasonable access to ICTs is also important for the acquisition of competence with hardware and soft ware (UNESCO, 2002) but even when these facilities are available they may be confined to the educational technology cell of teacher education institutions while teaching and learning may be carried out in classrooms through didactic means. Hence, it is questionable whether teachers are prepared as knowledge workers.

School based realities-

Conduciveness of the working condition is crucial for adopting the pedagogic shift required in knowledge society schools. However, Indian classrooms have constraints that are potent to impede the adoption of these practices. For instance, classrooms often have a high student–teacher ratio (Jha, 2012) in-spite of the Right to Education mandate on this aspect. There are also infrastructural inadequacies (Dhar, 2012). The constraints imposed by infrastructural inadequacies get compounded with limited access to technology. Students and teachers must have

sufficient access to digital technologies and the Internet in their classrooms and schools and ICTs will improve learning very little if teachers and students have only rare and occasional access to the tools for learning and high quality, meaningful, and culturally responsive digital content must be available for teachers and learners (UNESCO, 2002). Although India's National policy of ICT use in schools requires that access to ICT in schools be enhanced but a school bereft of basic infrastructure is unlikely to possess the ICT required including internet. This assumption is not based merely on the common perception of Indian schools but on the report (Internet Live Stats, 2014) on India's low Internet penetration and internet facilities not being widely available. Even when it is available, the speed is often too less for teaching-learning activities involving data sharing in various modes and media. This is because India's broadband penetration is very low and even in terms of information and communications technology (ICT) access, its use and its skills, India ranks 129th among 166 countries and against the target of achieving 175 million broadband connections by 2017, only 85.74 million have been achieved with the current download speed of only 512 kbps (Business Standard, April 18, 2015). It is not difficult to make out that schools still grappling for adequate infrastructure and trained teachers are not likely to be close to high speed broadband facilities and teachers capable of integrating ICT for teaching.

Conclusions-

The competencies required in a knowledge society are different from that of an industrial age and since ICT catalyses the creation and sustenance of a knowledge society, the needs of a knowledge society are better fulfilled through activities involving ICT use. Hence, behaviouristic approaches are to be replaced with constructivist pedagogies that utilise ICT. This expectation however demands readiness of teachers and of the situation in which they function.

As far as teacher preparation is concerned, the concerns expressed by the NCFTE over the didactic pedagogic approaches adopted during teacher education indicate that teachers are nurtured within a behaviourist environment but are expected to practice a radically different approach comprising constructivist pedagogies. Teachers' inability to make this transition is reflected from reports (Chhapih 2013; Gohain 2014; Planning Commission, [Government of India] 2013) of Indian students resorting to rote learning, which is contrary to the expectations of knowledge age instructional procedures. The UNESCO (2002) recommendation to infuse ICT in the entire teacher education curriculum is also still undermined in favour of the much criticised approach of isolating ICT knowledge from the rest of the curriculum. This raises questions about teacher preparation for ICT use for supporting constructivism in schools.

The infrastructural inadequacies of schools and the non compliance with the mandated student teacher ratio leading to crowded classrooms in many schools are also not conducive for practising constructivist approaches. Further the absence of adequate computers, internet and broadband facilities at schools makes the demand for ICT mediated teaching and learning unrealistic. At present, the country is nowhere near meeting the target for a service considered almost a basic necessity in many developed countries regarding access to broadband and there is an urgent need to review present policies, the current state of implementation of building infrastructure required for penetration of broadband, the means and the supporting software/apps that will provide the content (Business Standard, April 18, 2015).

In view of the way teachers are being prepared and the inadequate access to technology, the vision of schools developing knowledge workers seems to be removed from ground realities. Unless there are serious and sustained efforts to

overcome these twin challenges to instructional processes, the need for developing knowledge workers could be hard to fulfill.

References-

- Bereiter, C. (2002). *Education and mind in the knowledge age*. USA: Routledge.
- Bigge, M. L., & Hunt, M. P. (1980). *Psychological foundations of education*. New York: Harper & Row Publishers.
- Boulos, M.N.K., Inocencio M. I. & Wheeler, S. (2006). Wikis, Blogs and Podcasts: New Generation of Web-based Tools for Virtual Collaborative Clinical Practice and Education. *BMC Medical Education* 2006, 6:41.doi:10.1186/1472-6920-6-41.
- *Business Standard* (April 18, 2015). India ranks below Bhutan & Sri Lanka in broadband penetration: TRAI. http://www.business-standard.com/article/economy-policy/india-ranks-below-bhutan-sri-lanka-in-broadband-penetration-trai-115041700839_1.html
- Chhapiyah. H. (June1, 2013).India chickens out of international students assessment programme again. *The Times of India*.
- Dewey, J. (1915). *Democracy and Education*. Delhi: Akar Books Publication.
- Dias, B.L. (1999). *Integrating Technology some things you should know*. ISTE - L&L 27 (3). Retrieved from <http://www.dirkdavis.net/cbu/etc520/resources/Integrating%20Technology.pdf> on 15th June,2010.
- Dhar, A. (2012, April5). Lack of school infrastructure makes a mockery of RTE. *The Hindu*. Retrieved on 15th June, 2013from <http://www.thehindu.com/news/national/article3281720.ece>

- Gohain, M.P. (6 March, 2014). [CCE has improved scores, not teaching](#). New Delhi: *The Times of India*.
- Hargreaves, A. (2003). *Teaching in the knowledge society: education in the age of insecurity*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- *Internet Live Stats* (2014). Elaboration of data by International Telecommunication Union (ITU), United Nations Population Division, Internet & Mobile Association of India (IAMAI), World Bank. www.InternetLiveStats.com
- Jarvela, S., Hakkarainen, K., Lipponen, L. & Lehtinen, E. (2001). Creating Computer Supported
- Collaborative Learning in Finnish Schools: Research Perspectives on Sociocognitive Effects. *International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education and Life Long Learning*. 11 (4-6). 365 – 374.
- Jha, R. (2012, Feb. 02). Skewed pupil-teacher ratio takes toll on govt. schools. *The Indian Express*. Retrieved on 18th June, 2013 from <http://www.indianexpress.com/news/skewed-pupilteacher-ratiotakes-toll-on-govt-schools/906829/>
- Laurillard, D. (1993). Balancing the Media. *Journal of Educational Television*. 19(2), 81-93.
- Laurillard, D. (2002). Rethinking Teaching for the Knowledge Society. *EDUCAUSE Review* January/February 2002.
- McLoughlin, C. & Lee, M.J.W. (2007). Social Software and Participatory Learning: Pedagogical
- Choices with Technology Affordances in the Web 2.0 Era. *International Journal of Learning Technology*. 3 (1), 87-107.

- Moreno, J.M. (2005). Learning to teach in the Knowledge Society. *Final report. HDNED, World Bank*. Retrieved on 15th April, 2015 from http://siteresources.worldbank.org/EDUCATION/Resources/278200-1126210664195/16369711126210694253/Learning_Teach_Knowledge_Society.pdf
- *National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE)* (2009). New Delhi: NCERT
- *National Policy on ICT in school education (2012)*. Ministry of Human Resource Development Government of India.
- New Zealand Council for Educational Research (2009). *The knowledge age, shifting to 21st century thinking in education and learning*. Retrieved on July, 3, 2010 from http://www.shiftingthinking.org/?page_id=58
- OECD (2000 e). *Knowledge Management in the Learning Society*, CERIParis. Retrieved on July, 3, 2010 from <http://www.oecd.org/innovation/research/1842070.pdf> Retrieved on July, 3, 2010
- Oliver, R. & Herrington, J. (2003). Exploring technology-mediated learning from a pedagogical perspective. *Journal of Interactive Learning Environments*, 11(2), 111-126.
- Planning Commission (Government of India). 2013. *Twelfth five year plan (2012-2017) Social sectors, Vol.III*. 47-124. New Delhi: Sage Publications.
- Pons, J.P. (2010). Higher Education and the Knowledge Society. Information and Digital Competencies. *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya Barcelona* 7(2), 6-15.
- *Report to the Nation* (2006). National Knowledge Commission. Government of India.

- Tan,C.S., Hung, D. & Scardamalia, M. (2006). Education in the Knowledge Age – Engaging Learners through Knowledge building. In D. Hung & M.S. Khine (Eds.). *Engaged Learning with Emerging Technologies* (pp 91-106) Netherlands: Springer.
- Tuomi, I.(2008). Skills and Learning in the knowledge society (Abstract). *Eu e learning 2007 conference, Lisbon 16 October 2007.*
- UNESCO (2002).*Information and Communication Technologies in Teacher Education: A Planning Guide*. Paris : UNESCO
- UNESCO (2011). *UNESCO ICT Competency framework for teachers*. Paris: UNESCO.

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Paper-21

Self Evaluation in Student Teaching

Dr. S.Prakash

Self Evaluation in Student Teaching

Dr. S.Prakash³¹

Abstract

Pre-Service teacher education is a very crucial component of teacher education as it prepares the future teachers. Pre-service teacher education has two aspects-theoretical studies and practical activities. The theoretical components help the student teachers to equip themselves with the knowledge of various dimensions of teacher education and the practical components help them acquire the essential teaching skills. The objective of the study is to identify effectiveness of student teaching in terms of self evaluation. Survey method was used. A self evaluation tool constructed by the investigator was used to collect the data. 87 student teachers of TVS Teacher Training Academy, Madurai were taken as the sample. The findings showed that the student teachers are weak in the parameters using different methods while teaching, drawing diagrams on blackboard, use of A.V aids, relevancy of it and finishing lesson in time.

Key words: College of Education, Self Evaluation, Student Teaching.

Introduction-

Pre-Service teacher education is a very crucial component of teacher education as it prepares the future teachers. Pre-service teacher education has two aspects-theoretical studies and practical activities. The theoretical components help the student teachers to equip themselves with the knowledge of various dimensions of teacher education and the practical components help them acquire the essential teaching skills.

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Practicals in teacher education are generally of three categories- practicals on theory subjects, practicals on work experience and community development and practicals on school work. The last category of practical work is known as student teaching, practical teaching, internship etc. The practical work plays a vital role in developing the teacher effectiveness.

Need for the study-

The component of teacher education which enjoys more support from the education community and which is evaluated so positively by prospective teachers is student teaching. It provides a gradual, controlled entrance into classroom teaching. It gives answers to the questions, “Can I teach?” and “Do I like to teach?”. After a period of observation and participation, the prospective teacher takes over teaching duties for a period of 40 working days. The regular teacher acts as a guide prescribing the roles and responsibilities of the student teacher .The Guide teacher spends a good deal of time with the student teacher answering questions, suggesting approaches he might try, and generally helping him get acclimated to his new role.

Here, the present study is intended to evaluate the effectiveness of student teaching. For this, self evaluation of teaching is to be carried out by the student teachers.

Objectives of the study-

The objectives of the study are –

1. To identify the effectiveness of student teaching.
2. To identify the effectiveness of student teaching in terms of self evaluation
3. To identify the merits and limitations of student teaching.
4. To suggest appropriate measures to enhance the teaching effectiveness.

Methodology-

Survey method was followed-

Population of the study-

Student teachers studying B.Ed. course in colleges of Education affiliated to Tamilnadu Teachers Education University were considered as the population for the present study.

Sampling Technique of the study-

Cluster sampling technique was used.

Sample of the study-

87 student teachers of TVS Teacher Training Academy, Madurai were taken as the sample.

Tool used-

A self evaluation tool constructed by the investigator was used to collect the data.

Data Collection-

The 'Self Evaluation of Lessons' check list was given to the sampling unit after completing his/her lesson and asked to attend the checklist. This data was used for statistical analysis to evaluate the teaching efficiency of prospective teachers.

Statistics used-

Percentage analysis was only used to analyze the data.

Data analysis-

The relevant questions and the responses of the student teachers are tabulated as follows

Table 1- Self evaluation in student teaching Questionnaire

Sl.No	Questions	Yes (%)	No (%)
1.	Did I frame the relevant objectives of the lesson?	100	0
2.	Did I plan the class to achieve the objectives of the lesson?	92	08

3.	Did I achieve the objectives of the lesson?	89	11
4.	Did I motivate effectively?	92	08
5.	Did I stimulate the students for further learning?	77	23
6.	Did I consider the individual differences?	83	17
7.	Did I ask questions?	97	03
8.	Did I rectify the student's faulty responses?	98	02
9.	Did I utilize the student responses in developing the lesson?	80	20
10.	Did the students ask questions?	81	19
11.	Did I use relevant audio-visual aids?	60	40
12.	Did I use audio-visual aids successfully?	64	36
13.	Did I use the blackboard to the full extent?	86	14
14.	Did I draw clear diagrams on the blackboard?	69	31
15.	Did I evaluate the major concepts as the lesson progressed?	91	09
16.	Did I summarize the main concepts of the lesson?	97	03
17.	Did I give home assignments?	75	25
18.	Did I finish the lesson in time?	73	27
19.	Did I use different methods while teaching?	66	34
20.	Did I integrate the skills of teaching effectively?	78	22
21.	Did I follow the systematic procedure in presenting the lesson?	89	11
22.	Did I speak Tamil/English fluently while teaching?	76	24
23.	Did I supervise the class during teaching?	80	20
24.	Did I maintain the discipline properly?	79	21
25.	Could I improve the lesson if I have second opportunity to teach the lesson?	97	03

Results and discussions-

The findings are given in the form of graphical representation

Fig 1- Self evaluation in student teaching- Strong parameters

Fig 2- Self evaluation in student teaching- Moderate parameters

Fig.3- Self evaluation in student teaching- weak parameters

From the above table and figures, the strong, moderate and weak parameters of self evaluation of student teaching have been identified.

The study clearly indicates that the student teachers are strong in the parameters framing relevant objectives, plan in achieving the objectives, achieving the objectives, summarizing the main concepts, asking questions to students, rectifying students faulty responses, motivation, following systematic procedure in classroom teaching, Use of blackboard , evaluating major concepts and improving the lesson in second opportunity.

This study also states that the student teachers are moderate in the parameters in integrating skills in teaching, allowing students to ask questions, utilizing student responses, supervision, considering individual differences, maintaining discipline, stimulate students for further learning, giving home assignments and speaking fluently.

It is clear from the above results that the student teachers are weak in the parameters using different methods while teaching, drawing diagrams on blackboard, use of A.V aids, relevancy of it and finishing lesson in time.

Educational implications of the study-

- It is the foremost duty of colleges of Education to strengthen the weak parameters of student teaching.
- Use of different teaching methodologies to be practiced in a simulated condition and the student teachers should be asked to use at least three to four methods in their period of teaching practice. Mere lecture method in classroom transactions to be avoided.
- More inputs on preparation, selection of AV aids to be given to student teachers through workshops, seminars and video films.
- Blackboard sketches play an important role in teaching. Experts in this field may be invited and a session can be arranged with student teachers.
- More importance has to be given in managing the time in the classroom so that the students make use of optimum utilization of it within a period.

Conclusion-

This study has thrown some light on the self evaluation in student teaching, identified their weak areas and the measures to rectify it. This is high time that student teachers are given helping hands from college of education so as they transform into a complete teacher.

References-

- **Aggarwal, Y.P. (1988).** *Better Sampling Concepts, Techniques, Evaluation.* New Delhi: Sterling Publishers.
- **Rastogi, K.G. (1969).** *Supervision of Practice Teaching.* New Delhi: CIE.

- **Shankar, U. (1984).** *Education of Indian Teacher.* New Delhi: Sterling Publishers.
- **Srivastava.R.C. (1970).** *Evaluation of practice teaching in Teacher Training Colleges.* Delhi: CIE.

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Paper-22

**Reflective Practice – A Valuable Tool for
Building Social Inclusion in India?**

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Reflective Practice – A Valuable Tool for Building Social Inclusion in India?

Dr. Susan M.B. Davies³²

Abstract

Social exclusion can be the consequence of numerous, frequently interacting, factors and can result in discrimination and denial of equal rights. India, although enjoying strong fiscal growth, has failed to reduce social inequality. The discourse of social inclusion focuses attention on the need for action by public, private, and voluntary sectors, not only at the structural level, but also to change the social attitudes and beliefs of practitioners. Engagement by practitioners with reflective practice has the potential to facilitate these changes- it can improve professional creativity, critical thinking and accountability. The research project that is reported identified the factors that supported teacher engagement with reflective practice to develop inclusion. A number of crucial issues were found including practitioner ownership, collaboration and interaction with the evidence; these are interpreted using Activity Theory, and provide evidence for why a wider use of reflective practice would further develop social inclusion in India.

Key words: Social inclusion; educational inclusion; reflective practice, action research, Activity Theory; India.

Introduction-

Social exclusion, and its inverse social inclusion, are difficult terms to define because they are complex and multi-faceted (Levitas, 1999; Norwich, 2005).

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Although it is not always clear how these terms are any more useful than existing concepts of (in)justice and (in)equality, they do enable the exploration, because they are ‘umbrella terms’, of the many intersecting factors that underlie disadvantage and deprivation (Subrahmanian,2003).Social inclusion seeks to understand and reduce the structural, attitudinal and physical barriers to equal and non-discriminatory opportunity for disadvantaged individuals or groups in society (Booth & Ainscow, 2011). This agenda has great relevance for India because despite the country’s recent massive economic growth, there remain many neglected sectors of Indian society that have yet to benefit from this prosperity (Dreze & Sen, 2013).However the discourse of social exclusion is one that originated in the Global North, and needs further interpretation in terms of its relevance for the South (Subrahmanian, 2003).

This paper will begin with an overview which will examine the relevance of the concept of social exclusion for India and will also briefly examine the changes at the different levels of an organisation that can contribute to the development of inclusion. The focus will then narrow to look in more detail at what an individual professional can do to reflect upon and improve her/his own practice. It will be suggested that reflective practice is a useful method which can be used to develop inclusive and non-discriminatory ways of working. Evidence will be presented from a research project conducted in seven UK secondary schools which illustrates the value of reflective practice, for developing inclusive methods of professional working. The paper will then interpret the findings using the framework of Activity Theory before concluding with a discussion of why reflective practice can be a valuable method for the public and private sectors in India to support progressive change for greater inclusion and equality.

Social Exclusion in India-

Social exclusion is a process that deprives individuals and families, groups and neighbourhoods of the resources required for participation in the social, economic and political activity of society as a whole. This process is primarily a consequence of poverty and low income, but other factors such as discrimination, low educational attainment and depleted living environments also underpin it. Through this process people are cut off for a significant period of their lives from institutions and services, social networks and developmental opportunities that the great majority of a society enjoys. (Pierson, 2002, p.7)

Although written with the UK in mind, this definition has equal resonance for India, the only proviso being that the proportion of society who are enjoying these benefits is smaller than in the UK.

Social exclusion can be the consequence of numerous, frequently interacting, factors that can characterise a group or an individual. Poverty, low or stigmatised social class, ethnicity, gender, age or disability can all result in discrimination and denial of equal rights. There is strong evidence that all who work in the public, corporate and voluntary sectors in India need to pay urgent attention to how these factors, and failures in existing policy and practice, contribute to perpetuating exclusion (Dreze & Sen, 2013).

India has had strong economic growth since the 1980s, however reduction in the numbers living on very low incomes and other key poverty indicators such as the availability of sanitation facilities and child immunization has not kept pace with this growth; and progress lags behind that achieved by India's less wealthy near neighbours and indeed sub-Saharan Africa (Alkire & Seth, 2013). Inequality, as measured by the Gini Coefficient, has significantly increased in recent years (Dev & Ravi, 2005; Kapoor, 2013). Irrespective of poverty levels, it can be argued

that reducing economic inequality, both between individuals and identity groups is essential for the future development of the country(Weiskoff, 2011).There are powerful moral, political, economic and social arguments for the benefit to society of reducing inequality (ibid.) Perhaps the most compelling and detailed evidence is presented by Wilkinson and Pickett (2010) in their influential book ‘The Spirit Level’, where they argue that reducing inequality will improve the quality of life for the majority, not just the oppressed.

The failure of social policy to adequately address poverty and inequality may in part be due to the neo-liberal, market driven model adopted by the world economy as it has globalised (Jordan, 2006).It is perhaps too often forgotten that a contribution “to the improvement of the position of vulnerable groups, minorities and women” (MVO Platform,2012, chapter 2, para. 6) should be part of the mission of companies(*ibid.*) and must be a priority for governments (Dreze & Sen 2013).

Evidence indicates that being born into poverty reduces access to health care (Balarjan , Selvaraj & Subramanian, 2011) and achievement in education (Dreze & Sen, 2013). Being female (Ramachandran,2004), of low caste (Harriss, Jeyaranjan & Ngaraj, 2010),a member of an ethnic or religious minority (Thorat & Neuman, 2012),having an impairment (Miles & Singal,2010) are also associated with poor educational outcomes. The quantity and quality of education received by a child or young person is crucial to breaking the inter-generational cycle of poverty and disadvantage (Feinstein, Duckworth & Sabates, 2004), not least because education can be the route to employment and better life chances (Chakraborty, 2005). Therefore reduced access to opportunities to develop educational and associated social and economic capital perpetuates disadvantage and exclusion from full and equal participation in society (Field, 2003).

Does the concept of social inclusion have any usefulness or purchase for Indian society? Not least it has value because it focuses attention on the social, attitudinal and economic barriers that prevent full access to equal rights and opportunities. Other discourses of disadvantage can place responsibility for poverty and exclusion on an individual's personal weaknesses and lack of moral fibre (the 'undeserving poor') (Levitas, 1999). In contrast, social inclusion is underpinned by a social model which places responsibility on social systems, both public and corporate, and how they are manifested in policy and practice.

Accepting this perspective of social inclusion places a duty on all sectors of society, including government, private and voluntary organisations, to identify policies and promote practices which will improve the spread of wealth and opportunity to all sections of the Indian population. Structural changes that promote greater equality include measures such as legislating against discrimination, introducing policies to facilitate access to education and employment and establishing organisational guidelines for improved healthcare provision. Although in India there are a number of government policies and programmes which aim to improve the health, education and employment prospects of the most disadvantaged; and some positive results have been achieved, they have not had sufficient impact on the inequality which is at the heart of Indian civil society (Dreze & Sen, 2013). There is evidence to suggest that progress is being retarded by inefficient systems of governance and accountability in central government, state government, corporate administration (Chitnis, Dixit & Josey, 2012) and the poor practice of individual professionals (Goyal & Pandey, 2012). In addition one of the engines of institutional discrimination can be the prejudices of individual members of the workforce (Department for International Development, 2005).

Therefore as well as addressing shortcomings at the macro level of government, state or company policy, it is also essential to promote change at the micro level of individual professional practice. To embed inclusion requires attention not only to policy but also to the social culture of organisations and the attitudes of practitioners. An example of an educational inclusion programme used in the UK will illustrate this- The Index for Inclusion, now in its third edition (Booth & Ainscow, 2011). This audit and development toolkit has been distributed by the UK government to all schools, as well as being extensively purchased by organisations and individuals (Vaughan, 2002). Change, using this model, involves attention to three interacting dimensions-creating inclusive cultures, producing inclusive policies and evolving inclusive practices. It is based on collaboration between all members of a school community, and is a gradual and reflective approach which places the values of the individual at its core, 'Doing the right thing involves relating actions and values. Relating your actions to your values can be the most practical step you can take in developing your school'. (*ibid.*, p.11).

Therefore developing social inclusion is not only about developing enlightened policies and new administrative structures, it is also about scrutiny of the culture of an organisation, and how that influences, and is influenced by the values and practices of management and workers (Kugelmass, 2004). Change towards more inclusive practice must involve challenge and,

'...go beyond descriptive questions such 'What are the teachers doing?' and 'Are they doing things differently now?' Such enquiry needs also to probe into the discourse and community behind teachers' actions, with questions such as 'Do they judge differently?' 'Do they talk differently about mistakes?' 'Do they deal differently with disagreements?' 'Do they deal adequately with challenging

information?’ ‘What do they really care about?’ (Howes, Davies & Fox, 2009 p.29-30).

The interrogation of practice must be informed by values, principles and theories; however these may not provide the most accessible starting point for practitioners- the focus for change may need to be more context specific and experience based (Thomas & Loxley, 2007). For this purpose, the methodology of reflective practice is a valuable tool that can be used for both critical ethnomethodological analysis of the workplace (Finlay, 2008) and for delivering continuing professional practice that is ethically based and socially progressive (Thompson & Thompson, 2008).

Reflective Practice-

The impact of reflective practice on training and practice has a wide reach across many professions- social work, healthcare, education, industry (Thompson & Thompson, 2008).It offers a method for professional growth that can develop both practice and attitudes(Evans, 2002). It can enhance not only the productivity of the workplace but also it’s standard of ethics (Boud, Cressey & Docherty, 2006).Professional practice that is ‘reflective’ is effective because it enables self scrutiny and evaluation of work experience, which can result in new insights and improved practice (Finlay, 2008).

Schon’s seminal work identified two major categories of reflection: reflection-on-action (reflecting after practice has been completed) and reflection-in-action (reflecting while engaged in practice)(Schon, 1983). Subsequently other theorists have added reflection-for-action (reflecting before carrying out a practice) (Thompson & Thompson, 2008). Schon’s conception of the creative flexible thinker, sensitive and responsive to the demands of the workplace developed from, and acknowledged, the need for these professional characteristics in a world that is complex, often unpredictable and is at times unscrupulous. Other theoretical

influences include constructivism (learning is constructed by reflection on lived experience) and situated learning theory (learning occurs as the result of joint, participative activity) (Fenwick, 2003).

Becoming more reflective can include developing more intense and focused thinking (sometimes called mindfulness), a questioning and critical disposition, a greater openness to new ideas and creativity, and enhanced empathy. Also, crucially for social inclusion, reflection which ‘challenges assumptions, ideological illusions, damaging social and cultural biases, inequalities, and questions personal behaviours which perhaps silence the voices of others or otherwise marginalise them.’ (Bolton, 2010, p.3)

It does not work well in top-down organisations that impose compliance but is premised on practitioners being given opportunities to take responsibility for their practice, including how it develops and contributes to the cultural, social and political ethos of the organisation (*ibid.*). Reflective practice can be carried out solo, or collaboratively in groups-the latter has many advantages such as mutual support and shared thinking (Thompson & Thompson, 2008).

A critical engagement with day to day, perhaps taken for granted, practice can encourage fresh insights and new thinking. It can increase awareness of moral and political factors that influence work, it can expose gaps and conflicts between the official ethical stance and values on the ground- uncomfortable but essential for improved social inclusion, and better organisations Boud et al.(2006)consider ‘ethical practices characterised by ‘reflective doing’ are an intrinsic dimension of excellent practices’. (p. 134).

It can also be a method to improve accountability about performance- a reflective practitioner can be clear not only about what s/he did but also why s/he did it- this

is essential when called to account for professional actions (Thompson & Thompson, 2008).

Lastly reflective thinking leads to reflective learning in practice. It is learning that is characterised by being focused on activity, based on experience, developed within a social context, engaged with criticism and challenge and valuing difference(Brockbank, McGill & Beech 2002)

There are many methods for developing reflective practice, for example keeping reflective journals/ diaries, role playing and using other practical exercises, studying critical incidents (Finlay, 2008). Action research is a practitioner research technique which can be applied as a method for reflection on practice (Bolton, 2010)).It can be used by an individual working alone but is most productive when conducted in participation with others (Cressey, 2006).

Action research is generally applied to small scale, real life issues. It is a cyclical process of reflection, planning, doing, evaluating with the evaluation informing the next cycle of intervention and evaluation. It has been described as ‘a self reflective spiral of cycles of planning, acting, observing and reflecting’ (Carr & Kemmis, 1986, p.165 cited by Bolton, 2010). It can be powerful because it brings together people who share a common work environment, who identify a shared goal, and can work collaboratively to an outcome in which they all have a vested interest. Although there is a large body of knowledge that supports the use of action research as a critically reflective and collaborative mechanism for change, there is less certainty about the conditions that are needed in the workplace to support these changes- this was the focus for the study (Howes *et al.*, 2009) which will now be reported.

Prosiect Dysgu Cydradd-

Prosiect Dysgu Cydradd (the name of the project in English was ‘Facilitating Teacher Engagement in More Inclusive Practice’) (PDC) gathered data from secondary schools in England and Wales over a two year period. The research was supported by the UK Economic and Social Research Council. The main purpose of PDC was to identify the contextual factors which supported and hindered teacher engagement in action research, and to extend the theoretical understanding of the value of reflective practice as a method for developing inclusion. The underpinning rationale was that educational inclusion is a socio-cultural process which ‘incorporates a view of the human self that finds meaning in relationship to others’ (Howes *et al.*, 2009, p.4) and requires a ‘critical reflective approach towards change within school and its communities’ (*ibid.*,p.5).A case study methodology was chosen because it is particularly useful for interrogating theory by answering ‘how’ and ‘why’ questions and provides a basis for understanding issues in complex, real world situations (Yinn, 2009). Therefore for this research , the construction of case studies were considered the best way to engage with the many intersecting variables that impact on inclusion in general, and influence change in schools and classrooms in particular.

It was decided to base the research in secondary schools (pupil age range eleven to eighteen years) because their larger size and more complex structure can make developing inclusion more challenging than in primary schools (statutory pupil age range five to eleven years).The six secondary schools ,each located in different local authorities, were chosen to be representative of urban/rural, large/small, monolingual/ bilingual characteristics of schools in the UK .One school withdrew from PDC half way through and another similar school was selected to replace it; therefore in total there were seven participating schools. Table 1 provides further details of the schools’ characteristics.

School	Number of pupils	Catchment area (1)	Language medium (2)	Pupils entitled to free school meals (%) (3)	Pupils on special needs register (%) (4)	Pupils from ethnic minority backgrounds (%)
A	900	Semi-rural	Bilingual	8	11	0.2
B	600	Semi-rural	Bilingual	2	34	2
C	1050 (excluding sixth form)	Suburban	English	7	4	16
D	1030	Urban	English	14	27	0.1
E	1000	Semi-rural	Bilingual	10	17	2
F	1800	Urban	English	6	12	5
G	1400	Semi-rural	English	8	30	2

Table 1: Characteristics of project schools

1. The catchment is the geographical area from which pupils are accepted for entry by a school.
2. The project was conducted in Wales and England, both parts of the UK. In some Welsh schools, teaching is bilingual and through the mediums of both Welsh and English.
3. Entitlement to free school meals is used in the UK as an indicator of disadvantage, as only children from low income backgrounds are entitled to this benefit.
4. All children who have been identified as having special educational needs (SEN) are recorded on a register in UK schools.

Using a qualitative method, data from a variety of stakeholders, gathered by a variety of methods (shown in Table 2) were triangulated and enabled the construction of detailed case studies of teacher led action research projects.

Target	Instrument	Data gathered
Teachers	Pre-project questionnaire	Opinions of social inclusion and action research
Teachers	Focus group at beginning of project	Assumptions and views of issue that is the focus of their teacher project
Teachers	Interviews, informal discussions by researchers on visits to the school.	Views of teacher project as it developed.
Teachers	Post –project questionnaire	Reflection on factors that helped and hindered progress. Impact of teacher project on self and their pupils. Comparison with other methods of continuing professional development.
School Headteacher	Pre-project interview	School context
Local Authority representative	Pre-project interview	School context
School Headteacher	Post-project interview	Impact of project.
School educational psychologist	Pre- and post project questionnaire	School context and impact of teacher project. Factors that supported and hindered teacher engagement.

Classrooms	Ad hoc observations by researchers on visits to school	Teacher-pupil interaction. Implementation of teacher project methods.
Pupils	Pre – and post project questionnaire: Myself as learner (Burden, 1998)	Views of self and own learning.
Pupils	Pre- and post project questionnaire: Individual Classroom Environment Questionnaire (Rentoul & Fraser, 1979)	Views of classroom environment and learning in the classroom.
Pupils	Pre- and post project questionnaire: What I Think About School (Howes et al., 2007)	Interest , engagement and participation in learning.
Cross section of pupils	Focus group	Impact of pupils and views about inclusion.

Table 2: Data gathered to construct teacher project case studies

The timing, order and location of the collection of case study data was noted to enable any future replication. Data collection followed rigorous ethical guidelines. A group of teachers, in each school undertook a project during phase one; results were analysed by the PDC team and then a further cycle of projects were conducted by different groups of teachers in the same schools which refined the methods used. Schools were allowed freedom to choose how they selected teacher participants: most were selected by the Headteacher (nine teacher projects), in one school on the basis of a bidding competition between academic departments; the remainder were volunteers. Group size also varied between two and seven members.

In both phases teacher action research groups were asked to reflect on the relatively narrow concept of ‘pupil engagement in learning’, to identify a classroom issue related to this issue, and plan an intervention which would be the focus of their action and reflection. The issue of pupil engagement was chosen because it actualises the sometimes nebulous concept of inclusion and because it fits well with teachers’ interests, motivations and professional agency (Fielding, 2006). Inclusive change must involve engagement with teachers’ knowledge and views because what teachers think, say and do mediates the learning and participation of their pupils. Cochran-Smith and Lyttle (1999) believe that critical reflection, which they conceptualise as ‘inquiry as stance’, is an essential part of professional practice and at the heart of teacher development:

Teachers and student teachers who take an inquiry stance work within inquiry communities to generate local knowledge, envision and theorise their practice, and interpret and interrogate the theory and research of others. Fundamental to this notion is the idea that the work of inquiry communities is both social and political; that is, it involves making problematic the current arrangements of schooling; the ways that knowledge is constructed, evaluated and used; and teachers’ individual and collective roles in bringing about change. (ibid., p.289)

The teachers in the present research took the opportunity provided by collaborative action research to take this stance, reflect about their classroom practices, and share this thinking with colleague co-researchers. The types of projects which resulted can be grouped into two broad types: action focused projects that trialled new ways of working as a route to inclusion e.g. a pupil peer mentoring scheme, developing a new reward system; and issue focused projects where the effects of one or more actions were evaluated to meet a particular issue of pupil engagement e.g. addressing girls’ underachievement; improving poor language skills.

Working in schools over a two year period allowed the construction of multiple case studies, and to identify features in common across the different cases. The results indicated, as anticipated, that teachers, although familiar with the rhetoric of inclusion, had difficulty in understanding what it meant in practice. Action research was also an unfamiliar process. However locating their project around testing concrete changes in day to day practice contextualised and made the abstract 'do-able'. For teachers' projects to be effective it was important that teachers' professional practice was developed creatively and was sufficiently resourced and supported by school organisation.

Other enabling features were the composition of the group- a diversity of previous experience within the group was a huge stimulus to creative collaborative thinking. The role of school management was found to be crucial in sustaining the projects (Davies & Howes, 2009). It was important for management not to 'steal' the leadership of the group from the teachers but 'backstage support' made projects more effective, for example protecting free periods for staff, listening to and celebrating ongoing developments, and promoting the project by linking it into other school systems such as staff appraisal. Celebrating the project at whole school events, and making connections with other agendas such as continuing professional development widened the impact of projects across the institution. Projects were situated in particular institutional contexts, and evidence suggested that where new practice and the aims of new practice are valued, change can become embedded and sustained (*ibid.*).

However three key issues were identified as crucial to teacher engagement; these were teacher ownership, teacher collaboration, and teacher interaction with evidence (Howes *et al.*, 2009). Ownership was vital- teacher groups who discussed and evolved their own projects were more effective in developing inclusion than

those where the level of teacher involvement or the focus of the project was decided by management. However this could only happen when management offered teachers real choices, and the teachers were keen to take up the challenge, and to take responsibility for progress. Secondly, as the literature suggests, and the project's findings confirmed, collaboration between colleagues around a shared project, can be powerful and transformative. For example, teachers again and again mentioned how talking and listening to each other opened up conversations about practice which deepened their practical understanding of inclusion. However the project also gained insight into what is needed by understanding the difficulties and frustrations encountered by teachers, and how they can be resolved. For example, time to meet and talk together was often a major obstacle- and schools who arranged dedicated time or came up with other solution such as creative timetabling- were repaid by effective teamwork. Thirdly, critical reflection must include the systematic evaluation of relevant evidence. Too often the engagement of policy makers, organisations and individual practitioners is temporary and short term, related to specific incidents. Action research provided a method for sustained engagement with, and evaluation of, evidence. For example, the evidence suggested that this often led to teachers changing their relationships with, and attitudes to the pupils who were most disengaged.

Data gathered about progress of pupils by teacher projects reported positive impact on motivation (six projects), participation (four projects) and attainment (three projects). Pupil views, expressed in focus groups showed that they valued opportunities for active participation in their work; to have and make choices; and to have a warm and respectful relationship with their teachers.

To summarise, the key support factors which were identified in the analysis of the teacher projects are shown in Figure 1.

Figure1: Collaborative action research for inclusion (adapted from Howes *et al.*, 2009 p.107)

The use of collaborative action research can be understood in terms of three aspects: the new professional actions that are developed; the collaborative processes that inform and embed these actions and the enabling features of the context on which the processes and actions depend (Howes *et al.*, 2009). The diagram also shows the outcomes for inclusion- for the recipients it means increased inclusion and the implications for roles, relationships and assumptions;

for the practitioners it means increased awareness of inclusion and; for the institution it means opportunities to learn and to embed inclusive practices. The diagram also highlights and locates the concept of ‘emergence’:

Emergence [is] the sense that the development of inclusion cannot be organised according to a schedule, but it involves connections and opportunities that are not known in advance. Emergence may be thought of as potentially located in the links between the three aspects of collaborative action research. It is in the emergent interaction between these aspects that the development of inclusion and capacity for inclusion take place. (ibid., pp.107-8)

It is in the emergent space, that reflection and creativity take place -assumptions are challenged, contradictions are confronted, critical questions are asked, differences of opinion are discussed, values are interrogated, new ideas are born- it is where reflection for, on and about inclusive practice happens.

PDC implemented a case study methodology with care and rigour. Data was systematically collected from a wide variety of sources; it was carefully analysed and triangulated to both strengthen internal validity and increase concurrent validity. There was close attention to timing and procedures across the two cycles of the data collection with the aim of increasing the reliability of the findings. The use of case studies as a research methodology has been criticised in the literature because it may restrict the generalisability of the findings (Ashley, 2012; Yinn, 2009 summarise this perspective). However findings based on multiple case studies, as in this research, can increase generalisability (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2011)and the use of evidence from case study research to extend theory can be considered a type of generalisation (*ibid.*).

Discussion-

As discussed earlier, redistributive and anti-discriminatory legislation and organisational policy have an essential role to play in reducing inequality and exclusion, however to achieve a fully inclusive society, change must also occur in the “hearts and minds” of individuals (Mittler, 2000 p.xi). The drivers of exclusion are many and have historical, cultural and social origins. For example at a personal level how we regard and treat others is informed by beliefs, attitudes about ourselves and others; at a cultural level there can be an assumed social consensus about what is true, right, good and normal, and accepted codes of conduct; and within society there are structures and institutions that perpetuate social divisions (Thompson,2006). These drivers are transmitted across generations, and between and within identity groups.

In addition the multi-dimensionality of exclusion means that individual or group experiences of discrimination can vary hugely, and be very context specific (Sayed & Soudien, 2003).Consequently the development of inclusion is many layered and multi-voiced, the process “brings together different voices, experiences and expectations and beckons the need for processes that can helpfully mediate these differences.”(*ibid*, p.12)

Any process to develop inclusion must be able to handle this complexity, and Activity Theory (Engeström, 2005) will be used to help to understand how reflective practice can be a method by which ‘expansive learning’ about inclusion can be accomplished. Activity Theory provides a framework for understanding the inter-relationship of the learning experience of the individual and the socio-cultural systems in which it takes place (Engeström, 2005). It proposes that learning environments are activity systems comprised of many voices (for example in PDC- the teachers, the management, and the pupils) which are in interaction and sometimes collision with other activity existing systems (for example the school,

the education authority, the central government). The historical evolution of the activity system is also considered a significant influence (for example changes in the school over time and the impact of these on its local community), and the potential for change and the development of new practice arises as a result of contradictions that emerge between old and new elements of systems or between different systems. When a system is able to accommodate these contradictions and to use them as a stimulus to develop new and improved practice, the changes that occur are labelled as 'expansive' learning (Davies, Howes & Farrell 2008).

Engeström (2005) describes how the process of expansive learning can be accomplished, and the characteristics that he outlines can also provide a model for how to implement effective reflective practice. Firstly the process should be multi-voiced, allowing different viewpoints and approaches to be heard in the discussion. In a school this might mean classroom teachers working alongside each other and consulting with managers, pupils, parents. The discussion should focus on existing or innovative practice and any disruptions, conflicts that are being experienced. So in a school, this may mean, for example the identification of some groups that are not achieving or participating well in a particular curriculum area- perhaps the engagement of pupils with an impairment with science practical work. The process should now drill down into the issue, analysing data, views, ideas. In our example, interrogating the arrangements for science for disabled pupils could expose teacher prejudices, low pupil self expectations, environmental barriers, a lack of appropriate resources, and perhaps some contradictions. One contradiction, which is central to inclusion, is the 'dilemma of difference' (Norwich, 2013), this can characterised as if something additional/different is provided for a child with an impairment will this isolate and stigmatise them and perhaps be wasteful of resources and /or other children's progress? However if the additional/ different

provision is not made, then will the child's needs not be met effectively? Analysis of issues and contradictions provide a fertile soil for the development of new types of practice. In this example, the practitioners, informed by the views of pupils and parents, may decide to adapt the mainstream practice of the classroom (termed differentiation), rather than introduce specialist programmes which may isolate and stigmatise those receiving them. The implementation of any new practice should be subject to rigorous evaluation, and will then lead to a further cycle of activity.

The key enabling factors identified by PDC have many similarities with the distinguishing features of expansive learning. The findings of PDC can be interpreted by, and offer support to, this theoretical framework. PDC found more expansive contexts to be characterised by practitioners open to collaboration and critical engagement with evidence; able to implement and evaluate new actions; and supported by management who made an explicit commitment to the process. When these features were present 'emergence' of new inclusive practices could occur. This supports the conclusion that when a method for reflective practice embraces certain characteristics-the multi-voicedness of many stakeholders, a critical engagement with conflicts and contradictions found in professional practice, an evaluation of new practices- it can be a tool that can accommodate the multi-dimensionality of inclusion.

However although action research offers a method for reflection it can be carried out without reflective engagement, and this was one of the pitfalls identified by PDC. Shortage of time for reflective practice is a real challenge for busy professionals (Thompson and Thompson, 2008). It was found that fast forwarding through analysis by teacher projects saves time but misses opportunities for reflection and discussion of conflicts and contradictions; this can lead to interventions that are taken 'off the shelf', may be formulaic and do not deliver

expansive impact on practice. Another pitfall, acknowledged in the literature and further identified by PDC is an unsupportive organisational culture, which does not help to develop practitioner collaboration or enable expansive learning.

Conclusion-

The methods investigated by PDC will not be unfamiliar to practitioners in India. The 'learning organisation' is a concept that has been used by some companies (Lulla, 2009), and individual and collaborative reflective practice are important aspects of this programme. Reflective practice can also be found as part of the discourse of professional development for teachers and other caring professions in many States, although it may not always be actualised in practice.

Social inclusion is a concept that has also gained recognition and leverage in India in the last few years (Sayed & Soudien, 2003). Policy initiatives to address inequality of access to basic rights such as health and education have been enacted. However there is often a failure to deliver effective practice. The reasons for this are many (Dreze & Sen, 2013) but an important factor is ineffective implementation of a policy by an institution or an individual practitioner (Subrahmanian, 2003).

Inclusion is a multi-dimensional concept, and exclusion can be manifested in practice in the complex interplay between government and institutional policies, the life experiences of different identity groups, and the everyday procedures of professionals. For example it can be seen that teachers' attitudes and behaviours are crucial to effective inclusion, yet in India some teachers' perceptions of 'educability' have not changed very much, and this can surface in blaming children for moral weaknesses which may be culturally perceived as linked to their caste; in addition mechanisms for professional accountability are poor and teachers regulate

their own behaviour at the individual level, and this further exacerbates the challenge of implementing inclusion (Subrahmanian,2003).

PDC highlighted the value of developing reflective practice in the specific professional context of individual professionals. A twenty month study of educational exclusion in India also identified the importance of localising and contextualising the study of the processes of inclusion (Sayed & Soudien, 2003). Reflection about the local and the familiar is a non-threatening way to challenge ingrained assumptions, think about taken for granted and new practices. It also provides a way to develop, implement and evaluate new practice. Conducted collaboratively it builds professional networks and empowers shared creative thinking. It is flexible enough to adapt to the demands of different environments, organisations and relationships; this can extend to the participation of marginalised groups in the action research. The perspectives of those who are excluded or at risk of exclusion should at the very least be part of the data analysed, and the approach can be extended to involve members of marginalised groups as co-researchers. In essence reflective practice supports expansive learning.

Inclusion is about reducing barriers to equal opportunity at the environmental, structural and attitudinal levels. It cannot be only about developing new and enlightened policies, it must also be about the transformation of professional practice. The research reported in this paper provides evidence that reflective practice is a valuable tool for developing inclusion, and that it may have useful applications for the Indian context.

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References-

- Alkire,S. & Seth,S. (2013). Multi-dimensional Poverty Reduction in India between 1999 and 2006: Where and How? *OPHI Working Paper No.60*. Oxford: University of Oxford.
- Ashley,L.D. (2012). Case Study Research. In Arthur,J., Waring,M., Coe, R. & Hedges,L.V. (Eds.) (2012) *Research Methods and Methodologies in Education*(pp.102-107). London: Sage.
- Balarjan,Y., Selvaraj,S., & Subramanian,S.V. (2011). Healthcare and equity in India. *The Lancet*,377,505-515.
- Bolton,G. (2010). *Reflective Practice* (3rd ed.). London: Sage.
- Booth,T & Ainscow,M. (2011). *Index for Inclusion* (3rd ed.). Bristol: Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education.
- Boud, D., Cressey,P.,& Docherty,P. Setting the scene for productive reflection.(2006). In Boud, D., Cressey,P.& Docherty,P.(Eds.) *Productive Reflection at Work* (pp.3-10) Abingdon: Routledge.
- Brockbank, A., McGill,I. & Beech,N. (Eds.). (2002). *Reflective Learning in Practice*. Aldershot: Gower.
- Burden, R.L.(1998).Assessing children’s perceptions of themselves as learners and problem solvers. *School Psychology International*, 19,4, 291-305.
- Chakraborty,A. (2005). Kerala’s Changing Development Narrative. *Economic & Political Weekly*, February 2005, 541-547.
- Chitnis,A., Dixit,S & Josey,A. (2012). Bailing Out Unaccountability. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 51, 22-25.
- Cochran-Smith,M. & Lytle,S. (1999). Relationships of knowledge and practice: teacher learning in communities. *Review of Research in Education*, 24, 249-305.

- Cohen,L., Manion,L. & Morrison,K. (2011) *Research Methods in Education* (7th edn.). Abingdon: Routledge.
- Cressey,P. (2006) ‘Collective reflection and learning: from formal to reflective participation’. In Boud, D., Cressey,P.& Docherty,P.(Eds.). *Productive Reflection at Work* (pp.54-65). Abingdon: Routledge.
- Davies,S.M.B., Howes, A., &Farrell,P. (2008). Tensions and Dilemmas for Change in an Analysis of Joint Working Between Teachers and Educational Psychologists. *School Psychology International*, 29, 4, 400-417.
- Davies,S.M.B., &Howes,A. (2009). ‘Developing Effective Schools: Creating School Contexts that Facilitate Engagement with Collaborative Action Research. *The Welsh Journal of Education*, 14, 2, 3-17.
- Department for International Development. (2005). *Reducing Poverty by Tackling Social Exclusion*. London: Department for International Development.
- Dev, S. M., &Ravi, C. (2007). Poverty and Inequality: All India and States, 1983-2005. *Economic & Political Weekly*, February 2007, 509-521.
- Dreze, J., & Sen, A. (2013). *An Uncertain Glory: India and Its Contradictions*. London: Allen Lane.
- Engeström, Y. (2005).*Developmental Work Research: Expanding Activity Theory in Practice*. Berlin: Lehmanns Media.
- Evans,L. (2002). *Reflective Practice in Educational Research*. London: Continuum.
- Feinstein, L., Duckworth, K., & Sabates, R. (2004). *A Model of the Intergenerational Transmission of Educational Success*, London: Centre for Research on the Wider Benefits of Learning, Institute of Education.

- Fenwick,T.J. (2003). *Learning Through Experience: troubling Orthodoxies and Intersecting Questions*. Florida: Krieger Publishing Company.
- Field, J. (2003). *Social Capital*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Fielding, M. (2006). Leadership, personalisation and high performance schooling: naming the new totalitarianism. *School Leadership & Management*, 26, 4, 347-369.
- Finlay,L.(2008) *Reflecting on 'Reflective practice'*, A discussion paper prepared for PBPL CETL. Retrieved 1 September 2013 from www.open.ac.uk/pbpl .
- Goyal, S., & Pandey,P. (2012). How do Government and private Schools Differ? *Economic & Political Weekly*, 22, 67-76.
- Harriss, J., Jeyaranjan, J., & Ngaraj, K. (2010). Land, Labour and Caste Politics in Rural Tamil Nadu in the 20th Century: Iruvelpattu (1916-2008). *Economic & Political Weekly*, XLV, 31, 47-61.
- Howes, A., Davies, S.M.B., &Fox, S. (2007) *What I Think About School*. Manchester: Authors.
- Howes, A., Davies, S.M.B., &Fox, S. (2009). *Improving the Context for Inclusion: Personalising teacher development through collaborative action research*, London: Routledge.
- Jordan, B. (2006). *Social Policy for the Twenty- First century*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Kapoor, R. (2013). Inequality Matters. *Economic & Political Weekly*, XLVIII, 2, 58-65.
- Kugelmass, J. (2004). *The Inclusive School: Sustaining Equity and Standards*. New York: Teachers College Press.

- Levitas, R. (1999) .Defining and measuring social exclusion: A critical overview of current proposals. *Radical Statistics*, 71, no page numbers.
- Lulla,S. (2009) How Tatas keep employees motivated, stay a learning organisation. *DNA Analysis*.Retrieved 15th December 2013 from <http://www.dnaindia.com/money/report-how-tatas-keep-employees-motivated-stay-a-learning-organisation-1260675>
- Miles, S., & Singal, N. (2010). The Education for All and Inclusive Education Debate. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*,14,1,1-15.
- Mittler,P. (2000). *Working Towards Inclusive Education: Social Contexts*. London: David Fulton.
- Mvoplatfrom. (2012). *Corporate Social Responsibility Frame of Reference*. Amsterdam: Mvoplatfrom.
- Norwich,B. (2013). *Addressing Tensions and Dilemmas in Inclusive Education*. London: Routledge.
- Pierson,J.(2002) *Tackling Social Exclusion* . London: Routledge.
- Ramachandran,V. (Ed.). (2004). *Gender and Social Equity in Primary Education: Hierarchies of Access*, New Delhi: Sage.
- Rentoul, A.J. & Fraser,B.J.(1979) Conceptualisation of enquiry based or open classroom environments. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*,11,233-245
- Sayed, Y., & Soudien, C. (2003). (Re)Framing Education Exclusion and Inclusion Discourse: Limit and Possibilities. *IDS Bulletin*, 34,1, 9-19.
- Schon, D. A. (1987) *Educating the Reflective Practitioner*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Subrahmanian,R. (2003). Exploring Processes of Marginalisation and Inclusion in Education. *IDS Bulletin*, 34,1, 1-8.

- Thomas, G. & Loxley, A. (2007). *Deconstructing Special Education and Constructing Inclusion.* (2nd ed.). Maidenhead: Open University Press.
- Thompson, S., & Thompson, N. (2008). *The Critically Reflective Practitioner.* Basingstoke: Palgrave MacMillan.
- Thompson, N. (2006). *Anti-Discriminatory Practice* (4th ed.) . Basingstoke: MacMillan.
- Thorat, S. & Neuman, K.S. (2012). *Blocked by Caste: Economic Discrimination in Modern India.* Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Vaughan, M. (2002). *The Index for Inclusion.* Bristol: Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education.
- Weiskoff, T.E. (2011) Why Worry about Inequality in the Booming Indian Economy? *Economic & Political Weekly*, XLVI,47, 41-51.
- Wilkinson, R. & Pickett, K. (2010) *The Spirit Level: Why Equality is Better for Everyone.* London: Penguin.
- Yinn, R.K. (2009) *Case Study Research: Design and Methods* (4th ed.). London: Sage.

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Paper-23

**Students' Perception of Academic Library
Services in their Learning Progress**

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Students' Perception of Academic Library Services in their Learning Progress

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Introduction-

Library plays an integral part in students' development. With the development of higher education, colleges and universities are increasing services to provide a variety of opinions based on students' demands and needs (Nagata et al. 2004). Do college services have an impact on students' learning progress? How can library services be linked to students' learning progress? The academic libraries considered as the heart and the center of academic life (Gunasekera, 2010). When connecting students' learning progress and library services, we find that library is a needed service to develop and improve students' learning. College and universities play an important role in providing services to students to improve their learning to in order to have excellent outcomes achievement. It can be said that students' learning progress and library services are relative and share a symbiotic relationship.

Aim and Purpose of the Study-

Through investigating different studies about academic library services and students' learning progress, researchers explored how library services help in developing students' learning and having an excellent studying and learning progress. Through centuries, most of researches observed about the importance of academic libraries. Therefore, the main purpose of this paper is to explore the impact of library services on students' academic achievement, as there are a little of

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research about this topic in the UAE. This research will be carried out in one of the higher education institutions in United Arab Emirates (UAE). This study will use quantitative approach through survey technique.

Research Objectives-

- Identify the library services
- Determine students' perception of library services on their studying progress

Research Question-

What is the student' perception of library services in their studying and learning progress? This study is comprised of four parts followed by references and appendices. The first part outlines the literature review by exploring the students' perception of library services. The second part will discuss the context, sample methodology used for this research, research design and data collection. The third part will provide an in-depth analysis of findings and discussion of library services. The final chapter will conclude the study with some recommendations and limitations.

Library Services Support Students' Learning Progress-

Through the last decades in different countries, the use of library needed by students has increased mostly because of the increase in the number of students and college and university libraries need to meet the students' demand in the best possible way (Eskola 1998). Pervious literatures on the impact and the role of academic library on students' learning progressshow an integral role in ensuring the success of students' researches in college and university (Jubb & Green 2007; Rasul & Singh 2010).Academic libraries considered as the heart and the center of academic life and the gateway to information (Gunasekera, 2010; Rasul & Singh 2010). Academic library has been defined as a collection of wide range of learning and teaching materials in one place, organized and indexed by staff to serve the

readers (Waite 1989), where the main key purpose of academic library is to support its objectives in the area of teaching, learning, research and services (Ania 2004). Rajendran and Rathinasapathy (2005) stated that library is a vital intellectual resource for academic community where it helps them to complete the curriculum prerequisites. Generally, in higher education system, academic libraries have to provide support services for educational programs and to facilities students' research because in any academic library (Gunasekera 2010).

According to Foo et al (2002), in these days, academic library takes the key role of offering a competitive advantage for colleges and universities as a learning and research center for students. While Campbell (2006) claimed that academic libraries are complex places with numerous of roles. They are not providing only fiction and non-fiction to students for their study but they also supply services to facilitate students' academic achievement such as; references services (Campbell 2006). Olanlokun and Salisu (1993) added that students cannot obtain knowledge and needed information through textbooks or classroom lectures only, they will need to refer to other books where the library is a great helpful for them for acquire knowledge. Moreover, Oni-orisan (1987) stressed that education system is not completed without having a library with operational services either direct through contact with student or indirect through carried activities. Clark (1999) pointed out that academic libraries serve students through providing a variety of materials and encouraging students to read and use the libraries. The components of the academic library consist of (Field 1998):

1. Input: staffing, budgeting, collections and accommodation
2. Processes: collection development, organization and management
3. Outputs: reference services, usage of finding tools, catalogs, collections and document services

4. Continuous training of users and service providers through direct contact
5. Ongoing feedback from stakeholders: students, staff and the public

Generally, most of the studies during different years agreed that academic library use is certainly beneficial for students to accomplish their learning. But to approve to what degree is the academic library contribute to students' learning progress is not easy. Merrill (1983), for example, examined the relation between library resources services and students' learning progress and he found that the use of library services were linked significantly with better learning outcomes of students. This finding agreed with findings made by Crossley & Murby (1994), who stated that there is a remarked relation between college library services and level of students' learning. Ory & Brakamp's early study (1988) expressed that participating in academic library activities was sort of associated with students' achieved in their critical thinking skills. Likewise, Whitmire (2002) noticed that students' usage in library resources and services has a good impact on their critical thinking skills. Guskin (1996) added that the use of academic libraries promotes active learning to students to have the ability to think critically and either work independently or in group.

A number of authors have written in their researches about academic library use. In a study by Okiy (2000) about students use of academic libraries in Nigeria found that students used books more than other materials where they searched in the selves to find out the needed materials. Where Amkpa (2000) found out that most of students did not use the library because they don't know how to use library catalogs. On the other hand, Williams (1995) and Julien (2000) discovered in their study that students who use the library regular, they participate more in their classes and their academic learning improved. Additionally, Fidzani (1998) indicated that text books, library books and journals are the most popular resource information for

college and university students in their course work and research. Other studies have examined the correlation between academic library use and services, and students' learning. Toda and Nagata's study (2007) underlined the relation between the academic library use and students' learning progress in Bunkyo University Koshigaya campus, and their analysis indicated a positive correlation between library use and benefits of library use on students' learning progress and the way in which students' use the academic library. Laird and Kuh (2005) found that students' participation in library activities such as; asking librarian staff for help, or using library website to get some needed information, were positively correlated with student engagement in order to improve their learning outcomes. Another study by Barkey (1965) realized that students who checked out more books got higher grade marks in their study; likewise, Knapp (1966) discovered that there is a correlation between library uses and students' grades. Both of the studies are important and more evidence of connection between academic library uses and students' learning progress is required.

More researches have appeared that there are further relationships between academic library use and students' learning progress. Wong and Webb (2011) found out that there is a positive correlation between the number of items checked out by students from the library and their academic grades, however the correlation was between small to medium because it only focused on the relation between checked out items from the library and their students' academic achievement. Where students engage in different kinds of activities and interact with the libraries and it is important to examine the different interactions on students' learning progress (Soria et al 2013).

Olanlokun (1982) discovered that students use the library for different purposes, they used it for class work, research, discussion, references and other purposes, as well

as Fowowes' study (1989) found out that 94.8% of student use library facilities. Another study by Simmonds and Andaleeb (2001), explored that the use of the academic library is influenced by students who use the library regular, therefore, to motivate more students to use the libraries, librarians need to educate them how to use the library resources like how to find a book from the shelves and from library catalog as well. This paper attempts to find out students' perception of library services of their learning progress

Present Study-

This study aims to investigate students' perception of library services that affect their learning progress. This part will discuss the context and the research sample. Then methodology will be discussed through using quantitative approach.

Context-

This study has been conducted in one of the higher education institutions in United Arab Emirates (UAE). This institution has been chosen because it is an easy access to the participants.

Participants & Sample-

The participants are Emirati female students from different programs. The sample size for the questionnaire is fifty students were randomly selected from different programs and the participants were volunteering in this study (Table 1).

Major	Number of Participants
Business	13
Applied Communication	5
Information Technology	6
Engineering	13
Education	10
Other	3
Total	50

The researcher used simple random sampling, where in this type each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected (Cohen et al 2007, Creswell 2004) and the researcher wanted to get information to answer the question of the study from different aspect of needs from different programs.

Methodology-

The study attempts to understand library services support of students' learning progress. To conduct this research, researcher has to select quantitative approach in order to measure the frequency of opinions, collect data and to generalize the results from the sample (Creswell 2012).Therefore, the research methodology of this study that will assist in collecting data is through using survey technique. This survey tool helps to investigate the opinion of the students about library services and how it is linked to their learning progress. Creswell (2012) justifies that survey collect the data and analyze it to figure out the responses from the questions to test these results later, and to build a relationship between results and literature review.

Survey method will be use in this study to see how the library services affect on students' learning progress. The researcher wants to keep the survey simple and short for the participants to ensure that they will answer all the questions on the survey without getting bored. There are different ways of using surveys to carry out the data like; through the mail, face-to-face interviews, handout or electronic web based survey or e-mail (Taylor & Hermann, 2000).

In this study, the method used is web-based survey through using one survey website which called questionpro. Moreover, reliability and validity are two significant terms to consider in any investigating procedure (Johnson& Christensen, 2008). Joppe (2000) defines reliability as "...the extent to which results are consistent over time and an accurate representation of the total population under study is referred to as reliability and if the results of a study can

be reproduced under a similar methodology, then the research instrument is considered to be reliable". While Jary & Jary (1995) define validity as "...the extent to which a measure, indicator or method of data collection possesses the quality of being sound or true as far as can be judged...in the social sciences generally, the relationship between indicators and measures and the underlying concepts they are taken to measure is often contested' (p 714).

Therefore, in this study, participants complete the questionnaire accurately and honestly in order to ensure validity (Belson 1986). Hudson and Miller (1997) suggest that maximizing the responders' rate for the questionnaire will increase the reliability and that could be through different strategies. Some of these are; stress the benefit and the reason for this questionnaire and understand the nature of the sample in depth (Hudson & Miller 1997).

Framework of the Study -

In this questionnaire, the independent variable is library services which consist of time factor and services factor, where dependent variable is student perception of library services which consists of nine statements.

Hypotheses of the Study-

The hypotheses of the study are developed as below-

- H1: There is a significant relationship between time and students' perception
- H2: There is a significant relationship between services and students' perception

Data Collection-

This study used a quantitative approach (questionnaire) as mentioned before to collect data and it will be described in more details below.

Questionnaire -

The questionnaire technique is commonly used to collect data where it helps the researcher to investigate their opinions and perspectives (Creswell 2012; Cohen et al 2007). The layout of the questionnaire is important to look easy and interesting and avoid unclear and boring questions. At the same time, the researcher has to include a brief purpose for doing this questionnaire, so the participants are aware about it and involved in it (Cohen et al 2007). This study attempts to understand students' perception of library services in their learning progress. Therefore to conduct this research, the researcher selected a questionnaire technique (Appendix A) in order to measure the frequency of opinions, collect data and to generalize the results from the sample (Creswell 2012). In this study, the questionnaire layout is divided into two parts consists of closed-ended questions which are quick and straightforward to code (Bailey 1994), highly structured (Oppenheim 1992), and directly focus on the topic (Wilson & Mclean 1994). The first part is called demographic information which consists of two close-ended questions about the age of the participants and their major. The second part is about library services and students' perception of it and it consists of close-ended questions and rating scale questions, as they are widely used in research because they are more reliable (Cohen et al 2007). The rating scale category of this study are strongly disagree/ disagree/ neutral/ agree/ strongly agree. The researcher used Statistical Package for the Social Science program (SPSS) to analyze the collected data. In this study, fifty participants from different majors responded to the questionnaire as Table (1) showed. The next part will be about the data analysis of the finding from the questionnaire and there will be a discussion part based on these findings.

Finding & Discussion-

This study examines students' perception of library services in their learning progress. The findings in this section will help to give a good explanation to find

out how library services support students' learning progress. The data was collected through quantitative approach through receiving responses of the questionnaire. Quantitative data analysis is a powerful research tool and to collect the data, the researcher chose a quantitative approach in order to measure the frequency of opinions and collect data (Cohen et al 2000, Creswell 2012). The researcher entered the data into the SPSS program to analyze the data and to get statistical results.

Descriptive Analysis-

The questionnaire was answered by female college and universities students from different programs ($n=50$) and the participant's sample was selected randomly. The questionnaire is divided into two parts. The first part is the demographic data which includes the age and the major of the participants. Part two, is about library services supports students' learning progress. This section focuses on analyzing the responses provided by participants to all questions of the survey.

Analyzing the first part of the questionnaire-

The participants were from various age groups as Table (2) shows. As can be seen in the table (2), the majority of the students were in the range from 21 and above (66%), while a small minority of the students are in the age range from 17 and 18 (6%).

Age Group	Number of Participants	Percent
17 - 18	3	6.0
19 - 20	14	28.0
21 and above	33	66.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 2: Participants' age Group

The second question from the first part of the questionnaire is to find out the student's major which allows us to know the needs of each program in relation to

library services. For this study, random participants are selected from different programs as shown in table (3).

Major	Number of Participants	Percent
Business	13	26.0
Applied Communication	5	10.0
Information Technology	6	12.0
Engineering	13	26.0
Education	10	20.0
Other	3	6.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 3: Participants' Major Group

Analyzing the second part of the questionnaire-

In figure (1) below, the bar chart illustrates participants' response to question on how often they visit the library. It seems that from students' responses. Most of them visit the library at least once a week (32%), (26%) of participants visit the library once every three week, where 24% of them visit the library once a month. The results showed that most of the students' responses are studying Education and Engineering where 50% of responses who visit the library once every three weeks are Information Technology students. 40% of responses who visit the library at least once a week are Applied Communication students and 40% of them visit the library once every three week as shown in figure 2.

Figure (1): participants' responses to their number of time they visit the library Moreover, as is shown in table (4) (Appendix 2) from students' responses to question on the main reasons for using the library, where 1 is to borrow fiction/non-fiction books, 2 is for reference/research, 3 is to use the young adult area, 4 to borrow videos, CD's or audio tapes, 5 is to read magazine, 6 is to read newspaper, 7 is to use the internet, 8 is to get information for projects, 9 is to use government publications, 10 is to use the computers (non-Internet) and 11 is to study/work. The result showed that most of the students' responses of using the library are for reference/research, to get information for projects and or study/work.

Figure (2):participants' responses to their number of time they visit the library by program.

The students also responded to services they received while they visit and use the library. 33% of students' responses found out that library staff was helpful and pleasant as it shown in table (5) and most of these responses came from Information Technology students (around 83%), then from Education students (80%) and around 77% from Engineering program as it shown in figure (3).

Describe the service you received	Frequency	Percent
Staff was helpful and pleasant	33	66.0
Staff was too busy to help me	4	8.0
I did not ask for help	12	24.0
Staff did not have the knowledge to help me	1	2.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 5: students' responses to service they received

Figure (3): participants' responses based on the services they

Received by program-

Furthermore, as it is shown in table (6) from students' responses to question on the main reasons of reading books, where 1 is for pleasure, 2 for business, 3 for college research, 4 for personal research, 5 for self-improvement and 6 for other reasons stated by the participants. The result showed that most of them reading for college research as for their projects and research and most of them are from Business Program.

Reason of Reading Books	Frequency	Percent
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Business	2	4.0
College Research	15	30.0
Personal Research	3	6.0
Self-Improvement	1	2.0
3,4,5	7	14.0
1,3,5	2	4.0
3,5	4	8.0
4,5	2	4.0
1,5	3	6.0
3,4	4	8.0
2,4,5	1	2.0
1,4,5	2	4.0
1,3,4,5	2	4.0
2,3,5	1	2.0
2,3	1	2.0
Total	50	100.0

Table 6: students' responses to reason of reading books

Additionally, the result in figure (4) shows if the participants think that using library is better or worst academically. The pie chart illustrates that 74% of participants' responses found out that using the library is better for their academic study while only 8% responded that the use of the library is worst for their academic study where 100% from Education program found out that using library is better for their academic study followed by Applied Communication (80%), then Business program (figure 5).

Figure (4):participants’ response based on the using library is better or worst academically

Figure (5):participants’ response based on the using library is better or worst academically by program

Table (7) summarizes the result of the nine statements using the rating scale and it also consists of the mean and standard deviation for each statement. The highest mean was (2.28) with (.991) of standard deviation was for the last statement which said that – the librarian helps me in my research/projects - and it had the majority of strongly agree and agree from the participants with 68% and only 8% of the

participants strongly disagree and disagree. Moreover, the majority of students strongly agree (32%) that they think that the library helps them in finding reliable information in statement two. However, none of students strongly disagree and disagree with this statement.

In the fifth statement, 62% of students agree that the library provide assistance in searching information resources which help them in their projects and study with mean of (2.1) and standard deviation of (.614).As it shown in figure (6), the programs have different level of opinion on the assistant of the library in their information resources searching. This figure shows that 90% of participants from Business students strongly agree and agree about that statement and 80% of Education and Applied Communication thought the same comparing with other program, 75% from Engineering students, 65% from other programs and 32% from Information Technology

Figure 6: participants' responses to be provided assistance in searching information resources per programs

Figure 7: participants' responses to how they are satisfied with library services

Statement Responses	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Std. Deviation
The library plays a role in my research and my study	22%	54%	20%	2%	2%	2.0800	.82906
The library helps me find reliable information	32%	48%	20%	0%	0%	1.8800	.71827
The library enables me to be more efficient in my academic research	30%	56%	4%	0%	0%	1.8499	.65027
The library is a gateway for learning and research	28%	48%	20%	2%	2%	2.0200	.86873
The library provides assistance in searching information resources	14%	62%	24%	0%	0%	2.1000	.61445
The library creates awareness on plagiarism	16%	42%	40%	2%	0%	2.3000	.81441

among researchers							
The library is able to satisfy your educational needs	22%	58%	20%	0%	0%	1.9800	.65434
The library plays a very important role in the development of students' reading habits	30%	44%	22%	2%	2%	2.0600	1.01840
The librarian helps me in my research/projects	18%	50%	24%	2%	6%	2.2800	.990657

Table 7: Statistical analysis of participants' responses to library services

Generally, the participants' responses to the last question which was about if they are satisfied with library services or not. 72% of students' responses that they are very satisfied, satisfied and slightly satisfied with library services, while only 28% of them are very dissatisfied, dissatisfied and slightly dissatisfied with library services as shown in figure (7). Moreover, it shown in figure (8), 90% of participants from Business students very satisfied and around 85% of Engineering students thought the same comparing with other programs.

Figure 8: participants' responses to how they are satisfied with library services per program

Inferential Statistics Analysis-

Reliability Test-

Reliability is the scale to measure and ensure there is no error, where 1.0 is better, value over .80 is good, value in .70 is accepted and below .60 is poor (George & Mallery 2003, Sekaran 2003). All the eight statements of student perception of library services were tested for consistency reliability by using Cronbach's alpha – split-half test reliability analysis. The result showed that the score of all the items is 0.626 that means the scales of the items were stable and consistent, where the reliability of library services variables of time factor and services factor is weak (.055).

Pearson Correlation Coefficient-

This type is testing the relation between two variables and knowing the means and standard deviations of the dependent and independent variables (Sekaran 2003), where the correlation range between -1.0 and + 1.0. The finding from this analysis

are compared the dependent and independent variables (student perception of library services factor and library services factor). As shown in table (8), it seems that there is a weak correlation between the two variables (.192) which means that not all of the responses are satisfied with library services that offered to them.

		StudentPreception .Factor	LibraryServices .Factor
StudentPreception.Factor	Pearson Correlation	1	.192
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.182
	N	50	50
LibraryServices.Factor	Pearson Correlation	.192	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.182	
	N	50	50

Table 8: correlation between dependent and independent variables

Regression Analysis-

In this study, regression analysis is used to analyze the relationship between a dependent variable and multiple independent variables to find out if there is a significant relationship between independent variables and dependent variables or not (Hair et al 2006).

Hypothesis 1:

H0: There is no significant relationship between time and students' perception

H1: There is a significant relationship between time and students' perception

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.218 ^a	.048	.028	3.58696

Table (9): The relationship between time and students' perception

The relationship between time and students' perception was investigated using Pearson correlation coefficients. The results in table (9), indicates a weak relationship between time and student perception (R square = .048), this means 4.8% of their perception is determined by time.

Hypothesis 2:

H0: There is no significant relationship between services and students' perception

H1: There is a significant relationship between services and students' perception

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.108 ^a	.012	-.009	3.65411

Table (10): The relationship between services and students' perception

The relationship between services and students' perception was investigated using Pearson correlation coefficients. The results in table (10), indicates a weak relationship between services and student perception (R square = .012), this means 1.2% of their perception is determined by services.

Overall Result Summary-

This section presents an overall summary of quantitative results. In general, the overall results showed major preferences of the library services impact on students' academic achievement. It seems that students from different program are satisfied with their library services with 72% of responded. However, the majority of students think that using library is better for their academic study. They believe that using library encourages them to have a better standard in their learning process and achieve better academic. This has been reviewed in the literature by Toda and Nagtat (2007) who indicate that there is a positive relation between library use and students' learning outcomes and the way in which students' use the

academic library. It is also supported by Laird and Kuh (2005) in the literature who found out that students' participation in library activities like asking librarian staff for help, using library website to get more information, and checked out more books were positively correlated in order to improve their learning outcomes.

From the descriptive analysis, it also seems that the majority of participants from different programs use the library for their study work, for references and to get information for their projects where at the same time, they found that they received good services while they are dealing with librarian staff. As presented in the literature review, Olanlokun (1982) discovered that students use the library for different purpose, they used it for class work, research, discussion, references and other purposes, as well as Fowowes' study (1989) found out that 94.8% of student use library facilities. Also it explored in the literature review that when librarians educate students who to use the library resources, the students become more motivated to use the library more. On the other hand, from inferential statistics, after analyzing the correlation between dependent (students' perception) and independent variables (library services), it found out that there is a weak relation between them. The weak of relation could be happened for some reasons. The first reason might be the sample size, because it was a small number of participants that's why the researcher could not get accurate finding from the data. The second reason is that the coefficient of variable of the dependent and independent variables is 0.386 which means that there is a high variability in responses because of the different field of program that the participants study. For instance, Education program students need to use library services more than other program students. From the findings above and the literature review, it would appear that using academic library services is effective on students' learning progress but at the same time, it has a weak relation because of different programs needs.

Conclusion-

This paper aims to study the students' perception of library services affect on their learning progress. Academic library is an important part for students where they can improve their study and learning. After conducting a literature investigation, it was concluded that most of the educators who support the students' to use the library services in order to develop their learning progress and there is a relation between academic library use and students' learning progress. The investigation of the methodology has been reviewed after collected the data through using the questionnaire approach and it has showed that there is no relation between academic library use and students' learning progress because of some reasons. One of the reasons is that the small number of sample size and the different needs of using the library depend on the students' program. Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge that number of limitation will exist within this study, namely;

1. The timing of the research was critical because the students were busy with their finals which affected the sample size.
2. Participants were from one of the public higher education institution in the UAE, but private and semi-public higher education institutions were not considered in this study, accordingly the result cannot be generalized to other colleges and universities campuses.
3. The researcher was not able to collect data from all levels because the study was conducted during the assessment period.

Recommendation-

Based on the outcomes of this study, some of the recommendations for future research are the following-

- A. Theoretical recommendation:

- Since this research is based on a sample size of fifty participants, future research is recommended to use a larger sample size to achieve a greater perspective and reliability.
- The researcher might increase the site through involving other colleges and universities for future research.
- The researcher has to use hand out questionnaire to ensure that the participants understand the questions to have accurate answers.

B. Practical recommendation-

- Since this study was based on six majors, future research could explore the library services in other majors such as Health Science programs, Law programs.
- Future research could cover different level – new batch and senior levels – within each program which would help to get more students’ perspective on the library services.

References-

- Amkpa, S. A. (2000). Students’ use of University of Maiduguri Library: an evaluative study. *Gateway Library Journal*, vol 2 (3), pp. 70 – 80.
- Bailey, K.D. (1994). *Methods of social research*. 2nd ed. New York: The Free Press.
- Barkey, P. (1965). Patterns of students use of a college library. *College and Research Libraries*, vol 26 (2), pp. 115 – 118.
- Belson, .A. (1986). *Validity in survey research*. Aldershot: Gower.
- Campbell, J.D. (2006). Changing a cultural icon: the academic library as a virtual destination. *Educause Review*, vol 41 (1), pp. 16 – 31.
- Clark, S.O. (1999). *Fundamentals of library science*. Lagos: Functional Publishers.

- Cohen, L, Manion, L & Morrison, K (2000). *Research Methods in Education*. 5th ed. London: RoutledgeFalmer.
- Cohen, L, Manion, L & Morrison, K (2007). *Research Methods in Education*. 6th ed. London: Routledge Falmer.
- Creswell, J.W (2012). *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. 4th ed. Boston: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Crossley, M., & Murby. M. (1994). Textbook provision and the quality of the school curriculum in developing countries: issues and policy options. *Comp. Educ*, vol 30 (2), pp. 60 – 99.
- Eskola, E. (1998). University students information seeking behaviours in a changing learning environment – How student’s information needs, seeking and use affected by new teaching methods. *Information Research*, vol 4 (2), pp. 1 -15.
- Fidzani, B.T. (1998). Information needs and information seeking behaviour of graduate students at the University of Botswana. *Library Review*, vol 47 (7), pp. 329 – 340.
- Foo, S., Chaudhry, A.S., Majid, S., & Logan, E. (2002). Academic libraries in transition: challenges ahead. *In proceedings of World Library Summit* [online]. keynote address: Academic Library Seminar. 22 -26 April. National Library Board: Singapore. [Accessed 26 March 2015]. Available at: http://www3.ntu.edu.sg/home/sfoo/publications/2002/02FengChia_fmt.pdf
- Fowowe, S. O. (1989). Students’ use of an academic library: a survey at the University of Llorin Library. *Nigerian Library and Information Science Review*, vol 7 (1), pp. 47 – 57.

- George D & Mallery P (2003) *SPSS for windows step by step: A sample Guide & reference Boston; Allyn & Bacon.*
- Gunasekera, C. (2010). Students usage of an academic library: a user survey conducted at the main library university of Peradeniya. *Journal of the University Librarians Association of Sri Lanka*, vol 14 (1), pp. 43- 60.
- Guskin, A. E. (1996). Facing the future. *Change*, vol 28 (4), pp. 26 – 38.
- Merrill, A. W. (1983). *Relationship of class-size to achievement and attitude in learning basic card catalog skills*. EDD. Thesis. Temple University USA.
- Hudson, P & Miller, C. (1997). The treasure hunt: strategies for obtaining maximum response to a postal survey. *Evaluation and research in education*, vol 11 (2), pp. 102-112.
- Jary, D. & Jary, J. (1995). *Collins Dictionary of sociology*. 2nd ed. Glasgow: Collins Publishers.
- Johnson, B & Christensen, L (2008).*Educational Research: Quantitative, Qualitative and Mixed Approaches*. 3rd ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications.
- Joppe, M. (2000). *The Research Process*. Viewed 15 March 2015. <http://www.ryerson.ca/~mjoppe/rp.htm>
- Julien, H. (2000). Information literacy instruction in Canadian academic libraries: Longitudinal trends and international comparison. *College and Research Libraries*, vol 61 (6), pp. 510 – 523.
- Jubb, M., & Green,R. (2007). *Researchers' use of academic libraries and their services*. Viewed 30 March 2015. www.rin.ac.uk/system/files/.../Researchers-libraries-services-report.pdf
- Kanpp, P.B. (1966). *The Monteith College Library Experiment*. New York: Scarecrow Press.

- Laird, T.F., & Kuh, G.D. (2005). Student experiences with information technology and their relationship to other aspects of student engagement. *Research in Higher Education*, vol 46 (2), pp. 211 – 233.
- Nagata,H., Sato, Y., Gerrard, S., & Kytomaki,P. (2004). The dimensions that construct the evaluation of service quality in academic libraries. *Performance measurement and metrics*, vol 5 (2), pp. 53 – 65.
- Okiy, R. B. (2000). Assessing students and faculty use of academic libraries in Nigeria: the study of Delta State University, Abraka. *Frontiers of Information and Information Science*, vol 1 (1), pp. 65 – 75.
- Olanlokun, S.O. (1982). Attitudes of Nigerian university students toward library sue and services. *Lagos Librarian*, vol 10 (2), pp. 106 – 123.
- Olanlokun, S.O., & Salisu, T.M. (1993). Understanding the library: a handbook on library use. Lagos: University of Lagos Press,
- Oni-orisan, B.A. (1987). The library as an organ of academic discipline. *Nigerbiblios*, vol 12 (3), pp. 18 – 26.
- Oppenheim, A.N. (1992). *Questionnaire design, interviewing and attitude measurement*. London: Pinter.
- Ory, J.C., & Braskamp, L.A. (1988). Involvement and growth of students in three academic programs. *Research in Higher Education*, vol 28 (2), pp. 116 – 129.
- Rasul, A., & Singh, D. (2010). The role of academic libraries in facilitating postgraduate students’ research. *Malaysian journal of Library & Information Science*, vol 15 (3), pp. 75 – 84.
- Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research method for business: A skill building approach*. New York: John Wiley & Sons Inc.

- Simmonds, P.L., & Andaleeb, S.S. (2001). Usage of academic libraries: the role of service quality, resources, and user characteristics. *Library Trend*, vol 49 (4), pp. 626 – 634.
- Soria, K.M., Franen, J., & Nackerud, S. (2013). Library use and undergraduate student outcomes: new evidence for students’ retention and academic success. *Libraries and the Academy*, vol 13 (2), pp. 147 – 164.
- Taylor-Powell, E., & Hermann, C. University of Wisconsin Extension, Cooperative Extension. (2000). *Collecting evaluation data*.
- Toda, A., & Nagata, H. (2007). Students’ library use and their learning outcomes: a study on outcomes assessment in college and university library. *Journal of the Japan Society of Library and Information Science*, vol 53 (1), pp. 17 – 34.
- Waite, J. (1989). The school library and GCSE. *School Library*, vol 37 (4), pp. 140 – 155.
- Whitmaire, E. (2002). Academic library performance measures and undergraduates’ library use and educational outcomes. *Library & Information Science Research*, vol 24 (2), pp. 107 – 128.
- Wilson, N. & McLean, S. (1994). Questionnaire design: a practical introduction. Newtown Abbey, Co. Antrim: University of Ulster Press.
- Wong, S.H., & Webb, T.D. (2011). Uncovering meaningful correlation between student academic performance and library material usage. *College and Research Libraries*, vol 72 (4), pp. 361 – 370.

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Paper-24

**Current Innovation for Teacher Education
in Indian Education**

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Current Innovation for Teacher Education in Indian Education

Dr. Sunil Kumar Sain³⁵

Abstract

Successful innovation in teacher education depends upon resolving issues regarding four interrelated themes: identity, non-passivity, control, and curriculum. There are continuing demands on education and training to explore ways of improving learning and widening access to learning opportunities, including access for less favored and excluded groups. This article opportunity to develop new approaches to innovations in education and training. This article has aimed at deepening the understanding of educational innovations. It has gathered empirical evidence of innovative education and learning arrangements and developed specific methodologies and guidelines for enhancing the design, implementation and evaluation of learning innovations. It has specially explored the issue of social disadvantage and exclusion, with a particular emphasis on exclusions from education and training.

Keyword:- Innovation, Curriculum, Approach, Training, Learning

Introduction Teacher Education Scheme-

The Centrally Sponsored Scheme of Restructuring and Reorganizing of Teacher Education, consists of the following components: Establishment of District Institutes of Education and Training (DIETs) to provide quality pre-service and in service training to teachers and Adult Education Non-formal Education instructors,

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thus providing academic and resource support to the, elementary and adult education systems and to engage in action research and innovation in these areas.

- Up gradation of selected Secondary Teachers Education Institutions (STEIs) into Colleges of Teacher Education (CTEs)/ Institutes of Advanced Study in Education (IASEs) to provide similar facilities to the secondary school education system. The IASEs are expected to take up the training of elementary teacher educators besides emphasizing on research and innovations.
- Strengthening of State Councils of Educational Research and Training (SCERTs) by conferring an independent and autonomous status on them with the responsibility to supervise and guide the functioning of DIETs, District Resource Units (DRUs) and other teacher training institutions.
- Strengthening of the Departments of Education in universities (through the UGC) so that they can provide academic support to the network of training institutes set up at various levels.
- Special Orientation Programmed for Primary Teachers (SOPT), was taken up in 1993-94, to provide orientation to primary teachers in the use of teaching learning material supplied under Operation Blackboard and to also train them in the Minimum Levels of Learning strategy with focus on teaching of language, mathematics and environmental studies.

Block and Cluster Resource Centers-

Block Resource Centers (BRCs) are visualized to give an impetus to elementary education at the block level by providing opportunities and facilities for professional growth to elementary school teachers and heads, Adult Education (AE) and Non-Formal Education (NFE) functionaries. They will in fact be extensions of DIETs at the sub- district level and act as resource centers. it is also

proposed to set up Cluster Resource Centers (CRCs) on a pilot basis for a cluster of primary schools in rural areas. They would provide a forum for professional development of teachers through peer group interaction under the overall guidance of DIETs/BRCs. The objective is to enhance teacher competency through group discussions and interaction with resource persons on a regular basis.

Teacher Training through Distance Education-

India has considerable experience and expertise in interactive distance education. This mode has been used to cover large numbers with improved quality of training. A significant innovation in distance education is the means to reaching teachers in remote areas through satellite transmission. This technology (interactive teleconferencing) has been successfully tried in the two states of Karnataka and Madhya Pradesh for 850 and 1,450 primary teachers respectively, for a one week in-service training course. A National Plan for Action providing in-service training to primary teachers through interactive distance education has also been developed.

National Council for Teacher Education-

The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) was established by the GOI on August 17, 1995, as an apex organisation responsible for the regulatory as well as professional aspects of teacher education. The major functions of the council are: developing norms for various teacher education courses, recognition of teacher education institutions, laying guidelines with respect to the minimum qualifications for appointment of teachers, surveys and studies, research and innovations, and prevention of commercialization of teacher education. During the brief period of its existence, the council has laid down norms and standards for pre-primary, elementary and secondary level teacher education institutions. Norms for B.Ed. through the distance education mode and M.Ed. have also been prepared.

Minimum Levels of Learning-

The National Policy on Education, 1986, brought to the forefront the need for focusing not only on quantitative aspects but also on quality in terms of achievement levels. Towards this end, a committee constituted by the Ministry of Human Resource Development specified the basic competencies to be achieved by all children at the primary stage in the form of Minimum Levels of Learning (MLLs) in selected subjects such as Language, Mathematics and Environmental Studies across the country. The effort of the programme is to make the curriculum and text books more comprehensive and relevant as well as to facilitate uniform, comparable levels of achievement among the states. The first phase of the programme was implemented through voluntary agencies, research institutions, SCERTs and DIETs. Currently, 12 states are implementing the programme through the institutional mechanism of around 200 DIETs and the programme is being up-scaled. MLL approach has so far been successfully introduced at the primary level. The program aims to lay down learning outcomes expected from basic education at a realistic, relevant and functional level, prescribes the adoption of measures that would ensure that all children who complete a stage of schooling achieve these outcomes. The Endeavour is to monitor learning achievement, to direct greater resources where levels of learning are lower, and to consciously accelerate the pace of development in the needy areas, thereby reducing disparities, equalizing standards and determining inputs for quality improvement and enhanced efficiency of the system. It is proposed that in future, efforts made so far will be consolidated and further support will be extended to various activities contributing to enhanced levels of learner achievement. Under this scheme, financial assistance is being provided to the state governments for a wide range of activities such as preparation of competency-based textbooks, training of teachers, preparation of teaching

learning materials, orientation of education personnel and conducting benchmark surveys.

It has developed a new approach to innovations in education and training based on the idea of "learning patrimony" and the impact upon this by a set of social, cultural and, above all, political and economic factors. Learning patrimony is defined as: -

- A modus operandi that is a series of prevailing socio-institutional and educational practices, pedagogic arrangements and relations.
- A set of values, dispositions, attitudes and expectations in regard to education and training.

Key Conclusions-

The key conclusions are-

- There has been a fundamental "clash" between the view of education as an end in itself for living a human life and the view of education as a mere instrument of the economy and people as workers.
- Policies in western countries are characterized by disengagement of the state from the economy and increasing involvement and intervention in education and training at all levels.
- Intervention in education has generally been based on an economic rationale and focused on "re-designing" legislative arrangements in terms of different forms of centralization-decentralization.
- There has been a transfer control of services and resources from the professionals of education to managers from the business field. This has involved a major restructuring of the professional culture, working practices, college management styles and conditions of service, including the employment conditions of the teaching staff.

- Performance models of assessment and systems of vocational qualifications based on "measurable competencies" has resulted in a specific pedagogy where learning objectives have to be stated in such a way that they can be unequivocally measured.
- This has resulted in a conflict between the "democratic views of accountability" (education has to "respond" to society and its members) and economic or market-driven views of accountability (Judged in terms of the market).
- Despite strong resistance from educational institutions and professionals, there has tended to be a convergence towards a process whereby values, criteria and procedures from the world of production are transferred, imposed or borrowed by the education and training sectors.
- Education and training is experiencing a series of tensions coming from economic and political spheres. Whilst, some of these tensions can be creative and give rise to genuine innovations, others can considerably disrupt existing arrangements and do not contribute to innovations.
- Many opportunities for innovation are related to the introduction and deployment of ICT in education and training, particularly when it is embedded in well organized pedagogic practice and institutional arrangements.
- A balance between student-centered approaches and more teacher-centered education is still an unresolved 'big issue' in the schools sector.
- Overall, pedagogic innovation is a less developed aspect of innovations in education and training.

Key Recommendations-

The Researcher made the following recommendations-

- Policy-makers' decisions should be informed at a more general level by the reforms and innovation cycle of each country/sector.
- Foster innovative networking and partnership arrangements by-
 - Encouraging public institutions to support the setting up and running of innovative partnerships, and facilitating their medium and long-term sustainability.
 - Granting more autonomy to higher education institutions for modification of their internal structures. In particular fostering university-industry partnerships in critical scientific-health-industrial sectors is a key need.
- Develop current efforts being made in the higher education sector by-
 - Networking public centres (e.g. museums, libraries) and facilitating easy access to such resources for home-based students.
 - Developing new territorial multimedia resource centres as student meeting places and self access resources.
 - Supporting pedagogic research in virtual teaching.
- Address the needs of schools as a whole by-
 - Revising national curricula and encouraging the integration of current worthwhile innovations.
 - Supporting the teaching profession in their efforts to develop the school model.
 - Changing the curriculum to allow full institutionalisation and integration of ICT.
 - Developing new evaluation and accountability models that make the school more responsive to society as a whole.

- Encourage the use of ICT in both schools and higher education institutions by-
 - Revising the national curricula and programmes to encompass online teaching and learning.
 - Encouraging institutions to envisage and implement inter-departmental re-design and collaboration, including collaboration between teachers, domain experts, animators and other rapidly emerging teaching functions, both within and between institutions.
 - Encouraging the setting up of joint programmes between institutions (both schools and universities).
- Improve continuous vocational training and skills updating by-
 - Defining wider frameworks, which allow both employees and unemployed to benefit from the training on offer.
 - Encouraging collaboration between educational and training institutions and private sector companies.
 - Strengthen the position of older and low skilled employees in the corporate setting.

Specific policy recommendations related to social disadvantage and on the provision of training for unemployed and disadvantaged groups-

- Improve the position of organizations and community centers providing training and other services to the unemployed and disadvantaged within the tendering processes by: -
 - Increasing the representation and involvement of small providers for the disadvantaged in decision-making structures and bodies.
 - Providing information and training to small providers and associations about how to access and bid for funds, and how to manage projects.

- Encouraging and facilitating greater collaboration and association among the small organizations and centers providing for the disadvantaged.
- Encouraging innovation at the level of organizational arrangements and partnerships.
- The principles of efficiency and need should be combined, and needs-based policy decisions sought, so as to ensure that providers closer to the unemployed access the funds available.

Induce work through the provision of worthwhile quality training by: -

- Combining current Labour Market Supply Efficiency & Labour Market Performance Indicators with new Labour Market Indicators such as Job Gaps Indicators and Wages Gap Indicators.
- Designing and delivering worthwhile, quality training for the unemployed and disadvantaged.
- Replace 'job-inducing' training schemes with quality training programmes.

Improve the funding and monitoring of training initiatives for the unemployed and disadvantaged by: -

- Setting up a funding framework, which provides both stability and efficiency.
- Using both quantitative and qualitative measures as indicators of performance.
- Education is one of the most important building blocks for a nation, serving as an instrument of economic and social development. Within this context, the all important role of the teacher is well recognized, as imparter of knowledge and information to students who are the future

citizens of tomorrow. In India, the role of the teacher as not only an educator but also a guide has been emphasized through the centuries. In the present context too, the role remains as critical as ever.

- In India, teachers comprise the largest, most steadily growing profession. During 1990-95, the total strength of teachers at different levels of school education increased from 4 million to 4.4 million, an increase of 6.5%.
- One area that is considered as vital for the enhancement of the education system is teacher education. This field has been accorded special emphasis in the face of recent social, economic, political and technological advances, particularly the challenges posed by information and communication technologies, globalization, growing rate of knowledge obsolescence and lack of social cohesion. The Government of India has upgraded educational infrastructure to prepare hundreds of thousands of teachers for their profession.

Reference-

- Khan, M.S. 1983. Teacher Education in India and Abroad. New Delhi. Ashish Publishing House.
- Khosla, D.N. 1970-71. Innovative Practices in Teacher Education in India at the Secondary Level: Vol. I and II. New Delhi. National Council of Educational Research and Training.
- Lipkin, J.P.1970. Secondary School Teacher Education in Transition. New Delhi. Asia Publishing House.
- Nagpure, V.R. and Inamdar, S. (et al.) 1986. Teacher Education in Maharashtra (India). Maharashtra.
- State Council of Educational Research and Training.

- National Council of Educational Research and Training.1985.
- N a t i o n a l CurriculumforPrimary and Secondary Education: A Framework.\
- National Council of Educational Research and Training. 1986. Teacher Education inIndia. Mimeo. New Delhi.
- National Council of Educational Research and Training. 1986. Development of Education: National Report of India. New Delhi.National Policy on Education: Programme of Action. 1986.
- Tan, R.M. (et al.) 1985. 'Recent Chinese Innovations in Teacher Education.'Journal of Teacher Education. 36:16-19.

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Paper-25

**A Study of Attitude of Teacher Trainees
towards Teaching Profession.**

Sailaja kaza

A Study of Attitude of Teacher Trainees towards Teaching Profession.

Sailaja kaza³⁶

Introduction-

Education gives us comfortable and dignified life. It is responsible for the holistic development of individual and society. Education means to lead out hidden talent of a child. It is an activity which helps students in attaining needed information, ability, attitude, perception. The quality of a nation depends upon the quality of its citizens. The quality of the citizens depends upon the quality of education system and the quality of education depends upon the combined efforts planners, educationists and administration, however, the most significant factor is the quality of the teachers. It means excellent and efficient teachers can change the fate of the nation. It is in the schools, colleges and universities that the development of the attitudes and dispositions necessary for the progressive life in a society takes place. Education is imparted by teachers. If the teacher is capable, energetic, mentally healthy and having positive attitude, it is well and good for the school. A teacher helps a child in bringing out the hidden capabilities. He/she unfolds what is within, hidden and untapped. He/she makes explicit what is implicit in the students. So teachers' importance in teaching-learning process is very much. The Secondary Education Commission (1952-1953) report stated, **“We are convinced that the most important factor in the contemplated educational reconstruction is the teacher, his personal qualities, his educational qualifications, his professional training and the place that he occupies in the community.”**It is very right that,

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“no people can rise above the level of its teachers.”(NPE, 1986).The Teacher is the real and dynamic force of any institution. The school without him/her is a sole less body. Without good, devoted and competent teachers, even the best system is bound to fail. A good teacher can certainly give best result out of the worst system. He/she is a powerful and abiding influence in the formation of character; the influence of a great teacher indirectly extends over many generations. The pivot upon which an educational system moves is the personality of the teacher. Teaching is often called a calling, not a profession or a trade or simply a job. This means that a teacher should regard himself/herself as one specially called to do this work, not so much for the pecuniary benefits which he/she may derive from it as for the love of it .The strength of the schools depends upon the attitudes of the teachers. For qualitative improvement in secondary education of our country, the selection of right type of prospective-teachers is a must. This require not only improving the knowledge and teaching competence of prospective-teachers but also to inculcate in them healthy professional attitudes and desirable teacher like qualities. Therefore, securing the right type of prospective-teachers for training is very important. Unless such prospective-teachers are found our secondary schools cannot deliver as per our expectations. Therefore, for the professional preparation of prospective-teachers, the study of attitudes held by them is very important. A positive favourable attitude makes the work not only easier but also more satisfying and professionally rewarding. A negative or unfavourable attitude makes the teaching task harder, more tedious and unpleasant. Thus, effective and productive learning on the part of the pupils can be achieved by employing teachers with desirable attitudes towards teaching profession.

Need for the Study-

Attitude plays an important role in determining people reactions to particular situations. Attitude is a predisposition to respond favourably or unfavourably to an object, person, or event. Defined it as “a mental and neural state of readiness, organized through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individual’s response to all objects and situations with which it is related”. Other researchers define attitude as a positive or negative emotional reaction toward a specific situation. Assert that Attitudes are evaluation; positive or negative statement about objects, people or events. Thus the successful attainment of the teacher training goal of providing season professionals to cater for the manpower need of the education system depends strongly on the students’ attitudes towards the profession. It is believed that if students’ perception towards the profession is negative, it is likely that, the teacher training goal of providing season professionals will not be realised. Maintained that, the teacher’s attitude is an important variable in classroom application of new ideas and novel approaches to instruction. Therefore teaching attitude is one of the main factors that determine the success of any programme.

Review of related literature-

“Assessment of Prospective Teachers Attitudes towards Teaching Profession: The Case of Northwest University”, the study done by Kano-Nigeria Aliyu Musa, and Ado Abdu Bichi observed that the prospective teachers have positive attitude towards their teaching profession.

A descriptive survey design was adopted with a sample of 220 prospective teachers selected using a stratified random sampling technique. Professional Attitude Scale for Prospective Teachers (PASPT) constructed and validated by the researchers was used to collect data. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics and Independent Sample t-test to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of

significance. A significant gender difference was observed in their attitudes towards the profession. However the results further showed no significant difference in the prospective teachers' attitudes towards the profession in relation to field of study and level of study. The implication is that, this favourable attitude towards teaching profession will bring about professional competence in the future practice.

“Attitudes of Prospective Teachers towards Teaching Profession” was another study by Mohammad Parvez¹ and Mohd Shakir, stated that many prospective teachers join this profession not by choice but by chance or due to other reasons. A sample of 180 prospective teachers, 90 from private and 90 from public institutions was taken through purposive convenient sampling method. “Teacher Attitude Inventory (TAI)” by Dr. S.P. Ahluwalia was used to collect the data. Mean, SD and t-test were used for the analysis of the data. Research findings revealed that there is a significant difference in the attitudes of prospective teachers studying in private and public B.Ed institutions. There is no significant difference in the attitudes of female and male, Muslim and Non-Muslim, science and social sciences prospective teachers towards teaching profession.

“Under achievement of B.Ed students in relation to their home environment and attitude towards teaching” was the study taken up by A. Selvaraj Gnanaguru, M. Suresh Kumar revealed that the underachievers have satisfactory home environment and unfavourable attitude towards teaching. A sample of 892 B.Ed students was randomly selected from different districts of Tamilnadu State. The findings of the study are there is no significant relationship found between the underachievers home environment and their attitude towards teaching. Male and female students differ significantly in their home environment and attitude towards teaching but not in their achievement score and intelligence score.

Statement of the problem-

“A Study of attitude of prospective teachers towards teaching profession”

Objectives of the study-

1. To study the levels of teaching attitude among prospective teachers.
2. To study the effect of the following variables on teaching attitude among prospective teachers.
 - a). Gender
 - b). Age
 - c). Level of teacher education

Hypotheses of the study-

1. There is a significant difference in the levels of teaching attitude among prospective teachers.
2. The following variables make a significant difference on teaching attitude among prospective teachers.
 - a). Gender
 - b). Age
 - c). Level of teacher education.

Sampling Technique-

Convenience sampling technique was used to select the sample and size of the sample was 150. The sample consisted of prospective teachers of D.Ed and B.Ed.

Tool used-

The tool was developed by A. Selvaraj Gnanaguru and M. Suresh Kumar (2007). This scale consists of 48 items with five choices i.e. strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree. The maximum score for this scale is 240 and the minimum score is 48. The reliability of tool was 0.77 by split-half method and 0.65 in test-retest method.

Methodology-

As survey method is one of the best methods to collect primary data from a large group, the author have chosen survey method for this purpose.

Data analysis-

Hypothesis No. 1 Levels of Teaching attitude among prospective teachers:

The distribution of sample prospective teachers in their teaching attitude levels.

Teaching attitude	N	Percentage
High	14	9.3
Medium	122	81.3
Low	14	9.3

The above table shows that the distribution of the sample in the High and Low categories is balanced on either side with most of the sample (81.3). This result when read with the fact that the mean value of the whole sample on teaching attitude levels is 204.19 indicates that most of the prospective teachers have medium levels of teaching attitude.

Hypothesis No. 2

a) Comparison of Gender and Teaching attitude:

Comparison of mean scores of males and females show no significant difference between the two gender groups. This is evident from the table.

Gender	M	S.D	N	D	SED	C.R
Male	205.55	20.52	29	1.69	4.38	0.38
Female	203.86	23.93	121			

The obtained CR value is 0.38, is less than 1.96, it is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, it is inferred from the above table that the gender of prospective teachers does not make any significant difference in their levels of teaching attitude.

b) Comparison of Age and Teaching attitude:

The sample prospective teachers of this investigation have been grouped into two age categories: below 19 and above 19. The teaching attitude mean scores of these 2 categories have been separately computed. They are presented in the following table.

Age	M	S.D	N	D	SED	C.R
Above 19	200.12	24.34	100	12.45	3.56	3.49
Below19	212.57	18.38	50			

It is observed from the above table that the obtained CR value is 3.49 is more than 2.56, which is significant at 0.01 level. To say in another way, the two age groups of the prospective teachers make a significant difference in their teaching attitude. It is observed from the above result that the above19 age group is having more attitude towards teaching than below19 age group.

c) **Comparison of Level of Teacher Education:** The mean scores of sample prospective teachers (B.Ed and D.Ed) are computed separately. They are presented in the following table.

Level of teacher education	M	S.D	N	D	SED	C.R
B.Ed	197.09	25.61	74			
D.Ed	211.10	18.38	76	14.01	3.64	3.84

The obtained CR value in the above table is 3.84 is more than 2.56 which is significant at 0.01 level. So, the level of teacher education makes a significant difference on their teaching attitude. The obtained CR value is in favour of B.Ed students. Hence, it is inferred that B.Ed students have more attitude towards teaching.

Findings-

1. The most of the prospective teachers have medium levels of teaching attitude.
2. The gender of prospective teachers does not make any significant difference in their levels of teaching attitude.

3. It is observed from the above result that the above19 age group prospective teachers are having more attitudes towards teaching than below19 age group.
4. The level of teacher education makes a significant difference on their teaching attitude. Hence, it is inferred that B.Ed students have more attitude towards teaching.

References-

- Garret, H. E. (1973). Statistics in Psychology and Education. New Delhi: Paragon International Publishers
- Kano-Nigeria Aliyu Musa, and Ado Abdu Bichi,(2015) “Assessment of Prospective Teachers Attitudes towards Teaching Profession”: The Case of Northwest University,
- IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME) e-ISSN: 2320–7388,p-ISSN: 2320–737X Volume 5, Issue 3 Ver. I (May - Jun. 2015), PP 17-24
- Mohammad Parvez1 and Mohd Shakir,(2014) “Attitudes of Prospective Teachers towards Teaching Profession”, American Journal of Social Sciences 2014; 2(6): 120-125
- A. Selvaraj Gnanaguru(2008), M. Suresh Kumar, “Under achievement of B.Ed students in relation to their home environment and attitude towards teaching” Edutracks journal, August 2008, Vol. 7, No.12

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Paper-26
The Octa-Hedral Structure of
Intellect

Moumita Saha

The Octa-Hedral Structure of Intellect

Moumita Saha³⁷

Abstract

The present day educational instruction is multi-dimensional. Therefore, a pupil from the very beginning has to be versatile. So the structure of intellect is constructed or formed according to his needs. The needs should be considered as basic needs which include-a) motor ability, b) moral ability, c) reasoning ability, d) creative ability, e) practical application and f) memory. The inter-relation of all these factors provides absolute stable structure and forms an OCTAHEDRAL FIGURE of intellect. The structure interpretes that when all these six factors become inter-related, intellect gives out a halo that enlightens one's personality.

Key Words- Intellect, Octahedral, Structure, Ability, Inter-relation.

Introduction-

Intelligence is a manifestation of a high mental capacity for learning, reasoning, understanding, and similar forms of mental activity; aptitude in grasping truths, relationships of facts and meanings and etc.

Intelligence is derived from the Latin verb "intelligere" that means to comprehend or perceive. It is also the ability of communication, self awareness, memory, planning, creativity and problem solving. It is also the ability to perceive information and retain it as knowledge for further application.

Intelligence is most widely studied in humans. Within the discipline of psychology various approaches to human intelligence have been adopted. Intelligence provides human beings the cognitive abilities to learn, form concepts, understand, reason, recognise patterns, solve problems and use language to communicate. Thus intelligence enables humans to experience and think.

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Intelligence is not present in equal proportion among all human beings. Its presence is based on the upbringing of an individual that is related to health , wealth, culture, education, heredity, profession and family surroundings.

Different theories of Intelligence-

There are a number of theories on intelligence. All the theories are grouped under two categories: a) factor theories and b) cognitive theories. The factor theories are–

- i) Unitary theory or monarchic theory.
- ii) E. L Thorndike's Multi factor Theory or Anarchic theory.
- iii) Spearman's Two factor Theory.
- iv) L. L Thurstone's Group factor Theory.
- v) G. H. Thompson's Sampling Theory.
- vi) Vernon's Hierarchical Theory.
- vii) Guilford's S. I. Model.

The cognitive theories are –

- i) Cattell and Horn's Theory of intelligence.
- ii) Jensen's theory of Mental Functioning.
- iii) Campion and Brown's Theory of Intelligence.
- iv) Sternberg's Information Processing Theory of Intelligence.
- v) Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligence.

The Octahedral Structure of intellect falls under the category of Factor Theories.

Structure of Intellect-

Prominent educators have always been concerned with intelligence. The structure of intellect and its application to education is important to the development of understanding and improving the educational process. The existence of different theories of intelligence proves a need for a structure of intelligence in the changing structure of society and educational reforms. We can truly reform and

reshape educational process by changing the way we instruct and assess to match the goal of educational objectives. Thus we need a comprehensive structure of intellect suitable to the modern scenario.

The first structure of intellect was proposed by eminent psychologist Guildford. It was a three dimensional structure of intellect model consisting of Content, Operation and Product. Besides there are other theories of intelligence propounded by Thorndike, Thurstone, Spearman, Vernon, Cattell, Howard Gardner, Sternberg, Anderson, Eysenck where different factors of intelligence are suggested namely group factors, general factors, specific factors, primary factors.

The Octa-hedral Structure of Intellect-

The new proposed Structure of Intellect is named as the OCTA-HEDRAL STRUCTURE OF INTELLECT which is formed or structured on the needs of a modern-day competition prone versatile pupil. The structure can be explained thus-

Our intellect consists of six basic factors-

a) motor ability b)moral ability c)creative ability d)reasoning ability e)practical application f)memory.

All these six factors work together to bring out the overall intelligence of a person that leads to greater success in life. Therefore, these six factors are related to each other. This interrelated structure of intellect can be defined as the **OCTAHEDRAL STRUCTURE OF INTELLECT**

Explanation and Analysis :- The six basic factors can be explained thus-

- a) Motor ability =the ability that is specifically related to the performance of a motor skill. Motor abilities establish achievement potentials for motor skills.
- b) Moral ability= It is concerned with what is right or wrong in human behaviour,based on what one thinks is right and good.

- c) Creative ability= our creative ability lies in the development of our mind and how it is focussed to direct what we feel . It helps to cope with novel situations and to profit from experience.
- d) Reasoning ability= It is a process of thinking about something in a logical way in order to form a conclusion or judgement.
- e) Practical application= it helps to adapt to the demands of the environment.
- f) Memory=It is the ability to memorise quickly, to recall something when necessary. It also indicates the ability to utilize one’s memory to attain the proposed goal.

The following figure will well explain the matter.

Therefore, according to this figure factor A is related to B,C,D,E and F; B is related to A,C,D,E and F; C is related to A,B, D,E and F; D is related to A,B, C,E and F; E is related to A,B, C,D and F; F is related to A,B, C,D and E.

It is clear that Intelligence is a combination of all these six factors and it can be explained as $I = A+B+C+D+E+F$, and the most simple structure of intellect is like an Octagon.

Apart from this fact, it is also noticed that in some persons, instead of all the factors, some factors are related to each other. On the basis of how many among the six factors are related or associated with each other or how many are prominent in a person, a person is determined to be intelligent, least intelligent, less intelligent, more intelligent, most intelligent and so on; And according to the association of factors and based on their proximity, the following sub-structures of intellect can be derived from the most stable Octahedral Structure ;-

1. Triangular Structure of Intellect

In this triangular structure of intellect, here only three basic factors are interrelated to each other.

2. Square Planar Structure of Intellect

In this square planar structure of intellect, four basic factors are associated and related to each other.

3. Tetrahedral Structure of Intellect

This is the tetrahedral structure of intellect that relates four factors to each other, but here the coordination among the factors is better than that is in the square planar structure.

4. Square Pyramidal Structure of Intellect

It is the square pyramidal structure of intellect, here five factors are related to each other.

5. Trigonal bipyramidal Structure of Intellect

Here in this trigonal bi pyramidal structure five basic factors are related to each other.

E C
D

Though in both square pyramidal structure and trigonal bi-pyramidal structure of intellect, five basic factors are co-ordinated, the proximity of the factors forms the structure of intellect in these two cases and both the coordination and proximity among the factors are different in both the cases.

Applicability of this Structure-

Being a complex and stable structure of Intellect, this theory can be applied in multiple spheres regarding educational process. By applying this theory for judging the I.Q. of an individual based on the six basic factors, we can get the following informations-

An individual passes through the stages of infancy, childhood, adolescence and adulthood. All these stages have their own characteristics. The ability of an individual in associating different factors helps the researcher to form a concrete idea about the mental growth of an individual. And for the teacher it is helpful to form appropriate instructions according to the needs of the individual.

The association of the factors differs from persons to persons ; and this creates differences among the individuals and based on these individual differences, educational objectives for the individual can be planned easily and the potentialities of the pupil can easily be identified.

Once the associations of factors in an individual is known, we can easily identify the problems of that particular individual in case of developing other mental abilities that hinders mental growth. And once the problem is detected the remedial actions may be taken accordingly.

A sound mental health is always important in the teaching learning process. Getting access of one's intellectual structure means getting access of his or her

mental health. This access to one's mental health helps in further planning in one's educational instructions and accelerates the teaching- learning process.

A strong access to one's mental health, his or her mental abilities and inner potentialities helps to provide a proper plan for a proper guidance in his or her career advancement. An experienced counsellor will show the righteous way which will gain support by the mental health and the structure of intellect.

All this effectively result in proper curriculum formation, using appropriate teaching aids, selecting appropriate co-curricular activities and composing text-books.

Conclusion-

Analysing the interrelation of all the factors it is determined that, which factor is related to whom and how much co-ordination is there, what is their proximity and how the structure of intellect varies from person to person all these help to form the intellectual structure of an individual. So there are different persons with varied levels of intelligence.

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Paper-27

New horizons of ICT for Women

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New horizons of ICT for Women

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Abstract

The information Communication Technologies (ICTs) are the most important tools for the development of any society. The ICT consists of segments as diverse as telecommunication, TV, Radio, computers and mobile phones. ICT can also be met through the traditional means such as print media to be important to large number of people, particularly in rural area. However, new technologies have potential for empowerment. In India, as elsewhere in the developing world, women play a central role in family, community and social development. However, women often remain invisible and unheard. . Women have traditionally been excluded from the external information sphere, both deliberately and because of factors working to their disadvantage such as lack of freedom of movement or low levels of education. ICT opens up a direct window for women to the outside world. Information flows to them without any distortion or censoring. This leads to broadening of perspectives, greater understanding of their current situation and the causes of poverty and the initiation of interactive processes for information exchange. For this information exchange, ICT offer the opportunities for direct, interactive communication even by those who lack skills, who are illiterate, lack mobility and have little self-confidence. In this paper we discuss some aspects of life which have a direct influence of ICT especially on women.

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Key Words- Information Communication Technologies (ICTs), Women Empowerment.

Introduction-

“Information and communication technologies are not a panacea or magic formula but they can improve the lives of everyone on this planet. However while technology will shape the future, it is people who shape technology and decide what it could and should be used for. These new technologies should therefore be embraced while recognizing that this is an endeavor that transcends technology.” Speech by Kofi Anna, UN secretary-General to the World Summit on information technology (2003)

Today, from the time we awaken in the morning to the time before we sleep, we are surrounded by the media such as news papers radio, television and computers. Some time we are not even aware that we are surrounded by these media. All these media come under the overall umbrella of what are known as today’s ICTs. Knowing and using ICT is important in today’s fast changing knowledge society, but we very often are confused about what these media are. ICT refers to Information and Communication Technologies. It includes any communication device or application, encompassing: radio, television, cellular phones, computer and network hardware and software, satellite systems and so on, as well as the various services and applications associated with them, such as videoconferencing and distance learning.

Even though the newer ICTs, namely mobile phones and computers tend to dominate discussions of ICTs, print media, radios and televisions, often referred to as traditional mediums still play important role especially in developing countries, as they expand the reach of ICT initiatives and facilitate the spread of information.

Technology and communication go hand in hand. Without technology communication would have been very slow. Now a days, any information spreads from one part of the world to the other in a few seconds. Communication technology is crucial for the development of a society. Technological growth helps communication to develop very fast. The information and communication technologies (ICTs) have invaded every aspect of human life today from community radios in the most rural parts of the globe to cellular phones in the hands of women and men in every community, to computers in almost every medium to large organization. The advancement of ICTs has brought new opportunities for both knowledge sharing and knowledge gathering. ICTs can now reach unconnected individuals, families, and people to understand their needs and challenges.

ICT and Women-

In India, as elsewhere in the developing world, women play a central role in family, community and social development. However, women often remain invisible and unheard. Women more than men have to balance the complexities of surviving in extreme poverty, yet these women are excluded from discussion because they are often illiterate, they lack confidence and they lack mobility. ICT offer the opportunities for direct, interactive communication even by those who lack skills, who are illiterate, lack mobility and have little self-confidence. Here are some aspects of life which have a direct influence of ICT especially on women:

- Women's increased access to job Market and improve entrepreneurship using ICT
- Increase of average household income in villages
- Women empowerment
- Shrinking Information Asymmetry through ICT.

- Improved Governance
- Indigenous Knowledge
- Easy-Family communication
- Increase Social awareness

The Government of India has invested heavily in strengthening the ICT infrastructure and has taken several policy initiatives to attract private sector investments in ICT infrastructure and service delivery. As part of the National Governance Plan NGP (2010) “A massive country wide e-infrastructure reaching down to the remotest villages is evolving and a large-scale computerization of back-end is taking place to enable easy and reliable access of public service over the Internet” (Government of India, 2009). The midterm assessment of the eleventh five year plan accepts the existence of a digital divides in terms of internet and broad band connectivity between the urban and rural India and the need for policies to address this issue by Planning Commission 2010. The studies have shown that some of these initiatives have also contributed to the empowerment of rural women (Nath, 2001 and Gurumurthy, 2006). However, Indian women still face huge imbalances in the ownership and access to many of these technologies.

The swift emergence of a global “information society” is changing the way people live, learn, work and relate. An explosion in the free flow of information and ideas has brought knowledge and its myriad applications to many millions of people, creating a number new choices and opportunities in some of the most vital realms of human endeavor.

Kassenbrock, Rachel(2014) in her article ‘*8 Ways Digital Media Has Changed Women’s Lives*’,in a magazine highlighted eight ways digital media has changed women’s life. These are- Digital media has provided a forum for community-building, it has helped to empower women as leaders, it has made it easier for

women to start their own businesses, it has provided a forum for women to engage publicly on meaningful topics, it has helped activists to raise awareness about misogyny online, and given people tools to combat it, it has increased public awareness of women's rights violations worldwide, it has improved girls' access to education worldwide, and provided young women with more career options.

Varma, Roli(2014)in research paper '*Gender Differences in Factors Influencing Students towards Computing*' examined students' pre-college experience with computers. she found significant gender differences in how students develop interest in computers; exposure to computers at home; availability of computers in high schools; and high-school preparations for college study in a computing field. The paper has a number of implications to improve the digital divide for women. It is based on 150 in-depth interviews of female and male undergraduate students, members of five major ethnic/racial groups (White, Afro-American, Hispanic, Asian American, and Native American) from seven institutions in the USA.

Meera, Kenkarasseril Joseph (2013) conduct a study, '*Critical Theory for Women Empowerment through ICT studies*' The purpose of the study was to cover Habermas-based critical theory to understand the politics of women's empowerment through the use of ICTs. The researcher studied the role of ICTs in developing marginalized women from the coastal areas of southern India. The paper was based on a qualitative study and presented a set of questionnaires developed specifically to assess women's development through the use of ICTs. The study presented Habermasian based approach to address women's developmental goals. **Beena and Mathur, Madhu (2012)**. conducted a research on '*Role of ICT Education for Women Empowerment*'. The sample size of the research was 200 by no. of trainees and 30 by no of instructors of different Governmental and Nongovernmental Organizations of Jaipur district. Researcher

used random sampling technique to select the sample for the study. The data was collected with the help of self constructed questionnaire. The analysis of mean and graphical representation used for the analysis of data indicated that the Age group, Marital status, Educational level had significant effect on different variable of women empowerment like Self confidence, Self awareness, Independence and Feeling of freedom. This research concluded that the information and communication technology empower a women in various areas like social, educational, personal, psychological, political, technological and economical.

Anitha, L. and Sundharavadivel (2012). In a research paper '*Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Women Empowerment*' concluded that It is important to view ICT as a tool to meet women's development needs and accordingly all forms of ICT should be considered to determine which are more appropriate in a particular setting and for the a particular program. It is our responsibility to make technology work for the people and in many cases; this requires a gradual transition in ICT usage. Technological empowerment was identified as a significant new under theorized form of empowerment that requires more research. The results of this study suggest that enhancing rural women's technological empowerment is urgently required. As well as for personal and social purposes, effective access to and use of ICTs is becoming increasingly important to rural women's leadership and participation in community and economic development.

Oliva Adwoa Tiwaah Frimpong Kwapong (2009). Wrote an article, '*Comparison of ICT Knowledge and Usage among Female Distance Learners in Endowed and Deprived Communities of a Developing Country*'. The article looked at the ICT situation among female distance learners in both endowed and under-served parts of Ghana, to check the user differentials among the two contrasting groups through a survey that covered 174 respondents.

From the results one could not strongly say that there were vast ICT knowledge and usage gaps among the two groups considering the extent of the developmental gap that the regional differences presents. Factors like time or convenience, space, and income have to be considered in using ICT for education and development among women. Exposing the women to multiple usages of ICT is also critical. Another core observation from this study is that women who are generally categorized as not being technology friendly are overcoming at least that. This applies not only to women in relatively well-endowed areas but also to those in underserved areas. This is a good starting point for undertaking gender specific projects that will promote e-learning, e-government, e-medicine, e-commerce and all other applications among women in both urban and rural communities. **Qiu, Jack Linchuan (2008)**, conducted a study, *'Working-class ICTs Migrants, and Empowerment in South China'*. The study explored how and if working-class information and communication technologies (ICTs) lead to the empowerment of the information have-less. By using a new data collection method called 'survey group,' the study provided a combination of quantitative and qualitative evidence, collected in 2002 and 2006 in urban South China through a participatory empowerment design. Findings from the study suggested that working-class ICTs had diffused widely among migrants and that migrants' socio-economic status significantly affected ICT connectivity. That impact created openings for empowerment as well as disempowerment under a variety of social settings. The research design and its preliminary results had wider implications for ICTs for development research in China, Asia, and globally.

Hilberg, J. Scott, Ed. D.(2007). has investigated that Information and Communication Technology has become indispensable in the daily lives of many and despite having grown up with computers and internet, today's college students

may lack the preparation required to effectively use ICT in 21st century. The purpose of this study was to assess the ICT fluency of undergraduate general education students and to describe their ICT fluency when disaggregated by gender, race/ethnicity, class year, major and ICT educational experience. Participants in the study were 198 undergraduate students enrolled in one of seven computers and information science (CIS) general education courses. The assessment instrument used was “Educational Testing Services’ (ETS) ICT literacy assessment. A survey instrument, ICT fluency questionnaire was also developed. Results of the study have implications in ICT education, assessment and curriculum development.

After analyzed above studies researcher concluded that the ICT is most powerful tool for women empowerment and ICT is the need for development of the women in present scenario.

One resource that liberates people from poverty and empowers them is knowledge. It is also now well understood that any attempt to improve the quality of life of people in developing countries would be incomplete without progress towards the empowerment of women.

With the shift towards a ‘knowledge society’, the role of interactive communication technologies such as email and the Internet in sustainable community and economic development is becoming increasingly important. The effective use of ICTs in community development projects has been argued to have many potentially empowering benefits and effects, such as greater inclusion, cooperation, participation and wellbeing.

Information technology links people, irrespective of caste, class, sex, religion, race or political alignments. This is why it becomes even more important to evaluate and assess the role of communication technology in empowering women,

particularly from the point of view of access and utilization. Gender equality presupposes elimination of all kinds of bias against women, and communication technology intervention can accelerate the pace of equality through gender sensitization. Communication technology can be used to impart information, and that in turn will lead to motivation, mobilization and action. Communication technology can encompass different approaches—welfare, participatory and catalyst approaches with women as change agents. Information, reinforced with success stories, can motivate women to adopt healthy lifestyles. Computers and the Internet are altering the way we work, communicate, learn and play.

Access is the central issue necessary for women's empowerment. Women have traditionally been excluded from the external information sphere, both deliberately and because of factors working to their disadvantage such as lack of freedom of movement or low levels of education. ICT opens up a direct window for women to the outside world. Information flows to them without any distortion or censoring. This leads to broadening of perspectives, greater understanding of their current situation and the causes of poverty and the initiation of interactive processes for information exchange. For this information exchange, Digital media plays an important role. Digital media can provide effective tools for women to:

- Document and generate knowledge on local conditions in the city.
- represent and share their experiences and their knowledge
- gain confidence in their own voices and their place within society, and speak out about their lives, needs and the issues they face
- Create, use and share information and knowledge actively for their own lives, with and for their families, in 'women advising women' models of solidarity, and in a broader community.

- discuss, ask questions, and meet others with different experiences and points of view the internet enables interaction across a city, the entire country, or the whole world
- pass on their new skills to their peers
- work through difficulties
- develop their ideas and creativity
- celebrate their successes and share their joys with each other and the world
- critically engage with the mass media and politics from the perspectives of their own lives
- offer means for self-reflection and self-advocacy
- pursue self-directed and collaborative learning and open windows to vast stores of information and knowledge on the internet
- create peer-to-peer knowledge networks
- initiate or take part in women's solidarity networks, other democratic processes and participatory governance.

ICTs are revolutionary in addressing Gender Based Violence in culturally difficult countries. ICT can be used for Preventative and Curative Strategies for addressing gender Based violence. Some of the examples are Cell Phones, Help lines, Blogging and Social Media.

Cell Phones can be used for mapping violence against women. They can be used as Hotline for providing information and counseling to the victims of gender Based violence. Cell phone can be used in case of emergency, to immediately contact supporter. It can also be used for collecting evidence such as pictures, audio and video recording.

There are many Helpline which provides information, counseling and referral services to victims of gender based violence. they also provide direct services to women.

Women can use Photography, Photo editing and Photo Story to advocate for their cause. Photography can be used as a strong advocacy tool.

With the help of social media and blogging any news can be spread anywhere. These media shows many stories which make women to be aware alert to live safely and rise there voice against violence against women.

Digital Stories based on true stories of violence (either from their personal lives or their communities) can be developed. These digital stories can be used to sensitize communities and policy makers about the issue of violence against women, it will break silence around the violence and will encourage women to speak up.

Being ICT-literate can generate a positive impact for women in many spheres, including:

Education and life-long learning - ICTs serve as teaching aids and tools for developing skills. Women can access basic and advanced education courses and life-long learning, as well as different training courses via the Internet. Women can access books, articles and general information in e-libraries and on the web, and they are able to get in touch with others to perform joint projects, regardless of physical location.

Information services - Women can access information that is important to nearly every activity they do, ranging from health care to small business management. If they need information concerning how to price their products, for example, they can learn how to obtain it from reliable sources. This can contribute to longer and healthier lives for women and their families.

Communication and networking - In many countries, women entrepreneurs are often social entrepreneurs first and foremost. The majority of small-scale women entrepreneurs often bear several community responsibilities beyond the immediate household. These women need to build on existing modes of networking to extend their reach out to business intermediary agencies and wider markets. When women are ICT-literate, they can participate in online social networks, keep in touch with family members and friends, and organize and advocate for their rights through civil society movements.

Indigenous knowledge, values and culture - Women can transmit their own cultural values and traditions through ICTs, preserving their cultural heritage. They can produce Web content in their own languages and post it online. Migrant women can stay in touch and establish links with their home communities. ICTs have also played an important role in preserving and identifying threatened or marginalized cultural artefacts and traditions. Communities have a wealth of indigenous knowledge that remains “untapped” and unshared, but which can now be recorded and handed down to future generations.

Access to job opportunities - ICTs open a wide range of opportunities for increasing women’s income. Women with ICT skills will have more opportunities to find interesting and well-paid employment. Also, ICTs can be used to buy and sell products. Additionally, women can work from home using ICTs, which can reduce time constraints in women’s daily agendas.

Political participation - ICTs provide women with information on government activities, political parties and candidates for public office. When women can freely access information about their communities and governments, they can more easily participate fully in the political process.

Human rights - Women and men with basic ICT skills can more readily (and if they wish, anonymously) report on human rights violations. With the use of ICTs, the international community has become more aware of the abuse of women's basic human rights. And can rise their voice against violence.

ICT helps women to be alert and quick. With the use of smartphone women are more active and alert. They can get information at any place and quickly spread it anywhere. For example while traveling in a taxi alone, she can click the photo of the driver and taxi number and post it on social media in order to make him know that she is not alone and is connected with many people. If she feels anything wrong, she can use help lines. To end violence against women there are some mobile phone apps and helpline numbers to get access to service for survivors for gender based violence women can easily access these apps and numbers.

Thus ICT has influence on social, educational, psychological, economical and political and personal aspects of development. It helps in overall development and empowerment of women. It increases self confidence and self esteem in women. it gives great motivation, inspiration, enthusiasm and interest to develop new skills and knowledge. It decrease the feeling of isolation and fills life with happiness and enjoyment. It helps them in gaining access to new useful knowledge information and awareness about the topics of their interest. It helps them to obtaining the friendship and support of other women and develops skills and abilities which are required to participate in various groups. They can openly discuss issues and share concerns and experiences. It helps them to choose their career and to take their own decision. It help them in knowledge up gradation to be up-to-date. It helps them to be aware of their rights and rise their voice against violence against women. It help them to be more alert and active.

Conclusion-

It is important to view ICT as a tool to meet women's development needs and accordingly all forms of ICT should be considered to determine which are more appropriate in a particular setting and for the a particular programme. As a number of studies related to ICT and women empowerment have been done at national and international level but there is still a need to explore the scope of ICT in the life of women. Considering the limited work in this area it may be fruitful in the present scenario.

References-

- Anderson, N. (2009). *Equity and Information Technology (ICT) in Education*. vol.6, New York: Peter Lang publishing, Inc.
- Anitha, L. and Sundharavadivel. (2012). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Women Empowerment. *International journal of advanced research in management and social sciences*, vol.1, no.4, 143-152
- Annan, K. (2003). Address to world summit on information technology, 10 December 2003.Quated in Anderson N.(2009).*Equity and Information Technology (ICT) in Education*. vol.6, New York: Peter Lang publishing, Inc.
- Beena and Mathur, Dr.Madhu. (2012). Role of ICT Education for Women Empowerment. *international journal of economical research*. vol.3, i3,164-172
- Gupta, S.N.(2010). *A study of awareness and use of information and communication technology (ICT) By Teacher Educators*. M.Ed. Dissertation, Department of education, University of Lucknow.
- Hilberg, J. Scott, Ed. D.(2007). quoted in, Gupta, S.N.(2010) *A study of awareness and use of information and communication technology (ICT) By*

Teacher Educators. M.Ed. Dissertation, Department of education, University of Lucknow.

- National Governance Plan NGP (2010). Quoted in Rasheed Sulaiman V, N. J Kalaivani and others. (2011). *ICTs and Empowerment of Indian Rural Women What can we learn from on-going initiatives?* Centre for Research on Innovation and Science Policy (CRISP) Hyderabad-500034 India. March 2011.
- Kassenbrock,Rache.(2014). 8 Ways Digital Media Has Changed Women's Lives. Retrieved from <http://msmagazine.com/blog/2014/09/23/8-ways-digital-media-has-changed-womens-lives> on 17-11-2013.
- Meera, Kenkarasseril Joseph. (2013) "Critical theory for women empowerment through ICT studies ", *Qualitative Research Journal*, Vol. 13 Issue: 2, pp.163 – 177. Retrieved from <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/doi/full/10.1108/QRJ-01-2013-0002>. accede on 04/06/2015.
- Nasreen, S.(2012). *A study of the impact of technology on the socialization of students in higher secondary level*. M.Ed. Dissertation, Department of education, University of Lucknow.
- Olivia Adwoa Tiwaah Frimpong Kwapong.(2009). Comparison of ICT Knowledge and Usage among Female Distance Learners in Endowed and Deprived Communities of a Developing Country, *E-Learning and Digital Media*, vol-6, no2. Retrieved from <http://www.wwwords.co.uk/rss/abstract.asp?j=elea&aid=3569&doi=1> on 16-11-2014

- Patil, S.B.(2012). *Role of Communication in Empowering Women Through SHG*. PhD, Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Karnatak University, Dharwad.
- Qiu, Jack Linchuan (2008), Working-class ICTs, migrants, and empowerment in South China. *Asian Journal of Communication*. Volume 18, Issue 4, 2008. Retrieved from <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01292980802344232> retrieved on 04/06/2015
- Singh, S.(2013). *A study of impact of information and communication technology on creativity of students at secondary level of education*. M.Ed. Dissertation, Department of education, University of Lucknow.
- Varma, Roli,(2014). Gender Differences in Factors Influencing Students towards Computing. Retrieved. *ERIC*. from <http://eric.ed.gov/?q=digital+women&id=EJ861684> on 16-11-2014
- <http://wcd.nic.in/research/ict-reporttn.pdf> retrieved on 20-10-2014.
- <http://www.empowerwomen.org/news/csw58-side-event-icts-and-women-and-girls-empowerment> retrieved on 10-11-2014.
- <http://www.iiav.nl/epublications/2003/Overcoming.pdf> retrieved on 14-11-2014.
- http://www.itu.int/ITU-D/sis/Connect_a_school/Modules/ES/ES05.pdf retrieved on 17-11-2014.
- <http://womenforsustainablecities.org/empowerment-through-digital-media> retrieved on 20-11-2014.
- <http://www.awaregirls.org> retrieved on 11-07-2015

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Paper-28

**Implementation of Health Service Program
in Schools**

Dr. Sunita Singh

Implementation of Health Service Program in Schools

Dr. Sunita Singh⁴⁰

Abstract

The health of children and youth is a fundamental value. Health Services for school children are must for building healthy young children. It must be an integral part of school education. In the present paper a brief discussion about historical view of health and its importance. The objectives of this paper are 1) To study the condition of Health Service Program of primary schools.2) To suggest the strategy for implementation of Health Service program in schools. A self developed observation schedule is used to know the condition of Health services in schools. The Investigator found that most of the sample schools do not have condition of health service in primary schools satisfactorily.

Introduction-

Health plays a very important role in all types of developments like mental, social, emotional etc. According to World Health Organization (WHO, 1948) health is defined as “a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of a disease or infirmity.” This definition of health was further updated in 1978 and now it includes “The ability to lead a socially and economically, productive life.” When we combine these two definitions, health is defined as” a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of a disease or infirmity. It is the ability to lead a socially and economically productive life.” There are number of factors that affect the health of a person which in turn affect the community. Like *Physical well-being, Mental and*

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emotional well-being, Social well-being, Spiritual well-being. A person should have adequate strength and stamina to carry out daily activities. The person should feel a sense of well-being. Thus it includes the main elements such as Nutrition, Exercise and relaxation, Habits. *Mental and emotional well-being* refers to the tensions, worries, emotions such as hatred, fear, love or anxiety that affect the health. An individual should be mentally strong and able to handle the emotions. A mentally depressed person develops physical troubles also. On the other hand a healthy mind helps to overcome obstacles and becomes physically strong too. A socially healthy person has many qualities like tolerance, helpfulness, and caring, pleasant and affectionate attitude. The Social well-being of community depends upon the broad-mindedness, thoughtfulness and social security of its members. Social life influences the physical and mental life of the persons and vice-versa. Due to stress and strains of modern life, it is very important to consider *Spiritual well-being* aspect of health also. Moral values, ethics and meditation are some ways to attain spiritual well-being. Positive attitude and strong faith in one's capabilities along with meditation or prayers help in gaining the inner strength.

Historical view of health and its importance-

Health may be conceived as "an integrated method of functioning which is oriented towards maximizing the potential of which the individual is capable of. Origin of the concept of health also appears in ancient cultures, in ancient Greece, people did all in their power to maintain health by physical education sports etc. The greatest empire of India was Mauryan. The king Mauryan was conscious about health and hygiene during his rule. According to Megasthenes, the Ambassador at the court of Chandragupta Maurya, the philosophers belonging to the highest caste were guardians of public health. An earlier Greek author Arrian quotes that the philosophers of India concerned themselves much with the subject

like forecasting rains, diseases and future. Megasthenes refers to the six committees in charge of health activity. Kautilya in his “Arthashastra” gives elaborate details regarding the principles of hygiene for the health and welfare of the common people. There were good arrangements for promoting general sanitation by means of provision of pure water supply, drains for houses and employment of scavengers for sweeping the thoroughfares of the city. There were strict rules and regulations for prevention of nuisance and adulteration of foodstuff. Buddhist literature mentions that Ashoka made provision for medicines in his capital for the benefit of the sick. “Dharmashastras” and “Manusmriti” contain very clear injunctions for maintenance of health and hygiene. The famous maxim in ancient texts of medicine reveals that arogya or health is essential to realize the fourfold objectives of life viz. the ethical, artistic, economic and spiritual development of men. It was a practice that no one could go to a temple for worship without a bath and clean clothes. Similarly, it was a common belief that an individual gets unclean during child birth, by contact with a dead body or having a disease which is contagious. Great social value was attached to cleanliness so as to prevent impairment of health. Health is not only freedom from sickness and disease but also freedom from anxiety and social and psychological tension. All this shows, how an individual and community as well maintained and protected health by its own actions and efforts.

If a child is physically unfit he will not be able to pay attention on any work in school or home. He may not be able to learn anything because of poor mental development. A weak child avoids playing with his age-mates; more over he may remain irritable or crying all the time. The social development is thus bound to be affected. Health has impact on the emotional development too. Person afflicted with illness is emotionally imbalanced. Only a healthy child grows normally.

Health is a positive quality of life with physical, social, mental, emotional dimensions. The factors affecting health are not only physical but also interacting components of social, mental and emotional development, which plays an important role in life.

The child who is physically fit looks willing and bound to pay attention to other tasks as well. Physical fitness, affects the child to a great extent particularly his interest and physical activities. Physical development is most important during the first ten years of life. There is high co-relation between physical and mental development. The sharpness of mind is important and unless it is sound the whole body will tend to be inert and dull. The mental fitness will make a child more useful person for the World. He will be able to help others as he is equipped to undertake more work and occupations. In the absence of sound mental development enduring body health remains missing. Sickness is a major cause of absenteeism and school backwardness (Prasad 2005).

Our emotions play a significant role in directing and shaping our behavior and personality. The expressions of emotions in childhood are uninhibited, natural and powerful. Children may be frustrated if they are unable to do something physically or possess something they want. Children are often frightened by strangers or darkness. Children whose reactions are laughed at, punished or ignored may grow up to be shy and unable to express emotions normally. If parents or teachers have patience and sympathy when a child expresses strong emotions, the child is more likely to be happy, secure and well balanced in personality. The child as he grows up develops not only physically, mentally, emotionally, attitudinally but also socially. Looking at the present socio-economic scenario it is important that values are also to be imparted since the early childhood, to make it a part of the personality when he/she grows up as an adolescent or an adult.

The above discussion shows that health is directly linked to all developments of a child. Hence a program related to health is necessary in the schools. The school is an effective place where attempts can be made for physical, intellectual, emotional and social developments of children. The children have an attitude for learning. Learning is their prime interest. This is ideal time to inculcate in them the good habits of healthy living. For a school child the school is the first experience of group life, outside the cloistered home environment. Children are constantly going under changes physically, mentally, emotionally and socially. The children are a vulnerable group and become easy victims of many diseases of childhood. Living together in the school incurs the dangers of communicable diseases. A sound health service program for the school going children is, therefore, considered very indispensable.

Health Services-

It is service provide through the school system to improve the health and well being of children and in some cases whole families and the broader community. Now a day there is lacking of adequate health services. Only 30% of schools provided health checkup for students of school population of India(Kocher 2013).Even in schools; where planned, health instruction is lacking or minimum, all teachers are responsible both legally and professionally for activities associated with health services and the quality of the environment. Active involvement of school teacher can create awareness among students towards health and control morbidities(Kakkar et.al 2012). Health services include the procedures carried out by members of the school health team (physicians, nurses, dentists, psychologist, teacher dietitians and others) to appraise, promote and protect the health of every child in the school; the well being of the total child is the concern of health services. Having received a well child, the school is obligated to protect and

maintain that condition. Certain activities usually provide for that purpose include the continuous observation, medical examination. Screening (vision and hearing) and teacher- nurse conference. The quality and quantity of health services in the school have a great bearing on the development of emotional, mental and physical health of the students and also of the entire school personnel. The school health services influence the parents as well as the community. We cannot afford to allow the students to remain underdeveloped. All efforts must be made to ensure that the students do not become a prey to any disease. The protective measures regarding health should be taken on a large scale and of a good quality to maintain and improve the health of the students. The school must establish good quality health services to ensure a sound healthful environment.

Objectives-

These are the objectives of the present work-

- To study the condition of Health Services Program of different type primary schools.
- To suggest strategy for implementation of Health Services program in schools.

Methodology-

All primary schools of Lucknow city comprise the population of present work. The sample of the present study consisted of 30 primary schools, 10 each of government, government aided and unaided primary schools of Lucknow city selected by random sampling. A self developed observation schedule is used to know the condition of Health services program of schools. This observation schedule has aspects like medical checkup, provision of first aid box, vaccination, medical record etc.

Result and Discussion-

Condition of Health Services Program in primary schools-

Health Services is one of the essential components of school program, its covers medical facilities like medical checkup, availability of doctors in schools, first aid etc. An attempt has been made to assess the adequacy of health services available in the schools. Health services are categorized as excellent, very good, good, poor and very poor on the basis of its conditions.

Table 1
Condition of 'Health Services' in primary schools

Type of school	Government school		Government aided school		Unaided school	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Excellent	None	None	None	None	None	None
Very Good	1	10	None	None	None	None
Good	5	50	None	None	1	10
Poor	4	40	6	60	7	70
Very Poor	None	None	4	40	2	20

It is evident from the table and graph that 20% of school has unsatisfactory conditions of the 'HS'. In 17 schools condition is also not good. Out of 30, only in 6 schools condition of this component is good. Only one school, out of 30 has 'HS' condition is very good. The findings of Kochar (2013) also supported the present work.

As can be observed from Table 1 that not a single government school is having deteriorated condition in health services but in 4 government-aided and 2 unaided schools, condition of health services is very poor. These schools have no provision for medical checkup of students at the time of entrant in the school. It is also unfortunate to note that no health records of students are maintained in these

schools. Thus, there is no information about the reasons behind the inattentiveness of students in studies. All the children, therefore, must be medically examined at the time of first entrance, so that the basic health defects can be handled at the earliest possible stage. It can also be helpful to understand the reason behind absenteeism. First-aid is must for every school but in these schools, even a single first-aid box is not found. There is no vaccination facility for the students. The teachers of these schools do not observe the students regarding their cleanliness like nails, hairs, shoes, clothes etc. Due to this, students do not take proper care about their cleanliness and they come to school in dirty clothes. If schools take care (concern) in all these aspects, a preventive check can be exercised to check spreading of common diseases and healthy habits can also be developed. Emphasis should be given on health services because health status has a significant impact on the performance of the students. This is also supported by findings of Verghese, Marry (1991) study.

Schools in which health services are found to be poor, there is a provision for yearly medical checkup of students but no health record is kept in most of the schools. Due to this any improvement in health status of students cannot be identified. It is essential to have the presence of the parents during the medical examination of the students. It is found that in majority of schools, none of the students are accompanied by parents during medical examination. So parents are unable to provide proper treatment to their child/ward for health problem or diseases. Due to lack of emergency care and dispensary, students are to be taken to the hospitals for ordinary health problems. Weekly checking regarding cleanliness is done by the teacher. So, on the day of checking, children come to school in neat and clean dress/uniform and on rest of the days they are least bothered about

maintaining hygiene and cleanliness. If teachers observe the cleanliness daily it would develop healthy habits and attitude in the students.

It is found that only in six schools conditions of health services are good. These schools have not only yearly medical examination of students by doctors but they also prepare and maintain the health records. Students of these schools are accompanied by their parents during medical examination and doctors discuss child's health problems with their parents. So parents may follow the advice of doctors. They can also consult the other doctors if their ward, has any health problems. The school in which health services are in good condition, there is a provision for daily observation of student's regarding cleanliness of nails, hairs, uniform during assembly. That's why students are aware of maintaining cleanliness which helps the students in having good concentration on their studies.

Only one government school is found to have very good condition or we can say that condition of health services is satisfactory in comparison to other schools. In this particular school yearly medical checkup is done by doctors. The teachers keep proper records of the health progress of the students. They also discuss the health problems with their parents, so, that parents may solve the health problems of the child. There is also a facility of emergency care. Thus, schools provide first-aid to the students in any case of emergency. Students are instructed to wear clean uniform. Teachers or class monitors check cleanliness of nails, hairs, teeth etc daily. Because of daily checking of the cleanliness, the students will definitely keep themselves clean. In this way a healthy attitude will develop. They may also keep themselves and their school and home environment clean.

Strategy for Implementation of Health Services Program in Schools-

One of the important obligatory functions of school is to provide health services to students. Health services refer to the medical inspection by the medical experts,

recording the facts regarding the existing state of health of individual student and reporting the details to the proper authorities and guardians of the wards suggesting the medical remedial measures. Here on 'Health Services' researcher has tried to discuss: days and duration, objectives, content and practices at the primary level.

Days and Duration-

Once in a week, duration 30 minutes.

Objectives of Health Services-

It covers following points-

1. To make pupil understand the health services
2. To develop the skills to maintain health
3. Preliminary knowledge of cuts, burns and minor accidents and their first-aid.
4. To develop an idea as to how medical care is an important activity for the nation.

Table 2

Agencies and component of health Services

Agencies of school health services	Components of school health services
School Medical Department under the charge of School Doctor (Exists only in well established schools)	Medical inspection of the students and maintenance of records of medical inspection and health of the student and sending it to their parents. Referral of serious cases for clinical treatment. Correcting medical defects among students. Identification and education of the handicapped students.
School Health Doctor (only in well established	Provision of health guidance services.

schools)	Follow up programme on the medical inspection of the students i.e. remedial steps
School dispensary under the charge of school Doctor (Normally part-time Doctor)	Protective measures to prevent communicable diseases by timely immunization.
Red Cross Society of the School	Provision of mid-day meals or nutritional services. Provision of healthful school conditions. First Aid and Emergency care
Physical Education/ Sports Department under the charge of the Physical education teacher.	Health examination of school staff.

Table 3

Objectives and content of Health Services

Objectives	Contents
Knowledge	Experts Lectures on – Importance of medical checkups, vaccination, counselling and cleanliness (for students and parents both) Health problems of students with Parents(through discussion)
Practices	Medical checkups and preparation and maintain medical record (yearly), vaccination camps (regular intervals) General observation regarding cleanliness (daily)

Objective of health services may be achieved through two ways-

1. Health Teaching
2. Health Protection

1. Health Teaching-

One of the important dimensions for this is to bring critical awareness of health. Schools may organize the experts' lecture on different topics such as communicable, non-communicable diseases, importance of medical inspection, vaccination and cleanliness, etc. for the parents and students. Due to this students as well as their parents are aware about need of health services. Slides, films strips, audio-video films which are related to health are also used for these purposes.

Schools should also have a provision of discussion on health problems of students with their parents on parents - teacher meet.

Selection of Content-

Diseases-

Symptoms, prevention and control of communicable and non-communicable diseases.

Safety and First-Aid-

Accident prevention, injury prevention and control.

Health Protection-

For health protection of students and staff, school should provide a hygienic environment. School may have provision of medical checkup yearly and maintain the medical record timely. Results of medical checkup should be reported to proper authorities and concerned guardians. The Secondary Education Commission has aptly remarked in this context, "In any case such remedial measures, as the school medical officer may suggest, should be adopted and the school authorities should see that they are carried out". For control of common diseases schools may also arrange vaccination camps at regular intervals for students and staff both. For developing a healthy attitude, school should have provision for general observation regarding – cleaning the teeth, cutting the nails,

cleaning and combing hairs, cleaning eyes, ears and nose and wearing cloths according to the season.

Conclusion-

The child of today is the citizen of tomorrow and therefore, the maintenance of the health of the child is essential. Poor health is a deterrent to effective classroom interaction and the serious implications of the existence of this poor state are unimaginable causing all round loss. It will ultimately affect the creature and productive channels of the individual, retards harmonious his/her growth of the personality. It brings degeneration in the standards of individual and group activities and performances. It leads to psychological disturbances creating imbalances in the mode and style of behaviour and in certain cases leads to a state of delinquency.

The great poet Kalidas has aptly remarked, “The body is indeed the principal instrument of Duty”. Kalidas’s statement fairly reflects the logic of health in the absence of which it would be difficult to perform one’s own duty. Physical and mental health is a dynamically integrated force to face the contemporary challenges and adjust accordingly without leaving any scope for backwardness and retardation and failures in the performance of life.

References-

- CDC. (1996) *Guidelines for School Health Programmes to Promote Life Long Healthy Eating*. M.M. W.R.; 45 (RR-9).
- Chenoweth and Sellkirk (1947). *School Health Problem*. Appleton.
- Davis M.B. (1954). *Hygiene and health Education for Training College*. Great Britain.

- Education for Health (1991). *A Manual on Health Education in Primary Education* (WHO 1988 Geneva). New Delhi: Jaypee Brother Medical Publisher.
- J. P. Sherry (19th Edition). *Health Education*. Agra: VinodPustakMandir.
- Kakkar R. Kandpal S.D. and Agrwal P.(2012). Health Status of Children under school health services in Doiwala Dehradun. Indian Journal of Community health. Vol 24.n0.1
- L. Ramchandran and T. Dharmalingam (1993). *Health Education: A New Approach*. New Delhi: vikas publishing house Pvt. Ltd.
- Mohanty and Mohanty (1994). *Early Childhood Care and Education*. New Delhi. Deep and Deep Publication. F- 159 Rajouri Garden.
- Prasad K.R. (2005). School Health. Indian Journal of Community medicine. Vol 30 no.4.
- Shivraj Kumar R.D.(2012). Schoo,HealthServices.retrived from www.slideshare.net on October 2014.
- UNICEF, WHO, UNESCO, UNFPA, UNDP, UNAIDS, WFP and World Bank (2002). Facts for Life. New Yark: UNICEF, 3UNPlaza.
- Verghese, Mary (1991). A study of the health status of primary schools pupil and it`s in influence on achievement for forming a SHP. In M.B. Butch (Ed.), fifth survey of Educational Research, Vol.II, New Delhi: NCERT, pp1331.

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Paper-29

**Decentralised Educational Governance in
India- Challenges to Universalisation of
Elementary Education**

Anuradha Bose

Decentralised Educational Governance in India- Challenges to Universalisation of Elementary Education

Anuradha Bose⁴¹

Abstract

India is chiefly characterised by hierarchical social order and plagued by discrimination and wide ranging disparities. In such a scenario, can disparities and decentralisation co-exist? Can democratisation in its true spirit be realised without the relevant evolution of the society and its institutions which thrive on the prevalent multiple incapacities and discriminations benefiting the political agendas of the local elite and disempowering the grassroots India. Decentralisation has prevailed in practice since the early ages in India; in the Constitution since 1950s. However, post 1992 Amendment, significant progress has taken place in the form of legislations. This paper is an attempt to understand how the process of decentralisation has unfolded in rural India particularly with reference to governance in education. Can decentralisation reforms in education achieve the goal of universal elementary education?

Introduction-

Equality and inclusiveness are the basic features of a true democratic society. The diversity in India expresses the need of democratic decentralisation, to facilitate enhanced people's participation in all aspects of life and increased accountability of the governance bodies. Inequality exists due to various demographic variables such as religion, ethnicity, gender, caste, class, and geographical conditions etc. which act as contributing factors towards inequality in education also.

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Governance in education system has been decentralised corresponding to the three tier system of Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs). Assuming that local institutions and agencies can better understand local priorities, problems and their solutions, responsibilities of educational governance at the local/ village level have been devolved to these local bodies. Democratic management of educational institutions aims to ensure increased access (equality) to education facilities by adopting inclusive approaches which shall accommodate the local needs and aspirations. Decentralisation thus becomes a medium to ensure equality and quality in education. This equality in education will ultimately lead to equality in other walks of life and will result in inclusive society.

Therefore, decentralisation has also been termed as ‘democratic decentralisation’ (Mukundan, 2003; Govinda & Bandyopadhyay, 2010) as a part and parcel of democratic system. In other words, it is an essential component of democratic system. The basic tenets of democracy are equality, liberty, fraternity and justice. Owing to this nature of the system, it (democracy) needs decentralisation in all its aspects i.e. social, political and economic. Decentralisation has been defined as “the transfer of decision making authority, responsibility and task from higher to lower organizational levels or between organizations” (Hanson, 1998)

Decentralization provides several benefit like, increasing people’s participation and access to decision-making, especially for the poor; increasing the range of people’s choices; effective delivery of services; facilitate improved interaction between people and governments, making government more responsive leading to greater transparency and accountability. However, decentralization suffers several constraints which hinder its implementation and practice for effective governance.

Decentralised Governance in India-

Article 40C of the Constitution of India states that “The state shall take steps to organize village Panchayats and endow them with such powers and authority as may be necessary to enable them to function as units of self government.” Decentralization of governance was therefore the agenda of the government in India from the onset of the Constitution in India in 1950. However, it was not given due importance over the next four decades up to the early nineties.

Bureaucratic control, Sheshagiri & Upendranadh (2008) state, coupled with the dominance of a single political party both at the centre and the states, and the process of centralized governance as an ideology of planned development, all inherited from a colonial legacy, served to undermine whatever effort there was at participatory local governance.

In 1958, the Balwant Rai Mehta Committee while reviewing the Community Development Program, 1952 recommended the establishment of an interconnected three-tier organizational structure of democratic decentralization at the village, block and district levels. This shaped the trajectory of rural development for the coming years.

By 1959, almost all states had passed Panchayati Raj legislations and the three-tier system was being popularly implemented across the country. However, even after the enactment of the Panchayati Raj Acts, with limited power and resources at their disposal these bodies could not develop and become functionally effective.

The second phase began in with the Ashok Mehta Committee recommendations which lead to a period of renewed interest in decentralization. States like Maharashtra, Gujarat, Karnataka, Andhra, West Bengal and J&K attempted their own models of PRIs, modifying the existing ones. All these developments, lead to a significant response in the form of the 64th Constitutional Amendment Bill, which was finally adopted in 1992 as the 73rd and 74th Amendments (catering both

to rural and urban local governance). This constitutional mandate recognized the importance of decentralised governance through local initiative and participation of people enabling democratic decision making.

Education governance through decentralisation implies an important stake for parents of the children, community members/ representatives, teachers and civil society in the decision making processes leading to articulation of aims, decisions related to knowledge and curriculum, the teaching-learning process and so on. Local institutions of therefore become representative of the voices of this collective.

Education Governance and Decentralisation in India-

The decentralization of education governance is of prime concern for a pluralistic society with diverse social compositions and geographical expanse like India. Education Commissions such as the Kothari Commission (1964-66) reiterated a national commitment, while the National Curriculum Framework (NCF) documents since the 70's invoked and implied decentralization in terms of creating space for local knowledge and experience to be weaved into the curriculum, to give the 'local' element its due importance in the education of the child.

The National Policy on Education (NPE), 1986 was a significant development in the education landscape of the country. The NPE has articulated grassroots level involvement through micro-planning. The Program of Action (POA) of 1992 was prepared to work out the specific details needed to take forward the NPE. However, it did not consider the devolution of powers to local self governing institutions. NPE essentially talked about de-concentration – streamlining the bureaucracy, decongesting the higher level education offices and creating a district board of education vested with authority and autonomy. Apart from these, village education committees (VEC) were formed through government orders in most

states. In many cases, these committees were seen as a subset of the local PRI (with the PRI head as the chairman of the committee), though they were not autonomous in any real sense. Local education governance therefore was not in the purview of NPE, though there were efforts to revive the discourses on decentralization.

In the 1990, with the initiation of the 73rd constitutional amendment and the insertion of Article 243G of the eleventh schedule the face of decentralised governance in India was bound to change. However, the structures of local governance are not adequately developed and face several hindrances; it is often at the mercy of the power elites due to political contestation of power and prestige. Thus decentralised governance, to be really effective, had to accompany serious efforts to alter the existing structures of power within the communities and to improve opportunities for participation and voice and hitherto engaging the disadvantaged or disenfranchised in political process.

As suggested by the Balwant Mehta Committee, India aspires for democratic decentralisation which thrives on a representative governance structure, ensuring equality through participatory decision making institutions and accountability to the general populace. Decentralisation itself may or may not guarantee participation and empowerment of the people at the lowest level and accountability of the institutions since it necessarily does not imply democratic practices.

The goal of universalisation of elementary education in India first through Sarva Siksha Abhiyan, 2001 and thereafter the landmark Right to Education Act, 2009 has shifted the trajectory of education development and decentralised governance in education in India. Emergence of bodies like VEC, School Management Committee/ School Development and Management Committee (SMC/ SDMC), Parent Teacher Association (PTA), Mother Teacher Association (MTA), etc.

provided an elaborate platform and legitimacy to participatory decision making, recognising the various stakeholders/ actors and accountability mechanisms of institutions of governance. Yet widespread access combated with high dropouts and low levels of educational attainment due to diverse reasons, high pupil teacher ratio, inadequate infrastructure, poverty, gender discrimination, severe caste disparities, geo-spatial disadvantages, dysfunctional governance strategies, variations in policies and aspirations, etc. have affected the overall education status in India.

Through the three-tier Panchayati Raj system, in the context of political decentralization, the block level (consisting of 100-150 villages) became the unit of development administration. The Block Development Office was therefore established while the district, created during the British period, continued to function as the centre and retained the major authority for educational governance at the rural local level.

Later, with the expansion of the education system, Block Education Office was established forming a link between the district and the villages. However, no clear lines of authority and functioning were established nor was there adequate resource disbursement which resulted in under-utilisation of this de-concentration approach. Also, the socio-cultural and politico-economic factors also affected the representation and participation pattern at the grassroots level. While, considerable authority was still rest at the district and state levels, especially concerning teacher appointments, transfers, development of textbooks, planning location of new schools, etc.; governance and delivery in education could not achieve gainfully due to imbalances between funds, functions and functionaries.

Can decentralisation reforms in education achieve the goal of UEE?-

In theory and provisions decentralised governance has achieved its deemed significance and has become the essence of a democratic and diverse nation like India. However where it falls short is due to a plurality of reasons. However, Mukundan (2003) highlights that in case of Kerala, a progressive state; decentralised planning implementation was left to the rhetoric rather than reality. This was due to two major reasons, since the actors at the local level lacked the capacity to take the powers and also because the lower as well as the higher level actors was not convinced about the relevance and need of decentralisation.

McGinn & Welsh (1999) while advocating for decentralisation also noted that certain components of the education system need to be treated differently. They state that two kinds of conditions must be met for implementation of any kind of reform, including decentralization: there must be political support for the proposed changes; and those involved in the reforms must be capable of carrying it out. Most decentralization reforms have failed to reach the objectives set for them, because they did not meet adequately one or both of the two conditions.

A similar examination was undertaken in the Indian context by Roy & Banerjee (2011) through a study based on fieldwork in Kalipur village of Dhaniakhali block in Hooghly district. The attempt was to analyse that can decentralisation reforms effectively attain UEE without removing the barriers of hierarchical social structure. It also elucidates that the village education committees which are meant to ensure the participation of the village community, including the socially disadvantaged groups, in the management of universal elementary education, have been reduced to mere formal bodies and seemed to have turned into another tool in the hands of the party leaders to extend their sphere of domination.

Acharya (1985) revealed a close correlation between educational achievements in terms of literacy and enrolment and agrarian class structure- caste status and

income level of the rural people as two important factors. He shared that literacy and enrolment rates declined very steeply in accordance with the hierarchical order of agrarian society. This scenario has, to some extent, changed after the recent reforms in the educational structures. But have these structural reforms ushered in basic changes in the very hierarchical order that had acted as the principal obstacle in the way of decentralisation and democratisation? As far as educational reforms are concerned, the achievement particularly in terms of enrolment has been spectacular during the last two decades. Almost all the children are now being enrolled at the primary level of education as part of the government campaign to achieve UEE. But universal enrolment does not only refer to universal enrolment and universal retention.

Therefore, decentralisation of educational governance is a prime concern for a diverse and geographically expansive nation like India, characterised by severe inequities and disparities in terms of socio- economic backwardness, caste, class, ethnicity, language, spatial, religion etc. All these issues affect the entire governance structure of education as well. Considering all these problems of inequality, decentralisation becomes imperative in the quest for equality. This system has been considered as a way to social justice. In decentralised system local communities can manage the educational services delivery according to their local needs. Local level problems can be identified without delay and quick solution can be provided in their own way which might never have been understood by the authorities in the centre. Central and state government and their administrative machinery facilitate in the terms of resources, monitor their management as well as provide technical support to these bodies.

This increased capacity of decision making at the local level has been hoped to improve the educational delivery system and its quality directly by increasing the

amount of input and its quality in the schooling. Programmes designed at this level are guaranteed to be relevant and also can reduce inequalities in access to education of quality. This territorial decentralisation benefits the central and state governments by establishing a network with the local government and linkages for effective implementation of policies. It is vital to our understanding that it is not the policy that is disjointed from the actual setting, rather its implementation pattern that determines the success or failure of the policy.

The issues of inequality in elementary education are believed to be addressed by decentralisation of education system through participation of parents as stakeholders and community members. But, the representation in these local and school level bodies of SMC/ SDMC and PRIs are largely affected by local prejudices and discriminations. It is well evident in several parts of the country that the education system is in an abysmal state. Therefore, we need to identify that what are the reasons that are affecting the education system, which are the contributing factors, and, the major issues which are creating obstacles in the path of democratic decentralisation and posing threat before the national goal of equality and social justice, some of which are:

Local Elitism. This implies resource capture by the dominant sections of the society and simultaneously utilised for their own benefits rather than the actual beneficiaries. Therefore, whose interest gets safeguarded is a matter of elite politics even in education where allocation of teachers, disbursement of funds etc. is affected by these contextual factors.

Illiteracy and low educational level have a cumulative impact on the realisation of the participatory governance / decentralisation. Illiteracy hinders the scope for self determination and the flow of information to some sections of the community,

making them further disempowered. The socially and economically deprived groups are hardly able to raise voices and communicate their educational needs.

Lack of support from PRIs which has limited resource at its disposal and often flavoured by dominance of upper caste interests dilutes the importance of participatory governance through representation. Likewise, bodies like the PRIs, SMC/ SDMC, earlier VEC, are influenced by social and political factors which affect educational governance at the local level especially gender norms, caste considerations, class, religion, region, etc.

Education sector is deprived of the administrative leadership and technical expertise that are experienced and have adequate knowledge of the system as well as interest to improve the system. Today, educational planning and management requires self motivated personnel who can realise the existing policies like decentralised management and can conceive innovative plans and strategies to implement them.

The gaps in the policies get replicated when adopted by the states and local governments without consideration for contextual suitability, due to insufficient planning expertise at the local level. All policies may or may not be suitable across all contexts and in such a scenario they have to be modified with respect to the context of implementation. However, the situation becomes grimmer with increasing gap between schools and local community/ society.

Is decentralisation really the answer?-

Experiences suggest that decentralisation can indeed provide beneficial solution to some problems depending upon the particular circumstances. This implies that the effectiveness of this approach to governance is conditioned to the context of its implementation or practice and therefore, it cannot be standardised across all areas. With specific reference to the goal of UEE, decentralisation can stimulate diversity

in educational provision to meet the needs of different target groups. It can allow teaching in different languages, for example, and permit different curricula and timetables to suit different religious, occupational and other groups.

Decentralised structures can also encourage individuals and non-governmental organisations to make human and financial contributions to education which might not be forthcoming in centralised systems. In this respect, decentralisation can help mobilise additional resources for education. Also, by reducing the number of links in a chain of control and reducing delays in the processing of decisions, decentralisation can help improve efficiency in education systems.

However, decentralisation can also create major problems. Among the most obvious is the tendency for disparities to increase. In the case of territorial decentralisation, this means disparities between states/provinces, or, if the decentralisation is below the state/provincial level, disparities between districts and schools thus sufficing the whole power debate (power struggle in terms of delegation of functions and functionaries) between the fortunate and the dispossessed. Also, decentralisation can lead to proliferation of different models of schooling, which makes operation of a unified system of education more difficult. This may have implications for social cohesion as well as for other domains. It is important to note that no country is either fully centralised or decentralised, what is important is what should be decentralised and what should remain centralised depending on the context.

References-

- Acharya, P. (1985). Education: Politics and Social Structure. *Economic & Political Weekly*. Vol XX, No 42.

- Bray, M. & Mukundan, M.V. (2003). Management and governance for EFA: is decentralization really the answer? “Paper commissioned for the *EFA Global Monitoring Report 2003/4, The Leap to Equality*”.
- Devarajan, S. Khemani, S. & Shah, S. (2007). *The Politics of Partial Decentralization*. The World Bank. <http://siteresources.worldbank.org/DEC/Resources/KhemaniPoliticsOfPartialDecentralization>
- District Primary Education Programme (DPEP): Logic and Logistics. <http://www.educationforallindia.com/page91.html>
- Government of India (1986). *National Policy on Education, 1986*. MHRD, New Delhi.
- Government of India (1992). *National Policy on Education, 1986. Programme of Action, 1992*. MHRD, New Delhi. http://mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/document-reports/NPE86-mod92.pdf
- Government of India (2009). *Right to Education Act, 2009*. MHRD, New Delhi.
- Hanson, M. E. (1998). Strategies of educational decentralization: key questions and core issues. *Journal of Educational Administration*. Vol. 36(2).
- McGinn, N. & Welsh, T. (1999). Decentralisation of Education: Why, when, what and how? *Fundamentals of Educational Planning*. Series 64. IIEP, Paris. <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001202/120275e.pdf>
- Mahal, A., Srivastava, V. & Sanan, D. (2000). Decentralization and Public Sector Delivery of Health and Education Services: *The Indian Experience*,

ZEF – Discussion Papers on Development Policy No. 20. Centre for Development Research, Bonn.

- Roy, D. & Banerjee, P.S. (2012). Decentralised Governance Reforms in Primary Education: Some Reflections on West Bengal. *Economic and Political Weekly*. June 2012. Vol XLVII no. 24
- Sathyamurthy, T. V. (1996). *Centralised State Power and Decentralised Politics: Case of India*. *Economic and Political Weekly*. Vol. 31. Issue No. 13
- Sheshagiri, K.M. & Upendranadh, C. (2008). Decentralization of Education in India: Reflections on meanings, experiences and possibilities. A study for NEG-FIRE.

[https://www.academia.edu/252341/Decentralization_of_education_in_India
-- reflections on meanings experiences and possibilities](https://www.academia.edu/252341/Decentralization_of_education_in_India_-_reflections_on_meanings_experiences_and_possibilities)

- Tripathi, K.K. & Bajpai, A. (2011). Decentralised Management of Education in India. <http://www.aiaer.net/ejournal/vol231212/5.%20Tripathi%20&%20%20Bajpai.pdf>
